

**A Bourdieusian Analysis of the Linguistic Repertoires of
Algerian Secondary School Teachers in the Berber Regions
of Chaoui and Kabyle**

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Declaration

I hereby certify that this thesis is based on my original work except for quotations and citations, which have been duly acknowledged. I also declare that it has not been previously and is not being currently submitted for any other degree at the University of West of Scotland or any other institution.

Name: Hanane Belaidi

Date: 1st December 2023

Dedication

This work is dedicated to the memory of my beloved Father, Youcef Belaidi, who always loved, supported, and believed in me. You may be gone from my sight, but you are never gone from my heart!

To my beloved mother, my supporter, my shelter, my fighter, my hero, and my all!

To my beloved grandmother!

To my beloved sister and brothers!

To my beloved and dearest friends Wafa, Nawal and Hadjer, who are the family I choose. Your unwavering support and love have made this journey unforgettable. grateful for every moment we've shared.

To Kawther and Rayane!

To my beloved niece Noriane and nephews Rayan, Amine, Youcef, Adam and Yazan!

To all my beloved friends!

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Abstract

This study analyses the linguistic repertoires of Algerian secondary school teachers in the two Berber regions of Chaoui and Kabyle, which to date has been an understudied area in the discourse. It demonstrates the multifaceted dimensions of language dynamic, language attitudes, language practice, language policy especially within the field of education and the perceived language dynamics among Berber teachers in Chaoui and Kabyle regions, including an understanding of how they acquired and learned languages in their repertoires. This qualitative study adopted a case study research method given the particularity of studying the less known (but nevertheless important) linguistic repertoires of Algerian teachers in the two Berber regions in question. The study drew on the teachers' subjective constructions of their experience in the acquisition of their linguistic repertoires and from the researchers' interpretivist standpoint in the analysis of the findings. Data was collected through in-depth interviews (n21) and focus group discussions (n2). Utilising Bourdieu's concepts of 'Habitus, field and capital' as a theoretical lens, the study revealed the involvement of different forms of capital that helped acquiring and learning the languages included in participants' linguistic repertoires. Berber teachers' attitudes toward the languages in their repertoires in this study were influenced by the historical, socio-economic and political factors, which were ingrained in their societal habitus. Additionally, the language perceived value in this study was indicated to be dependent on the field in which languages are exercised, as well as the extent to which languages dominate in fields of power. The study found that language practice among participants in this study is related to the interlocutor, to the context and the topic being addressed. Language was seen as a form of currency that buy speakers' privileges and benefits in a marketplace. The study argues there is ambiguity in the process of issuing the language policy in Algeria by highlighting contradictions within Algerian language policies that result in the lack of alignment between policy and implementation. The study provides a foundation for developing inclusive language policies that recognize the linguistic diversity in Algeria. It thus contributes to the broader discourse on multiple language learning, providing a platform for voices often marginalized in the discourse on language policies and educational practices.

Keywords: Linguistic repertoires, Algeria, Secondary School Teachers, Bourdieu, Case Study

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List of Abbreviations

ASA: American Sociological Association

BSA: British Sociological Association

ENS: Ecole Normale Supérieure

FFS: Front des Forces Socialistes

FIS: Front Islamique du Salut

FLN: Front de Liberation Nationale

HCA: The High Commission of Amazigh Affairs

ICT: Information and Communication Technologies

L1: First Language

L2: Second Language

MTLD: Mouvement pour le Triomphe des Libertés Démocratiques

PBUH: Peace Be Upon Him

PPA: Parti du Peuple Algérien

RCD: Rassemblement pour la Culture et la Democratic

SRA: Social Research Associations

SR: Smile Revolution

Chapter One

Introduction

This study provides an analysis of Algerian secondary school teachers in the Berber region, particularly focusing on the Chaoui and Kabyle areas. It places the perspectives of these teachers into their historical, social, and political lifeworld in order to capture nuances of their linguistic repertoires. From a Bourdieusian theoretical perspective, the study provides insights into the language practices of Algerian teachers in different fields of power including education, attitudes towards the languages in their repertoires, in addition to language power relations, including language policy for Algerian education and teachers' engagement with these dynamics.

1.1 Statement of the problem

The sociolinguistic situation in Algeria represents a complex phenomenon because of the various invasions that Algeria has experienced (Abdelhamid, 2002). Many invaders came to Algeria including the Phoenicians, the Romans, the Arabs, the Spanish, the Turkish, and finally the French (El-Mili, 1986; Benrabah, 2004). All these invasions are reflected in the current sociolinguistic and cultural situation in Algeria. They brought various cultures, languages, and traditions (Serai, 2022) especially, the Arabs and the French who had the most impact on Algeria's social history (Benrabah, 2014a). Many studies highlighted the complexity of the sociolinguistic situation in Algeria. Berger (2002, p.8) deemed the Algerian educational policies as "the most severe problem of Algeria in its present and troubled state" (Berger, 2002, p.8), while Djité (1992) argues that the only country where the issue of language plays a central role in the anti-colonial struggle is Algeria. Moreover, Mohammed (2022) reported that Algeria's sociolinguistic situation is a complex area of study. Stone (1997, cited in Le Roux, 2017) indicated that the sociolinguistic map of Algeria is intricate and changing based on geographical location and social status. This complex linguistic situation in Algeria presents a valuable opportunity for examining the linguistic repertoires of teachers in the Berber region (Kabyle and Chaoui).

Language is inseparably intertwined with power dynamics and is intimately connected to national and individual identity, culture, history, and religion. Where countries have been colonised and the language of the coloniser has been imposed such as in Algeria, the issue of

language becomes significantly more complex, and sensitive (Berrabah, 2013; Le Roux, 2017). Although policy on language use or practice in Algeria has received attention in the discourse, the debates over them remain a fertile area of study (see Holt, 2013). What is missing or merely appearing in these debates are the experiences and perspectives of teachers, particularly from Berber regions such as Kabyle and Chaoui where sentiments remain strong about language as a marker of identity, religion, culture, and power.

Berbers (Amazigh) are the indigenous people of North Africa (Morocco, Algeria, and Tunisia) (Djennadi, 2006). In Algeria, Berbers (Amazigh) are divided into four groups: Kabilyan, Chaoui, Mzab, and finally Touareg. About two-thirds of Algerian Berbers are Kabyle, who live in the mountainous Kabylia in the southeast of Algiers. The Chaoui population, who originate from the Aures Mountains south of Constantine and further east, make up the second-largest group after the Kabyle population. The Mzab (Ibadi Muslims) in the southern region near Ghardaia and the Touareg nomads of the Sahara Desert are the two remaining communities both of which are negligible in terms of national significance (Maddy-Weitzman, 2001; Roberts, 1982).

Although the Berber (Amazigh) populations of Algeria, who constituted a majority prior to the arrival of the Arab population, have maintained the use of their language; however, it was a minority language because of the pervasive influence of Arabic and French (Dourari, 2016). The Kabyle and Chaoui contexts are unique among Berbers in that they played a significant role in pivotal events throughout the history of Algeria. The former (Kabyle) had a long history of claiming the recognition of the Berber language (Tamazight) and culture (Chaker, 2001). The Kabyle context was involved in significant events throughout Algerian history such as 'The Berber Spring' and 'Black Spring', which played a major role in promoting the status of Tamazight in Algeria. While the latter (Chaoui region) is considered the place where the Algerian revolution officially started (Wallenbrock, 2018). The Chaoui context is known for producing Mustapha Ben Boulaid, one of the nine historic chiefs. He served as the first commander of Wilaya 1, which was the initial region to pose significant trouble for the French army in the years 1954 and 1955 (Roberts, 1982). Throughout Algerian history, the Chaoui context was also subject to the influence of the Reformist movement led by Ben Badis and the Association of the 'Ulama during the 1930s and 1940s. As opposed to the Kabyle context, which experienced minimal effect from this movement the Chaoui context was strongly

affected by its principles (Roberts,1982). Therefore, the socio-political context of language use in Algerian social life especially regarding the place of minority languages such as Tamazight provides a strong rationale for understanding teachers' attitudes towards the languages included in their linguistic repertoires and how they implement the national policy in schooling contexts.

Understanding teachers' linguistic repertoires is important particularly to understand how professionals (participants) negotiate between their ethnic/cultural identity and national policy in their engagement with and use of their linguistic repertoires (Benrabah, 2014b; Negadi, 2015). It provides important insights regarding policy-practice conformity or mismatch, particularly among Algerian Berber secondary school teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle).

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to explore Algerian teachers' linguistic repertoires in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). This aim informed the following objectives:

- To explore what constitutes teachers' linguistic repertoires, that is, what languages are included in their repertoires.
- To investigate teachers' historical and social trajectories to understand their language practices in different fields including education and to explain how they acquired or learned the languages included in their repertoires.
- To highlight teachers' attitudes towards each of the languages included in their linguistic repertoires and explaining what determines such attitudes.
- To explore teachers' perceptions regarding language and power in Algeria and illustrate how language's perceived value is subject to change from one field to another based on the required linguistic capital in the field or the market as referred to by Bourdieu.
- To address the language policy in education and Berber teachers' (Kabyle and Chaoui) engagement with this national language policy.

1.3 Research questions

- a. What languages make up the linguistic repertoires of Algerian secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle)? How do Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) use their linguistic repertoires in different fields?

- b. What are the Algerian Berber teachers' attitudes toward the languages included in their linguistic repertoires? How are these attitudes developed among the teachers? If at all, how do their attitudes differ based on the Berber region they come from?
- c. What are the Algerian Berber teachers' perceptions about their linguistic repertoires in relation to the complexities of language and power?
- d. How do Berber teachers in the Kabyle and Chaoui contexts engage with the political rhetoric and national policy on language use in education?

1.4 Motivation

On a personal level, my inclination towards this topic primarily stems from being a Chaoui person who belongs to the Chaoui setting. I was born in a family where multilingualism is the norm, as happens in many Algerian families in the Chaoui context. My parents spoke Tamazight (Chaoui dialect), Derja, French, and Arabic.

My father was raised in a family where Derja and French were utilised. Despite his proficiency in Tamazight (Chaoui dialect), it was noted that he only used Tamazight in instances where the interlocutor was also speaking Tamazight or when conversing with my maternal grandmother who mostly speaks Tamazight in her daily interactions. My father was also fluent in French. However, he did not use French with us, rather he used to mix Derja and French expressions. On the other hand, due to the nature of his occupation as an architect he used to utilise French in his professional field and with his friends who are similarly fluent in French.

Prior to her retirement, my mother was a teacher of French. Due to her previous teaching position in a rural area within the Chaoui context, it was necessary for us to reside there temporarily. My mother provided French language instruction to me and my siblings. However, it was also noted that in our day-to-day interactions, she did not exclusively utilise French, instead she opted for a combination of Derja and French expressions. I asked my mother once why she refrained from utilising the French language when communicating with us to learn the language more. According to her response, the utilisation of French was regarded as prestigious and as a symbol of high social status. Consequently, its usage in rural areas would be interpreted as an act of ostentation. My mother also used to utilise Tamazight with her mother and sister but not with us.

As a result of being raised in a multilingual family, my linguistic repertoire included different languages. I have acquired Tamazight through exposure to my mother's conversations with

my grandmother and aunt, Derja through immersion in my local environment, and French through both instruction from my mother and practical usage as there is a mix between Derja and French in day-to-day interactions. I learned Arabic through formal education, and finally learned English due to my academic pursuits and a prolonged period of residence and study in the United Kingdom, which improved my English. Upon reflection on my linguistic repertoire, it is apparent that I utilise various languages based on the given situation or interlocutor with whom I am communicating. I communicate in the English language with my Algerian friends who speak English too. In my familial context, I employ both Derja and French. Despite lacking fluency in Tamazight due to having acquired it receptively through auditory means rather than actively speaking it, I occasionally try to converse in Tamazight with my grandmother.

In addition to the complex linguistic situation in Algeria (Benrabah, 2007), which makes it a notably informative case study. My personal experience with multilingualism as a Chaoui person motivated me to investigate this phenomenon in the Berber context (Chaoui and Kabyle). My personal experience drove me to investigate the linguistic repertoires of teachers in the Berber region in order to know the component of their linguistic repertoires, their attitudes towards the languages in their repertoire, and their usage of their linguistic repertoires. I also aim at uncovering what factors affect their language attitudes and choices in addition to the relationship between language and power in Algeria. As a researcher in education and social sciences, I have linked my interest in investigating the linguistic repertoires in the Berber region (Kabyle and Chaoui) to education through investigating how teachers in the Kabyle and Chaoui contexts engage with the language policy in education.

1.5 Structure of the thesis

The present thesis is divided into nine chapters. The first chapter is an introductory chapter where the statement of the problem, aim, objectives, research questions and motivations are addressed.

The second chapter describes the context of the study by highlighting the sociolinguistic situation in Algeria. It provides a historical outline of the Algerian multilingual situation, where different languages are in contact, politics and identity in the context of Arabisation, language planning in education during colonial and post-colonial times, policy practice tensions, in addition to the challenges and opportunities for linguistic pluralism in Algeria.

Chapter Three provides the literature review of the study by covering important concepts, that serve the objectives of this research, such as the monolingual and multilingual visions of language, monolingual and multilingual competence, linguistic repertoire, language and context, language choice, hierarchy in multilingualism, language attitudes, language and identity, code-switching and translanguaging, in addition to previous studies.

Chapter Four discusses the theoretical framework of this study. It explains Bourdieu's theory of Practice particularly his three main concepts "habitus, capital, and field" to apply it as a lens to analyse and discuss the data in this research. Bourdieu's key concepts are used to explain the link between language and power in the Algerian context from Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) teachers' perspectives. It is also used to understand how teachers exchange their linguistic capital in different markets.

Chapter Five provides an outline of the research methodology. It explains the research design of the study, which includes the adopted philosophical assumptions, the research method, the data collection tools, the sampling technique, the pilot study, the data analysis process, the trustworthiness of the research, and the ethical considerations that were considered during the course of the research. In addition, the chapter addresses the transcription and translation processes in light of researching multilingually.

Chapter Six explores Berber teachers' (Chaoui and Kabyle) linguistic repertoires. It demonstrates the components of their linguistic repertoires and provides an understanding of how they use the languages included in their repertoires in different fields and what affects their language choice. The findings of this chapter provide an answer to the first research question.

Chapter Seven displays teachers' attitudes toward the languages included in their linguistic repertoires. It provides explanations behind teachers' attitudes through looking back to their historical trajectories, which affect their perceptions. This chapter's findings answer the second research question in this study.

Chapter Eight demonstrates the relationship between language and power in Algeria from teachers' perspectives. It applies Bourdieu's theory of practice particularly his key concepts of habitus, capital and field to explain how the different languages in Algeria are valued

differently from one field to another and what affects teachers' perception in relation to language power.

Chapter Nine turns attention to the Algerian language policy in education and Berber teachers' (Kabyle and Chaoui) engagement with such policies. It investigates teachers' awareness of the Algerian language policy in education and their attitudes toward such policies.

Chapter Ten concludes the study by summarizing the findings from the data analysis in previous chapters. It offers conclusive answers to the research questions and acknowledges the limitations of the study. It also provides recommendations based on the findings to address identified issues in language policy and education. Additionally, the chapter highlights the contribution of the research.

Chapter Two

Language Situation in Algeria: Past, Present, and Future

2.1 Introduction

Questions about language have always been an issue of interest in colonial and post-colonial Algeria; from Frenchification during colonialism, Arabisation after independence, the Berber Spring, and Black Spring, until the present day (Daoudi, 2018). In both colonial and postcolonial Algeria language was and is used as a top-down power-ideology framed as being necessary for unifying the country (Daoudi, 2018). This chapter describes the language situation in Algeria, both past and present, highlighting issues such as politics and identity, Policy and planning for languages in education, tensions in language policy, planning and implementation, challenges, and opportunities for linguistic pluralism, and finally predictions of language planning and policy in Algeria. Addressing these issues regarding language situations during and after colonialism in Algeria can help in examining the linguistic repertoire of secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). According to Tittenbrun (2016) the social world is historically accumulated; therefore, looking back to the past and present situation of language in Algeria will help to know how the different languages existing in Algeria nowadays were internalised in the collective habitus of the Algerian society. This Chapter helps to explain individual linguistic habitus or linguistic capital, which is embodied in teachers included in this study. The chapter also provides some interpretations to explain Algerian Berber teachers' attitudes towards each of the languages existing in their multilingual repertoires and to know how teachers' habitus and attitudes affect their linguistic choices when they are in different fields including education.

2.2 Language, politics, and identity in the context of Arabisation in Algeria

The diversity of language in Algeria due to its long history with colonialism, makes the question of language far from being a simple case. Language politics during and after colonialism is tightly related to different ideologies, which opens room for issues related to identity, religion, and ethnicity (Daoudi, 2018). That is why understanding the different contexts of colonial and post-colonial periods, will permit more understanding about the micro-politics of language.

2.2.1 Colonial period

Regarding the French colonial period, language was a vital instrument to achieve the political and ideological endeavours of the coloniser. According to Benrabah (2004) language and politics go hand in hand, he described the relationship between them as a “wedded in an indissoluble union” (Benrabah, 2004, p. 60). In order to exert control over the Algerian population, the French colonial used language as a hard power, which is a defining feature of colonialism. According to Nye (2004) hard power involves the deployment of military force and economic power to influence and shape societal practices and change the ways of doing things.

Maamri (2009) reported that in 1830, when French colonialism was introduced in Algeria, many political and administrative institutions were constituted, which affected people’s lives, and how they work, learn, and interact. One main consequence of this strategy in Algeria was the exclusion of language (Daoudi, 2018).

To assimilate the Algerian society into the French culture, the colonial authorities adopted the idea of linguistic nationalism, which connotes the employment of one language to unify a nation and started to impose it on the Algerian population. According to Briggs (2010), the coloniser sought to merge the French language in Algeria by enforcing it as an official language and by imposing Frenchification in the educational system. During this period the main indigenous population of Algeria was Berbers and Arabs who had Tamazight and Derja as languages as described by Lorcin (1995). Daoudi (2018) reported that the imposition of Frenchification had deleterious effects on both Berber and Arabic as local languages (Daoudi, 2018). The French coloniser aimed to dispose the individuals of their identity and considered language as a tool and policy to achieve their aim. The intention of coloniser was not only to benefit from the Algerian economy, and its military, or even dominate it politically, but it was to join Algeria to France, as L’ Algérie Française (French Algeria), and to eliminate the language, religion, or any indicator of identity and culture (see Daoudi, 2018; Maamri, 2009; Haddam-Bouabdallah, 2022). Maamri (2009) reported that the colonial system forced a programme of acculturation and assimilation, and language was the main tool to realise this programme. They located French as a dominant language in Algeria (Maamri, 2009). According to Maamri (2009), the devastating state that is left by the colonial, who exercised

the policy of divide and rule, among others, caused a series of cultural issues that are related to the national identity of the country.

The colonial attempts to disregard the Algerian identity and local languages (Arabic and Berber), and replace them with French did not work, because back then, most of them considered those languages particularly Arabic as a symbol of identity that represent them, and as a symbol for resistance against colonialism. Therefore, according to Maamri (2009, p.77) the Algerian society “whose true identity had been denied” for more than a century, saw the necessity to construct their identity and thought about the Arabic language as the substratum to achieve that (Maamri, 2009). According to Briggs (2010), the French authorities failed to obliterate the other non-French languages, and French, Arabic, and Berber, remained in post-independent Algeria. However, more than fifty years after its independence from French colonialism, the country is still having problems with restoring the relationships between the various elements of its personality (Maamri, 2009), including language issues.

In his study, Judy (1997) pointed to the issue of language in Algeria. He brought into view the declaration of Soummam and its connection to language matters. Leaders of the Front de Liberation National (FLN), based on the Soummam declaration that took place in 1956, stated that the Arabic language should be brought back as the language of Algerians, and this should be a vital objective of the revolution. Judy (1997) explained the policy adopted by FLN as a legitimization of the elimination of diversity and differences within the Algerian society to obtain national unity (Judy, 1997). Reclaiming the Arabic language was the logo led by the FLN (1954–1962), which dates to Abdelhamid Ben Baddis, who instituted the Association of Algerian Ulemas in 1931. Abdelhamid Ben Baddis was a supporter of a unifying ideology, which calls for one religion, one language, and one country (see Daoudi, 2018; Benrabah, 2004). Consequently, under the claim of his association “Islam is my religion, Arabic is my language and Algeria is my country” (Ruedy, 2005, pp.133–135), and under the colonial situation, the Algerians felt the necessity of adopting this unifying ideology in which the language is a tool for the Algerianness and Islamisation of the country (Daoudi, 2018).

According to Bourdieu (1991, p.164), symbolic power is defined as that “invisible power, which can be exercised only with the complicity of those who do not want to know that they are subject to it or even that they, themselves, exercise it”. The employing of that symbolic power is what can produce symbolic violence (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992). During the

period of colonialism, the Algerian leaders of the revolution neglected the fact that the Algerian society is diverse (Berbers and Arabs), and decided to create a unifying identity for people, entailing sharing the same language (Arabic), which according to them will be motive for a liberating revolution. Although people under the colonial circumstances share different languages and identities (Tamazight and Arabic/ Amazigh and Arabs), they felt the necessity of accepting the FLN leaders' decision because they believed that would bring them a step forward to freedom. According to Judy (1997), the equation of language plus culture equals community, which gave great importance to language, was legitimised and accepted by most of the Algerian population who saw it as a clue for liberation.

2.2.2 Post-colonial Period

After the Algerian independence in 1962, the country turned into a battleground of various nationalist and Islamist ideologies calling for a strict Arab-Muslim identity (see Daoudi, 2018; Benrabah, 2013). The post-independent government witnessed a serious problem with the lack of legitimacy, the leaders who undertook political positions tried to build a state without considering this issue. According to Benrabah (2004), this lack of legitimacy dates back to Algerian ancestors who used to have a bad terms relationship with the central power since ancient times (Ottoman and French colonialism), which resulted in mistrust between people and the government. Benrabah (2004), stated that the relationship between the authorities and the nation was based on the "domination subjection" principle and was maintained by brutal force. Thus, the individual mode of representation of the central power was always characterized by suspicions towards the government (Benrabah, 2004). The new government after the Algerian independence viewed language as a tool to achieve legitimacy, it was used as a soft power. Language was seen as a policy or instrument that indirectly influences and manipulates people and controls their decisions (Daoudi, 2018).

The FLN government of Ahmed Ben Bella proclaimed the temporal continuity of bilingualism as a condition for the post-independent economic sector (see Judy, 1997). Ben Bella's government considered bilingualism as important for achieving fast industrialization. However, that decision was a legitimizing reason for the military coup that took place in 1965 (Judy, 1997). For Houari Boumediene, maintaining French instead of Arabic in the economic sector meant that the revolution is not complete. In 1963, Algeria was declared to be a socialist state, which has both Islam and Arabic as an official religion and language (see

Daoudi, 2018). In 1965, Houari Boumediene became the president of Algeria, after leading a coup d'état. This period demonstrated a state of unrest as a consequence of the lack of legitimacy, which led the new president to opt for radical nationalism in different fields as a solution to the legitimacy issue (see Daoudi, 2018).

In 1962 after the military coup, the Ulemas -a religio-conservative movement- had a vigorous contribution to the process of Arabisation. While the new government was looking for an instrument to solve the issue of legitimacy, the Ulemas proposed their support (Benrabah, 2004). In return, they were offered different positions in the government. A third of the government's positions including the Ministry of Cult, the Ministry of Information, and the Ministry of Education - were granted to them (Benrabah, 2004). The policy of Arabisation was highly supported by this movement, which had an ideology that calls for the impossibility to separate language and religion. Therefore, the Arabisation of society for them was considered inevitable with the Islamisation of the country (see Benrabah, 2004). The Ulemas considered language as a policy and tool to impose another culture rather than a medium that embodies an already existing culture. Thus, they denied the religion and the cultures of the people, and they rejected dialects and languages that represent them, which brought a sense of marginalisation of Berbers -the indigenous citizens of Algeria-, and a sense of alienation for most Algerians who had French education (see Benrabah, 2004; Daoudi, 2018).

Speaking about the connection between language and politics, the issue of legitimacy appears on the surface. According to Benrabah (2004), to make up for the lack of legitimacy witnessed after the Algerian independence, the political leaders -for political and ideological motives- adopted several instruments including socialism, nationalism, and Islam. Both nationalism and Islam entail the question of language (Benrabah, 2004). Islam is considered a legitimizing instrument, and a distinguishing feature that identifies Arab-Muslim countries where central power or the government is connected to the Arabic-written Quran. It was a very powerful instrument in the context of resistance against colonialism prompting the Algerian government to strategically exploit it of as a mean of acquiring political legitimacy. As for nationalism, the government found it an important agent for legitimizing, considering the fact of being an ex-colonized country. It helped the Algerian authorities in creating militant diplomacy, a history saga, and the language policy of Arabization. Benrabah (2004, p.63) has noted that "Arabic became a constituent part of Algerian nationalism because of its link with

the Quran and Islam". According to Benrabah (2004), the link or connection between nationalism and Islam is the Arabic language. Therefore, following independence, Algerian authorities applied the policy of Arabisation and imposed Arabic as the official and national language of Algeria.

According to Benrabah (2004, p.59) "Arabisation" in Algeria was adopted from the "assimilation" policy that dates to 18th-century liberal revolutions that sought to foster a sense of sameness among the majority of community members by sharing the same thoughts, the same behavioural habits, and the same language. This project (Arabisation) was a way to advocate Pan-Arabism led by other Arab countries, trying to be part of the wider Arab region (Daoudi, 2018). According to Benrabah (2004), the supporters of this view in Algeria, considered monolingualism as a type of nation-building, especially after coming out from a long period of colonialism, and as a key to lessen the conflicts (Benrabah, 2004). They saw linguistic pluralism as a source of miscommunication, inequality, and alienation between people of the same society. Benrabah (2004) reported that some political and social leaders (members) who used to serve the regime also had a belief that Arabisation would reduce and fill the gap between the state and nation because they considered the linguistic and cultural pluralism in Algeria as an issue that tends to cause disagreement between people. He gave an example of one political leader named "Nait Belkacem" who supported the Arabisation policy and reported that:

"The Arabic language and Islam are inseparable. Arabic has a privileged position as it is the language of the Quran and the Prophet, and the common language of all Muslims in the world, language of science, language of culture" (Benrabah, 2004, p. 63)

Benrabah (2004) indicated that the FLN (Front de Liberation Nationale), failed to bring unity among people. This failure was a consequence of the ethnic, cultural, and linguistic diversity that exists in Algeria, which was neglected by political leaders. Following Hobsbawm (1990) the FLN can be characterised as an internationalist movement, as opposed to a nationalist movement that aims to unite individuals based on shared ethnicity, language, culture, historical background, and similar factors (cited in Benrabah, 2004). In other words, Arabisation -in Algeria after independence- is quite similar to that adopted by the French regime during colonialism (Briggs, 2010). Correspondingly, to the colonial attempts to impose the French language among Algerians to absorb them into the French culture and to divest

them of their identity, the Algerian authorities also tried to impose Arabization on citizens from different ethnic, cultural, and linguistic backgrounds, in order to create unity in the country. However, this policy exacerbated things and created alienation among citizens.

Ironically, the government and the Algerian political leaders who supported Arabization contradicted themselves and preferred to send their children to French schools in order to gain more cultural capital and to get jobs (see Gillies, 2014; Daoudi, 2018). Arabization for Algerians was seen as exclusion and rejection of plurilingualism, which is a feature of the Algerian society. Being unable to use one's own language to convey and communicate thoughts created tensions and feelings of hatred toward the government, which weakened by its turn the legitimacy of authorities (Benrabah, 2004; Boukhchem and Varro, 2001).

According to Boukhchem and Varro (2011), the Arabic language, which was once a symbol of resistance against French colonialism, and a weapon for the unification of Algerians to get independence was not serving anymore neither in uniting the nation nor in the development of the country. Gillies (2014) considers that one of the reasons behind the failure of Arabization was the lack of prior planning and the recruitment of Egyptian teachers who were not qualified. Although Benrabah (2004) considers that Arabization was a means to provide political legitimacy to the government and as an instrument for controlling people, he believes that this policy failed to reduce conflicts and brought critical issues to both the authority of the system and to the social unity and solidarity because it was almost based on political and ideological factors.

2.3 Policy and Planning for Languages in Education in Algeria

From colonial to post-colonial Algeria, education and language have consistently served as influential tools employed by the government to pursue its political objectives. According to Benrabah (2013) schools were perceived as a device to linguistically dominate the population. The historical development of Algeria can be characterised by three periods, each of which had a significant impact on the language policies implemented in the field of education (Benrabah, 2007).

The first one is recognised by colonial occupation in Algeria; during this era, the French language was imposed in the schools and the educational system. The second period spans from 1960 to 1990 and was paralleled with European 19th-century nationalism, and with the

economic socialism era. The government during this period enforced Arabic gradually in the educational system. The third period started in the 2000s, it was characterised by the switch to a free economic market, which influenced the language policy in education and lead to less emphasis on the Arabic language (Benrabah, 2007).

The question of Language policies in Algerian education is a critical issue that has always been connected with politics. Implementing and planning Language in education is generally rooted in the history of Algeria itself and came as a reaction and resistance to colonialism and foreign interference (Or, 2017). Education and controlling language were used as an engine to produce or reproduce the existing dominant social order or the one that those who hold power aim to construct (Benrabah, 2004).

2.3.1 First phase: Colonial occupation

Controlling and assimilating Algerians into French culture was illustrated through the field of education during the colonial period. The French task during colonialism was characterised by the hegemony of the French language and French culture over other cultures and languages (Wardhaugh, 1987). The French authorities aimed at promoting their language with the sacrifice of the Arabic language, and schools were the key to achieving their aim, especially if the new generation is enrolled in their schools (Turin, 1983, Cited in Benrabah, 2005). However, they overlooked the fact that Algerians already have their own vision about education and civilisation (Benrabah, 2013). The Algerian schooling system was connected to religious institutions, and Islam was the mean used for thinking (Benrabah, 2013; Valensi, 1969).

Benrabah (2005) reported that twenty years after the appropriation of Algiers, and during the French occupation, the Algerians suffered from extreme kinds of cultural aggression as opposed to previous conquests. Therefore, the traditional educational system was falling during the last quarter of the 19th century (Colonna, 1975, Cited in Benrabah, 2005). Up to 1914, the efforts of French coloniser to provide education to Algerian children was not sufficient. In 1907, only 33000 Algerian children had formal education (in the Western sense), and it was not until 1917 that primary education became mandatory for boys, but after that, this changed to be limited only to those who live three kilometres away from the public school allocated for Algerians only (Benrabah, 2013). Parents were against the French education

offered by the colonial; they saw it as a threat to Islam, thus they preferred not to send their children to French schools even if that means to stay illiterate (Saad, 1992).

To convince Algerian children to attend French institutions, the French colonizer founded three types of schools. First, they established similar schools to those in metropolitan France, and then Arabic schools under the control of colonizer, and finally French-Arab schools where both languages are used as means of instruction (Benrabah, 2013). Although the Algerian traditional education failed, the majority of Algerians refused all kinds of education provided by the colonial authorities (Djeghloul, 1986, Cited in Benrabah, 2005). It was not until 1920-1922, that the Algerians started to accept the French schooling system, and their cultural resistance diminished, and instead, they started demanding more education in French (Heggoy, 1984, Cited in Benrabah, 2005). On the other hand, in 1920 many free private schools (medersa) were established throughout the country by the nationalist association, the Ulemas. It used the Arabic language to provide education to children (Smati, 1999). Although these schools abandoned teaching scientific disciplines, however, they provided students the chance to learn oral and written competence in standard Arabic. They were more concentrated on teaching the Arabic language and implanting the Islamic cultural identity, and the Pan-Arab values (Bennoune, 2000). Since then, education in the Arabic language started to increase more and more.

Although the attitudes of Algerians changed towards education in French, both the number and the progress of Muslim children's education in French were low compared to European children's schooling (Bennoune, 2000). The progress concerning using Arabic in education during that time was worse. The French language was considered the language of learning and culture, on the other hand, the Arabic language had no position or status. In 1935, the French authorities proclaimed Classical Arabic as a foreign language (Benrabah, 2013). They applied an ideology in which the disqualification of all languages, but French is their main endeavour (Grandguillaume, 1983). It was not until 1961 that Charles De Gaulle signed a decree in which he imposed Arabic teaching as a mandatory subject in primary cycle and acknowledged that 1938's decree that states that classical Arabic is a foreign language was a fault, and should be cancelled (Grandguillaume, 1983).

2.3.2 Second phase: 1960-1990s

After independence (1962), the Algerian authorities became dedicated to Arabisation. They considered Arabic as a language of civilisation (Gordon, 1978) Neglecting the fact that Algeria is linguistically and culturally diverse (Benrabah, 2004), the new government refused any status for other spoken languages in Algeria and promoted instead classical Arabic (Roberts, 2003). According to Benrabah (2004), the implementation of the policy in issue reflected an authoritarian approach, as there was a lack of effort to achieve consensus on this complex matter. Furthermore, there was a complete disregard for the linguistic and cultural diversity inside the country.

From 1963-1964, the usage of French gradually decreased, and teaching Arabic became mandatory at all levels and programmes (Bennoune, 2000). In 1963, the hours dedicated to teaching the Arabic language increased to ten (out of thirty) per week for all levels; while in 1964, grade one in primary schools was completely Arabised, and both religious and civics subjects were added to the programme (Grandguillaume, 2004). The authorities did not take into consideration the changes left at the end of French colonialism, including the raised number of students who are enrolled in the primary cycle, in addition to the issue of providing competent teaching personnel, which was not available as a result of the mass departure of educators in 1962 (see Bennoune, 2000). According to Bennoune (2000), these factors led to the growth of illiteracy among Algerians. Therefore, in 1964 the government hired one thousand (1000) Egyptians to teach the Arabic language (Grandguillaume, 2004). These teachers showed a stronger tendency towards providing ideological indoctrination to the students rather than focusing on teaching, primarily because most of them were members of a Muslim fraternity (Saad, 1992). According to Grandguillaume (2004) they relied on traditional teaching methods, which are considered to be inappropriate; in addition, their Arabic was not understood by Algerians in general and Berbers in particular. Benrabah (2004) indicated that Egyptian teachers turned out to be inadequate and unknowledgeable about the social situation in Algeria.

Under Boumediene's presidency following a military coup (1965-1978), Arabisation gained more encouragement. In 1967, the Algerian minister of education Ahmed Taleb Ibrahimi imposed Arabisation in the two first grades of the primary cycle, which was paralleled with poor educational quality, thing that prompted parents to postpone their children's enrolment

until grade three in which the French language is introduced (Saad, 1992). Parents' refusal to register their children until grade three is a strong indication of their refusal of linguistic hegemony and Arabisation policy. Ahmed Taleb Ibrahim, the minister of primary and secondary education stated that the policy of Arabisation is not going to work but still it will be applied (Grandguillaume, 2004).

Following independence, the Algerian educational system remained the same as in the colonial periods, which was composed of three levels. The first cycle is primary school; it includes five years. The second cycle is middle school, which is composed of four years. Finally, a secondary school comprises three years. However, starting from 1976 a new reform called the fundamental school was introduced in the educational system; both primary and middle school were merged to be nine successive years with total Arabisation for all subjects except for foreign languages (see Assous, 1985; Saad, 1992).

With the nomination of Mostafa Lachref as a minister of primary and secondary education in 1977, by President Boumediene, the Arabisation process witnessed a pause (see Grandguillaume, 2004). The fundamental school was side-lined, personnel who supported Arabisation in the ministry were discharged, and teacher training in French was reintroduced. The new minister also initiated bilingualism in primary schools with the French language as a medium to teach scientific disciplines (Maths, Calculus, Biology). Mostafa Lachref was an advocate of bilingual education and gradual Arabisation (Berri, 1973, cited in Benrabah, 2007). However, his attempts to initiate bilingual education did not see the light when he resigned after the death of President Boumediene in 1978.

The new president Chadli Bendjedid preferred the Arabophones (Islamists, conservatives, and nationalists) during his presidency (1979–1992). He preserved Arabic as an essential component of the Algerian Arab Muslim identity (Daoudi, 2018). In 1979 he appointed Mohamed Cherif Kharroubi as a minister of primary and secondary education. Kharroubi's first decisions included the initiation of the fundamental school system again, restarting the total Arabisation process, and introducing religious instruction as a mandatory discipline at all levels (Tefiani, 1984, cited in Benrabah, 2007). He also delayed teaching French as a first mandatory foreign language to grade four and introduced English as a second mandatory foreign language in grade eight. In the 1990s supporters of Arabisation put the minister of education under pressure to again postpone teaching the French language in the fundamental

school; however, the minister refused their claims, and instead, he qualified English to be in the same position as French (Laib, 1993, cited in Benrabah, 2007). To diminish the status of the French language, in 1993 the pro-arabised lobby granted children of fourth grade the option to choose between French and English language as a first foreign language (Grandguillaume, 2004). Yet, students' choice was in favour of the French language, which determined this language competition (Benrabah, 2013).

Algerian language planners see English as a language of modernity and technology. Also uncritically, they see English as needed because it has become a more powerful and dominant language. Controversially, perhaps, they see English as a language with no colonial background with Algeria, which according to them, makes it a powerful rival to the French language they seek to replace. However, the policy moves from French to English have not been embraced by francophone influenced Algerian elite who see the switch to the English language as something not beneficial to the country's education and economic life given the long history the country has had with the French language (Daoudi, 2018).

2.3.3 Third phase: 2000s

The issue of language implementation in the Algerian educational system started to be a matter of controversy from the early 2000s (Benrabah, 2007). The question of whether to stick to monolingualism or to move to bilingualism (Arabic and French) reached its peak in 2002 when Arab-Islamists (supporters of Arabisation) came with a *fatwa* (edict) opposing modernists (e.g., secular and/or francophone members of the population and the elite) who prefer the implementation of bilingualism policy and the reforms in the educational system (Abdelhai, 2001, cited in Benrabah, 2007). The fatwa states that the supporters of the reforms are enemies of Islam and the Arabic language (Djamel, 2001, cited in Benrabah, 2007), and it was a reaction to the recommendations of the National Commission for the Reform of the Educational System.

In mid-March 2001 the National Commission for the Reforms of the educational system founded by Abdelaziz Bouteflika the new president of Algeria, recommended reintroducing the bilingual educational system by adding the French language as a compulsory first foreign language starting from grade two (6-7 years) instead of grade four (8-9 years) as it was introduced since 1970. It also proposed for scientific subjects to be taught in French instead of Arabic starting in secondary schools (Sebti, 2001, cited in Benrabah, 2007). By making these

recommendations they sought to boost student level by creating bilingualism and biliteracy, and to shift from weak (French as a subject) to strong bilingualism (scientific discipline taught through French and Arabic). The new suggestions were to be applied in September 2001; however, as a result of the opposition witnessed by opponents of bilingual education, the Ministry of Interior suspended the reforms (Benrabah, 2007).

According to Messaoudi and Schemla (1995) the educational system was always portrayed as an ill-fated system. Both President Mohamed Boudiaf and Abdelaziz Bouteflika described the schooling system as a doomed one (Messaoudi and Schemla, 1995; Benrabah, 2013). Both government and the people saw the need for implementing reforms to the educational system. Thus, in 1999 the authorities conducted a survey to explore Algerians' attitudes towards including French in education and using it as a medium to teach scientific subjects. Seventy-five per cent of the population supported the idea of implementing French to teach scientific disciplines (Djamel, 2001, cited in Benrabah, 2007).

According to Benrabah (2007), three main reasons contributed to the transition from the monolingual schooling system to bilingual/multilingual education. First, the 11 September 2001 event put pressure on the Algerian government to include educational reforms as part of the worldwide war against terror (Gherzouli, 2019). Second, internationalism and the shift to a market economy imposed economic reforms that do not fit with the monolingual educational system. Finally, the socio-political factors that call for democratisation and the linguistic rights of the minority. Both the first languages of Algerians (Berber and Algerian Arabic) and French were targets of Arabisation. Thus, implementing the policy of Arabisation in the educational system, according to Benrabah (2007), was a black mark in the historical development of the Algerian educational system. It is considered one of the main reasons behind its failure and behind the religious fanaticism, and the civil war that took place in Algeria since the 1990s (Benrabah, 2007).

When President Bouteflika was put into power, he dealt with the issue of language in his speeches. He stated that, "for Algeria, I will speak French, Spanish, and English, and, if necessary, Hebrew" (Benrabah, 2013, pp.76). In another speech he adds that "an uninhibited opening up to the other international languages...does not constitute perjury...This is the price we have to pay to modernise our identity" (Benrabah, 2013, pp. 77), and he also said that "it is unthinkable to...spend ten years studying pure sciences in Arabic when it would only take

one year in English” (Benrabah, 2013, p.75). Bouteflika’s attitude toward languages may be explained as a result of him being a complete and ideal epitome of a bilingual person. (Daoudi, 2018). His statements concerning language questions were a way to declare the failure of the Arabisation policy, and to encourage bilingualism, in addition to getting out of the French-Arabic dichotomy (Daoudi, 2018; Kaplan and Baldauf, 2007).

In Algeria, since 2000s, the educational reforms were primarily focused on improving teachers’ level and their socio-economic status, reconsidering the situation of foreign languages, in addition to revising the content of the curriculum. The recommended changes revolved around three key areas. Firstly, the restructuring of educational sector, which involved implementing a dedicated pre-school program for children aged five-year-old, modifying the primary and middle school durations by reducing the former from six to five years and expanding the latter to four instead of three years, and introducing general education and technical education as streams at the secondary school level (Tawil, 2006). The second focus on restructuring teachers' training covered efforts to enhance teachers' and inspectors' knowledge, evaluating training programs, and facilitating the integration of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in educational institutions. The third dimension focused on pedagogical reform, specifically dealing with content and methods. This included the implementation of new curricula, the provision and assessment of instructional resources, and the adoption of innovative teaching approaches aligned with the objectives of the curriculum (Tawil, 2006).

The Algerian Language policy in education has always been authoritarian entailing top-down decisions (Benrabah, 2004; Benrabah, 2005). Maintaining a hold on power gives the government the ability to dominate the population and impose their culture and norms on them using language and education as weapons to reach their aim. That is, reforms made concerning monolingual/bilingual/multilingual education in Algeria are more than just educational and language issues, rather they are an outcome of political ideology, political initiatives, and tides of political change (Baker, 2003). In other words, as reported by Benrabah (2004, p.60), “language and politics in Algeria are “wedded in an indissoluble union”. Imposing the Arabisation project after independence as an example, was a reaction to French colonialism, which tried to impose their culture on Algerians, which created a sense of resistance to the French language even after independence. The Algerian government after

independence also imposed the same language policies, which were imposed by France on Algerians. By forcing Arabisation in Algeria, a sense of alienation and mistrust was created among people toward the Centrale power. Ignoring the fact of being a multilingual and multicultural country (Arabs, Berbers) created many tensions between the different groups of people and the government.

2.3.4 Al Hirak (The smile revolution)

Al Hirak or also referred to as the smile revolution (SR). It started on 22nd February 2019 and persisted until its interruption due to the global Covid-19 pandemic. According to Maraf and Vanci (2023), the emergence of the SR can be traced to the intricate political system and the low socio-economic conditions that had prevailed in Algeria for decades. According to (Kessar et al., 2021) the Hirak movement focused primarily on opposing former President Bouteflika's nomination for a fifth term, considering it a clear breach of the constitution as his health condition hindered his ability to fulfil his constitutional duties.

The roots of the SR protests were not isolated incidents; rather, they can be traced back to historical and political developments in Algeria during the 1980s. After independence in 1962, Algeria underwent a period of single-party rule until the 1980s, when President Chadli Ben Jedid initiated a transition to a multi-party system (Benrabah, 2004). Subsequently, in 1991, Algeria experienced elections that marked a significant departure from its dominant political party FLN to FIS, an Islamic political party. Following its electoral loss, the government cancelled the election results and declared a state of emergency (Maraf and Vanci, 2023).

The circumstances described were the beginning of the 'black decade', which was viewed by some as a civil war and by others as a counter-terrorism war (Benrabah, 2004). In 1999, after a decade of political instability, the dominant political party FLN successfully reintroduced its rule, bringing stability back under the rule of Abdelaziz Bouteflika, the former president of Algeria. Bouteflika was initially perceived as a figure who could bring an end to conflict and violence of the black decade; however, over the course of more than two decades, Algeria experienced widespread deterioration marked by corrupt practices (Maraf and Vanci, 2023).

In addition to the overt political and governance-related demands expressed by Algerians (Bentahar, 2021) including the termination of Bouteflika's regime on account of his medical condition and involvement in corruption; the expansion of democratic possibilities within the

nation; the establishment of a social and cultural movement aimed at fostering the development of individuals and groups as active citizens; and the improvement of Algeria's economic situation by reducing foreign influence across all sectors (Maraf and Vanci, 2023), there were underlying cultural demands that start with the linguistic matter in Algeria (Bentahar, 2021). Language played an essential role during the movement. It displayed unprecedented capacity to overcome social and economic disparities, uniting substantial segments of the population in pursuit of a common political goal (Maraf and Vanci, 2023). The Hirak illustrated the diverse linguistic landscape in Algeria by incorporating multiple languages in its slogans, such as English, Arabic, Tamazight, and French. This movement united these languages with a singular purpose: to amplify their voices and convey their message to the world. The subsequent slogans demonstrate that:

Figure 1: Multilingual Hirak Slogans

As part of the government's response to the demands of the Smile Revolution, there were suggestions to promote the development and integration of the English language within educational institutions at both the university and school levels (Maraf and Vanci, 2023).

2.4 Policy-Practice Tensions in Language Policy, Planning, and Implementation

French colonialism in Algeria had a traumatic effect on Algerians in both the colonial and post-colonial periods. The feeling of insecurity and uncertainty about one's identity became one outcome of the long colonial period (Benrabah, 2013). Language as a component of one's

identity and culture had a crucial role in shaping events in both periods. In a multilingual space, “Language conflict arises when people try to carve out a space for their own tongue, which expands to other linguistic territories” (Benrabah, 2013, p. 2). When languages expand to other linguistic areas, they create tensions between the speakers of the different languages (Nelde, 1997). That is, being a former colony with a multilingual background, gave rise to conflicts related to language planning and language policies in Algeria. When the different cultural groups (Berbers and Arabs), particularly minorities underwent the process of Arabisation and the reforms included in education, they felt neglected, undervalued, and marginalized (Benrabah, 2013). This marginalization applied by the government contributed to the maintenance of mistrust toward central power.

Historically speaking, the invaders in colonies generally enforce their own languages on the colonized in order to eradicate the diversity among local tongues and cultures. This process is referred to as linguicide, it is a way of destructing languages. A radical version of it is called linguistic genocide through which the colonizer uses military forces, or the educational systems in order to destroy the targeted languages (see Benrabah, 2013). According to Phillipson (1992), schools are very important for teaching languages and are deemed as crucial linguistic devices for domination. Benrabah (2013), on the other hand, considers schools as a weapon for language death. Similarly, during French colonialism, the European and Arab-Berber cultures were brought into violent contact. This cultural conflict between the French colonizer and Algerians, was a consequence of the centric belief of the former that the French culture and language are superior to indigenous languages and cultures (Berbers-Arabs) (see Benrabah, 2013).

In the nineteenth century, Europe had a great power as being the centre of the world, this provided its elite with a complete belief in the superiority of their culture and civilisation and lead them to reject any idea of an alternative or equal culture or civilisation (see Benrabah, 2013). According to Benrabah (2005) the French mission of the so-called civilisation process was based on the dominance of language and culture over local languages and cultures. Thus, their attempts to assimilate Algerians into French culture were demonstrated through education. They relied on the following three methods, which according to them were of high importance: divide and rule, instruct to conquer, and language superiority (see Benrabah, 2013). However, in a similar way, the Algerians were certain that their language and their

culture are superior to that of the colonizer, which brought the two languages into contact. According to Benrabah (2013) they refused and resisted the assimilation policy, adopted by the French colonial, which in its turn inflamed the tension between the two communities for more than a century. He reported that the linguistic process opted for by the French coloniser entailed the phenomenon of hierarchizing languages, and marginalizing languages of indigenous people, which resulted in creating a base for conflict and oppression. Benrabah (2013) explained that the significant resistance emerged from Islam as a religious and cultural entity with a profound legacy, as well as from Arabic, the linguistic medium associated with the Quran, the sacred text of Muslims. The disagreement and tensions between the coloniser and the colonised led to a war that started in November 1954, and ended in July 1962 with Algerians gaining their independence (see Benrabah, 2013).

The new central power in ex-colonized countries often opts for the same ideology applied by their colonizer during colonialism. They employ that ideology to produce or keep certain hierarchical relationships between the existing languages in that country, and to minimize other languages which, according to the new governor, do not serve people outside their linguistic spaces, as opposed to the intended dominant language, which is considered as a language of civilization. Therefore, they prepare the required conditions for language dominance by reproducing colonial practices. In other words, officialising one language over the others comes under nationalistic justification, but it exceeds the intention of dominating speakers of certain minor groups (Benrabah, 2013).

The process of Language planning and language policies in multilingual and multicultural countries are usually employed to lessen the linguistic strife existing in the country as a step toward its development. Language planners impose their policies as a pretext for restoring unity in the country (Benrabah 2013). However, as Kaplan (1990, p.4) stated, language policies are “commonly stated in altruistic terms but often not based on altruistic intents”. In other words, although the explicit intention of implementing a dominant language is to promote participation and access among different groups of a nation, however, implicitly it produces the expropriation and deprivation among speakers of other existing languages (Benrabah, 2013). Moreover, language planners are often elites, who occupy social, political, or economic power positions, which give them the ability to implement languages according to what serves them. These unplanned, top-down language policies generally produce resistance

against the unjust and unequal linguistic policies from the marginalised speakers of other languages (Benrabah, 2013).

Announcing that Algeria and Algerians are Arabs by Ben Bella in 1962, was seen as a kind of formalisation of the Arabo-Islamic ideology in Algeria (Benrabah, 2013). Defining Algerian identity as fundamentally Arab suggests that Algeria mirrors the trajectory of its former colonizer. It emphasized a nationalistic approach that promotes monolingualism in Arabic. This decision was authoritarian, that is, it was a top-down and unplanned implementation through which indigenous groups felt the alienation and the marginalization of their own local languages (Berber, Derja). Thus, according to Rouchdy (2013), the language contact in Algeria and the way the government dealt with it, lead to many tensions and ideological conflicts that turned Algeria into a battleground).

The 1980s in Algeria marked significant tensions, exemplified by events like the 'Berber Spring' and 'Black Spring', which emerged as consequences of language contact. In 1949, during French colonialism, a clash between Arabo-Islamists and Berberists erupted over language planning in the future independent Algeria. According to Goodman (2004), this conflict is considered 'the first Berber Spring' in Algeria. Back then, before 1954, the members of PPA (Parti du Peuple Algérien) and MTLD (Mouvement pour le Triomphe des Libertés Démocratiques) -two revolutionary movements created by Massali, who supported the Arabo-Islamic ideology during colonialism- were divided into supporters of the Arabisation of the future independent Algeria, and opponents (most of them belong to Kabyle roots) who call for equality between the different languages and cultures existing in Algeria. Massali, the founder of these movements and the supporter of Unitarianism, overvalued language hegemony and ignored the linguistic plurality, which was the reality of Algeria. The latter group, however, believed and still believe that Algerianness should comprise all languages of Algerians including Berber and Colloquial Arabic. This strife between the two groups produced the 1949 Berberist crisis, which was the beginning of many conflicts that took place after the independence as a result of language diversity (see Ouerdane, 2003).

Following the accession of Bendjedid to power, many conflicts related to language and identity emerged. Between 1979 and 1980, Algeria witnessed two main conflicts related to language matters. The first crisis was in November 1979, when Arabised students at Algiers universities led a strike for two months, against the government's unfair preferential

treatment to those who are competent in the French language at the expense of Arabised graduates. Their favouritism was demonstrated when it comes to real economic opportunities. As a consequence of the protest and fear from the reaction of Islamic fundamentalists, who were gaining power at that time, the government promoted Arabisation at the secondary and university levels and provided many positions at the level of ministries and educational institutions to proponents of Arabization, which gave more jobs to unemployed arabised graduates with the maintenance of competent speakers of French as dominant in the economic sector (see Benrabah, 2013).

Another conflict known as “Berber Spring” erupted in Kabylia owing to “uneasiness had been fuelled by, among other things, attacks on Berber Language and culture” (Benrabah, 2013, p. 67). Berbers saw the need to preserve their culture and language, which are being under threat and siege (Maddy-Weitzman, 2001). In April 1980, the Kabyle setting went into civil disobedience against the government. They called for institutionalising the Berber language as a language of teaching, and media (see Benrabah, 2013). They opposed the compulsory Arabisation, claimed the official admission of Berber culture and language, and called for the liberalisation and democratisation style of the western, which they considered as the sole means to assure their rights as a non- Arab, but as Amazigh (Maddy-Weitzman, 2001). According to Goodman (2004), “20 April 1980 is already a repetition, a reappearance of a demand for Berber culture that had long been inhibited” (p.63). The police attempt to restrict and discourage the strike of students and workers resulted in the death of more than 30 persons, and the injury of hundreds (Benrabah, 2013; Maddy-Weitzman, 2001). This crisis was the first serious conflict in the history of independent Algeria and was a clear indicator of the predictability of the end of formalised Arabo-Islamism (Benrabah, 2013).

Following this conflict, between the 1990s and 2000s, Kabylia was again in turmoil (see Benrabah, 2013). The malfunction of the Algerian government in the early 1990s faced Kabylia and Kabylia Berbers with new challenges and opportunities (see Maddy-Weitzman, 2001). In the 1991 elections, Kabylia were against the Islamist Front Islamique du Salut (FIS), instead, a small percentage of them supported the Rassemblement pour la Culture et la Democratique (RCD), headed by Dr. Sa'id, while the rest advocated the Front des Forces Socialistes (FFS). FFS was more national and supported a neutral stance between the government and the FIS. On the other hand, the RCD was more communal/ethnic. Both

parties shared the vision of modern Algeria, which entails modern culture that joins Islam with the Berber language, respect for Berber traditions, and modernity that emerge from the French language. However, their vision was threatened by the civil war, and by the various attack on the Kabyle figures who were considered as symbols of evil culture by Islamists (see Maddy-Weitzman, 2001).

During the first year of warfare, the FFS party remained with the same demands, while the RCD was against the government, and at the same time were calling for defeating the fundamentalists' forces as a main objective. The latter stance was more pleasing to Berbers who were claiming the recognition of Tamazight and Berber culture (see Maddy-Weitzman, 2001).

In 2001 a young Kabyle aged 18 was killed after the state forces shoot at the crowd. This incident, referred to as the 'Black Spring', inflamed ongoing unrest in Kabylia and Algiers, which in its turn led to the death of more than one hundred people (see Goodman, 2004). Later in 2002, the government as a reaction to the "Black Spring", announced the Berber language (Tamazight) as a national language and decreed an article that dictates that in the constitution. In effect, the 2002 declaration was a kind of recognition of the linguistic plurality and pluralism in Algeria (see Benrabah, 2013).

To sum up, the language contact in Algeria before and after colonialism, and the language policies adopted by the authorities were always a source of conflict and tension. The fact that Algeria is a multicultural and multilingual country requires careful cultural and linguistic planning from the government. That is, the authorities should take into consideration all the ethnic groups existing within the country while taking decisions concerning language management. However, historically speaking the Algerian government opted for authoritarian policies that glorify monolingualism at the expense of other local languages (Berber, Derja) these unplanned top-down policies produced mistrust, hatred, and tensions towards the government. The feeling of alienation and marginalization of one's own culture and language, and the expropriation of one's identity led the targeted groups of people to resist the government and call for pluralism, which is the only way to restore their identity, culture, and language.

2.5 Challenges and Opportunities for Linguistic Pluralism in Algeria

Algeria as a multilingual and multicultural country entails different ethnic groups including Berbers who are considered the indigenous population, and Arabs who came to North Africa to spread Islam in the area. This history combined with French colonialism, which remained in Algeria for more than one century, produced the linguistic pluralism of present Algeria. The diverse cultural background of the Algerian population, and the different linguistic repertoires they have can be seen as a good opportunity for linguistic pluralism in the country, however, the Algerian policymakers and for political and ideological reasons, keep creating challenges for this linguistic pluralism, and instead, they keep paving the way for a monolingual country.

In pre-independent Algeria (1954), the members of PPA also known as MTLD were divided into two groups: Advocates of Arabisation who are against pluralism in the future independent Algeria, and opponents of Arabisation who call for equality between all the existing languages and cultures. The latter group “believed that, in addition to the Arabic and Islamic constituent parts, Algerianness should also include Berber, Turkish and, why not – although not openly declared – French elements” (Benrabah, 2013, p.46). However, the controversy between the two views ended in favour of the former (Harbi, 1993; Ouerdane, 2003). In other words, post-independent Algeria decided to be centralized Jacobinism and Unitarianism, rather than culturally and linguistically pluralistic, which is a characteristic of its population.

Language competition in postcolonial Algeria came mainly in two forms, which are status and acquisition planning (Benrabah, 2013). Following independence, Arabic was proclaimed the official language of Algeria (Daoudi, 2018; Benrabah, 2013). President Ben Bella’s triple assertion in April 1962, restricted the Algerian national identity as fundamentally Arab and disregarded the reality of being a multilingual country (Benrabah-2013). In 1963 the parliament voted for introducing Arabic in all administrations (Gallagher, 1968), and in 1964, it was initiated as the working language in the parliament. At the status level, leaders of the newly independent Algeria imposed Arabic at the expense of the linguistic pluralism of the country (Derja and Tamazight) (see Benrabah, 2013). Benrabah (2004) reported that on the acquisition level, assuming that schools are tools for socializing individuals and reproducing the same societal order that comprises dominant groups and dominated agents, the

government used education to set up their desired social order. Thus, after independence, the first institution to be Arabised was the educational system.

The Arabization policy that was shown as a tool for creating national unity by asserting the Algerian identity as Arab and Muslim overlooking other identities (Déjeux, 1965 cited in Benrabah, 2013 p.53) was not that “disinterested”, according to Kaplan (1990, p.4). Kaplan (1990, p.4) believes that the language interventions and management are “commonly stated in altruistic terms but often not based on altruistic intents”. In other words, the Arabisation policy in decolonised Algeria can reflect the “elites' own interests as a dominant group seeking to maintain their position of power” as stated by Benrabah (2013, p.15).

Benrabah (2013) argues that “the establishment of unjust and violent structures in societies in general and colonised communities, in particular, generate the necessary conditions for linguistic oppression and conflict” (p.4). Similarly, the Algerian language policy adopted by those in power aimed to eradicate the diversity of indigenous tongues by forcing individuals to accept Arabic as a dominant language. This top-down linguistic policy can be regarded as a violent and oppressive way of dealing with languages of the indigenous speakers as it seeks to marginalize the minorized languages. Therefore, while the outer aim of Arabisation was to unify Algerians under the same culture and language (Benrabah, 2004; Daoudi, 2018), yet in reality, it served as a factor of disunity. It marginalised the native inhabitant of Algeria (Berbers), in addition to many Algerians who got French education (Daoudi, 2018). The multilingual and multicultural nature of Algeria (Berbers and Arabs), in addition to its history with French colonialism, are regarded as opportunities for linguistic pluralism. These factors can be deemed as good indicators of the convenience of linguistic pluralism in independent Algeria.

However, the Algerian authority's rejection to institutionalize the local languages (Berber and Derja) was demonstrated through their response to a sociolinguistic survey, which was undertaken by a team of American sociolinguists from the University of California, Berkeley in 1963/1964. The survey aimed at framing the sociolinguistic situation of Algeria. As a result, the team suggested the institutionalisation of Berber and Algerian Arabic languages as they are the most widely utilized (Elimam, 1997, cited in Benrabah, 2013). The notion of nationalism or the monolingual policy adopted by the Algerian government thus challenged the possibility of embracing linguistic pluralism in the country. “The ideological and political

decision-making process and the refusal to acknowledge the sociolinguistic reality of the country have produced a language policy that has exacerbated existing conflicts and created new ones” (Benrabah, 2004, p.74).

2.6 The Future of Language Planning and Policy in Algeria

Language contact in a multilingual setting is not always associated with conflicts, rather there can be linguistic peace among speakers of different tongues. Language strife happens when individuals try to impose their own languages at the expense of other languages within that setting (Benrabah, 2013). According to Nelde (2017), tensions and resentment are generated when languages spread on the territories of other languages. Fishman (1972) stated that language conflicts that arose from language contact are linked to the language planning and language policy exercised after independence (Fishman cited in Benrabah, 2013).

Language management including its three dimensions (Corpus planning, acquisition planning, and status planning) can produce many conflicts in a multilingual context. That is, status planning may produce tensions between speakers of different tongues after selecting one language or more as an official or national language at the expense of others. On the other hand, corpus planning can create conflicts as a reaction to favouring one particular word, writing system, or pronunciation over the rest. As for acquisition planning, strife can appear from the choice of one language over the existing languages as a medium of instruction in the educational system (Benrabah, 2013). Therefore, language management, in all its forms, which are connected to each other, instead of reducing the conflicts and unifying the population, may boost and exacerbate these tensions (Benrabah, 2013; Benrabah, 2004).

In the Algerian case, the language planning and policies exercised after independence were in favour of centralized monolingualism in Arabic. Although its population was marked by multilingualism and multiculturalism, the implementation of Arabization was an authoritarian top-down policy. The government did not seek any consensus on this linguistic issue (Benrabah, 2004). This rejection to recognize the sociolinguistic situation of Algeria caused conflicts between its population and the government (Benrabah, 2004).

This is opposed to top-down language planning and policy, in which the vast majority is neglected, and decisions are concerned with people who hold power and authority (Kaplan and Baldauf, 1997), bottom-up linguistic management positions the community in a powerful

status, which means that the process of planning reflects direct interventions from people (Baldauf, 1994). This strategy may be a good opportunity that gives rise to linguistic pluralism and linguistic peace.

Multilingualism is seen by some theorists as a challenge to nation-building, however, the sociolinguist Agnihotri (2009) considers linguistic pluralism as a means to smooth reciprocal understanding and inter-group communication. He regards multilingualism not just as a way to stop the detrimental sociolinguistic stereotypes that aim to disgrace some linguistic forms and elevate the status of other forms, but also as a phenomenon that fosters social tolerance, cognitive resilience, higher levels of linguistic and scholastic achievement, and the diverse way of reasoning (Agnihotri, 2009)

Friedrich (2007) suggest two approaches to foster both linguistic pluralism and linguistic peace. The first strategy is linguistic education, which has to be promoted from an early age and should aim to create tolerance towards plurilingualism. The second approach is linguistic activism, which should be undertaken by fostering democratic and participatory societies that aim to eliminate the sociolinguistic stereotypes held by policymakers.

In sum, the authoritarian language planning and policy adopted in Algeria raised many crises in Algerian society. This policy is regarded as an obstacle to plurilingualism, which is considered as a characteristic of the Algerian population (Benrabah, 2004). Therefore, according to what Algerian and foreign observers have indicated, the Algerian language policy and planning need a serious evaluation. "One possible way out is to give priority to a global societal project grounded on an ideology that favours pluralism in general and multilingualism in particular" (Benrabah, 2004, p.75). In other words, Benrabah (2004) suggested that to help the progression of Algeria towards linguistic democracy, it is essential to initiate an effective language planning method that is grounded in methodological principles and sociolinguistic surveys. This approach would embody a bottom-up planning approach. This would foster unity in society and establish effective communication channels between the government and people across different levels (Baker, 1988).

2.7 Conclusion

In conclusion, this contextual chapter provides a comprehensive picture of the linguistic situation in Algeria. It traces the historical evolution of the dynamic interplay between

language, political ideologies, and societal identities within Algerian context during and after colonialism. The chapter shed light on the Arabisation, which was influenced by the monolingual policies of the French colonialism in Algeria. It also examines the policies and planning for languages in education revealing a landscape marked by tensions between the explicit policy intentions and their practical implementation. Moreover, the chapter highlights the challenges and opportunities for linguistic pluralism in Algeria, emphasizing the need to navigate these complexities for a more inclusive and responsive language policy framework. Algeria, with its multilingual and multicultural situation, needs thoughtful planning and policies for the future to ensure that different languages can harmoniously coexist in the country. This chapter serves as a foundation for understanding the linguistic repertoires of Algerian Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) teachers in Algeria.

Chapter Three

Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a review of relevant literature to the study. It starts with identifying key issues and concepts extracted from selected literature related to the nature of this study. The literature review examined in this chapter identified the following key issues in the discourse: monolingual/multilingual visions of language, multilingual competence, linguistic repertoire, language choice, hierarchy in multilingualism, Language and identity, language attitudes, code-switching, and translanguaging. The literature provides a contextualisation to the study within the existing literature, paving the way for an understanding of the linguistic complexities in the Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) educational context. The chapter also provides a review of previous research conducted at both global and Algerian levels on the topic. While these studies may not mirror the exact focus of this study, they offer valuable insights and contributions to the understanding of linguistic repertoires from diverse perspectives.

3.2 Monolingual/multilingual visions of language

According to Georges and Bernard (2009), the majority of the twentieth-century language models focused on studying languages as a single and independent system. As Language boundaries were demonstrated and drawn, languages were considered as separated entities. Therefore, concepts such as interference, code-switching, transfer, and translanguaging, which usually take place within a multilingual setting, were seen as imperfections that must not be tolerated, and as an illegitimate phenomenon that should be resisted. In this regard, supporters of this view judged bilingual individuals as having a deficiency, and as being a danger for the competence of controlling both the singular language per se and the culture attached to it, the thing that will put one's cognitive and social identity under threat. Even in settings where plurilingualism is the foundation and the norm, language contact was distrustful (Georges and Bernard, 2009).

The monolingual perspective on language generally prevails among those who have powerful languages for wider communication such as French, English, Spanish. Usually, this linguistic myopia is associated with a lack of cultural awareness and is applied through the policies that elevate one language at the expense of other languages (Edwards, 1994). Plurilingualism was

deemed a deficiency and a neglected phenomenon, however, during that time, many studies on bilingualism and multilingualism were initiated and undertaken from a monolingual infrastructure in which plurilingualism is considered a duplication of monolingualism (Georges and Bernard, 2009).

Because of the increased linguistic contact both internationally and regionally, research in sociolinguistics indicated the possibility of using more than one language with no obstacles (Georges and Bernard, 2009). The concept of language variation (Hymes, Fishman, Labov, Blanche Benveniste, Lagarde, etc.) had a very important role to play in the shift from the monolingual understanding of language, which has been eminent for so long to a more pluralistic vision (Georges and Bernard, 2009). Georges and Bernard (2009) stated that if all languages exhibit variation, knowing one language can be considered as a start to plurilingualism. That is, to move from one language to another by using utterance that belongs to it, is like using a variant from the same language. Thus, the interest in verbal interaction started to grow more in the field of sociolinguistics.

Research in bilingualism claimed a more holistic and integrated vision of bilingualism. A vision that entails much more than just two monolingual systems (Hornberger and Link, 2012). Grosjean (1985) indicated that bilingualism should not be regarded as two separate complete or uncompleted monolinguals. Garcia (2011), trying to elucidate her vision of plurilingualism (indicating both bilingualism and multilingualism), gave the analogy of a bicycle. According to her a bilingual reflects more than a monolingual twice. Bilingualism can be metaphorically likened to an All-terrain vehicle, characterised by wheels that possess the ability to adapt and conform to the irregularities of the terrain, in contrast to the simplistic analogy of a bicycle with two uniformly round and balanced wheels (Garcia, 2011). When communication happens, features such as Craters, ridges, and gaps float to the surface and become salient. Thus, a simple bicycle with two wheels would not work in this terrain (Garcia, 2011). Similarly, a traditional vision of plurilingualism, which values the separated and disconnected wholes, that is, the separation of languages regardless of the situation or the context, is not the way for successful and fruitful communication between human beings. In summary, introducing a new language to be taught is not enough to fabricate true multilingual teaching. One should stop looking from a monolingual perspective to multilingual individuals and should instead transcend from the classical notion of competence to a more pluralistic one such as code-

switching and translanguaging, which depict the use of the whole linguistic repertoire or verbal resources (Georges and Bernard, 2009).

3.3 Monolingual/Multilingual competence

Crystal (1987), in the field of linguistics, defines "monolingual" as an individual who can speak and use only one language, and a community proficient in only one language, he also referred to as unilingual. According to Richards and Schmidt (2002), the term "monolingual" refers to an individual possessing active proficiency in a single language, although they may have impassive knowledge of others as well. This definition suggests that an individual with submissive knowledge of other languages may still be considered monolingual. On the other hand, Cenoz (2013) defines multilinguals as individuals who are proficient in and use more than one language, including bilinguals and trilinguals. Wei (2008) provides a definition of a multilingual individual as someone capable of communication "in more than one language", whether actively through "speaking and writing" or passively through "listening and reading" (p. 4). Cenoz (2013) suggests that multilingualism encompasses both individual and societal dimensions, serving as both a personal and a societal capability. "Individual and societal multilingualism are not completely separated" (p.5). In communities with multiple languages, individuals are more inclined to speak several languages compared to those in societies with only one language (Cenoz, 2013).

According to Cenoz (2013) multilingualism has been associated with regions featuring regional or minority languages and border areas. However, the global spread of English as a lingua franca and increased population mobility to urban centres introduced new dynamics. Nowadays, individuals who have acquired proficiency in English can be found in monolingual regions. Whereas major cities in Europe or North America, which are shaped by substantial linguistic diversity, may still have monolingual speakers, particularly in contexts where English serves as the dominant language.

As noted by Bassetti and Cook (2011), definitions of multilingualism typically fall into two main categories: one that requires a high level of proficiency and another that allows for more modest language skills. According to Skutnabb-Kangas and McCarty (2008), the conventional notion that bilingual or multilingual individuals must achieve a perfect mastery and balance in two or more languages is no longer a strict requirement.

Grosjean (1982) states that the linguistic competence of multilingual individuals is made up of many fractional competencies, which complete each other to generate an arena of resources that serve to accomplish and achieve different life functions. Multilingual individuals thus, are not needfully required to be fluent in all languages in their repertoires, rather they are expected to have different degrees of control over these languages (Sridhar, 1996). The degree of command over these different languages may differ from knowledge of only a few words, memorized expressions like greetings, and basic conversational abilities, to a high level of proficiency encompassing comprehensive knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, as well as mastery of specialized registers and styles (Sridhar, 1996).

Selective functionality is another feature of the linguistic competence of multilingual people. Multilingual speakers draw links between each of the languages they have in their linguistic repertoire and their functions in different contexts. In this sense, they grow their competencies in each of these languages based on the degree they need it, and the context it will be exercised in (Sridhar, 1996).

3.4 Linguistic repertoire

The estimation of the existing number of spoken languages in the world ranges from 4000 to 8000. Each of these languages provides its holders with a unique way of perceiving the world, and an exclusive range of cultural opportunities (Wardhaugh, 1987). Taking into consideration the great number of the existing languages, and the degree of regional and international contact and spread between them- mainly due to territorial expansion and migration-, a multilingual repertoire should not be regarded as a departure from the normal, but rather, as the norm. In such contexts, at least a bilingual competence is sought after (Edwards, 1994).

The notion of verbal repertoire has attracted a lot of attention over the past decades. Linguistic repertoire is defined as the totality of linguistic varieties, which are used to communicate in a significant social interaction (Gumperz, 1964). It was first coined by Gumperz in the 1960s and initially referred to as verbal repertoire (Busch, 2012). The concept of linguistic repertoire entails all the possible ways of coining a message. It “provides the weapons of everyday communication, speakers choose among this arsenal in accordance with the meanings they wish to convey” (Gumperz, 1964, p.138). Blommaert (2010) defines the linguistic repertoires as all linguistic and communicative dispositions that people own and make use of when they encounter different situations. A focal point in the notion of

multilingual repertoires is that it embodies the whole, that is, it is not limited to languages, but it also includes dialects. Both languages and dialects “form a behavioural whole, regardless of grammatical distinctness, and must be considered constituent varieties of the same verbal repertoire” (Gumperz, 1964, p.140). According to Busch (2012) the concept of linguistic repertoire covers the whole, that is, all the available resources that contribute to forming the message to communicate. It goes beyond the traditional thinking that codes and languages are bounded structures.

The notion of linguistic repertoire can be addressed and discussed within both monolingual and multilingual contexts. In the former, speakers’ repertoires are made of a range of stylistic, social, regional, and functional varieties, while in the latter, the verbal repertoire indicates the total range of languages and dialects, which are used as resources to communicate. The repertoire in this case is considered more complex than in a monolingual context as it does not include just dialects, but also languages, each with its own set of pragmatic, lexical, grammatical, and sociolinguistic regulations, and conventions (Sridhar, 1996).

Taking into consideration that the linguistic repertoire is a sociolinguistic concept, it can be explained at both, social and linguistic levels (Gumperz, 1964; Nilep, 2006). It links and connects the grammatical systems of languages to society. Gumperz states that the linguistic repertoire as a linguistic entity “bridges the gap between grammatical systems and human groups” (Gumperz, 1964, p.151). That means that the linguistic repertoire that is used in certain situations is identified depending on the participants, the situation, and the topic or the content (Nilep, 2006).

A poststructuralist view of the notion of linguistic repertoire considers that the linguistic repertoire is not only defined by the circumstances of interaction, and the grammatical and social conventions, but it also involves the “time-space dimensions of history and biography” (Busch, 2012, p.19), in other words, it develops and expands historically through experiencing our linguistic interactions on both emotional and cognitive levels, and becomes incorporated in our linguistic habitus (Busch, 2012).

3.5 Language and context

Language is not considered just as a communicative device, rather it represents a human practice. In sociolinguistics, language is concerned with the study of linguistic behaviour that

takes into consideration the cultural background, and the social features of the speakers, in addition to the environment in which the interaction takes place (Hymes, 1962; Ervin-Tripp, 1964). The acknowledgment of the social context as a substantial operator when it comes to language use existed since the 1960s, when sociolinguists moved to new ground, in which the focus of the analysis of language is more on the social context rather than the structure (Hornberger and Link, 2012). Language gains a significant social meaning when it is associated with a particular group of speakers and a situation of use. It may carry within details about one's identity and about the kind of relationships that relates individuals with each other (Mesthrie, 2009). In most multilingual communities, the use of the linguistic repertoires of individuals differs from one field to another, depending on the expectations and requirements of that particular scope, and the capital each of the internalised languages provides to its holder. For example, a teacher in school will not use his linguistic repertoire the same way he uses it with his family, with his friends, or in administrative institutions. Therefore, the teacher's linguistic behaviour will be determined by the habitus, the field, and the capital he owns. This apparent interplay between languages in multilingual contexts caught the interest of linguists.

3.6 Language choice

Similar to grammar rules, which have a structure, the linguistic repertoire also has a structure. Yet, the structure of the verbal repertoires is quite different. It is mainly based on many alternatives that demonstrate the social and situational distinctions in speech (Gumperz, 1964). Bernstein (1964) declares that the lingual interaction is considered much more as the act of making decisions. The speaker, among many available expressions or languages, decides which utterances or languages suit better the situation or the context (Gumperz, 1964).

Gumperz was concerned about how language choices are linked to social constraints. He notes that the linguistic choice is eventually taken by the speaker, however, the license to taking decisions and selecting utterances and languages from his linguistic repertoire is always restricted by social and grammatical constraints (Gumperz, 1964; Busch, 2012). Therefore, he believes that there are social conventions that restrict the speakers' authority of selection. Those conventions are commonly agreed on, and based on them the speech is grouped into different categories such as literary, formal, informal, technical, vulgar, and humorous

(Gumperz, 1964; Busch, 2012). So, the social protocol of the linguistic choice is “learned along with grammatical rules and once internalized it becomes a part of our linguistic equipment. Conversely, stylistic choice becomes a problem when we are away from our accustomed social surroundings” (Gumperz, 1964, p.138). From this perspective, different forms of social structures or social relationships can produce different linguistic codes as they influence the selections and choices of speakers based on what is relevant to the context (Bernstein, 1964). Elias-Olivares (1976) stated that:

In a heterogeneous speech community, with varying degrees of linguistic diversity and social complexity, speakers interact using different speech varieties drawn from a repertoire of choices that for the most part are not random. On the contrary, the distribution of usage of these choices is determined by several factors in the social-communicative system of the community (1976, p.5).

Taking into consideration the existence of various codes or languages in multilingual societies and repertoires of multilingual individuals brought the question of how and when these languages are used, and how choices are made between the different languages in one’s repertoire (Sridhar, 1996; Fishman, 2020). Aiming to get answers in the field of sociolinguistics, the concept of domain was proposed as a very important element (Sridhar, 1996). Fishman (2020, p.68) provides the notion of the “domain of language choice” as an attempt to represent a “socio-cultural organization” and “socio-cultural context” for the different language choices made by individuals in multilingual milieus.

Barber (1952) at a socio-psychological level, recommends four domains, which are intimate, formal, informal, and intergroup. Individuals with multilingual repertoires, in multilingual settings, may prefer to use one language over the others in their repertoire to indicate intimacy such as within a family. They also may select or use another language and associate it with formal situations such as religious and ceremonial events, while to reflect informal relationships such as with neighbourhood, they may select particular codes from their repertoire; and it is the same for intergroup relationships (interactions with governmental-legal authority).

Schmit-Roher (1963 cited in Fishman, 2020), on the other hand, proposes the nine following domains: “the family, the playground and street, the school, the church, literature, the press, the military, the courts, and governmental administration”. Researchers exploring

multilingual societies, may add to these domains or minimise them as they may find that fewer domains are enough for some multilingual milieus (Fishman, 2020; Sridhar, 1996).

Aiming at describing and analysing the language choice of individuals within a particular multilingual milieu whereby different domains may exist, Fishman (2020) suggests the notion of role relation. He proposes that each domain is made up of or categorised into role relations. Religious domain for instance can refer to specific role-relation such as cleric-cleric, cleric-parishioner, parishioner-cleric, and parishioner-parishioner. Family on the other hand, which is considered a very important domain in studies of multilingual behaviour, may suggest various role relations including grandfather to grandmother, grandmother to grandfather, grandfather to father, and grandmother to father.

Greenfield and Fishman (1970) found that person, place, and topic are the factors that determine language choice in multilingual settings. That is, the nature of the topic, the person one is making conversation with, and the social context in which the interaction is taking place is what affects the selection of languages from the linguistic repertoire.

3.7 Hierarchy in multilingualism

Ortega (2018) suggests that multilingualism is a flexible and context-dependent array of communication practices. The valuation and hierarchical nature associated with different linguistic expressions in society imply that not all instances of multilingualisms are treated equally. Multilingualism, as a concept, is not neutral but carries inherent hierarchical and ideological characteristics. It is a complex, intricate, and pervasive phenomenon, taking on diverse forms and levels (Ortega, 2018).

According to Block (2017), language can be perceived as “an objective skill, acquired and possessed, that affords status, recognition legitimacy, and ultimately material remuneration, to those who possess it” (p.6). Block’s idea was not entirely new; Bourdieu’s (1982, 1991) concept of “linguistic capital” viewed language as a collection of attributes that individuals can accumulate through time to establish or enhance their social status or position. Additionally, Hogan-Brun (2017, p. xii) introduces the concept of 'linguonomics,' emphasizing that languages possess a 'market value'. Language proficiency, according to this perspective, can be conceptualized as 'assets' or dispositions that can be traded in the social interaction within the 'marketplace'.

Gal (1989) argues that language, at its core, lacks tangible value; however, by offering access to material resources, transform into resources themselves. In other words, the perceived value of a linguistic variety relies on its position in a linguistic marketplace and its effectiveness in opening doors to desired roles in the job market. Gal (1989) goes on to argue that certain language varieties, through recognition by formal institutions such as schools, they gain recognition and legitimacy too.

Languages in multilingual contexts differ in terms of power, vitality, attitude, and prestige they have. They may be classified in a hierarchy in which the value of each language is what determines its position in that hierarchy. This linguistic hierarchy is based on pragmatic considerations. In other words, the more functions and roles the language has to play in society, the more valuable it becomes, and the higher it ranks in the linguistic hierarchy, and vice versa, the less range of functions the language has, the lower it ranks (Sridhar, 1996).

The commodification of languages leads to the emergence of sociolinguistic hierarchies (Barakos and Selleck, 2019). In this context, certain language varieties are loaded with greater prestige, often associated with perceived socioeconomic and mobility benefits that a language is perceived to offer. In Western European context, Jaspers (2009, 19) discusses the existence of two distinct forms of multilingualism that highlight the contradictory nature of giving different value to some languages and language users over the others. These forms are referred to as prestige or 'pure' multilingualism and plebeian or 'impure' multilingualism. The former according to Jasper (2009), represents international, high-status languages, which are formally learned and associated with mobile, highly educated, transnational, and higher socioeconomic status individuals. The latter indicates minority and regional languages, which are learned in less formal contexts, and which are associated often with working class, and minority communities.

Hierarchy for multilingualism is dynamic and context dependent. Therefore, it is constantly subject to shift depending on the context (Barakos and Selleck, 2019). This is in line with Bourdieu's (1982; 1991) concept of symbolic and linguistic capital, where the position of languages is not limited to their perceived value but also depends on the dynamics of the 'linguistic marketplace'. This is supported by Costa (2015), who proposes that the perceived value of minority languages is generally low in contexts dominated by a single official

language. However, they may possess higher value in others markets due to their ability to represent a feeling of community, solidarity, or authenticity (Costa, 2015).

Each of the languages of the verbal repertoires of multilingual people in multilingual settings is associated with certain roles and reflects a distinct identity. All these languages work jointly to fulfil the communicative needs of a pluralistic society. The evaluation of these different codes (languages) is related to the domain they are exercised in. That is, the more valued the domain in which a particular language is used, the more valued this language will be, and vice versa (Sridhar, 1996).

Many movements nowadays in different parts of the world are calling for acknowledging the status of indigenous languages, which were marginalised and overlooked during colonial and post-colonial periods. Generally, they claim for expanding the roles of these languages and involve them in different domains of power, prestige, and authority (e.g., education and administration). At the same time, they invest efforts to reduce the hegemony of valued languages over smaller languages by limiting their use in different domains (Sridhar, 1996).

3.8 Language attitudes

As this study will consider the attitudes of Algerian Berber secondary school teachers towards each of the languages incorporated in their linguistic repertoire, The researcher will tackle the affective parameter of language awareness, which denotes the attitudes toward languages (Wolfram, 1998). In plurilingual contexts such as the Algerian context whereby minority and majority languages, in addition to second and foreign languages exist, and with the language policies implemented by the authorities it would be advantageous to explore the attitudes towards these languages (Ibarraran, Lasagabaster, and Sierra, 2008). Understanding what languages are favourable or unfavourable to participants will help to understand why certain languages in their repertoire are taking an important role in particular fields and not in others including the educational space.

According to Edwards, the term attitude as a fundamental concept of social psychology, refers to:

Dispositions to react favourably or unfavourably to a class of objects. This disposition is often taken to comprise three components: feelings, thoughts, and following up on these, predispositions to act in a certain way (Edwards, 1994, p.97).

In other words, the individuals' attitudes are built upon the process of knowing and believing something, and then building some emotional response to it, and finally based on that decision to act in a certain way is made. Two points should be referred to when dealing with attitudes (Edwards, 1994).

First, attitudes are not necessarily compatible with the behaviour related to it. Inconsistency may exist between feelings and actions (Edwards, 1994). Multilingual people for instance, can have positive attitudes towards a particular language in their linguistic repertoire; however, they speak another language or languages because the situation or the context requires that. It may also be the opposite, an individual may have negative attitudes toward a particular language from his repertoire, but he speaks it as the circumstances impose that. Therefore, what people think and feel, is not always reflected in their behaviour. Reasons for this inconsistency can be for personal interest, or to avoid embarrassment.

The second point is that there may be a state of confusion when dealing with the two terms: belief and attitude. This may be apparent when dealing with language attitudes through questionnaires and interviews. Beliefs are considered one component of attitudes. A belief can be known by asking a mother for instance about whether acquiring the French language would be advantageous for her child or not. The answer may be yes or no; however, to know about the mother's attitude one should go further by asking about her feeling towards the language. The mother may think that learning the French language would be important for her child's success, however, she may hate the language (Edwards, 1994).

3.9 Language and identity

Ethnic identity is the solidarity or loyalty to a particular small or large group that is related to one's ancestor. This group should have a sense of group boundaries that is sustained by different factors such as language, and religion (Edwards, 1994). In this sense, one can consider the Algerian society as divided into two ethnic groups, which are Arabs and Berbers since each of the two groups has a language that represents it namely Arabic and Tamazight (Berber language).

In multilingual settings where different languages can coexist. Generally, each of these languages or codes is related to a sub-group or certain activities in that community. It has been suggested that the linguistic choices made by people when communicating are a part of their linguistic self-presentation (Blom and Gumperz, 1972). In other words, the linguistic

choices of speakers can be deemed as a way of identifying themselves with certain categories or activities, as each of the languages may represent particular categories or activities (Gal, 1978).

The psychologist Tajfel (1974) presumes that identity originates from group membership. In this respect, he defines social identity as “that part of an individual’s self-concept, which derives from his knowledge of his membership of a social group (or groups) together with the emotional significance attached to that membership” (p. 69). Individuals thus, according to Tajfel (1974) may decide to change their membership from their group to another one if it does not reflect the positive elements of the social identity, they feel they belong to. However, this change in social identity and group membership is not always possible. In this case, limited choices are made such as changing one’s perception towards the features that characterise their group in order to get a more positive view about one’s social identity, or the individual can move to actions to create the change (Tajfel, 1974).

Influenced by Tajfel's (1974) theory of social identity, Giles and Johnson (1981), came up with an ethnolinguistic identity theory that concentrates on language and considers it as a prominent emblem of social identity and group membership. Giles and Johnson (1981) suggest that individuals of a particular group may resort to comparing their social group with other groups aiming at making their own group positively distinct, which may help to establish a positive social identity. Yet, if the social comparison turns out to be negative, they can embrace certain strategies that allow them to obtain positive social identity such as the assimilation to the group that holds the desired social identity. Taking language as a prominent marker of group membership, the individual’s assimilation to another group for obtaining a positive group identity requires linguistic adaptability that may result in subtractive bilingualism or even language erosion.

According to Gumperz and Cook- Gumperz (1982, p. 7) both ethnicity and social identity “are in a large part established and maintained through language”. The different components of the linguistic repertoire may represent various social identities that the individuals may assume (Blom and Gumperz, 1972, p. 421). People may have different languages as part of their linguistic repertoire, however, when they encounter a particular situation, they select a particular code in order to deal appropriately with the situation. In other words, language choices are a way of indicating relationships (Heller, 1982). In this sense, language can be

considered “a symbol of ethnic identity, and language choice is a symbol of ethnic relations as well as a means of communication” (Heller, 1982, p. 308).

As this study will be conducted in an Algerian context, it is worth mentioning that language has been always seen as a symbol of identity in Algeria. The Algerian society had a long history with French colonialism. According to Mostar (2009), the French colonial, for more than a century used language as a weapon to exclude and eliminate the Algerian identity. They sought to assimilate Algerians into the French culture by spreading the French language. After the independence, Arabic was declared and decreed in the national constitution as the official language of Algeria. Leaders during this period aimed at elevating Arabic in Algeria and turning it into a symbol of Arabic identity (Mostar, 2009). They opted for a similar nationalistic strategy to that of the French colonial. They aimed at unifying the Algerian society under one Arabic identity. However, the fact that the Algerian society encompasses different ethnic groups each with its language (Arabs and Berbers who had Arabic and Tamazight as a language) created tensions between the authorities and these groups. Berbers considered imposing Arabic as an official language to be a kind of marginalisation of their identity and existence in Algerian society, as a “person’s native speech is regarded as an integral part of his family background, a sign of his local identity” (Blom and Gumperz, 2000, p.112). This linguistic profile generated a multilingual infrastructure that entails Tamazight, Arabic, and French in Algeria nowadays. Therefore, it is likely to notice different linguistic practices such as code-switching and translanguaging in Algerian society.

3.10 Code-switching

Defining the concept of code-switching may differ from one researcher to another. Bagui (2014) states that code-switching has no one accurate and constant definition that can be appropriate to all contexts whereby code-switching takes place. Yet, a general definition suggests that it is the alternation between two different codes or languages while speaking. It might be between two different languages or two dialects of the same language. That is, as it may occur in multilingual contexts, code-switching may also take place in monolingual communities whereby a diglossic environment exists (Bagui, 2014).

Code-switching is a phenomenon or practice that denotes how people switch from one language to another in a bilingual or multilingual community. Many researchers have been interested in this phenomenon (Sridhar, 1996). Some of them had a belief that code-switching

is a consequence of incomplete knowledge of the language the individual initiates with. However, many of them now challenge the former negative view, and instead, they view code-switching as a way of extending one's communicative competence and functions (Reyes, 2004). In other words, code-switching may be used by the speaker to construct multilingual/multicultural identities (Kramsch and Whiteside, 2007), to accomplish the task, which is cognitively demanding (Reyes, 2004), to communicate intended ideas in a more accurate way (Zentella, 1997), and to accommodate with the language use of the interlocutor as it has an interpersonal, social function (Park, 2013).

Blom and Gumperz (1972) differentiate between two kinds of code-switching. First, they suggest situational code-switching in which the switching from one language to another is a result of the change in situation or the topic of conversation. The concept of situational switching thus, proposes a direct connection between language and the social context. The language choices made by individuals are based on the event or the context, and any breach of the conventions of selection will change people's perceptions of the event. Another point to mention in situational code-switching is that the degree of freedom in making choices differs from one situation to another. In other words, speakers may have a very limited range of choices in certain situations, while in other situations they may have a wider range of choices to select. The second type is metaphorical code-switching, this type of switching is more about the stylistic or textual functions such as shifting from a serious to a more comic tone, marking emphasis, and introducing a quotation (Blom and Gumperz, 1972).

In this sense, code-switching is not a random phenomenon, rather it is functionally stimulated. Explaining this practice is not only limited to the grammaticality of sentences and how sentences and conversations are structured. Rather, it transcends that to address the acceptability of utterances in relation to language functions and the context in which languages are used (Sridhar, 1996).

3.11 Translanguaging

Repertoire as a concept, entails a representation of the phenomenon of multilingualism. It implies how different codes and dialects are used and overlapped, considering multilingualism as a norm (Mouhleb, 2005). The repertoire concept, thus, might be further directed to include different linguistic practices that result from language contact and linguistic diversity such as translanguaging.

Translanguaging is generally ascribed to Cen Williams (1994) who first used it in the context of Wales to explain a pedagogical approach in which two languages are used for teaching and learning inside the classroom (cited in Wei, 2011; Lewis, Jones, and Baker, 2012). The concept was first used in education in the 1980s as a response to the split between English and Welsh, with regarding one (English) being more prestigious than the other (Welsh) (separation of two monolingualism). In the late 20th century, the Welsh language began to regain its status, and the process of revivification started to be more effective, this paved the way for a more positive view towards the use of two languages (Lewis, Jones, and Baker, 2012). Using both English and Welsh thus, started to be regarded as “mutually advantageous in a bilingual school, person, and society” (Lewis, Jones, and Baker, 2012, p.642). Moving from separating languages based on time, subject, and teacher to a more holistic, additive, and advantageous view of Welsh and English opened the door for the concept of translanguaging to emerge in education and especially at the classroom level. The increasing prevalence of translanguaging in the field of education thus, is regarded as a release from the traditional pessimistic vision of bilingualism (Lewis, Jones, and Baker, 2012).

William (2003 cited in Lewis, Jones, and Baker, 2012) considers translanguaging as a pedagogical approach in which the focus is on children rather than teachers, which is convenient with the child-centred approach applied in Welsh classrooms. For him, translanguaging represents how students make use of both languages to get a deeper understanding and performance. Garcia (2011) on the other hand, suggests that translanguaging is more general. She extended the term to include not only academia but also everyday domains such as home and street. In other words, “the term has been generalised from school to street, from pedagogical practices to everyday cognitive processing, from classroom lessons to all contexts of a bilingual’s life” (Lewis, Jones, and Baker, 2012, p.647). Wei (2011) and Hornberger and Link (2012) state that translanguaging is the move from one linguistic structure or system to another whether in its speaking, writing, listening, reading, or remembering forms. It involves:

The full range of linguistic performances of multilingual language users for purposes that transcend the combination of structures, the alternation between systems, the transmission of information and the representation of values, identities, and relationships (Wei, 2011, p.2).

The idea of translanguaging covers different multilingual behaviour or phenomenon such as code-switching, crossing, code-mixing, creolization, and practices that include shifting between two or more languages (Garcia, 2011). This concept traces back to the concept of languaging, which indicates the process of using one's language to acquire knowledge, make sense, and communicate one's thoughts (Wei, 2011). In this sense, language is considered a means for delivering our thoughts and ideas during interactions and communication. Translanguaging then, refers to the act of shifting between different linguistic structures, or systems to communicate one's thought and beliefs. The act of translanguaging constructs a social space for multilingual speakers, it allows them to bring combine various dimensions of "their personal history, experience and environment, their attitude, belief, and ideology, their cognitive and physical capacity into one coordinated and meaningful performance and making it into a lived experience" (Wei, 2011, p.2).

3.12 Previous studies

Numerous studies have been conducted to address the phenomena of linguistic repertoires within multilingual contexts across the globe. Researchers have explored the diverse and dynamic ways in which individuals navigate and employ multiple languages in their daily lives within various social, cultural, and communicative settings. Many studies have also been conducted to address the issue of language attitudes toward linguistic repertoires, which uncover the perceptions, beliefs, and preferences that individuals and communities hold regarding the languages they use.

3.12.1 Global context

Garza (2017) conducted a study with a Mathematics teacher in the seventh-grade to investigate and examine the utilisation of translanguaging practices in the classroom. He explored how these practices create a dynamic and inclusive learning environment for Latino/a students, enabling them to employ their full range of linguistic resources during mathematical interactions. The data presented in Garza's (2017) study came from a comprehensive ethnographic investigation conducted in a middle school located in Southcentral Texas in 2013-2014. The study employed qualitative research methodologies, including classroom observations and conducting a limited number of interviews with a mathematics teacher. This study examines how the teacher's awareness of students' language ability, along with students' engagement in mathematical endeavours,

fosters the development of a mathematics community of practice wherein bilingualism is regarded as the norm. Despite Spanish being the medium of teaching, the participant in the research, did not exhibit a preference for either language. In contrast, the individual utilised his linguistic skills as a singular linguistic system. His students, who are multilingual, utilised this platform to creatively employ their complete linguistic repertoires. The classroom of the participant in the research can be interpreted as a multilingual community of practice. The recognition by the teacher of his students' bilingual abilities established an inclusive classroom atmosphere in which their linguistic practices were not marginalised. Rather, these practices were effectively employed for bilingual academic objectives. Garza's (2017) study aligns with the findings of the present study by highlighting the presence of translanguaging practices in the classroom. Similarly, this study on Berber teachers indicates that language choices are flexible, and what matters most is effectively transmitting the lesson content. This resonates with the inclusive approach observed in Mr. León's classroom, where the use of multiple languages created a dynamic learning environment. However, the present study contrasts with the views of some teachers of foreign languages who prefer sticking to the second language (L2) for teaching efficiency.

Becker and Knoll (2022) examined the utilisation of English and German languages in day-care centres, focusing specifically on the prioritisation of these languages and its implications for the creation and reinforcement of language hierarchies. The study examined the utilisation of the linguistic repertoires, that include various languages, by teachers and children within the context of language policy restrictions in three day-care centres. According to Becker and Knoll (2022), Switzerland stands apart from other monolingual European states due to its official status as a quadrilingual country. The national languages of German, French, Italian, and Romansh are predominantly spoken in four distinct linguistic and geographical regions within the country. Among these languages, there is a wide range of dialects and idioms that are commonly linked to informal, everyday speech. These linguistic variations convey a sense of familiarity and intimacy between speakers, in contrast to the more formal and standardised variants (Christen, 2005, cited in Becker and Knoll, 2022). Switzerland's linguistic landscape, despite its formal quadrilingual language policy (Becker and Knoll, 2022), is influenced by a variety of heritage languages (HLs) such as Portuguese or Albanian, as well as the globally recognised lingua franca, English. Consequently, it is more accurately characterised as a

multilingual environment. The presence of linguistic diversity is evident throughout several domains of social existence and holds significant influence within day-care institutions (Becker and Knoll, 2022). According to Becker and Knoll (2022), the early social interactions of many children are influenced by adults and peers using a language different from their mother tongue. Multilingualism in day-care centres and the arrival of children at school without proficiency in one of the national languages are perceived as notable challenges on the social, educational, and integration policies. In day-care centres, it is common for the language spoken to correspond with the official language of the particular region. This assertion holds relevance for educators in day-care facilities, however it holds less significance for the children themselves who typically do not have an obligation to adhere to a specific language. Becker and Knoll (2022) examined the linguistic practices seen at day-care centres located in German-speaking Switzerland. The day-care centres, in addition to German, have adopted English as a secondary institutional language for both staff and children. These institutions can be characterised as having a conceptual bilingualism.

In their analysis, they demonstrated that the bilingual notion fails to accurately reflect the diverse multilingual reality. The scenario, according to Becker and Knoll (2022), can be characterised as a phenomenon known as "selective celebration of linguistic diversity" (Berthele, 2020, p.125), wherein the explicit promotion of multilingualism is accompanied by covert restrictions stemming from political agendas and ideologies that prioritise standard and prestigious language variations. Becker and Knoll's (2022) research parallels the current study's findings, particularly in the context of language policy dynamics. Much like the Algerian case, their study in Switzerland unveils a mismatch between language policies and the multilingual reality. The challenges faced by children in Switzerland's care centres, where national languages (German, French, Italian, and Romansh) are encountered as somewhat foreign, was also reported by Berber teachers in the current study. In both contexts, the initial encounter with certain languages, which are deemed foreign to the children, poses challenges. Berber teachers shared similar sentiments about the difficulties faced by children entering schools where Arabic, initially foreign to them, is introduced for the first time instead of Derja and Tamazight, which are the spoken languages.

Weirich (2021) also examined the language practice of minority individuals in Moldova as a case study to investigate the reasons behind the diminishing and constrained linguistic

resources in their transition from familial to public contexts following the Soviet Union's independence. The study suggests that sociolinguistic inequalities arise as a result of the implementation of official monolingualism in local language policies. The paper advocates the significance of multilingualism in language policy and planning, rather than just endorsing a "first language only" approach. According to Weirich (2021), advocating for the inclusion and recognition of all languages, minority communities can benefit from a broader range of linguistic resources, so enabling them to have a greater presence and influence in society.

Weirich's (2021) study provides valuable insights into the language practices of minority individuals in Moldova. It is notable for its focus on sociolinguistic inequalities arising from the implementation of official monolingualism in local language policies. It contributed to the understanding of the linguistic repertoires, in minority contexts by identifying the sociolinguistic inequalities rooted in language policies, and calling for approaches that recognize and include all languages within a community. The issue of sociolinguistic inequalities, as examined by Weirich, aligns the findings presented in the present study, which demonstrate the presence of a language hierarchy within the Algerian Berber context.

3.12.2 Algerian context

Many studies addressing the socio-linguistic situation have been conducted in Algeria. Rouabah (2023) examined the linguistic transition from Chaoui, a variant of Tamazight, to the adoption of Derja in Batna (a Chaoui context in Algeria). Her study was centred on the examination of gender disparities in language usage, while also exploring the influence of socialisation and cultural beliefs on individuals' linguistic decisions and choices, particularly in regard to men and women. Expanding on the conceptualizations of masculinity and femininity, this study explores the manners in which these gendered behaviours impose limitations or constraints on the utilisation of Chaouia among individuals belonging to the working-class Chaouia community. The study investigated the dynamic relationship between gender identities and language socialisation within the home, language preferences within educational settings, and language choices among peers. The community has experienced a notable shift in social and linguistic priorities as a result of increased interaction with the greater Arabic-speaking population. The results of the study revealed a distinct influence of parental factors on the development of a gendered linguistic pattern, whereby males were observed to be socialised in Chaouia dialect and girls in Derja. This habit was additionally

strengthened within the educational setting and through interactions with classmates, facilitated by teachers and social networks. The networks of females exhibited ethnolinguistic heterogeneity, while the networks of males were orientated towards the Amazigh community. Therefore, the conventional association between Tamazight and femininity underwent a process of re-evaluation in order to construct a narrative that assigns responsibility for the continuous linguistic shift and loss of identity (Rouabah, 2023).

Another study has been conducted by Sadouki (2023) to examine the phenomenon of language contact in Algeria and explore the sociolinguistic dynamics of language practice in everyday life. The study involved a total of 120 participants from Algeria, who were selected from various age categories. To accomplish the objective of this study, a mixed methods approach was employed. Firstly, a questionnaire was utilised to statistically present the findings. Secondly, a group discussion was conducted and qualitatively analysed to observe linguistic behaviour. Lastly, a semi-structured interview was employed to explore the attitudes of Algerians towards multilingualism. The results indicated a significant prevalence of native language utilisation, including Derja and Berber, alongside frequent usage of French and other languages such as English. Conversely, there was a limited utilisation of Arabic observed across several domains and in everyday linguistic interactions. Moreover, participants identified as multilingual individuals because of their daily interactions and the practice of switching between more than two languages (Sadouki, 2023). Sadouki's (2023) study confirms some of the results of the present study. Although different contexts (Berber region/Algeria in general) Both studies focused on language contact and explored sociolinguistic dynamics. Sadouki's findings align with the present research by highlighting the prevalence of native languages, including Derja and Berber, in everyday language use, in addition to the frequent usage of French.

3.13 Conclusion

This chapter examined the existing body of literature related to or adding value to the study. The literature reviewed the complex discourse surrounding monolingual/multilingual visions of language, multilingual competence, language choice, translanguaging, code-switching, language attitudes, hierarchy in multilingualism, language and identity, and linguistic repertoire. The selection and exploration of these concepts in this literature review are

fundamental to providing insights in understanding the linguistic landscape in the Berber region.

Defining the concepts of multilingualism and multilingual competence is essential as the study aims to investigate the linguistic repertoires of Berber teachers, who are inherently multilingual, and discuss their awareness of their multilingual abilities. They are central to exploring the diverse linguistic abilities and proficiencies of participants in this thesis, who navigate multiple languages in their daily interactions. Defining the concepts of language choice, translanguaging, and code-switching is also essential as the study aims to investigate language practices among multilingual Berber teachers within various domains. Given the multilingual nature of the setting, encountering concepts like these is inevitable. Moreover, concepts such as language attitudes and language hierarchy provide insights into the sociolinguistic dimensions of language use, highlighting the social dynamics and power structures that influence language practices among teachers. Defining language attitude as a concept can help to lay the groundwork for studying language attitudes of the participants in this towards the languages in their repertoires.

Additionally, defining the concept of language and identity is essential to understanding the intricacies between multilingualism, language attitudes, and language practice among Berber teachers. Language and identity refer to the dynamic relationship between language use and individuals' sense of self, belonging, and cultural affiliation. It helps to examine how language use can be shaped by individuals' identities and how language attitudes are influenced by perceptions of linguistic identity. This understanding is crucial for gaining insight of language behaviour and attitudes among multilingual secondary school teachers in the Berber region. Finally, the concept of linguistic repertoire as discussed in this thesis ties these elements together. It encapsulates the diversity and complexity of linguistic resources that participants draw upon, providing a holistic lens through which to analyse their communicative practices. These concepts will serve as crucial tools for the upcoming analysis, providing a theoretical lens through which to examine the diverse language practices, attitudes, and identities of educators, ultimately contributing to a deeper understanding of the linguistic dynamics within this unique cultural and linguistic landscape.

Given the multilingual nature of the Berber region, where linguistic diversity is a defining feature, these concepts are important. They provide a lens through which to explore how

language choice, translanguaging, and code-switching intersect with broader issues of language attitudes and hierarchies, shaping the linguistic repertoires of teachers. Additionally, concepts such as language and identity emphasise the personal and sociocultural dimensions of language use, highlighting how teachers' linguistic repertoires are intertwined with their sense of self and belonging.

Chapter Four

Bourdieu's Theory of Practice

4.1 Introduction

In examining the linguistic repertoires of Algerian Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) secondary school teachers, Bourdieu's theory of practice related to "habitus, field, and capital" is a relevant theoretical lens through which to understand this understudied but important issue about Algerian Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) teachers. Bourdieu's theory of practice helps to explore the durably ingrained linguistic habitus of Berber teachers to know how their linguistic repertoire is internalised, and what forms of capital were associated with the process of acquiring and learning their linguistic repertoires. It also helps to explore teachers attitudes towards the languages in their repertoires through looking into their historical trajectories, which may influence the dispositions they hold towards these languages. The chapter examines each of three key concepts underpinning Bourdieu's theory of practice in order to explore how these ideas help and how they work together to produce social practices, which provides a useful way of understanding important social issues in society. It also elucidates how this theory will contribute to my study.

4.2 Habitus

Bourdieu aimed to evolve a theoretical model of social practice, which reduces many dichotomies, such as individual and social, subjectivity and objectivity, and structure and agency. According to him, this theory should be considered as a primary inquiry to examine social reality for social scientists, thus, he suggested three key concepts in making clear the social practice theory. He introduced 'habitus, field, and capitals', and illustrated the relationship between them in an attempt to explain social practices (Suminar, 2013).

Bourdieu describes habitus as a set of dispositions within the individual including how to behave, act, think, and perceive the world. These dispositions are socially acquired (Bourdieu, 2018). When treating the concept of habitus, Bourdieu at times proposes a degree of consistency, however, at other times he acknowledges the distinction of individuals belonging to the same cultural category. Thus, according to Reay (2004), habitus can be deemed as a multi-layered notion that is more general at a societal level and more composite and distinguished at an individual level. Accordingly, Bourdieu distinguishes two kinds of habitus: the individual habitus and the class habitus (Reay, 2004). The former indicates that there is

no identical individual habitus because the histories of individuals are not identical (Reay, 2004), while the latter denotes that as there are classes of experiences, there are classes of habitus likewise (Bourdieu, 1990b; Bourdieu, 2018; Reay, 2004).

Habitus generates individual and collective practices correspondingly with history (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992; Grenfell, 2014; Bourdieu, 1990b; Bourdieu, 2018; Bourdieu, 2012; Reay, 2004). It points to something historical, which is connected to the historical trajectories of individuals (Bourdieu, 1990b; Reay, 2004). Therefore, histories are considered crucial to understand the notion of habitus (Reay, 2004). In other words, Bourdieu explains that habitus entails the acquired dispositions from the individual, which becomes durably incorporated in the body. Therefore, the term, continually, brings back the fact that it is linked to individual history (Bourdieu, 1993; Grenfell, 2014). It can denote how an individual holds his past within and brings it to present conditions, and how he chooses to perform in a particular way (Grenfell, 2014).

Bourdieu explains habitus as a property of agents whether individuals, groups, or institutions, which consists of “structured and structuring” structure (Bourdieu, 2012, p.345). He uses the concept ‘structured’ to indicate how one’s past and present conditions including family nurture and educational experiences structured this property; while by ‘structuring’ he tried to elucidate how the existing habitus of an individual helps to shape his present and future behaviour. He also uses the word structure, which entails a system of depositions that gives rise to perceptions, appreciations, and practices, to make it clear that it is systematically arranged not randomly (Grenfell, 2014; Calhoun, 2006).

Although ‘habitus’ is seen as an outcome of the early experiences of infancy, and socialization within the family, it is constantly re-structured by the outside world and the different fields an individual encounters (Di Maggio, 1979). For Bourdieu, habitus mirrors the social class in which it was established, yet it also holds within it the formation of new inventive responses, which go beyond the initial social conditions. The set of probabilities within one’s habitus can be illustrated in a continuum. At one extreme of the continuum, the habitus can be reproduced by coming across a ‘field’ that reproduces its dispositions. At the other extreme, the habitus can be subject to transformation through a process that either lifts or minimizes one’s expectations (Reay, 2004). Habitus thus, can be deemed as a complex incorporated dispositions that emerges from one’s experiences. Yet, the choice of the individual is placed

at the heart of habitus too. According to Bourdieu choice resembles the “art of inventing” (Bourdieu, 1990a, p.55). However, these choices are limited by a framework of opportunities and restrictions (Reay, 2004).

Bourdieu (1990a) states that all his ideas started from questioning how human behaviour can be managed without being an output of obedience to rules. Thus, he considers that the habitus of individuals, which plays a crucial role in working with the field and the capitals to shape human behaviour, does not only link the past, present, and future, but it also seeks the reconciliation between a series of dichotomies including the social and the individual, the objective and the subjective, and structure and agency. Habitus aims to transcend those dualisms and build bridges that link between them (Grenfell, 2014).

When it comes to the determination of human practice, Bourdieu opposes both the structuralists’ and phenomenologists’ views. The former argues that human behaviour is guided by structures such as rules, norms, and patterns of thought, whereas the latter claims that agency is what explains human actions. Bourdieu rejects the two stances as he addresses the question of what determines human actions. He instead instituted the concept of ‘habitus’ to mediate between agency and structure in shaping human actions (Maggio, 2018). Bourdieu uses the term ‘habitus’ to examine how social structure and individual agency work together to shape each other and shape practice, and he tries to transcend and minimize the dichotomy of structure/agency (Grenfell, 2014). He also uses the analogy of a game and the concept of strategy trying to explain the active, creative nature of actions. That is, he considers that every field can be seen as a competitive game, in which agents are strategically seeking to maximise their position in that field. Those actors come to acquire the rules of the game through time and experience. Bourdieu suggests the concept of the “feel for the game”, which develops through long immersion in the field to indicate the agents feeling for social regularities, and to connect those regularities of the field with the practical logic of the individual, which descends from habitus (Grenfell, 2014, p.53). Habitus thus, gives the space for agency, within a bounded set of choices, as opposed to structuralists’ determinism (Nash, 1999). The individual has limited choices of possibilities, which are placed at the heart of habitus. These choices are what generate creative and inventive practices (Reay, 2004).

Habitus also combines the individual with the social. This conveys that every individual is unique in terms of the content of his experiences; however, these experiences always remain

within a social framework. That is, those experiences are shared among people within the same social class, ethnicity, gender, region, and nationality. For instance, people who are from the same social class tend to have structurally comparable positions in society, which in its turn structurally generate similar experiences. As Maton (2014) explains, each one of us is a “unique configuration of social forces, but these forces are social so that even when we are being individual and different, we do so in socially regular ways” (Grenfell, 2014, p.52).

In explaining the reconciliation between “subjective” and “objective”, or the “outer” and “inner” in habitus, Bourdieu tries to depict how the social reality (facts) can be internalized. He considers habitus as a “socialised subjectivity” and “the social embodied” (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992, p.86). Thus, he describes the connection between the two dichotomies (objectivity and subjectivity) as “the internalisation of externality, and the externalisation of internality” (Bourdieu, 1977a, p.72). In other words, it is how the objective creates the subjective, and how the personal becomes social (Grenfell, 2014).

According to Bourdieu, habitus does not act alone when generating practices (Grenfell, 2014). It is considered just one notion of his conceptual toolbox (Reay, 2004). Bourdieu indicates that human actions or practices are a consequence of an “obscure and double relation” (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992), or an “unconscious relationship” (Bourdieu, 1993, p.76) between the two concepts of habitus and field (Grenfell, 2014). Thus, it is the ongoing interaction between habitus, field, and capital that produces the logic of practice (Reay, 2004). Bourdieu suggests that understanding and explaining incidents, social phenomena, and social interactions between agents, call for more than just considering what was said and what happened. For him, it is imperative to look at and examine the social space including the interactions, transactions, and events that happen within (Bourdieu, 2005; Grenfell, 2014).

4.3 Field

Bourdieu uses the term “field” to portray an area of land, a battlefield, and a field of lore. He used various analogies including the football field, science-fiction field, and force field in physics, to explain what field means. Each of these analogies has elements that contribute to the understanding of the field, yet none of them equate it (Grenfell, 2014). In that sense, Bourdieu put forward the analogy of a football game to explain his perception of the field. He describes the football space as a bounded field with internal divisions. To play the game and

based on those divisions, players have a set of positions, and it is based on these positions that the players act and move. The game is also built upon specific rules, which should be learned by debutants using their basic skill to be able to play it. Moreover, the condition of the space (dry, wet, well-manicured.) in which the game is occurring plays a role in influencing what players can do and how the game should be played. That is, just as in football games, the social field also has boundaries that limit what can be done, within these boundaries agents (people or institutions) take their positions, which are influenced by the conditions and the rules of the field (Grenfell, 2014).

Bourdieu adds that similarly to the game of football, the game played on the field is competitive, actors occupying different positions try various strategies to keep their positions or to upgrade them. Doing so requires individuals to accumulate capital, which is considered the process in, and the product of the field. In a social field players or agents who hold more forms of capital at the beginning of the game, are more advantaged and luckier because the field will depend on them. Thus, they are more likely to acquire and accumulate more capital, which will contribute to their advancement in the field compared to others (Grenfell, 2014).

The second analogy is that of science fiction force fields. According to Bourdieu science fiction force fields are erected from the construction of a barrier between the inside and the outside. For the sake of keeping the insiders protected, small self-reliant worlds are built. Within these worlds, practices are based on systematic and ordered patterns without which the social world inside the force field turns to be chaotic and stops to function. The order within these spacecrafts is structured hierarchically. Thus, some dominants have the power to legislate and make decisions, and subordinates function according to the dominants, which means that not everyone is equal (Grenfell, 2014). The rules inside the self-standing spaceship are similar to other similar craft. Although, some differences are required and likely to occur for survival; however, a common set of functions also exist. Thus, Bourdieu views the social field as a small world, and similarly to the science-fiction force field, each social field owns its particular distinctive logic of practice, and it works semi-autonomously with being a human construct, with its own combination of beliefs that explain the rules of field behaviour. Actors (agents) occupying different positions in social fields, understand how to behave and act based on their position in that field, this understanding does not come naturally, but can be demonstrated through the truths, or doxa of the field (Grenfell, 2014).

A social field is not permanent, it can be transformed and changed, and to grasp how the change occurs within a field, it is possible to trace its history (Grenfell, 2014). Bourdieu uses the term 'field' to point to a common social space that comprises multiple social fields. He also indicates that similarly to science fiction force fields, which have similarities between them, social fields too have important homologies among dominant agents and in their rules and patterns. The fields can be thought of as interdependent, that is, the relationships of exchange exist between them. Bourdieu posits that the field of power does not determine what happens in other social fields, but the influence is rather reciprocal, which implies that what occurs in the field of power can shape what happens in a social field and vice versa (Grenfell, 2014).

Finally, Bourdieu compares the social field to a field of forces in Physics, which is illustrated as vectors that display the forces exercised by an object on another. Similar to the force field, Bourdieu suggests that a social field can be deemed as a set of opposing forces. He postulates that both economic and cultural capitals work as two hierarchized poles within a social field, in which the determination of positions is based on their relationship to the four poles (Grenfell, 2014). Therefore, he suggests that the field can be described as at one pole the economically dominant and culturally dominated positions, while on the other pole, we find the culturally dominant and economically dominated positions (Bourdieu, 1988; Grenfell, 2014). In a physical force field, Bourdieu adds that there are no necessary boundaries, but instead, the forces just fade away at the edges, which opposes the notion of a social field in which the struggles occurring within are more at, and about those boundaries and the value of its capital (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992). Each of these social fields is characterised by a distinction or quality (Bourdieu, 1984), which is a representation of the quantity and the kind of economic and cultural capital in that field. Also, the position in that field is subject to measuring the accumulated volume and type of capital within agents (individuals or institutions), such as the educational level, the intended institutions, and social origins (Grenfell, 2014).

As opposed to a force field, which is constituted as a sole entity, the social field (field of power) can be constructed from multiple fields, and these multiple fields can also be divided into sub-fields. Though each subfield follows the logic of its overall field, yet, it also has its own inner logic, regularities, and rules. In order to move from an overall field to a more specialized field

that calls for a real qualitative advancement for actors and for those who aim to understand and investigate that subfield. The fields existing within the field of power do not all have equal authority, some of them are dominant, while others are subordinate fields. As an example, Bourdieu posited that all subfields in the cultural field were controlled by the economic field (Bourdieu, 1990a). He went further and added that institutions inside fields are also considered as subfields (Grenfell, 2014).

Although it is stated that the field is hierarchically structured with dominant actors and institutions who have the ability and the power to define what happens, however agency and change also exist. In contrast to field force in physics, which is controlled by fixed and unchanged laws, in a social field, people, as stated by Bourdieu, are not automatons, he described them as knowing and endowed agents with a functional sense that is an acquired system of vision, principles, preferences, and schemes of action (Bourdieu, 1988). As a summary of the previous ideas field can be defined thus:

A structured social space, a field of forces, a force field. It contains people who dominate and people who are dominated. Constant, permanent relationships of inequality operate inside this space, which at the same time becomes a space in which various actors struggle for the transformation or preservation of the field. All the individuals in this universe bring to the competition all the (relative) power that defines their position in the field and, as a result, their strategies (Bourdieu, 1998, pp.40-41).

The social field, in general, can be defined as a bounded space that limits what can be done and what cannot through following a set of rules that organise the functions within the social space. That field can have multiple divisions, which in its turn can be divided into subfields. Although the sub-fields generally follow the logic of the overall field, they have their own set of rules too, which may be like the logic of practice within similar sub-fields. Social fields are competitive spaces in which dominants in the field have the power to control, and subordinates follow the rules constituted by power holders. Positions in the field, therefore, are subject to the capital and dispositions that agents have. The more capital and capacities an individual has, the higher his position will be. However, the field is not fixed, it is changeable and can be transformed (Grenfell, 2014).

To understand the practices and interactions between people, it is not sufficient to look only into the field and habitus alone. It is also required to go beyond by examining and determining

the nature and structure of capital the agents have. Capital according to Bourdieu is considered the currency that positions agents within a field (Grenfell, 2014). It is acquired and accumulated through effort and work either in its materialised or embodied forms. This capital is possessed by agents within a field, and it allows them to obtain energy and status within that social space. The power that is displayed by agents during interactions with each other and within a social structure can be demonstrated through the capital they reign. Therefore, the capital affords the games of societies more certainties and gives them more than just a token of chance in which miracles can take place (Bourdieu, 1986). Bourdieu as opposed to Marx - who believes that social class and power are determined by economic capital - considers that social class and power are planted on the amount of capital owned by agents. This capital takes various forms: economic, cultural, and social (Grenfell, 2014), and it should be introduced in all its different forms in order to explain and interpret the structure of the social world and its functioning (Bourdieu, 1986; Tittenbrun, 2016). He considers that even the most materialized form of capital, which is known as economic capital can be convertible, and presented in other forms of capital such as cultural, social, and ones and vice versa (Bourdieu, 1986).

4.4 Capital

The concept of cultural capital was introduced by both Pierre Bourdieu and Jean Passeron (1979) to examine the influence that culture has over the social system and to analyse the relationship that links actions with social structure (Lamont and Lareau, 1988). Pierre Bourdieu and Jean Passeron (1979) used that notion first because they were concerned to indicate the educational system's and family socialization's contribution to the structure of power relationships, and because they were concerned about the symbolic relationships that exist among classes through the contribution to the reproduction of distribution structure of cultural capital between these classes. Bourdieu (2018) provided an argument of the schools where he considers that schools are socially biased institutions that mirror the experience of children from dominant classes. Children from such classes are provided with the necessary social and cultural requirements before entering schools, while children from the other working and lower classes are obliged to embrace new knowledge and skills to deal with their educational experience after going to school. Although those children can gain the linguistic, social, and cultural knowledge aligning with the upper and middle classes, their usage of and

familiarity with these competencies will not be as natural as those who were born within those classes, thus academically their penalization is legitimised and explained as lack of ability rather than differences in familial, social and cultural resources (Lamont and Lareau, 1988).

Bourdieu and Passeron classified under the concept of cultural capital many types of cultural preferences, goods, behaviours, and attitudes. Their publications concerning this concept indicate that it has various functions. In *Inheritors* (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1979) for instance, Bourdieu and Passeron explain that cultural capital appears in the form of informal academic standards, which are considered as features of the dominant class. It can include informal awareness and knowledge about the school, linguistic competence, traditional culture, and certain attitudes and personal style (e.g.: aloofness, naturalness, ease, creativity, brilliance, and distinction). While in reproduction, the concept holds a more narrowed definition as academic standards. The authors (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1977) described cultural capital mainly as linguistic competence or talent, prior academic cultural gains and knowledge, general culture, and qualifications. On the other hand, Bourdieu's work *Distinction* (Bourdieu, 1984), describes cultural capital from a distinct theoretical stance. He deems this concept as a measure and ground for a class position in which behaviours, preferences, and attitudes are all referred to as 'tastes' and are deployed for social selection. According to Bourdieu (1984), tastes go hand in hand with economic and cultural capital, thus they differ according to income and educational levels. Therefore, cultural capital can be referred to as a class attribute, a foundation for social selection, and a source of power that indicates the class position (Lamont and Lareau, 1988).

Bourdieu went further to explain that cultural capital can exist in three different forms. First is what he called the embodied state, which implies the individual's dispositions of mind and body, a fundamental state, which is connected to the body and requires embodiment (such as languages) (Bourdieu, 1986). In relation to languages, Bourdieu himself, came from a family that speaks the Béarnais dialect, which is different from French; however, when he entered school, the French language was forced as a language of instruction. That led Bourdieu to see his educational experience as a mechanism to consolidate social separation (Grenfell, 2014). Language as part of the embodied cultural capital plays a crucial role in the process of learning at school. It is a competence that is acquired over a long time, and it differs from one to

another depending on the environment and background each individual came from. Thus, within the educational field, children with higher linguistic capital are predicted to perform better than those with less linguistic capital.

The aggregation of cultural capital in its embodied form necessitates a process of internalization, and since that suggests incorporation and assimilation, it also requires time to be embodied. That time should be personally invested by the individual himself, and not by a second hand. In other words, the acquisition process involves self-improvement, an effort that entails a charge that should be paid personally, and it cannot be transferred immediately as gifts, bequests, exchanges, or purchases.

The second state Bourdieu referred to in relation to cultural capital is the objectified state, which indicates the cultural goods such as books dictionaries, pictures, and instruments. This form of capital can be explained properly when it is related to the embodied state of cultural capital. The objectified state of cultural capital is transmissible as a material, however, what is transmissible is the right of possession, and not necessarily the requirements of its appropriation. In other words, using a machine needs more than just owning that material, it presupposes the ownership of the means that allow the consumption of the machine, which is not more than embodied form of cultural capital. Therefore, cultural capital goods are appropriated both materially by having economic capital and symbolically through having access to embodied cultural capital personally or through proxy.

Bourdieu also indicated the objectification of cultural capital into academic qualifications. This objectification is what he labelled the institutionalised form of cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1986). It includes credentials, diplomas, and qualifications. The institutionalised cultural capital differentiates between the capital possessed by autodidact agents, which may be put into question at any time, and the one academically authorised and guaranteed. The qualifications or the certificates that grant their holders cultural legitimacy, also grant them a constant, legally ensured value with respect to culture.

Bourdieu gave an analogy of 'concours' -the competitive examination for recruitment- to illustrate the power of instituting in imposing recognition. A contest generally seeks the tiny differences between performances, in the end, generates sharp, absolute, and lasting differences between many performances. These differences are what differentiate and

separate the last successful candidate from the first unsuccessful one and create a crucial distinction between simple competence and the officially guaranteed and accepted cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1986). Institutionalising and recognising the cultural capital possessed by agents allows the comparison and exchange of the qualification holders. It also allows the conversion between cultural and economic capital by constituting a conversion rate that guarantees a value for each academic capital.

Cultural capital is thus a primary currency that gives agents value within a particular field with its different states. However, as Bourdieu explained, capital should be introduced in its different forms including social ones. The possession of membership into a particular group gives each member of the group the support that comes from the collectively owned capital. In other words, the total resources, which are connected to gaining a long-lasting social network of relationships, with mutual recognition and acquaintance is what Bourdieu referred to as social capital. These relationships may be maintained only through material and/or symbolic interchange. It can also be ensured and instituted socially by using common names such as family name, class, and tribe. Thus, the amount of social capital owned by individuals is controlled by the volume of the network of relationships they have, and the size of economic, cultural, and symbolic capital that is possessed by this network and can be deployed for their own right (Bourdieu, 1986). Having a network of relationships is not naturally given or socially anticipated, but it is the outcome of everlasting efforts to generate a long-lasting, useful network of connections that can guarantee material or symbolic gain. In other words, it can be seen more as an outcome of individual or collective investment, either consciously or unconsciously for the sake of generating lasting profitable relationships in the short or long term (Bourdieu, 1986).

Each of the three types of capital indicated by Bourdieu (economic capital, cultural capital, social capital) helps its holder to gain certain profits in each social space or field; however, we cannot claim that each of these capitals is separated from the others. In accordance with the principle of energy conservation, earnings in one zone are inevitably paid by costs in another zone, which suggests that the wastage concept has no sense (in the general science of the economy of practices). Thus, social energy is confirmed to be conserved through all its conversions. The same principle can be applied to the different forms of capital, which implies that a particular form of capital can be converted into another form at the cost of time and

labour (Bourdieu, 1986). Both cultural capital and social capital can be obtained through economic capital by investing time and effort for transformation, which is required to generate the kind of power demanded in the desired field. For example, some services and products can be accessed right away using economic capital only; however, there are other goods and services, which call for social capital connections that presuppose a long time and labour to be obtained and maintained as it should be out of its time of use. Thus, attention, care, and concern, which require time are all efforts that should be expressed aiming to personalise gifts and give them more value and meaning instead of their monetary import. In this case, and from an economic stance, the exchange process will be considered a wastage; however, from a social exchange logic, it is seen as an investment that will fruit ultimately in a particular form of capital.

Similarly, measuring the cultural capital possessed by agents calls for measuring the amount of time allocated for obtaining it. Thus, the conversion of economic capital into cultural capital entails the consumption of time, which can be secured through having economic capital. In other words, the effective transmission of cultural capital within a family depends on both the quantity of cultural capital and the usable time available to it. Therefore, the conversion of various forms of capital in pursuit of power within a particular field is regarded as a strategy that aims to guarantee the reproduction of capital (Bourdieu, 1986).

Taking the example of a language that is considered an embodied cultural capital, it can be said that it is the product of a long time and labour. In addition, it can be seen as an output of conversion and exchange between other forms of capital. A child for instance can inherit a language from his family. Because certain language is spoken among family members, the child unconsciously acquires the language through his socialization within that family. The child also may acquire other languages through having courses, lessons, and time for that, which can be feasible in the case of having economic capital, which can be transformed into embodied cultural capital. In a third case, the child may also interact and socialize with people who speak a certain targeted language, having such a network of relationships may help to learn the language, which can be described as an exchange between social and cultural capital.

Throughout his life and academic trajectory, Bourdieu addressed many issues of language. His childhood in the Bearn (in which the Gascon dialect, which is different from the language

of instruction) was spoken, and his experience in Algeria, made it more anticipated that issues of language may feature in his works (Grenfell, 2011). Bourdieu's first work after the Bearn and Algeria, was about education. The field of education was seen as an important contributing factor to rebuilding post-war France. The educational policies at that time attempted to guarantee equality of access for all, thus they raised the idea of a democratic school. However, Bourdieu saw that the culture of school was based on a particular way of seeing the world, which is that of the dominant classes. Language as a medium of instruction was involved in that educational system (Grenfell, 2011).

Bourdieu, therefore, considered language usage in its constitution and operation as a specific form of field. That implies that within every field language has a special value that is determined by dominant forms such as accents, terms, and ways of speaking. Bourdieu described this process as "a system of relations of force, which determines the price of linguistic products and that helps fashion linguistic products", and he used the term 'Market' to refer to that (Grenfell, 2011). Bourdieu gave an illustration of social agents who constantly rely on certain strategies to obtain linguistically superior positions. The strategies that can be used by agents can be exemplified in the overly correct form of language use of the bourgeois when compared to the lower or working class, which has no choice but to use broken forms, their uncoordinated language, or pass to silence. Bourdieu did not confine the linguistic valuation to the opposition between 'bourgeois' and 'populaire', but he also indicated that in addition to the publicly and highly recognised forms of languages, there are many forms that can take a status of legitimate language within a certain social context. Yet, the dominants have the power to legitimate, thus they can appropriate the language and implicitly force it through authorisation. Language, therefore, has a symbolic power that can be considered violence as it can institutionalise an order of supremacy and dominance that goes with the social structure (Grenfell, 2011).

The meaning of language should be considered as linked and connected to social structures and individual dispositions, rather than, just words and their linguistic structures. Language is a can be referred to as a play-off between the form and the information, that is determined by social conditions of production (Grenfell, 2011).

Bourdieu indicates that class position is, in part, determined structurally, but it is additionally embodied in agents' habitus (Bourdieu, 1992). Accordingly, linguistic performance or

competence is perceived as cultural capital in which taste, style, and ideology are parts of the embodied form of capital that indicates the social class position. Agents, therefore, in each field deploy their linguistic capital, which generates linguistic markets. Each of those markets has its particular rules and conventions of exchange that may give or not value to the linguistic competence and proficiency of a particular language. Bourdieu deems language not just an important indicator of social class, but more an index of position, identity, power, and social status (Luke and Graham, 2006).

4.5 Bourdieu and Language

Bourdieu considers the separation between sociology and linguistics as detrimental to both fields. He disagrees with the Saussurean view of language, which detaches language from its real uses and practical functions and considers it a self-contained system-. He believes that treating the internal logic of language as superior to the social or external circumstances would generate and open the door for thinking that the theoretical control over language is sufficient to cover the social and practical mastery of use (Wacquant, 1989). Grammaticality represents only one side of producing meaning (Wacquant, 1989). We cannot isolate language from its context.

Language is a centric medium in all fields. It is the core of the political field, the educational field, and the art field etc. The language used in each field holds a specified value, which is determined by the dominant forms of speech in a particular field (Grenfell, 2011). Bourdieu views language as a product of the interplay between linguistic habitus, and the market (Wacquant, 1989), and he uses the term “market” to describe these social processes. These processes are defined as a “system of relations of force, which determine the price of linguistic products” (Wacquant, 1989, p.47). Therefore, the content of my utterances is shaped and determined by the expectations of the profits or the price that I will obtain. (Wacquant, 1989). In other words, “linguistic communism” in which everyone has equal social competence to participate in language, is an illusion, and utterances are unequal, which means that speakers are not all the same and language is not all valuable and acceptable in the same way (Wacquant, 1989, p.47). It is based on the linguistic norm of a particular field, which is determined through a base rate, that a particular language or utterances are valued over the others (Grenfell, 2011). For example, the language of science would not be valued in the field of art because both fields have different norms. According to Bourdieu, language and

interaction comprise an entire social system (Bourdieu, 1977). Therefore, language variation can be explained through the structure of social relations in the social field and the positions occupied by agents (Grenfell, 2011).

4.6 Conclusion

Bourdieu's theory of practice is a well-known in the field of sociology. It aims at understanding social reality and how individuals act and behave within the different fields they encounter and looking at what determines their practices. Bourdieu underpins his theory of practice by thinking tools (Habitus, field, capital) that must be applied to enable more understanding of social practices and interactions. Linguistic behaviour or practice is considered a social practice. As a social practice, it occurs within a particular field and requires a linguistic capital that is durably incorporated into people's habitus through their personal experiences and social interaction. To sum up, human practice is an outcome of double and unconscious relationships between 'habitus', 'capital', and 'field' (Grenfell, 2014). This relation is recapitulated through the following equation: [(habitus) (capital)] + field= practice (Bourdieu-1986, p.101). Accordingly, agents' practice is defined through the mutual relationship or connection between their dispositions (habitus), their position within a field (capital), and finally the space of the game (field). This equation elucidates the interconnected nature of Bourdieu's key concepts (habitus, capital, and field). In other words, both the occupied social space and habitus are structured, and it is the relationship between these two structures that determines practices (Grenfell, 2014). Similarly, the linguistic practice of human beings can be understood by seeing through Bourdieu's lenses. Language is considered part of one's habitus or dispositions that are acquired through investing time and labour. As part of the embodied cultural capital of the individual, language also can be deemed as a currency that gives agents value and position within a particular field.

Chapter Five

Research Methodology

5.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a description of the empirical journey of this study where the linguistic repertoires of Algerian teachers in the Berber region particularly the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts were explored. The chapter provides a detailed account of the research methodology. It starts with underlying the paradigm that shapes this study, which is rooted in the qualitative research paradigm. Within this paradigm, the research design unfolds as a case study, strategically employing interviews and focus group discussions as the primary tools for data collection. The chapter navigates the reader through the philosophical assumptions, with constructivism and interpretivism serving as guiding world views. Moreover, it elucidates the sampling techniques adopted, providing a view of the decisions made in this aspect of the study. The chapter also explores the pilot study and its role in refining the research instruments. As we progress, attention is devoted to the data analysis process, opting for thematic analysis, and the subsequent steps taken to ensure the rigor and validity of our findings. Ethical considerations, are also addressed, ensuring the responsible conduct of research.

5.2 Philosophical assumptions

While conducting research, as researchers, we always bring with us our assumptions and beliefs. These philosophical assumptions are concerned with our views about the nature of reality, and by what means we can know this reality. The challenge for the researchers is to identify and be aware of these beliefs and views, and to decide whether they will be incorporated into their studies or not (Creswell, 2018).

The study is aligned with a constructivist view of the world because its focus was to examine human experiences. It sought to understand Algerian Berber secondary school teachers' experiences with having multilingual repertoires. Thus, teachers and their experiences were the sources of data for this study, and collaboration was between the researcher and the participants in the present study to generate interpretations and meanings from participants' experiences. This aim fits with constructivism as a worldview.

Constructivists believe that truth is socially constructed through interaction between individuals, and through engaging in interpretations (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Al Riyami, 2015). It is relative and based on peoples' perspectives (Baxter and Jack, 2008), the thing that makes it multiple (Creswell, 2018). Participants are given the opportunity to tell their stories and perception about a particular issue (Crabtree and Miller, 1999). These perceptions and stories, which demonstrate the participants' view of reality, are then interpreted by the researcher to make sense of and understand their actions (Lather, 1992). This stance "recognizes the importance of the subjective human creation of meaning but does not reject outright some notion of objectivity" (Crabtree and Miller, 1999, p. 10).

In qualitative social research, interpretivism is a philosophy that urges the necessity of collaboration between the investigator and the participants to gain knowledge. That means a researcher cannot be detached from the research, and his/her influence over the finding will be unavoidable (Angen, 2000). The emphasis in interpretivism is thus to understand "the multiple social constructions of meaning and knowledge" (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.25) by interpreting the participants' perspectives about a particular issue in relation to its context (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.25). To realise that researchers tend to use qualitative data collection tools, and generate more descriptive data (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Smith, 2006). Based on that, an interpretive approach was the most suitable for this study since meanings were constructed by participants based on their context and their engagement with the world they are interpreting (Crotty, 1998).

5.3 Research paradigm

In social research, and for several years, there was a fundamental choice to be made when conducting a research project. This selection is between quantitative and qualitative paradigms (Robson and McCartan, 2016). These two paradigms differ from each other. The former necessitates the rigidity of data (Gunzenhauser and Gerstl-Pepin, 2006), while the latter aims to represent a world whereby reality is socially constructed (Glesne, 1999). Advocates of the quantitative paradigm believe that social research should adopt the same principles and traditions of "natural science" such as biology, chemistry, and physics. However, social research is different from research in "natural science". Social research involves humans, and its focus is on humans in their social context (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Thus, the "human consciousness and language, the interactions between people in

social situations, and the fact that both researcher and researched are human” (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.18), are all factors that call for different approaches to social research. This approach is the qualitative paradigm.

Qualitative research studies aim at making sense of and interpreting the social phenomena in their natural settings, in terms of the meanings people bring to their lives (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Long and Godfrey (2004) define it as an approach that employs qualitative methods and tools in collecting and analysing data, which implies the use of conceptual or thematic rather than numerical data treatment. It aims at evoking the perceptions and understandings of participants and exploring the characteristics of the cultural and social setting (Long and Godfrey, 2004).

In this study qualitative research is well-suited to explore the complex relationships between the linguistic repertoires of Algerian Berber teachers, politics, culture, and identity in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). It allows capturing the depth and complexity of these interconnections to gain a holistic understanding of how language operates within the specific sociocultural, historical, and political context of the Berber region. It is also ideal for exploratory studies, which are often necessary when investigating relatively underexplored topics or regions such as the linguistic repertoires of teachers in the Berber region. According to Kalu and Bwalya “qualitative research is very useful for exploring complex phenomena that are difficult to measure with quantitative studies” (2017, p.43). They reported that qualitative research is employed in several academic fields, such as social sciences, to gain insight into human experiences and explain their cultural backgrounds, beliefs, and values (Kalu and Bwalya; 2017).

In addition, exploring the linguistic repertoires of Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle), their language practice, and language attitudes are subjective experiences, where both the researcher and the participants are involved in the process of making meaning of and interpreting; therefore, the qualitative paradigm is relevant to capture their subjective perspectives allowing them to share their stories and voices. The choice of a qualitative paradigm in this study is justified by its ability to provide in-depth, and rich insights into the complex and multifaceted nature of language, politics, culture, and identity within the context of the Berber region in Algeria.

Research designs are necessary for structuring research projects. Robson and McCartan (2016) stated that in social research, the design is considered a crucial element; it plays a very important role in planning and organising the research process. Robson and McCartan (2016) argue that if the researcher does not pay careful attention to the design, it may end up with internal contradictions or a mess (Robson and McCartan, 2016). The present study, therefore, was based on Jorrín-Abellán's (2016) Hopscotch model. This model links the two tendencies of teaching and learning qualitative research. First, the paradigmatic, which embraces the theoretical and philosophical aspects of the research, and second the pragmatic, which entails the methods and techniques that can take the form of steps and directions to conduct research (Jorrín-Abellán, 2016). The Hopscotch model allows the combination of both theoretical backgrounds of the research and the various technical procedures that will be tracked in the fieldwork (Jorrín-Abellán, 2016). It consists of many such as worldviews, goals of the research, conceptual framework, research questions, research traditions, data gathering tools data analysis, credibility, and finally ethical considerations (Jorrín-Abellán, 2016). Therefore, this chapter was sectioned based on hopscotch design elements.

5.4 Research Design

5.4.1 Research method: Case Study

There are many research methods in social research (Yin, 2003), such as narrative, grounded theory, phenomenology, ethnography, and Case study (Creswell, 2018). Deciding the relevant approach depends on the purpose and the research questions that we want to reach and answer.

While acknowledging the value of ethnography and observation methods in capturing detailed insights into the language practices and cultural dynamics of Berber teachers, it is also essential to recognize time constraints associated with these approaches. Ethnography, with its immersive nature and observation could have provided rich contextual understanding of teachers' linguistic repertoires. However, due to the extensive time required for their execution, these methods were not feasible within the scope of this study.

It is also worth noting that initially, this study considered using phenomenology as its methodology. Upon careful consideration, however, it became clear that the subjective nature of phenomenology did not quite fit with Bourdieu's emphasis on social structures.

While Bourdieu's framework does acknowledge the role of agency and subjectivity, it places greater emphasis on social structure. Therefore, to better align with the research aim of exploring the linguistic repertoires among Berber teachers in their real context and gaining a deeper understanding of the phenomenon, a case study approach was deemed more appropriate.

Most research questions in this study were “why” and “how” questions. Merriam (1988) stated that opting for a case study as a method of research, or not, is based on the questions and aim of the research, which means what is intended to be known by the researcher. Yin (2003, 2014) indicates that in the case of “why” and “how” questions in research, a case study is of crucial advantage. He (2003) also reported that a case study is research method that involves the empirical investigation of a current phenomenon within its actual setting, particularly when the distinction between the phenomenon and its context is not clearly apparent. Creswell's (2002) defines case study as an investigation aimed at gaining deep insight into a specific "case" or defined system, which requires comprehending a particular event, action, process, or one or more individuals in order to attain a profound understanding. Thus, the researcher is expected to start the research process by identifying a complex situation that would provide an in-depth investigation of the underlying dynamics inside the system in question. The system in question takes a function of the case, and the researcher selects event, activity, or process inside this system to shed light on it.

This study adopted case study as the method for the research. Smith (1978) defines a case study as a bounded system, while Merriam (1988) influenced by Smith (1978) perceives a case study as a thing, a particular entity, a unique entity has specified bounds. This entails that a case study may be considered as a person, programme, or community. Miles and Huberman (1994), by their turn, explain a case study as a phenomenon that happens in a delimited background or context, and they demonstrate it through a circle with a heart in the middle. The heart represents the focus of the study, while the circle indicates the limits of the study (Miles and Huberman, 1994). The present study aimed at exploring the lived experiences of Algerian Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) secondary school teachers in relation to their linguistic

repertoires. The focus of the study was the linguistic repertoires of teachers, while the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) was the edges that defined the 'case'.

Using a case study approach for exploring the linguistic repertoires of teachers in the Berber region, offers several advantages. A case study allows for a detailed and comprehensive exploration of the phenomenon, in this case, the linguistic repertoires of teachers in the Berber region. This approach enables in-depth understanding through investigating the complexities of language and politics, language dynamics, language attitudes, and language practices.

The Berber region is contextually rich. It comprises diverse contexts like Chaoui and Kabyle which, historically, had many tensions with the government concerning the language issue. Therefore, a case study approach allows to capture the contextual richness within the region, which is crucial for understanding how the linguistic repertoires of teachers are shaped by specific cultural, social, and historical factors. The use of a case study approach is especially suitable for this research as it aligns with the complex and context-dependent characteristics of linguistic repertoires in the Berber region. This approach facilitates a thorough and detailed investigation of the subject matter, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

5.4.2 Data gathering tools

This study used two data-gathering tools, namely semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions.

5.3.2.1 Face to face in-depth interviews

The study used semi-structured interviews to get an in-depth understanding of Algerian Berber teachers' multilingual repertoires. A total of twenty-one teachers (n21) from the Algerian Berber region (n10 from Kabyle and n11 from Chaoui) took part in the study. The participants were asked many questions related to how they formed their linguistic repertoires, for example (see appendix):

- How do they use it in different fields?
- What language practices dominate in their professional fields and why?
- What are their attitudes towards languages in their repertoires and what shapes these attitudes?

- How the educational policy influences the use of their linguistic repertoires in the classroom?
- How are language and power perceived among participants in the Berber context (Chaoui and Kabyle)?
- What are the attitudes towards the language policy in education?

The semi-structured interviews in this study provided rich data. Although there were instances where some participants expressed Reticence especially when dealing with issues related to language and politic; however, they granted the participants greater freedom to express their views concerning the investigated topic.

The process of conducting the interviews in the Chaoui context was challenging in this study. One of the obstacles faced was the timing of the interviews, which coincided with a period of grading the national baccalaureate examination. Teachers, who were the primary participants in this study were preoccupied with grading students' examinations. This led to difficulties in securing their availability for interviews. Despite multiple rescheduling attempts, teachers were unavailable to conduct the interviews as planned.

Addressing these issues faced during the interview process, I made the decision to invite teachers to my own place in Algeria. I interviewed an initial teacher participant who kindly connected me with his peers in the field of education. This choice aimed to create a relaxed and nondisruptive environment for uninterrupted conversations. The decision was out of necessity, as the rescheduling attempts failed multiple times; however, offering a familiar and welcoming setting, teachers from the Chaoui context felt more at ease and could participate in the interviews, even amidst their demanding schedules. This approach facilitated the interviews and encouraged a sense of mutual understanding and cooperation between me as a researcher and the participants.

On the other hand, the interview process in the Kabyle context proceeded smoothly. I had the privilege of conducting an interview with an initial teacher participant who kindly extended introductions to colleagues, encouraging a welcoming atmosphere within the visited educational institutions. The timing for interviews in the Kabyle context was empty of exceptional events that could disrupt scheduling interviews. I kept visiting schools regularly awaiting teachers who could potentially have break for conducting the interviews. The

absence of scheduling conflicts in this region allowed for a more smooth and systematic data collection process.

The interviews provided interaction between me as the researcher and the participants in the study, and based on that, knowledge of the social phenomena was understood. That is, by interpreting the meaning participants gave to their experiences through the interaction between the participants and the researcher. During the interviews, a set of questions about the study's topic were covered, and the participants had the space and the freedom to answer (Bryman, 2016). The questioning approach alternated between following the interview guide's prescribed format and adapting similar questions rather than strictly duplicating the exact wording outlined in the interview schedule. In addition, some questions were skipped because they were already covered under answers to other questions, while new questions were generated when needed, based on what participants shared during the interviews (Bryman, 2016)

Based on Creswell's several steps for conducting interviews in qualitative research (Creswell, 2018), the first step in this study was determining the questions, these questions were open-ended, and oriented to understand the linguistic repertoires of Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) secondary school teachers. They were designed to be clear and understandable to the participants (Creswell, 2018). Both taking notes and audiotaping, while interviewing, were applied in this study after taking the participants' permission (Creswell, 2014). Subsequently, an interview protocol was used during the interview to guide the discussion (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2015).

In this study, the gender distribution among participants in the interviews is ten females (n10) and two males (n2) in the Kabyle context, while two females (n2) and nine males (n9) in the Chaoui context. Treating the Berber region as a single case study, the interview sample consists of ten female and eleven male participants. While the gender distribution is relatively close considering the study one case, it is important to acknowledge the numerical difference in gender in the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts. However, gender is not a primary focus in this study, and the goal is to obtain a comprehensive understanding of linguistic repertoires within the Berber region; therefore, the existing distribution still allows for valuable insights.

5.4.2.2 Focus group discussions

The second research tool used in this study was focus group discussions (n2). Focus group discussions are considered a method of gathering data in qualitative research. It includes several participants (at least four or five) (Bryman, 2016). To get an in-depth understanding of the linguistic repertoires of Algerian Berber teachers' ten participants were organised in two groups, the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) consisting of six participants, and the second focus group discussion (Kabyle) included four participants.

Though focus group discussions have many advantages, however, they also may have some limitations such as difficulties to fulfil and realise it as it is hard to gather participants together at the same time, difficulties to control the focus group discussion, and bias as being subject to domination by some participants or by the moderator himself (Wong, 2008).

Similar to the challenges encountered during conducting the interview in the Chaoui context, organizing focus group discussion in the Chaoui setting during the baccalaureate exam grading period posed significant difficulties. Securing participants and planning their presence at the same place and time was exceptionally challenging. Consequently, I sought assistance from the academic sector, which engaged the school director to schedule a one-hour meeting involving six teachers. The outcome of this attempt was not as anticipated. The brief duration was not sufficient to fully address all the questions, and time was wasted on unrelated ideas to the topic during the discussion. In addition, participants were all speaking at the same time, which led to a loss of conversational control, making it challenging to manage the flow of the discussion.

Following that, I conducted another focus group considering all the previous challenges. My recruitment initially involved one participant, who played an important role in involving other participants for the focus group discussion. Despite facing several scheduling obstacles as discussed previously, eventually the focus group meeting was successfully arranged to take place at my residence, resulting in a productive and successful discussion.

As a moderator, during conducting the two focus group discussions to uncover how participants view the phenomena in question, guiding the conversation rather than dominating was the primary objective (Bryman, 2016). Unlike the challenges encountered in the Chaoui context, the focus group session in the Kabyle context proceeded smoothly. The process of participant recruitment was similar to that of the first focus group discussion

(Chaoui), with one participant serving as the connector to others. The focus group discussion was set in an educational institution, which facilitated the process. However, it is worth noting that despite the overall smoothness, there were instances where certain participants dominated the discussion. While endeavours were made to encourage active participation and provoke discussion among the participants in the second focus group discussion (Kabyle), it was observed that some remained passive during the focus group sessions. Their passivity was evident in their agreement, conveyed either verbally or through facial expressions, with the statements and viewpoints expressed by other participants.

The focus group discussions in this study provided the participants with the opportunity to explore each other's reasons for their perspectives and gave the chance for the interviewees to voice agreement on certain points that they did not think about and allow the researcher to gauge the groups' consensus (Bryman, 2016). They helped understand how participants collectively made sense of the phenomenon investigated, and how they established meanings of it (Bryman, 2016; Wong, 2008).

The two focus group discussions were tape-recorded (with consent) and then transcribed. It was difficult to keep notes about what exactly has been said and who said it especially when participants talk over each other. It was also destructive to stop interviewees or ask them to repeat what they say to write it down (Bryman, 2016). The process of transcribing focus group discussions was difficult and time-consuming compared to one-to-one interviews. It was challenging to distinguish the participants' voices. In addition, sometimes participants were talking over each other, which maximised the degree of difficulty while transcribing records (Bryman, 2016). Therefore, recording the two focus group discussions was crucial to not miss any views (Bryman, 2016).

The overall distribution in the two focus groups was four female and six male teachers. In terms of gender balance, the focus group discussions distribution is imbalanced, with more males in the Chaoui context focus group, and more females in the Kabyle context. This gender imbalance might influence the dynamics of the discussions and the perspectives shared if gender was a primary focus in this research. However, Like the interviews, gender was not the main focus in this study.

5.4.2.3 Sampling Techniques (interviews and focus group discussions)

Selecting the sample should be based on the participants' capability and efficiency to bring sufficient data that is valuable to understand a particular phenomenon (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2002). For this study, the main sample for both interviews and focus groups was Algerian Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) secondary school teachers. Selecting Algerian Berber secondary school teachers (Kabyle and Chaoui) for this study helped to examine their linguistic repertoires by knowing what languages they have their repertoire and how they acquired or learned these languages. In addition to how they use these repertoires in different fields, particularly in their professional field (education) taking into consideration the language policy in Algerian education.

The sample in this study for both interviews and focus group discussions was purposive, also known as non-probability sampling (Sharma, 2017). This means selecting a specific group of participants, who meet certain criteria, such as being Berber Algerian secondary school teachers from the Kabyle and Chaoui contexts with multilingual repertoires. Purposive sampling is often used in qualitative research to ensure that the selected participants have the knowledge and experiences relevant to the research objectives (Bryman, 2016). According to Patton (1990), qualitative researchers tend to purposefully choose each of their cases. This allows researchers to focus on a particular group that can provide in-depth insights into the research questions. He stated that "the logic and power of purposeful sampling lies in selecting information-rich cases for study in depth. Information-rich cases are those from which one can learn a great deal about issues of central importance to the purpose of the research" (Patton, 1990, p.169).

Patton's (1990) proposed sixteen purposive sampling strategies one of which is the snowball sampling technique, also referred to as chain or network sampling. This study employed snowball sampling in both interviews and focus group discussions, as described in the previous section (data gathering tools), by initially recruiting a single participant, who then acts as a link to introduce additional participants for both the interview and focus group discussions.

In addition, the fact that both Kabyle and Chaoui contexts represent the largest two Berber groups (respectively) that belong to the Amazigh (Berbers) in Algeria, and people in these two regions have Tamazight as a native language in their repertoires. Therefore, their linguistic

repertoires are likely to be diverse including languages such as Tamazight, Derja, Arabic, and French. This will make the study more interesting as it deals with investigating teachers' linguistic repertoires.

Thus, the study considered this point to explore how this linguistic history affects teachers' use of their linguistic repertoires particularly in their professional field (education). Adding to this, I would like to highlight that I ethnically belong to the Chaoui group, that is, an "insider", and this is one affecting factor in choosing the settings of data collection as I have a personal interest to know about language use in these two contexts. Finally, methodological demands of qualitative research necessitate an in-depth study of a small but well-defined sample to "penetrate social life beyond appearance and manifest meanings [allowing]... the researcher to be immersed in the research field, to establish continuing, fruitful relationships with respondents and through theoretical contemplation to address the research problem in depth" (Crouch and McKenzie, 2006, p. 483).

5.5 Pilot study

Research suggests the necessity of conducting a pilot study before starting the data collection process. Doing so provides warnings concerning the future possible failures of the project, allows the researcher to know whether the research methods and instruments are relevant or inappropriate, and guides the researcher's use of protocol (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). Pilot studies are undertaken to ascertain the feasibility of the research, to test the adequacy of the data collection instruments, to test the clarity of questions, to predict and identify possible problems that may occur, and guide the research protocol of collecting data. For this study, a pilot study for interviews and focus group discussions was undertaken. Before starting the process of data collection, two interviews were conducted with two Algerian Berber teachers as well as one focus group discussion.

During the pilot phase of the two interviews, the sessions progressed without any significant issues. However, it became evident that certain questions within the interview protocol were insufficient in addressing all the research objectives. Consequently, revisions were implemented by incorporating additional questions and modifying existing ones in order to ensure a comprehensive coverage of the research objectives.

Piloting the focus group discussions provided valuable insights into its dynamics, highlighting challenges such as simultaneous speaking, interruptions to each other, and time constraints. The experience led to adjustments in the process of conducting the focus groups. To address these challenges, participants were clearly communicated about the importance of speaking one at a time to facilitate note-taking and recording. Efforts were also made to establish a comfortable and distraction-free environment, emphasizing the importance of participants staying until the end of the interviews. Following the pilot study, adjustments were also implemented in the questions of the focus group discussion, involving adding, and changing some to better align with the study's objectives.

Piloting the study provided valuable practical experience and boosted the researcher's confidence by identifying the flaws, weaknesses, and potential challenges and rectifying these issues before implementing the full-scale study.

5.6 Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis is not straightforward. Using qualitative data collection tools such as Interviews and focus group discussions on qualitative research generates data in a form of a large corpus or unstructured textual material, which are complicated to analyse (Bryman, 2016). Data analysis in qualitative research thus, is not ready-made, it needs to be tailored, reviewed, and choreographed (Huberman and Miles, 1994). It also does not go alone, rather, it goes hand in hand with the other aspects of the research such as the process of collecting data, analysing data, and writing up. They are all interrelated parts (Creswell, 2014; Creswell, 2018).

Qualitative data analysis can be viewed from two sides or can be deemed as having two layers. The first layer is elucidated through Creswell's data analysis spiral (2018). It is more general (Creswell, 2014), and constitutes of several steps such as managing and organizing the data, reading and memoing emergent ideas, describing and classifying codes into themes, developing and accessing interpretations, and representing and visualizing the data (Creswell, 2018). The second layer is concerned with the specific analytical procedures that are embedded in each method or approach (Creswell, 2018; Creswell, 2014). Given that this was a case study, analysis of the data was based on strategies related to this research method as described in the sub-section below.

5.6.1 Process for data analysis

This study employed NVivo to facilitate the analysis of the data using thematic analysis. The analysis involves generating themes through the process of coding as described by Attride-Stirling's (2001) stages of thematic analysis. Instead of the traditional method of thematic analysis, where data are handled manually using coloured pens and physically cutting and categorizing data, NVivo enabled a seamless coding process. NVivo played a crucial role in managing the coding procedures, significantly reducing complexity and rendering the task more manageable (Hilal and Alabri, 2013).

The process of analysis began by entering the translated transcripts of interviews and focus group discussions into the software (NVivo). Employing the initial coding phase, the passages and texts deemed crucial for this research were systematically identified. Each of these significant portions was then assigned initial codes based on the idea embodied in it. Subsequently, all the passages that referred to the same area of discussion were coded similarly, that is, they were given the same name (Gibbs, 2007). This served as the foundation for subsequent analysis. Some of the initial codes that were generated during the recurrent reading of data (interviews and focus—groups' transcripts), by listening to the records repeatedly, checking the field notes (Ajjawi and Higgs, 2007), and identifying the relevant texts from the transcripts are “hesitation to talk about politics”, “awareness about language policy in education”, “vagueness of language policy in Algeria”, “written notes concerning language use in the classroom”.

To enhance clarity and organization, the next step of grouping related initial codes under specific organizational themes, creating a hierarchical structure. The term theme “captures something of interest or importance” to the research questions (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.468). As an example, the above stated initial codes were classified under one organisational theme which is “language policy in education”. This organizational theme allowed for a more coherent and manageable overview of the coded data, facilitating the analysis process.

Finally, the generated organizational themes in this study were consolidated under four global themes, providing a comprehensive and structured representation of the multi-layered data.

This systematic approach, facilitated by NVivo, ensured a rigorous analysis of the complex linguistic repertoires. To illustrate the process of analysis and the utilization of NVivo in this study, some images were included in the appendices.

Coding in this study was grouped into first level and second-level coding. The former entailed giving labels to clusters of words, while the latter indicated categorizing the formed codes into a smaller number of themes. Developing themes involved a constant state of questioning about what should go or seems to go with what (Robson and McCartan, 2016). The thematic analysis of this research involved both inductive and deductive approaches to qualitative methods. That is, some themes were influenced by Bourdieu's concepts (Habitus, Field, and capital), while new themes emerged from the data (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006).

The deductive approach involved applying Bourdieu's theoretical concepts to the data and identifying instances where these concepts were evident. For example, codes such as "societal habitus" were influenced by Bourdieu's notion of shared cultural dispositions and practices within a social group. Similarly, the identification of different "fields" such as administration, schools, home, and street reflected Bourdieu's concept of social spaces where individuals interact and compete for various forms of capital (linguistic capital). Additionally, the concept of "convertibility of capital" drew from Bourdieu's idea that different forms of capital (e.g., economic, social, cultural) can be converted into one another within specific social contexts. This concept demonstrates the process of learning and acquiring the languages included in participants' repertoires, and how the different forms of capital which are possessed by participants were converted into linguistic cultural capital.

Conversely, the inductive approach allowed for the emergence of new themes directly from the data, without being predetermined by existing theory. For instance, themes such as the "vagueness of language policy" and "perceived contradictions in language policy" were not explicitly linked to Bourdieu's concepts but emerged from the analysis of the data. By integrating both deductive and inductive approaches, the thematic analysis provided a comprehensive understanding of the linguistic repertoires of secondary school teachers in the Berber region. It allowed for the exploration of both theoretically informed concepts and new insights generated directly from the data, resulting in a rich analysis that captures the complexities of language policy, practice, attitudes, and power perception in this context.

Thematic networks, which is a technique to organise the process of thematic analysis was also applied in this research (Attride-Stirling, 2001). Thematic analysis “seeks to unearth the themes salient in a text at different levels, and thematic networks aim to facilitate the structuring and depiction of these themes” (Attride-Stirling, 2001, p.387). It organises, in a systematic way, the process of extracting the “Basic Themes”, “Organising Themes”, and the “Global Themes”, and then “illustrating the relationships between them” (Attride-Stirling, 2001, p.388). An illustration of how themes were developed is included in the appendices (see appendix 11).

5.7 Coding of participants

In the process of coding my research participants from the interviews, the following approach was employed to ensure data organization, confidentiality, and streamlined analysis. Each participant was assigned a unique code that integrated both the contextual origin and a numerical identifier. For instance, participants from the Chaoui context were labelled as "Chaoui" followed by a numerical distinction such as "Chaoui 1" and "Chaoui 2" Similarly, participants from the Kabyle context were assigned codes like "Kabyle 1" and "Kabyle 2."

This coding system offered different advantages. Firstly, it allowed for the easy categorization of participants according to their regional background. Moreover, this coding system contributed to participant anonymity, safeguarding their identities, while still enabling comprehensive data analysis.

By utilizing this structured approach to participant coding, the research process was made more efficient, enabling a methodical investigation of linguistic repertoires in the Berber region of Algeria. Although my study is not primarily designed to make direct comparisons between the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts, the structured coding system implemented provides insights into the distinct linguistic repertoires and contextual factors within the Berber region, specifically in the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts. By adopting this coding approach, the research aimed to understanding the linguistic practices without imposing an overt comparative framework. The following table demonstrates the coding system in this study:

<i>Interviews Participants (Berber region)</i>	
<i>Chaoui context</i>	<i>Kabyle context</i>
Chaoui 1	Kabyle 1
Chaoui 2	Kabyle 2
Chaoui 3	Kabyle 3
Chaoui 4	Kabyle 4
Chaoui 5	Kabyle 5
Chaoui 6	Kabyle 6
Chaoui 7	Kabyle 7
Chaoui 8	Kabyle 8
Chaoui 9	Kabyle 9
Chaoui 10	Kabyle 10
Chaoui 11	

Table 1: Participants Coding System

The participants in this study represent secondary school teachers hailing from urban areas in the Berber region particularly Chaoui and Kabyle contexts. They come from different age groups (22-57 years old) and have been teaching for different lengths of time (from 5 months to 33 years). Moreover, they teach a variety of subjects such as Math, French, English, Arabic, German, and Physics. Additionally, the participants have different levels of education and qualifications and speak three to five languages including Derja, Tamazight, Arabic, French and English. Collectively, this heterogeneous mix of participants provides a comprehensive exploration and understanding of the linguistic repertoires and language practices among secondary school teachers in the Berber region from various perspectives. To illustrate this diversity, a table in the appendices is provided, illustrating the diverse profiles of the participants and their linguistic repertoires.

5.8.1 Trustworthiness

Generally, positivist researchers criticise trustworthiness in qualitative research because they believe that terms such as validity and reliability cannot be approached similarly in naturalistic

works (Shenton, 2004). They consider that the term validity comprises a connotation of measurement that is concerned with quantitative rather than qualitative research (Bryman, 2016). Therefore, qualitative researchers often avoid using the term validity (Robson, 2002) and substitute it with terms such as trustworthiness.

Some qualitative researchers question the compatibility of the term validity with qualitative research; however, they also see the necessity for a qualifying measure for their research (Golafshani, 2003). Therefore, many of them preferred to coin terms that detach them from the conventional paradigm, and that indicate validity in their research (Golafshani, 2003; Shenton, 2004). Lincoln and Guba (1986) developed four concepts in the quest of evaluating the trustworthiness in naturalistic research, which are: Credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Shenton, 2004; Lincoln and Guba, 1986). These four concepts are paralleled with the standards applied to test rigor in quantitative research (Internal validity, external validity, reliability, objectivity) (Lincoln and Guba, 1986). That is, as an alternative to internal validity (truth value of inquiry or evaluation), external validity (applicability), reliability (consistency), and objectivity (neutrality), Guba proposed respectively the terms credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Lincoln and Guba, 1986; (Bryman, 2016).

However, the different nature of qualitative and quantitative paradigms necessitates that addressing these corresponding concepts should not be in the same way as in the conventional paradigm (Lincoln and Guba, 1986). Lincoln and Guba (1986, p.76) stated that the “criteria developed from conventional axioms and rationally quite appropriate to conventional studies may be quite inappropriate and even irrelevant to naturalistic studies (and vice versa)” (Lincoln and Guba, 1986, p.76). In other words, though the concepts proposed by Guba and Lincoln are paralleled with the criteria of testing rigor in conventional research, however, they were addressed in a manner that fits with naturalistic research axioms.

5.8.2 Credibility

Credibility parallels internal validity in quantitative research (Bryman, 2016). It indicates the researchers’ endeavours to present a true illustration of the phenomena under investigation (Shenton, 2004). In qualitative social research where the focus is on multiple accounts of reality, which are socially constructed (Bryman, 2016; Lincoln and Guba, 1986). It is the

credibility of the study that defines its acceptability (Bryman, 2016). Credibility can be achieved by following the principles of good practice (Bryman, 2016). In other words, this study implemented the following strategies to enhance the credibility of the research and make it more trustworthy:

Although participants in this research were selected purposively through selecting Berber Algerian teachers from the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts; however, participants in this study exhibited a diverse range of characteristics, including various age spans, distinct professional experiences, different academic disciplines and distinct genre. This diversity in the sample enriched the research process, as it allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the research topic from multiple perspectives.

The study employed a data triangulation approach, incorporating both semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions. Combining data from two different methods of data collection helped to enrich the findings of the research and provided data from various angles leading to a more credible research study. In addition, the study included a pilot study to enhance the credibility of the research study. piloting the interviews and the focus group discussions helped to test their efficacy to collect relevant data that answer the research questions.

The study also used a consent form that explained the aims of the study, provided an account of the researcher's background, and ensured the confidentiality of data and anonymity of participants. It also explained the ability of participants to withdraw at any time. These factors helped to gain the trust of participants and promoted more open and honest responses, to provide a thick description of the investigated phenomena (Shenton, 2004).

5.8.3 Transferability

Transferability parallels external validity in quantitative research. As opposed to quantitative research, which seeks to generalise findings, qualitative research is generally conducted with a small group of individuals, who have common characteristics. Thus, the findings tend to be unique to the studied context (Bryman, 2016). Thus, a thick description or a rich account of details is suggested to give other researchers a database for judgments concerning the possibility of transferring the findings to a different context (Bryman, 2016; Shenton, 2004). This study is a qualitative study that aimed at understanding a shared phenomenon among a

small group of people, which are Berber Algerian secondary school teachers in the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts. It did not aim to generalise, rather, it aimed to get a deep and rich account of details about Berber teachers' linguistic repertoires and how they are used).

5.8.4 Dependability

Dependability in qualitative research is equivalent to reliability in quantitative research (Bryman, 2016). Positivists address the concept of reliability in their works by applying methods that guarantee the same results of their work if it was repeated in the same context, with the same participants, and with the same methods (Shenton, 2004). However, the varied nature of the studied phenomena in qualitative research makes it difficult for the researchers to test the dependability (Shenton, 2004; Fidel, 1993; Marshall and Rossman, 1999). Guba and Lincoln highlighted the close relationship between credibility and dependability and stated that ensuring the former in qualitative works contributes to the achievement of the latter (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). This can be achieved through keeping a complete and detailed record of all steps in the research process available for access including formulating the problem, selection of participants, notes on the fieldwork, the transcripts, methods of collecting data, and steps of data analysis (Bryman, 2016; Shenton, 2004). This study provided documentation of all steps of the research process. This chapter provided a record of the different phases of this research for other researchers to access. This enables repeating the research in similar conditions.

5.8.5 Confirmability

Morrow (2005) states that in contrast to the quantitative paradigm, which considers objectivity as an endeavour, qualitative traditions recognise that the nature of qualitative works including the type of data and the process of gathering data are earthed in subjectivity (Morrow, 2005). Patton (1990), on the other hand, relates the concept of objectivity to employing instruments that are human value-free, and since it is difficult to achieve that in qualitative research, it is also difficult to eliminate the researchers' bias (Patton, 1990). While Welch states that "As we understand something we are involved and as we are involved, we understand" (Welch, 1998, P. 242). Therefore, it is impossible to completely suspend the researcher's bias to understand, yet it is possible to be aware of the degree and type of bias a researcher may have (Maxwell, 1996).

The issue of researcher bias can affect the trustworthiness of the findings (Patton, 2002). Maxwell states that the bias is most salient in the stages when the researcher tries to prove that the data interpretations are trustworthy (Maxwell, 1996). The researchers in this stage, start to deliver and put their own grasp and meaning to the data instead of the participants' perceptions (Maxwell, 1996). Though it is impossible to eliminate the researcher's subjectivity, however, some techniques reduce the implementation of research bias.

To achieve confirmability, this study overlapped methods by using interviews and focus group discussions. According to Shenton (2004), triangulation is a beneficial technique that prompts the reduction of researchers' bias (Shenton, 2004). A detailed description of the research methods was also illustrated in this chapter, which is considered helpful in reducing the bias of the researcher, as it allows the readers to decide to what extent the data and the ideas generated from it are accepted (Shenton, 2004). Finally, Confirmability can be achieved through being aware of one's own feelings, behaviour, and responses in connection with the experiences and behaviours of participants (Miles and Huberman, 1994, Shenton, 2004). Therefore, being transparent about the insider status and acknowledging one's ethnic background and potential biases upfront can help in building trust with readers and can demonstrate commitment to conducting an unbiased study.

My ethnic affiliation within the Chaoui group played a significant role in shaping the context of this study. As an insider to this community, I brought a deep understanding of the cultural nuances, language dynamics, and the specific context within the Chaoui context. This insider perspective allowed me to establish a level of trust and rapport with the participants, that an outsider may find challenging to achieve. While my background brings a unique perspective to this study, it is important to recognize that my goal was to provide an unbiased and insightful analysis of the linguistic repertoires in the Berber region, leveraging the advantages of my insider status, while adhering to rigorous research methodologies. Heshusius (1994) challenges the duality and the split between objectivity and subjectivity and considered it as a separation between the knower and the known. She, instead, supported the "awareness of a deeper level of kinship between the knower and the known" (Heshusius, 1994, p. 16). In other words, the researcher must make "implicit assumptions and biases overt to self and others" (Morrow, 2005, p.254).

5.9 Ethical considerations

5.9.1 Ethical standards for the study

Ethical issues can take place at different phases of the social research process (Bryman, 2016). It is crucial to take into consideration the question of ethics when conducting 'real' world research, which involves people as participants. Research can cause negative consequences for the participants. Anxiety, stress, harm, and many other destructive effects on the participants may happen, especially if the participants are vulnerable, or the topic of the research is sensitive (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Thus, ethics professional associations such as British Sociological Association (BSA), American Sociological Association (ASA), and Social Research Associations (SRA) are fundamentally concerned with issues revolving around how the researcher is supposed to treat and deal with people, who are participating in the research study, and how the relation with them is framed in terms of the activities that should and should not occur (Bryman, 2016). In addition to these professional associations, researchers should be familiar with the ethical guidelines of the institution they belong to. Colleges, universities, and most higher education institutions have an ethics committee that aims at protecting the participants, the researcher, and the institutions per se (Bryman, 2016). Ethical codes do not hinder sensitive topics, they just push the researcher to think carefully about the potential implications of the study conducted, including (sensitive questions vulnerable participants, and invasive/intrusive methodologies) (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Robson and McCartan stated that "being ethical does not prevent socially sensitive research; it requires responsible research" (p. 207).

Ethical codes can be violated in many ways, which can have negative consequences on the research process and the results of the study. This violation can be in the form of potential harm to participants, lack of informed consent, employment of deception, and invasion of participants' privacy (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Bryman, 2016). These key issues are explained in a more detailed way, as they are linked to the present research study.

5.9.2 Harm to participants

Any research that can cause harm to participants is considered intolerable by people. This harm can take different forms such as physical harm, stress, and loss of self-respect, dignity, and confidence (Bryman, 2016). Therefore, researchers should take caution to not cause any disturbance to both the participants and the participants' relationships with their milieu

(Bryman, 2016). The nature of the present study, which examines the linguistic repertoire of Algerian Berber teachers in the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts did not include special physical pressures that make it hard for participants to take part in the project; however, it involved the use of their data. As a researcher, I took action to protect the participants from potential psychological risks or harm. First, through providing them with informed consent that provide participants with clear and detailed information about the study allowing them to decide to participate or not and giving them the right to withdraw at any moment during the research. Also, through keeping personal information confidential by using pseudonyms to protect their anonymity and keeping records out of reach.

5.9.3 Confidentiality

Preserving the confidentiality of the records and the subjects involved in the research study is one way of protecting participants from potential harm (Bryman, 2016). This implies that both the records and the identity of people who are involved in the research project should be kept unrevealed. Also, the researcher should be careful when the final findings are being displayed, to make sure that the participants are not identifiable or identified (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Bryman, 2016). To keep the secrecy and confidentiality of personal data of participants in this research, all personal data enabling their identification were securely protected by choosing pseudonyms that made them anonymous in this study. Also, the personal details that threaten their confidentiality were separated from the interviews. In addition, the records and transcripts of both the interviews and the focus group discussions were accessed by the researcher only.

5.9.4 Informed consent

Through informed consent, the potential participants in the study are supposed to know as much information as might be required for them to decide whether they will participate, or not in the research. The individuals must be allowed to accept or reject cooperation (Bryman, 2016). The BSA stated in sociological research, the sociologist has to clarify what the research is about, and why it is being conducted. Similarly, the SRA suggested that the participants should be informed about the research as much as possible including being able to withdraw their participation at any time, and without giving reasons (Bryman, 2016).

In this study, the participants were given informed consent in both English and Arabic languages. This approach was adopted to ensure that the participants had a comprehensive understanding of the study and received clear information about it. The informed consent ensured that participants understood the aim and objectives of this research and enabled them to make well-informed decisions regarding their involvement in this study. It also granted them the autonomy to quit at any point. The consent form in this study served to protect the privacy of individuals' personal information. To maintain anonymity, through the pseudonyms employed, and guaranteed that records stay inaccessible.

5.9.5 Privacy invasion

The question of privacy is another concern of ethics professional associations. The degree to which privacy invasion can be tolerated is a crucial ethical issue. Privacy is deemed as “a tenet that many of us hold dear, and transgressions of that right in the name of research are not regarded as acceptable” (Bryman, 2016, p.131). The issue of privacy is connected to the informed consent concept. The informed consent in this study provided participants with details about the conducted research. It clarified what it is like to be involved in that study. Based on the information provided in the informed consent participants recognised that the degree of privacy invasion will be limited to particular area related to their linguistic repertoires, which contributed to their decision to participate or not in the research project (Bryman, 2016). Participants' identity, records, and any identifiers were kept anonymous and confidential. This was achieved by assigning pseudonyms to participants and restricting access to their records exclusively for the researcher to preserve their privacy (Bryman, 2016).

5.9.6 Deception

Deception is considered a widespread concept in social research. It involves lying and deceiving participants about the aim of the study, or any other kind of deception that entails limiting and hiding information about the study (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Deception is considered a way to weaken the trust between the researcher and his participants (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Bryman, 2016). This study used informed consent to inform the participants about the purpose of the study, and what is expected from them if they accepted to take part in the study. There was no deception of any kind. The participants had a period of one week to accept or refuse to participate in the study. Participants were informed that they will be audio-recorded if they are accepted to participate in the project. They were also

informed that their participation in this research study is completely voluntary, and they can withdraw from the research at any moment without giving any reasons.

5.10 Transcription and Translation

While often considered as a behind-the-scenes task, transcription plays a pivotal role in shaping how data are presented and understood. When transcribing interviews, researchers are faced with numerous choices that can significantly impact the representation and interpretation of the data. These choices include deciding whether to transcribe verbatim or non-verbatim, whether to handle non-verbal cues such as pauses and laughter or not, whether to correct grammar or retain colloquialisms (Oliver et al, 2005). Transcription practices encompass a spectrum ranging from naturalism to denaturalism, each reflecting distinct views on the representation of language and its relationship to reality. In a naturalistic approach, transcripts aim to faithfully capture every utterance, including elements such as stutters, pauses, and nonverbal cues (Oliver et al, 2005). Advocates of naturalism argue that language serves as a direct reflection of the real world, and thus, transcripts should provide a verbatim depiction of speech (Schegloff, 1997). Conversely, denaturalized transcripts prioritize the underlying meanings and perceptions embedded within speech, recognizing that language constructs our reality (Cameron, 2001).

The transcription process in this research involved both approaches as a result of researching multilingually. Initially, during the transcription of the records in their original languages, which was undertaken manually, I sought to capture the richness of participants' speech by including pauses, hesitations, repetitions, and non-verbal cues such as "Um" and "Uh" to indicate moments of reflection or transitions between ideas. The transcripts were conducted onto A4 papers, with the layout organized vertically to distinguish between questions and answers. The original transcripts were multilingual, incorporating Derja, Arabic, French, and English, with rare instances of Tamazight. The participants were teachers specializing in various subjects such as Mathematics, Arabic, English, French, German, Mechanics, and more. Therefore, there was no expectation for them to speak a specific language from their repertoire, as I explicitly stated that they were free to use any language they preferred. Consequently, the presence of the researcher did not significantly influence the language use of the majority of participants. However, one participant who taught English chose to

communicate in English because I speak English. Interestingly, some other participants who also taught English mixed languages while communicating, incorporating English along with other languages.

Pauses were illustrated through symbols such as (...), while non-verbal sounds such as laughter, or sighs were represented using letters, rather than symbolic representations. This method enabled a more comprehensive representation of participants' speech, facilitating subsequent analysis and interpretation of the data. As I engaged in the translation process, I made a choice to prioritise clarity and conciseness while maintaining fidelity to the intended meanings of participants, especially as I am employing thematic analysis where identifying passages and texts that are important for the study is crucial part of the analysis process. Drawing on my linguistic repertoire and understanding of cultural context, I selectively omitted repeated words and sounds that I deemed irrelevant to the research.

Translation plays a crucial role in cross-cultural research, especially in situations where there is a linguistic mismatch between the audience's native language and the data collected for analysis (Oxley et al. 2017). Translating the gathered data into the target language poses methodological challenges, particularly concerning colloquialisms, Jargon, idiomatic expressions, and ensuring precise word meanings and clarity (Oxley et al. 2017). Although one may initially choose a direct word for word translation of the data to maintain participant meanings, this strategy frequently fails to accommodate linguistic and cultural diversity (Oxley et al. 2017). Therefore, during the translation process, there were instances where I opted not to translate word by word. Instead, drawing on my cultural background, insider knowledge and fluency in both the original languages of the transcripts and English, I conveyed the meaning of the original text. This allowed me to capture the cultural context inherent in participants' language use, ensuring that the translated transcripts reflected the intended meanings and preserved the richness of participants' discourse within the context of the study.

I aimed to produce translated transcripts that captured the intended meanings and facilitated the thematic analysis process. However, I must acknowledge the inherent subjectivity in transcription and analysis as an insider in this research. Even with a commitment to accuracy, transcribers and researchers may inadvertently introduce interpretations influenced by their

own perspectives and dispositions. Reflexivity, transparency and awareness of potential biases are important to reduce this bias in addition to repeatedly listening to recordings.

5.11. Researching Multilingually

Numerous research objectives often require the utilisation of more than one language throughout the research process or the dissemination of findings (Holmes et al., 2013). This study employed a multilingual approach by conducting the interviews and focus groups using multiple languages. Participants were allowed to freely switch between languages (Arabic, Derja, Tamazight, French and English) during the interviews and focus groups. The consent form was also translated from English to Arabic, to ensure that the participants understood the aim and objectives of the present study.

Researching multilingually brought several benefits for this study. Allowing participants to use different languages (Derja, Tamazight, Arabic, French and English), during the interviews and focus group discussions, enhanced the depth and richness of the findings. The participants were able to articulate their thoughts and experiences in their preferred language, which provided deep insights about their perspective and removed language barriers.

Translating the consent form of this research to Arabic improved the clarity of the study. It helped participants to understand the aims of the study, its benefits, confidentiality and other information related to it. Comprehending the details of the study reduced the risk of miscommunication between the researcher and the participants. The present study investigated and explored the linguistic repertoires of Algerian Berber teachers (Chaoui and the Kabyle); therefore, allowing participants to use their multilingual repertoires during the interviews and focus groups was a way of recognising the linguistic diversity of Algeria.

Although researching multilingually is encouraged by some researchers (see Holmes et al., 2013), it also might be a challenging approach. Handling multilingual interviews and focus groups requires additional efforts throughout various stages of the research including collecting, translating and interpreting the data (Holmes et al., 2013). Holmes et al. (2013) reported that translations and interpretations when researching multilingually is a challenging task for researchers especially when they are not multilingual themselves. However, in this study the researcher is an insider, who shared the same languages of the participants. This allowed the access to the primary data sources, which helped avoiding the challenges of translation during the analysis process. Having an insider status, by sharing

similar languages of the participants, enabled the researchers to fully engage with the primary data and effectively navigate between the linguistically diverse datasets. This contributed to valuable insight and enhanced the interpretative process.

In conclusion, the decision to conduct interviews and focus groups using multiple languages from both the interviewer and interviewee was pivotal in the success of this research, offering a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the topic.

5.12 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter served as the methodological guide to the empirical exploration of the linguistic repertoires of Algerian teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). The chapter provides an overview of the research methodology employed in the current study. It provided the rationale for selecting the different design elements that form the foundation for understanding and exploring the linguistic repertoires of Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) secondary school teachers in Algeria, where multilingualism is commonly practised.

Chapter Six

Acquisition and Usage of Linguistic Repertoires

6.1 Introduction

This chapter examines how Algerian Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) secondary teachers acquire and use their linguistic repertoires. It points to how teachers allocate languages in their repertoires to different settings and fields and situations. The first research question is 'What languages make up the linguistic repertoires of Algerian secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle)? In addition, how do Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) use their linguistic repertoires in different fields?'

6.2 Awareness of Being Multilingual

Participants in this study were asked if they consider themselves multilingual. The findings revealed varying responses among Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle). Responses collected from the first setting (Chaoui) presented diverse range of perspectives, with some participants confidently recognising their multilingual abilities, while others displayed uncertainty about their language proficiency. Among the participants from this context, only few participants (n=4) possessed a clear understanding of their multilingual skills and confidently identified themselves as multilingual individuals.

Chaoui (1) considered herself as a multilingual person, expressing a high level of competence in specific languages and ongoing efforts to improve proficiency in other languages through daily interactions. Her statement reflects her view of multilingualism as one entity rather than clear-cut entities (Georges and Bernard, 2009). This aligns with Gumperz's (1964) notion of a verbal repertoire, wherein a multilingual repertoire encompasses all recognized means of conveying a message. Chaoui 1's perspective regarding multilingualism could be influenced by her institutionalised habitus, which has been developed and accumulated over time through her studies in linguistics. This alignment with Bourdieu's conceptual framework of "habitus," "capital," and "field" (Bourdieu, 1948) illustrates how individuals are shaped by the social contexts (field) in which they are immersed. This is evident in the case of Chaoui 1, who had a doctorate in linguistics, and as such familiar with linguistic concepts, which in its turn enabled her to identify herself as a multilingual person.

The rest of the participants (n7) from the Chaoui setting were ambivalent with 'yes' or 'no' responses, indicating that they did not consider themselves multilingual. For instance, Chaoui

3 shared his perspective stating that he does not perceive himself as a multilingual individual since he is only fluent in Arabic. He reported, that although he has a technical proficiency in French, he would not consider himself proficient in a literary sense. Chaoui 6 also expressed that he does not identify himself as a multilingual individual. Instead, he sees himself as a perpetual learner, who is always in the process of learning new knowledge.

The tentative answers of participants (n7) withing the Chaoui setting can be attributed to multiple factors. First, participants may have various languages in their linguistic repertoires; however, it is crucial to recognize that they may have varying levels of proficiency in each language. This variation can lead people to perceive languages with lower proficiency differently from those they are more proficient in, which can result in potential confusion concerning considering the languages with low competency compared to the ones with high competency or not. The contradiction was particularly noted among some participants, who reported that they are not multilingual, while they were using different languages during the interviews. This can be demonstrated through Chaoui 6's interview.

Moreover, it is important to consider that participants' comprehension of multilingualism and how they perceive it can vary based on their diverse educational habitus. In contrast to Chaoui 1's viewpoint, who consider multilingualism as one entity, participants who hesitated to label themselves as multilingual may believe that multilingualism is separated entities (Georges and Bernard, 2009), which requires full control and proficiency in each language.

In addition, it is important to acknowledge that some participants did not include languages such as Tamazight or Derja in their language repertoires. Teachers were disregarding them because of the beliefs and social conventions that were implanted in their habitus for years.

The findings revealed that participants (a total of 10) from the Kabyle setting showed awareness of their multilingual abilities. They listed between four to five languages in their linguistic repertoires, which can be illustrated by Kabyle 4, who reported that she is proficient in Tamazight as a native language, Arabic as the language used in education, French, English the language she is teaching, in addition to her basic understanding of the German language. Participants were certain of being multilingual. They were more confident saying they are multilingual.

The two focus group discussions in this study revealed that teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) are multilingual and that they are aware of their multilingual abilities. The first focus group discussion (Chaoui) indicated that being multilingual does not necessitate equal competency in all the languages included in the linguistic repertoires. Meanwhile, the second focus group discussion (Kabyle) revealed that being multilingual does not require equal competency in all languages; however, the individual should be able to hold a conversation to the end with one language and without switching. This perspective aligns more closely with a definition of multilingualism as separated entities (Georges and Bernard, 2009).

Participants' social backgrounds from Chaoui and Kabyle settings may play a role in their varying perspectives (Participants from the Chaoui context displaying some uncertainty about their proficiency in multiple languages, while participants from the Kabyle context demonstrating a stronger awareness of their multilingual abilities). The degree of awareness or lack of awareness regarding one's multilingualism can be shaped by the social habitus and self-representation within the Berber communities (Chaoui and Kabyle).

6.2.1 Disregarding languages

The study revealed instances where Berber teachers showed a lack of consideration for certain languages. Languages such as Tamazight and Derja, which are part of the linguistic repertoires of the participants, were not taken into consideration when investigating the languages, they speak and understand. Furthermore, when teachers were asked to rank languages based on preference and perceived value, these languages were excluded from consideration as well.

Derja and Tamazight were disregarded by participants (n10) in the Chaoui context. There was a tendency to overlook the use of Derja and Tamazight during various phases of the interview process. For example, when Chaoui 3 was questioned about the languages he speaks and understands, he reported proficiency in Arabic and French but omitted his knowledge of Tamazight and Derja. Subsequently, he was, particularly, asked about his proficiency in Tamazight, given the fact that the Chaoui community belong to the Berber region. His (Chaoui 3) answer was “The Chaoui language, of course! It is the language of our ancestors. It represents the linguistic heritage passed down through generations. Of course, we learned it from our parents. Thank God, I am fluent in Chaoui dialect”.

Chaoui 3 acknowledged his Chaoui ethnicity and his proficiency in the Tamazight language; however, when he was asked to list the languages he speaks and understands, he initially overlooked Tamazight. However, after further questioning about Tamazight, he included it among the languages he is proficient in. The initial exclusion of Tamazight among the Chaoui participants can be attributed to the perceived association of Tamazight with rural areas, backwardness, and shame. Chaoui 1, for instance, associated Tamazight and rural regions suggesting that people in rural areas are the primary speakers of Tamazight. This is demonstrated in the following quotation:

As I teach in a rural part of Khenchela where the Chaoui dialect of Tamazight is spoken, I use Tamazight to a limited extent. However, I do not use Tamazight to deliver the lesson; instead, I use it for brief alerts or warnings to the students. That is all. As I said earlier, the primary language used in their region is Tamazight (Chaoui dialect) (Chaoui 1).

Rural areas in Algeria tend to lack sufficient public facilities. The index of development and the infrastructure in these areas are low (Souidi and Bessaoud, 2011; Rouabah, 2020). Therefore, associating Tamazight with rural areas, which lack social and public facilities (Rouabah, 2020), may be a way of expressing the perceived backwardness of the language and thus being ashamed of it. The first focus group discussion (Chaoui) revealed a link between Tamazight and rural areas. This point is similar to the views expressed in Rouabah's (2020) study confirming the association between rurality and Tamazight in the Chaoui context (Rouabah, 2020). The focus group discussion (Chaoui) also revealed that teachers experienced childhood events that affected their perceptions of Tamazight. Some participants (n2) stated that their parents punished them for using Tamazight because it was associated with unintelligence and stubbornness. It was described as a step backward to a worse or less developed state, and a language that can never be a language of science. These childhood experiences implanted negative perceptions in participants' habitus in the first context (Chaoui). This is similar to McDonald's (1989) work where he discussed the hesitancy of Brittany peasant women to pass Breton to their children because of their belief that French is the language of "femininity", "urbanity" and "cultivation" (McDonald, 1989).

In the Chaoui social context, many participants identified themselves more as Arabs and supported the Arabisation and its visions of nationalism and Islamic unity. This is summarised by Chaoui 7, who stated that he is prouder of being an Arab than being an Amazigh and that

the people of Algeria are Muslims and to Arabism, they belong as stated by Ibn Badis. The Algerian government used the Quran and religion (Islam) to reinforce and give legitimacy and symbolic power to Arabic (Benrabah, 2004; Daoudi, 2018); therefore, it (Arabic) was recognised as a legitimate symbolic capital and power. According to Bourdieu, symbolic capital is “economic or cultural capital, which is acknowledged and recognized” (Bourdieu, 1990a, p. 135).

Recognising Arabic as one’s language and affiliation to Arabs, according to participants from the Chaoui context, might guarantee profits, privileges, acceptance, or symbolic power, which might be a reason for advocating Arabic and disregarding Tamazight. Moreover, Derja and Tamazight are both native languages in Algeria (Belmihoub, 2018); however, Derja has no apparent status in the constitution. It (Derja) is marginalised under the policy of Arabisation (Belmihoub, 2018). Although Derja differs from Arabic on all linguistic levels such as phonology, morphology, lexicon, and syntax (Saadane and Habash, 2015), participants were referring to Derja as Arabic considering that they are the same. This may be another reason for disregarding Derja among participants from the Chaoui context.

Participants (n9) in the Kabyle context did not consider Derja when they were asked to classify the languages included in their linguistic repertoires based on preference or perceived value. The limited use of Derja in the Kabyle context may contribute to its lack of regard. As per the accounts provided by participants from the Kabyle context, the primary languages used in their area are Tamazight and French, while Derja is not commonly employed. This may be a reason for disregarding it (Derja).

According to participants in the Kabyle context, Derja is learned through contact with people from other regions where Derja is spoken such as in Algiers (the Capital where some participants had their university studies). This is summarised by Kabyle 7, who stated that in the Kabyle context, both Tamazight and French hold prominent positions and that languages spoken within their community consist mainly of French and Tamazight. Additionally, Kabyle 9 emphasised that Derja has no presence in their context, and the issue is not related to regionalism but rather pertains to their mother tongue. They have a strong tradition of using Tamazight.

Most of the participants (n9) in the Kabyle context, proudly identified Tamazight as their mother language; however, only one participant (Kabyle 8) overlooked Tamazight in his

classifications. Tamazight is limited only to certain areas in Algeria, in addition, it is neither a language of instruction nor a compulsory subject in education, which is considered the professional field of participants in this study. As stated by Kabyle 8 that "I omitted Tamazight from my list because, in my view, it is not a language, that I utilise in my profession, although it is a language, I do not consider it a part of my professional or academic domain."

Tamazight is not a dominant language in major domains of power such as education, administration, and science in Algeria. Although it is considered a national and official language in the constitution (Hamdan and Kessar, 2023; Rouabah, 2022); however, it is not present in the different fields of power (marginalised) (Belmihoub, 2018). Many participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) stated that Tamazight is not a language of development and science. As an example, Chaoui 3 stated that "I do not believe that Tamazight is as linguistically rich as some other languages. It does have a significant heritage value, I agree with; however, it is not rich enough to be a language! I mean a second language for practical use and benefit".

Therefore, viewing Tamazight as a language that brings no benefits apart from being a heritage may be another reason for not considering it as a language in their linguistic repertoires.

Bourdieu (1986, p.81) defines the "embodied cultural capital" as a "long-lasting dispositions of the mind and the body", which enables producing profits. Considering language as an embodied cultural capital that brings profits and gains in a particular field, Berber teachers in this study confined their linguistic repertoires to languages that have status and that are perceived as prestigious and valuable across different fields of power. As such, they excluded Tamazight and Derja because they were not perceived to be valuable in major fields of power such as education and science. Disregarding languages from teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) may play a crucial role in determining participants' lack of awareness of their multilingual abilities. The factors discussed above may lead participants to exclude some languages from their linguistic repertoires, subsequently affecting their awareness of their multilingual abilities.

6.2.2 Social Habitus and Self-representation

"Social habitus" and "Self-representation" are other extracted sub-themes from the first organisational theme. The study found that many participants in the Berber region (Chaoui

and Kabyle) were referring to themselves collectively as if they were products of the same context, in which they live. Some participants (n6) from the Chaoui context frequently expressed a sense of belonging and pride by addressing themselves as a group, stating expressions such as “we as Arabs”, and “In our region”. Although they admit that they are, originally Amazigh, their affiliation is more to Arabs. Chaoui 9 was asked about the language or the languages he is making sure to preserve. He reported that Arabic is the language he is trying to learn the most because they are Arabs and Arabic is the national language and the language of religion. In another question, he was asked about the languages used in the classroom, he stated that they almost use Arabic, and added that they use Derja more by virtue of belonging to the Chaoui context. The following excerpts illustrate Chaoui 9’s perception “Especially Standard Arabic, it is the language we trying to learn the most. Why? I mean...first, because it is our national language and because of religion too. That is it. We try to master it because we are Arabs”. Additionally, Chaoui 7 reported that Arabic has its roots in their history as Muslims, and that Abd El Hamid Ibn Badis stated that “The people of Algeria are Muslims, and to Arabism, they belong”.

The social habitus, which was created through a long social process in the Chaoui context, led to enduring social convictions represented in the form of believing that people (Chaoui) there are Arabs. Although participants from the Chaoui context speak other languages and know deep inside that they are Amazigh, however, they identified themselves as Arabs. They viewed Arabic as their mother language, national and official language, and the language of religion. Participants might perceive monolingualism as a unifying policy in Algeria. Consequently, due to the social habitus ingrained in the Chaoui context, participants may be unaware of their multilingual abilities. This tendency was also evident in the first focus group discussion held within the Chaoui context, where four participants (n4) indicated that people in the Chaoui context tend to associate their identity with religion, and their religion with Arabic as it is the language of the Quran. Consequently, Chaoui individuals consider themselves as Arabs, while Kabyle individuals associate their identity with language, primarily Tamazight.

Within the Kabyle context participants (n7) consistently referred to themselves collectively too. They often used expressions such as “we Kabyle people” and “Here in the Kabyle context”. According to Kabyle1, Kabyle people have the ability to communicate in French,

which distinguishes them from residents of other provinces where French is not as commonly spoken. Additionally, Kabyle 9, reported that the French language is considered the closest language to the Kabyle people and the language that is widely used in households there. Kabyle 5 noted that the majority of families in the Kabyle context have immigrant family members, who are living abroad (France), which contributed to high proficiency in the French language in the Kabyle context. The second focus group discussion (Kabyle) also confirmed this. Participants (n4) expressed a strong attachment to French indicating that people in the Kabyle context are attached to French. They even described it as a 'second mother language'. The question addressed to participants was about their overall linguistic repertoires not about French in particular; however, they were specifically relating French to the Kabyle context. Kabyle 7 reported the following "We (Kabyle people) ...in our daily discussions, we integrate French a lot because it became part of us...especially Kabyle people"

The social habitus in the Kabyle context involves various languages: Tamazight as a mother language, and French holding a notable place as part of their culture, in addition to Arabic, which is the official and national language, and the language of education in Algeria. Participants in the Kabyle context were open for embracing other languages; therefore, they were aware of their multilingual abilities. This is indicated in Kabyle 8 statement:

In secondary school, I had a French teacher whose name is John. One day he said about us, Kabyle people, he told us: you Kabyle people, you speak many languages, but you do not master any language. Maybe he was right because to speak these languages Arabic, French, a little bit of English, and Tamazight of course, the mother language with its varied dialects...we have these languages, but to have the intention to master them all, I do not think so (Participant 8).

To sum up, these individual convictions are ingrained socially in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). The self-representation and the social habitus of participants from each context (Chaoui and Kabyle) were factors that determined their awareness (or not) of being multilingual.

Figure 2: Thematic Network of the Awareness of Multilingualism

6.3 Languages Forming the Linguistic Repertoires

Many participants in this study were uncertain of their multilingual abilities as it is demonstrated above. However, when participants (interviews and focus group discussions) were asked to list the languages they hold in their linguistic repertoires, the majority referred to three or more languages, which contradicted many previous stances concerning their awareness of multilingualism. These languages are mainly Derja, Arabic, French, English, and Tamazight. In addition, German, Russian, and Turkish were also present in some linguistic repertoires.

6.3.1 Learning and acquiring teachers' linguistic repertoires

Participants from were asked about how they acquired and learned the various languages they have in their repertoires. Many sub-themes such as milieu, schooling, books, Television, internet, and technological devices emerged.

6.3.1.1 Milieu

The finding of the study revealed that participants perceived the milieu (The environment and the surroundings) as an important factor in learning and acquiring Derja, Tamazight, and French in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle).

All participants (n11) from the Chaoui context stated that they inherited or acquired Derja through the milieu in which they have been born and lived. They reported that Derja was acquired naturally from the society and surroundings as it is the language of communication, and the language used by people in the region. They also declared that the process of learning was unconscious, spontaneous, and automatic. Few participants considered Derja as a mother language; therefore, they stated that they acquired it unconsciously from the milieu. This is indicated in the following excerpt:

First concerning the mother language (Derja), this language is acquired naturally and spontaneously. We acquire it from the milieu in which we were born and lived. As an example, the mother is the first person we communicate and live with. We spend all our time in our youth with our mother. I guess that is why it is called the mother language (Chaoui 6).

Participants also reported that they acquired Tamazight through the milieu (parents, grandparents, mother-in-law, family, society, and friends at university or work) as it is summarised by Chaoui 10:

Concerning Chaoui language, maybe through interactions. In Taberdga, though we speak a little bit of Derja, there were families who speak Chaoui! Even my parents, for instance, my father, mother, grandpa, and grandma, speak Chaoui. We learned it from them, and we, sometimes, tried to speak it until we learned it. Through the environment as I told you... (Chaoui 10).

While few participants stated that they acquired or learned French through their surroundings, such as Chaoui 8, who learned French in a manner similar to Arabic, both from schools and their surrounding society.

All participants (n10) from the Kabyle context, proudly, stated that Tamazight is their mother language; therefore, they acquired it from home where it is the language of communication. This is indicated by Kabyle 2, who reported that Tamazight is significant for them because it is within their family. He reported that as a Kabyle family, where the local environment predominantly uses Tamazight, they speak Tamazight. Additionally, Kabyle 1 reported the following: "Tamazight (Kabyle dialect) is my mother tongue. It is obviously acquired from home. We speak Tamazight (Kabyle dialect) at home". They also reported that French was acquired through the milieu in which they live (Kabyle context). Kabyle 8 reported that "French language in the Kabyle context is used a lot in the daily interactions between people or the professional fields. It is rooted more than Arabic in daily interactions". Moreover, they

explained that they learned or acquired Derja through the milieu too. Socialisation with people who speak it in different provinces helped many participants to learn Derja. This is demonstrated in the following quotations:

...Derja of course. Derja why! Because I studied in Algiers. Although Derja is Difficult for us because people ask, "Why you do not speak Derja"? When I passed my baccalaureate exam and went to Algiers...I have never been out of Bejaia before. Trying to make a correct sentence was like climbing a mountain for me. However, later you get used to it and you become fluent. I learned different dialects...I integrated and learned the language and the Derja (Kabyle 9).

According to participants in this study, these languages (Derja, Tamazight, and French) were acquired through socialisation and interaction in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle); however, belonging to two distant settings may result in different experiences. Based on teachers' statements, differences in the process of acquisition are noted.

First, it can be noted that the prevalence of French is higher among participants originating from the Kabyle context, as it is more prominently integrated into their daily interactions. According to participants they begin to acquire it inherently during their formative years, either through familial or societal interactions. In contrast, many participants originating from the Chaoui context perceived French as the language of colonialism. Consequently, while it does exist in the Chaoui context, its usage is comparatively less prevalent and used when compared to the Kabyle context.

Second, Derja is seen as a mother language among some participants from Chaoui context. It is the first language they were exposed to since childhood. On the other hand, Tamazight is regarded as the mother language for participants from the Kabyle context. It is the first language they grow up with and recognised.

Third, the acquisition of Tamazight in the Chaoui context primarily occurs through familial interactions with grandparents and parents, or through exposure to Tamazight, which is more prevalent and restricted to rural areas. The language spoken outside apart from rural areas is not Tamazight, whereas in the Kabyle context, Tamazight serves as the primary spoken language, while Derja is acquired through social interactions with individuals from other regions, where Derja is commonly utilised.

The focus group discussions also referred to the milieu as a way of acquiring languages. Participants (Chaoui) indicated that they learned Tamazight from their interaction with elderlies at home such as parents or grandparents. The participants (Kabyle) also reported that, they learned French from the milieu they have been raised in because French is spoken even among elderlies in the Kabyle context.

Participants from the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) acquired many languages (Derja, Tamazight, and French) in their linguistic repertoires through the social capital they possess. The networks of relationships including family, friends, and acquaintances in a particular context contributed to acquiring these languages in different phases in their lives.

6.3.1.2 Schooling

Another sub-theme under learning and acquiring teachers' linguistic repertoires is schooling. The participants in this study referred to the school as a source of learning some languages (Arabic, French, and English) in their linguistic repertoires. Quranic and public schools, according to participants, had an important role in learning some languages. Concerning Arabic, many participants from the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) declared that it is the language of education. They explained that they started learning Arabic when they entered the primary schools, or at the Quranic schools where they started learning the Quran. Many participants also noted that they learned French through education. They started learning it in primary, middle, and secondary schools and then at university, especially for scientific streams.

Regarding English, although it is less dominant among participants compared to French, many participants stated that they learned the language from schools. The focus group discussions in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) also referred to schools as a source of some languages in teachers' linguistic repertoires. Some participants from the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) stated that they learned Arabic, English, and French in school, while participants in the second focus group discussion indicated that, they learn Arabic for the first time in school.

To conclude, schools are considered a source of cultural capital. Participants from the Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) learned many languages (Arabic, French, and English) at schools. These languages are considered embodied cultural capital that brings benefits and profits to its speakers in different fields (Bourdieu, 1986).

6.3.1.3 Reading

The third sub-theme under learning and acquiring teachers' linguistic repertoires is reading.

Chaoui 9 reported that he learned Standard Arabic primarily from books. He expressed that he has a fondness for poetry and enjoy reading it and that when he comes across unfamiliar or archaic words, he turns to the internet for assistance. He also stated that the internet is the most frequently employed resource for enhancing his language skills. Kabyle 8 additionally reported that since television did not exist back at that time when he was a kid, people turned to strip cartoons as substitutes. Their preference for French essentially stemmed from the fact that children found what they enjoyed in it. He stated that in today's context, strip cartoons are akin to anime. Therefore, it served as their television, and it was the starting point before transitioning to reading detective stories (novels). According to Kabyle 8 This was how people from his generation acquired proficiency in French.

Participants in the study were referring to books, poems, articles, journals, dictionaries, magazines, and comic strips. Reading these cultural 'goods' helped to learn and refine some languages in participants' linguistic repertoires. Books, poems, articles, journals, dictionaries, magazines, and comic strips are all considered a source of cultural capital in their objectified state (Bourdieu, 1986).

6.3.1.4 Television, Internet, and Technological Devices

Television, the Internet, and technological devices are also stated to be sources of learning languages among participants from the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). Chaoui 1 reported that she learned Turkish because of her interest in watching Turkish series. As for Chaoui 7, he stated that his passion for watching movies and series led him to acquire the English language and understand it directly without a need for translation or subtitles.

Watching TV (cartoons, series, documentaries), and the internet including social media, YouTube, phone applications, movies, series, and songs are all forms of objectified cultural capital that have been invested to learn languages among participants from the Berber region (Chaoui and the Kabyle).

6.3.2 Convertibility of Capital

The study found that the linguistic repertoires of Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) are learned and acquired through the conversion of different forms of capital (economic, social cultural) (Bourdieu, 1986). Participants stated that they learned and acquired the languages

in their linguistic repertoires through the milieu they lived in, schooling, reading, television, internet, and technological devices as stated above.

The milieu is considered a social capital where participants get in touch with other people. Socialisation and establishing relationships with people from certain fields through investing time and effort raise the chances to get certain profits that may take different forms. Many teachers from Berber region declared that they learned some languages in their repertoires through the socialisation with other people, whether from different regions in Algeria, different countries, or even with family members. Kabyle 9 reported that when he successfully completed his baccalaureate exam and travelled to Algiers to pursue his studies, it was a new experience for him because he had never ventured beyond Bejaia before. Constructing a proper sentence in Derja felt as challenging as scaling a mountain for him. However, with time, he got used to it, and became fluent in Derja. This is also summarised by Chaoui 10 in the following excerpt:

My aunty is living in France. When she comes from France, her kids speak French when they are here in Algeria. That made me want to learn it. They speak French, and they do not know how to speak Arabic or Derja. That contact made me try to know what they were saying. That helped me when I was a kid to learn it (Chaoui 10).

Based on the above statements of Kabyle 9 and Chaoui 10, there was a conversion between the social capital that the participants had (living in the Kabyle context with Kabyle people who speak Tamazight, in addition to associating with family members, who came from France to visit) and the profits they got, which took the form of learning languages such as French and Derja (embodied cultural capital).

Reading, on the other hand, is a habit that can be acquired through family or that can be developed by a person. The process of reading involves investing money, which is considered economic capital to buy different objectified cultural goods such as books, magazines comic strips, and dictionaries. Reading these objectified cultural goods is invested to get profits in the form of embodied cultural capital (learning languages).

Well here (in the Kabyle context) the French language is the first used language in daily dealings. It is in the environment (milieu). When we were kids, what attracted me to the French language is the strip cartoons. We did not have televisions. It is like this that this love for the French

language came. We did not find attractive things to read in Arabic. I used to collect money each week and go to the bookseller's shop. That is it (Kabyle 8).

In addition, Television, Internet, and technological devices are all forms of objectified cultural capital that were acquired through investing economic capital (money), and which are being invested to get embodied cultural capital, which comes in the form of the languages included in participants' linguistic repertoires.

The languages included in the linguistic repertoires of participants are embodied cultural capital that was learned or acquired through investing different forms of capital: economic capital (money), social capital, and cultural capital. Therefore, the conversion of capital is demonstrated in the process of learning and acquiring languages among participants from the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle).

Figure 3: Thematic Network of the Languages Forming Teachers' Repertoires

6.3.3 The Usage of the Linguistic Repertoire

Participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) referred to the interlocutor and the context of conversation as the main factors that influence their choice of language.

6.3.3.1 The Interlocutor's Influence

Chaoui 2 explained that her choice of language in a conversation depends on the person she is dealing with. She reported that she uses Arabic with teachers of Arabic, Derja, and code-mixing with colleagues, who are close friends with her, French with colleagues, who teach the same subject as her, and a mixture of Derja and French with her family members. Chaoui 6 reported that he feels more comfortable using French to explain himself and discuss things in

general; however, the interlocutor has to understand this language otherwise he would be obliged to use Arabic or Derja. Kabyle 1 and Kabyle 2 also stated that they use Tamazight and French; however, if they have friends, who do not speak Tamazight, they use Derja or mix Derja and French. The following excerpt demonstrate this:

Out of Bejaia, I speak the language they are speaking. If they speak Derja I will speak Derja, if French I will speak French. If they speak all languages, I will speak Tamazight. At school with colleagues the same thing, Tamazight, and if they do not speak it, I speak Derja (Kabyle 1).

Chaoui 3 explained that the choice of language in a conversation is also connected to the educational and professional levels (status) of the interlocutor in a specific context. For example, he reported that he communicates in French with his neighbours, who are a university professor and a practicing doctor. He stated that he uses a blend of Derja and French. Bentahila (1983), who investigated codeswitching among Arabic-French Bilinguals in Morocco, also referred to this. Bentahila (1983) indicated that participants are more likely to switch from Arabic to French with doctors and employers in the medical, educational, and administrative sectors (Bentahila, 1983).

The two focus group discussions also revealed the influence of the interlocutor on the choice of language in a conversation among participants (Chaoui and Kabyle). Participants in the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) reported that in the Kabyle context, Tamazight and French are the languages that should be used because they are the common languages in the Kabyle setting. They stated that when interacting with adults in the Kabyle context it is possible to use Derja as they might be already exposed to it; however, it is necessary to use Tamazight when interacting with children, as they might not be exposed to Derja yet. This illustrates how the interlocutor and the context influence language choice in a conversation. Participants in the second focus group discussion (Kabyle) reported that they generally use French and Tamazight in everyday life; however, they also indicated that their choice of language is connected to the interlocutor (students, colleagues, family members).

The linguistic choices are tied to social constraints. Although participants from the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) have the agency to ultimately choose the language or the languages they use, language choices are also tied to social constraints (Busch, 2012). This is summarised in Chaoui 6, Kabyle 1 and Kabyle 2 statements. Participants have the agency to choose the language or the languages they want from their arena of languages as long as the

interlocutors have the same languages in their repertoires too. Once the interlocutor is unable to speak and understand a language from the speaker's linguistic repertoire, this language would be excluded from the choices of languages, as it would not fulfil the aim of communication, which is communicating and transmitting the message.

6.3.3.2 The Contextual Influence

The context is another factor that is perceived to influence the choice of language among participants from Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). Participants were asked about their choices of languages in different given fields: Home (family), street (neighbours and friends), public institutions, school (colleagues), and outside the Kabyle context.

The study found out that many participants (n9) from the Chaoui context mainly use Derja and French at home with family. Two participants, however, stated that they use Tamazight also at home with their parents. They do the same with neighbours and friends they mix Derja and French. On the other hand, all participants from the Kabyle context declared that they use Tamazight and French at home with neighbours and with friends. Participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) stated that they always mix languages in their conversations. They were also referring to Arabic as the language of education and the language that brings them more value in the educational field because it is the official language of education (primary, middle, and secondary schools) in the constitution. Chaoui 8 stated that it is better to use Tamazight in the Kabyle context as it gives more privileges. This is demonstrated in the following excerpt:

...in some areas, there is what we call racism. If you do not speak Tamazight, they will deal with you differently. I mean they will despise and underestimate you. I have lived this experience many times. In Bejaia for instance, I went to buy something, and they did not want to deal with me...when I spoke Chaoui dialect or Tamazight with them, they changed their way of dealing with 180% (it became positive...Because I speak Tamazight, he dealt with me more nicely (Chaoui 8).

While most respondents from the Kabyle context stated that, they speak Derja when they are out of the Kabyle context, and when the interlocutor does not speak Tamazight. For instance. Kabyle 2 reported that beyond Bejaia (Kabyle context), people are not familiar with Tamazight; therefore, the common languages used are Derja and French, "When they (people living out of the Kabyle context) do not comprehend, you often find yourself blending these two languages". Chaoui 8 also stated that using French is perceived to be better in

administrations as it gives the speaker more value being a language of prestige and a required language in administrations. He reported that he had an interaction with Algerian Airlines in Algiers, and he initially used Arabic, but the service was not very satisfactory. However, when he switched to French, they provided a better level of service.

The focus group discussions in this study also revealed that the context of the conversation plays a significant role in determining the choice of language among participants. For instance, participants (n4) in the second focus group discussion (Kabyle) referred to how their children are obliged to use Arabic when they start primary school. This is an illustration of how the context affects and guides the choice of language among multilingual speakers. Participants in the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) also indicated that the choice of language might depend on the context; that is, in the Chaoui context, as teachers, it is better to be able to speak the language of the area (Tamazight) even if they are teachers of mathematics or foreign languages.

Language is a crucial element in all fields; it is the motor of communication. Each domain or field holds specific conventions that give each language in the repertoire particular value (Grenfell, 2011). That means that languages in participants' linguistic repertoires are not all valued in the same way in all fields (Wacquant, 1989, p.47). Therefore, participants in this study allocated certain languages in their repertoires to certain fields. The chosen language or languages for each field give profits either by making the conversation easier, getting more privileges by using the language of a particular group, or even by providing the speakers with prestige and power to participants (Grenfell, 2011). In other words, the choice of language is the product of the interplay between the linguistic habitus, and the 'market' or the field (Wacquant, 1989). The expectations of profits that participants have are what shape their linguistic choices.

Figure 4: Thematic Network of the Usage of Teachers' Repertoires

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter analyses and discusses the first global theme of this research, which is 'the formation and usage of Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) teachers' linguistic repertoires. The chapter aims to answer the first research question: What languages make up the linguistic repertoires of Algerian secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle)? In addition, how do Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) use their linguistic repertoires in different fields? The study revealed, in relation to the first research question, that teachers' linguistic repertoires in the Berber region in Algeria is formed of many languages, which are mainly Arabic, Tamazight, French, Derja, and English in addition to other languages that were declared by some participants such as Turkish, Spanish and German.

The study reported that teachers' linguistic repertoires in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) are composed of four main languages, which are Derja, Tamazight, Arabic, French, and English. However, teachers' competency level and the learning or the acquiring processes in the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts are different.

This chapter revealed that the languages included in teachers' linguistic repertoires are acquired or learned through the milieu, schools, reading, television, social media, and technological devices. Derja, Tamazight, and French are mainly acquired from the milieu they lived in or the social capital they have, whether family, Friends, or society. Arabic and English are learned in schools. Teachers encounter Arabic in primary, middle, and then secondary

schools or in mosques where they start learning the Quran; and they learn English in middle and secondary schools and maybe at the university if they opted for English as a discipline. French is acquired from the milieu as well as from school starting from primary school. The study also revealed that participants used social media, the internet, television, and technological devices to support and improve the acquisition or learning of some languages in their linguistic repertoires.

The study identified Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) teachers' usage of their linguistic repertoires in different fields. The research revealed two main factors that influence teachers' choice of language: the interlocutor and the context. Participants reported that their choices of language in a conversation are connected to the field in which the conversation is taking place (education, home, administrations, different regions, etc.), in addition to the individual or people with whom they communicate (family, friends, acquaintance, colleagues, etc.). The study shows that mixing languages among participants in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) is the norm. Teachers in the Chaoui context generally mix Derja and French with family, and friends, while in the Kabyle context teachers mix Tamazight and French. The study also revealed that the educational level, the profession, and the socioeconomic status of the interlocutor influence language choices.

This study also highlights participants' awareness of being multilingual. The chapter reveals that the majority of participants from Chaoui context were not aware of their multilingual abilities because of overlooking some languages from their linguistic repertoires, because of self-representation, as they identify themselves as mainly Arab Muslims whose language is Arabic. In addition to the social habitus, which is structuring individuals and structured by individuals. On the other hand, although participants from Kabyle context were disregarding some languages, however, they were quite aware of being multilingual, which may be connected to their self-representation and social habitus as Amazigh whose language is Tamazight, in addition to the French language, which is perceived as part of their culture.

Chapter Seven

Attitudes towards Languages Forming the Linguistic Repertoires

7.1 Introduction

This chapter presents and discusses the language attitudes of Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) in Algeria. It aims to answer the second research question: What are the Algerian Berber teachers' attitudes toward the languages included in their linguistic repertoires? How are these attitudes developed among the teachers? If at all, how do their attitudes differ based on the Berber region they come from? The findings in this chapter are discussed in relation to the second research question, the literature review, in addition to the theoretical framework. Three main organisational themes were extracted from the second global theme, which is 'Attitudes towards the languages forming the linguistic repertoires'. Every organisational theme in this chapter includes many sub-themes, which will be analysed and discussed thoroughly to understand participants' attitudes and perceptions about the languages they have in their linguistic repertoires.

7.2 Language Preference and Representation

To explore participants' attitudes towards the languages included in their linguistic repertoires, they were asked about their language or languages of preference.

Most participants in the Chaoui context expressed a clear preference for Arabic. They described it as the mother language and the language of religion and Quran. Most participants (n8) favoured Arabic, while two declared that they prefer English and French. Tamazight was classified as the third or the fifth favourite language, while some participants (n3) did not include it in the classifications. English was ranked second or third, while French was generally classified the fourth or fifth. This is summarised by Chaoui 3, who reported that his language of preferences are as follows: Arabic first as it is their mother tongue. Following that is English, then Chaoui as their heritage language, and subsequently Derja as the language for communication, finally, French.

Meanwhile, participants (n9) from the Kabyle context reported that their language of preference is Tamazight, which they referred to as the mother language. They also classified French as the second language they prefer after their mother language (Tamazight). Only one participant ranked Tamazight the last (fourth) in her classification and French as the first. Arabic was generally classified as the third or fourth language. This is demonstrated by Kabyle

6 in the following quotation: “For me, the first language is my mother language (Tamazight). Tamazight, French, Arabic, and then other languages such as German and English”.

Figure 5: Thematic Network of Teachers' Preferences

Participants in this study loaded languages in their linguistic repertoire with certain connotations such as the language of prestige, the language of colonialism, the language of emotions, the language of religion, the language of civilisation, and the language of culture. These different representations are socially embodied through the past and present experiences that participants had and thus they became part of the social habitus in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle context). Participants' preferences and attitudes towards languages in their linguistic repertoires are thus affected by these representations. The above-mentioned representations will be discussed under the following sub-themes.

7.2.1 Language and emotions

The study found a link between language and emotions among participants (Chaoui and Kabyle). Emotions and languages were addressed on two levels: first, the effect of emotions on language choices. For instance, the association of certain feelings such as anger with a particular language that different languages express different emotions. Second, the emotional representations participants have towards the language per se. for instance detesting French because of its association with colonialism, and adoring Arabic because of its link to the Quran and religion. The former will be discussed under the 'language and emotions' theme, while the latter will be addressed separately under the following themes.

Chaoui 2 and Kabyle 5 showed that their emotions affect their language choices. Chaoui 2, who considers Arabic her mother language, and who acquired and learned French at home from her father and then from school, stated that when she is angry, she uses French with her daughters. She reported that she does not know the reason for that, but she could link it to her childhood experience. She explained that when she was a child in primary school, her teachers of Arabic were kind and tender, while all her teachers of French were harsh and strict, which may justify her use of French when she is angry. Dewaele (2012) reported that the relationship between multilingualism and emotions is dynamic. He indicated that the choice of language to express emotions and perceptions is connected to the experiences of speakers with the languages included in their linguistic repertoires. This confirms Chaoui 2's experience with the French language and also relates to Bourdieu's conceptual term "habitus", where personal experiences and historical trajectories in a particular field shape one's beliefs and dispositions (Maton, 2014). 9

Kabyle 5 stated that her mother language, which is Tamazight, is used when she gets angry or happy. She reported that when she is emotional either positively or negatively, she speaks her mother language (Pavlenko, 2004; Pavlenko, 2008; Bond and Lai, 1986). Dewaele (2012) supports the Kabyle 5 statement by indicating that the mother tongue is the language of the heart (Dewaele, 2012).

Participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) also demonstrated the connection between language and emotions through the representations they gave to the languages included in their linguistic repertoires such as colonialism, prestige, identity, and religion. This will be discussed under the following themes.

7..2.2 Language and religion

This study highlighted a deep connection between language and religion among participants, particularly within the Chaoui context. According to Bhat (2017: 186), "The language used in religious texts/scriptures become a symbol/part of religious identity". Thus, language preferences among participants from the first setting (Chaoui) were influenced by religion as many of them (n10) referred to Arabic as their favourite language because of being the language of the Quran and religion. Chaoui 7 reported that Arabic has its peculiarities for Muslims as It is the language of the Quran. He states that Allah says, in Surat Yusuf (12:2),

“We have sent it down as an Arabic Quran”. Therefore, he considered Arabic as a sacred language.

Islam and Arabic are inseparable and intertwined in Algeria; they are used as a powerful political tool by the government (Rouabah, 2020). Mostari (2005) argues that Arabisation is linked to two concepts, which are the quest for freedom and the defence of religion (Islam). Thus, Arabic in Algeria, was considered the language of liberty, identity, and religion (Islam) (Le Roux, 2017). This is summarised in the following excerpts:

Arabic has a special place for me. I love it. I love poems and literature. I read books in Arabic a lot. Now, concerning the Quran It (Quran) was revealed in a clear Arabic tongue. I say it honestly; I love the Arabic language so much. In my heart, it comes first, without any rival (Chaoui 2).

Language and religion, Arabisation, and Islamism have always been tools for power in post-colonial Algeria (Daoudi, 2018). During colonialism, Islam was a symbol of resistance and Arabic was the perfect fit for Islam, as it is the language of the Quran (Benrabah, 2004).

Some participants (n3) reported a quotation of Ibn Badis, who was one of the pioneers of nationalism and Islamic Arabism in Algeria during the Algerian revolution (Al-Nahas, 2009). The quotation indicates that the Algerian population is Muslim, and it belongs to Arabism. Other participants (n2) described Arabic as the language of paradise such as Chaoui 7, who stated the following: “Arabic has its roots in our history as Muslims. Abd El Hamid Ibn Badis stated that people of Algeria are Muslims, and to Arabism, they belong. That is it... We have in our doctrine the belief that Arabic is the language of people in paradise”.

Some participants (n3) also related learning Arabic to mosques. They stated that they started learning Arabic before entering public schools by studying the Quran in mosques, which may unconsciously affect their perceptions about language, religion, and the bond they may have.

Participants in the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) agreed that people in the Chaoui context link identity to religion and religion to Arabic, which explains why they identify themselves as Arabs although they know that they are originally Amazigh. They also reported that Kabyle people link their identity to language; they have a sense of pride concerning Tamazight.

The ties between Islam and Arabic among participants may date back to the colonial and post-colonial eras where many violating practices from the colonial regime to assimilate Algerians

and destroy any marker of identity and culture including languages (Maamri, 2009), resulted in long-lasting convictions (Attachment to Arabic language) that were reproduced from one generation to the other. This relates to Bourdieu's concept of 'habitus', which entails that the past and the present experiences of individuals can shape their dispositions and tendencies (Maton, 2014), at the same time, these convictions and dispositions are structuring and influencing the outer (the social) (Maton, 2014). That is, the violating history of Algeria with the French colonisation influenced participants' perceptions of the French language in a negative way. In parallel, these individual dispositions are affecting the social habitus.

Few participants (n4) from the Kabyle context related language to religion. They reported that Arabic is the language of the Quran however, they tried to explain that religion (Islam) can be understood with languages other than Arabic as the case in Indonesia where they speak Indonesian. Kabyle 2 for instance, stated that Arabic is good to understand the Quran; however, preserving and developing Tamazight will also help translate the Quran. She also gave an example of Indonesia, which according to her, did not put the language as a barrier as is the case in Algeria. She added that there are people who speak Arabic but do not understand the Quran very well. Kabyle 10 is an Imam in a mosque in addition to being a teacher, stated that when he is in the mosque he works in parallel between languages. This means that he uses both languages Arabic and Tamazight. He added that people are there to understand. Kabyle 10 gave a verse from the Quran that explains that messengers are sent to teach people in people's languages. Kabyle 10 emphasised that he is against fanaticism and that the aim of religion is to transmit the message and the ideas to the hearer.

The findings from the Chaoui context revealed a strong bond between language and religion among participants, which influenced their language preferences. However, in the Kabyle context the bond between language and religion was perceived differently. The participants recognised Arabic as the language of the Quran however, they were more attached to their mother language (Tamazight) and French than to Arabic. They believe that religion can be understood and practised with languages other than Arabic. Ibn Badis's Islamic reforms, which encompass his declaration that "People of Algeria are Muslims, and to Arabism, they belong" (Al-Nahas, 2009), seem to have a strong impact on participants from the Chaoui context regarding Arabic and religion, while they have no impact on participants from the Kabyle context (Roberts, 2014).

7.2.3 Language of colonialism

The language of colonialism is another theme that was especially highlighted in the Chaoui context. Many participants (n9) referred to French as the language of colonialism. When Chaoui 9 was asked to classify the languages in his repertoires according to preference, he stated that he prefers Arabic, English, Derja, French, and then Tamazight. He explained that French used to have a better ranking for him; however, after realising some historical events; he is unwilling to use French. Chaoui 7 reported that what is happening in Algeria (The Hirak) is an elimination of the French language. He added that French is a dead language in the modern world; therefore, English should be favoured in Algeria. He also stated that this is one of the effects of colonialism in Algeria, and it is time for Algeria to detach from the French language.

Although French is present in the Chaoui context as many participants stated that they learned it through the milieu and the schools, Chaoui 3 and Chaoui 10 showed that the only link that they have with French is it being the language of the colonialist. Chaoui 2 stated that Algeria is still colonised by France because the French language still has an important status in Algeria, he asserted, "We may have achieved military independence, but the influence of French is pervasive. Administrations continue to use French, and our political leaders communicate with us in French. The influence of France is still strong in Algeria, as it seeks to plant the French language in Algeria".

French is present among participants' in Chaoui context with different proficiency levels; however, they showed a feeling of hatred and hostility towards this language. Some participants perceived Arabic and French as a dichotomy where the presence of one of them means the exclusion of the other. This is summarised by Chaoui (7) in the following excerpts:

In Algeria, these movements are defending Tamazight to destroy Islam. They defend Tamazight using the Latin alphabet. You study Tamazight and you will be given a scholarship abroad. You will learn French. Where is Arabic from all this? There is no Arabic. You will be a foreigner to Arabic. You will not understand it. When you read the Quran, you will not be able to understand it. Therefore, you will not be able to apply it. So religiously, you will be just a frame. Therefore, you will be away from the core of Islam (Chaoui 7).

Chaoui 6, on the other hand, referred to the French language as a gain of war, which sounds more positive compared to the responses of the other participants from the Chaoui context. Chaoui (6) stated that French is the first foreign language because of the French colonisation and because of its status in the Algerian educational system. He declared that the French language is important and that the prophet Mohamed PBUH (Peace be upon him) said, "Whoever learns a people's language shall be safe from their plots". He additionally reported that French is "a capital if it is exploited in a good way".

Participants (n5) from the Kabyle context also referred to colonialism when speaking about French. However, their attitudes were positive towards French as they were explaining how people from other regions might view French as a language of colonialism, while they consider it as part of their culture. Kabyle 2 for instance, reported that Arabs are more oriented to English as they consider French as the language of colonial. She added that Arabs do not want to study it, while the United States and England themselves colonised other countries, and thus English is a language of colonial power too. Kabyle 10 described the French language as a colonial legacy, especially within the Kabyle context. He stated that, similarly to Arabic, which is the language of the Quran, it is impossible to abandon the French language because it is a legacy from the colonial. Moreover, Kabyle 9 stated that even if English replaced French, French would remain as they have become accommodated to it, and French has its roots in their context.

Unlike the Chaoui context, where a strong link between French and colonialism was evident, the Kabyle context viewed French as an integral part of their culture. To understand the varying attitudes and perceptions held by participants from the Berber region, particularly the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts, toward the French language, we must root into the historical context of the colonial era.

According to Maamri (2009), French colonialism in Algeria did not only aim for political domination and economic exploitation, rather it aimed to eliminate the Algerian culture by eradicating all its components especially languages, which were seen as a crucial tool for transforming a society. Therefore, Arabic and Islamic roots were attacked by the most destructive methods to create 'man free from culture, easy to manipulate' (Maamri, 2009, p.3). According to Rouabah (2022) The Chaoui support for Arabic as a means to eradicate the

remnants of colonialism was bolstered by their collective memory of the implemented French policies during colonialism.

The stronger the action, the stronger the reaction. The more the attempts to eliminate Arabic and native languages, the more Algerians became attached to the Arabic language. According to Mouhleb, Algeria had no ruler or royal family to stand behind during colonialism, therefore, “a unifying element was found in religion and language” (2005, p.87). The Algerian revolution against French colonialism started in the Aures Mountains (Chaoui context). Rouabah (2022) reported that the concept of independence in the Aures (Chaoui context) can be traced back to as early as 1916. The Chaoui context was the first group to engage in rebellion and resistance against France, with their region being the first to experience a state of siege and endure repressive measures and regrouping. Additionally, the French colonialist did not actively engage in initiatives aimed at fostering literacy among the Chaouia community, resulting in the establishment of Islamic educational institutions instead in the Aures, which facilitated the acquisition of competence in Arabic among people (Rouabah, 2022). This direct contact with Arabs and with the revolution in the Chaoui context may be a reason for the strong connection that participants in the present time have towards the Arabic language.

Moreover, the colonialist opted for a “divide and conquer” policy in which, according to certain research works undertaken during colonialism, France sided with the Berbers against Arabs and administered Kabyle contexts in a different way where Kabyle people were preferred (Tilmatine, 2016). This relates to Bourdieu’s key terms “habitus and field”. The social habitus (disposition, beliefs, and perceptions) of each field (the Chaoui and Kabyle) affects participants’ perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes towards languages in their linguistic repertoires as is the case for the French language (Maton, 2014).

The two focus group discussions in this study also revealed a notable link between language and colonialism. In the first focus group discussion (Chaoui), participants (n4) pointed out that French was the language imposed on Algerians by the French colonialists, and its influence still resonates in modern Algeria. In the second focus group discussion (Kabyle), participants acknowledged that French indeed carries the legacy of colonialism. However, they also expressed a sense of attachment to the language, stating that it has become an integral part of their culture.

7.2.4 Language, civilisation, and prestige

The study found a significant association between language, prestige, and civilisation among Berber participants (Chaoui and Kabyle). Chaoui 4 associated French with prestigious professions in Algeria. He stated that students whose parents are doctors or professors at universities are good at French. He elaborated that parents concentrate on teaching their children French because they believe that it is impossible to switch from French to another language in Algeria and added that he uses French mixed with Derja with his neighbours, who are doctors and professors. Moreover, Chaoui 8 reported that people in Algeria love to speak French because it is a language of prestige. That is, people who speak French are considered prestigious.

Chaoui 7 linked French to being intellectual and civilised; that is, if you speak French, it means you are an intellectual and civilised person as opposed to speaking Derja, which indicates that you are an ordinary person. He stated that Francophones, who use French believe that it is a language of civilisation. That was also indicated in the second focus group discussion (Kabyle) where participants (n4) agreed that French is perceived as a language of civilisation. Participants in the first focus group discussion indicated that, the elite children in Algeria are educated in French, which links French to prestige.

Both Chaoui 7 and Chaoui 8 agreed that speaking French grants more privileges as it opens doors for its speakers. Chaoui 7 noted, "Speaking French elevates one's social status, it makes them look intellectuals and it facilitate the fulfilment of their needs. Conversely, speaking Derja makes them look ordinary people". Chaoui 8 stated that some administrations in Algeria such as "Algerian Airlines" deal with you based on the language you use. He reported that he used Arabic when interacting with Algerian Airways, and their treatment was less satisfactory. When he switched to French, their service improved, and when he employed English, he experienced a more amicable reception.

Kabyle 5 associated economic status with language and prestige. She stated that, in Algeria, people do not speak a language because they know it, but because they are rich. She continued that most rich people in Algiers speak the French language because it is a prestigious language, while Kabyle 9 considered people who speak French "classy", and more cultivated and added that French culture and the French language reflect cultivation.

Participants in this study described French as a language of prestige and civilisation. They linked the French language to being prestigious, civilised, intellectual, luxurious, and wealthy. Understanding the above views implies revising the linguistic history of Algeria. According to Maamri (2009) the French coloniser sought to control and manipulate the Algerians for one hundred and thirty-two years and Language was the crucial element to pursue this aim. To the coloniser, Algeria presented as place for barbaric people, who lack traits of civilisation, while they (the French coloniser) considered themselves as a source of civilisation. Therefore, in the name of producing civilised people, they used education and language as primary weapons to transform Algerian society. These historical events that promoted French above the native languages in Algeria during colonialism may affect people's and particularly participants' perceptions and attitudes towards French in the present time.

Chaoui 2 was so proud when she spoke about her father, who was according to her from the minority that spoke French fluently in her area (Chaoui context). She stated that her father mastered French more than French people did, "If my father is sitting next to a French person, an intellectual one. Let us say a university teacher of French. If you compare that teacher to my father, there will be no room for comparison. My father would be way better whether in Writing or speaking".

To survive during colonialism and in their search for identification and recognition, the Algerian intellectuals tried to impersonate and imitate the coloniser's culture including manners, speech, and ideology (Maamri, 2009). This is expressed above by Chaoui 2 where she compared her father with French people. According to Maamri (2009), the French colonialist strongly attempted to implant the belief that civilisation is implanted in the French culture and the French language among Algerians. Therefore, the belief that French is a language of prestige and a language of civilisation among participants in this study can be explained by the above historical events of language in Algeria, which shaped the habitus of participants and affected their perceptions and attitudes, which relates to Bourdieu's concept "Habitus" (Maton, 2014).

7.2.5 Limitations and openness to the world

Participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) described some languages in their linguistic repertoires as limited/limiting languages that restrict their world, while they described other languages as widespread and worldwide common languages that broaden one's horizons. The

languages were described as limited languages in terms of vocabulary richness or limited languages in terms of expansion. That is, according to participants, these languages do not have sufficient vocabulary to express, perceive or discuss thoughts in all fields or they are limited to certain areas or countries.

The Findings of this chapter revealed that Berber teachers' attitudes (Chaoui and the Kabyle) are positive toward English. The participants agreed that English is an international language. They considered English as a widespread language that expands the horizons of knowledge and opportunities for speakers. English was perceived as a language that gives students the flexibility to study abroad when they want. It helps students to get any opportunity of studies or work abroad, in any place in the world. According to participants, people, who do not speak English, may miss future opportunities they may confront in life. The participants (Chaoui and Kabyle) reported that English is the common language of the world. This is summarised by Chaoui 6 in the following quotation:

...when it comes to learning sciences and scientific research, English is the first language. It is a lingua franca. It is a vehicle language in a very wide world. It is number one, the language of science. Most researchers in the scientific and literary fields, and human sciences write their articles in English so that they reach more readers (Chaoui 6).

Belmihoub (2018) indicated that it is a commonly held belief that empowering English in Algeria enables access to global knowledge and facilitates the transfer of technology from technologically developed countries to Algeria (Belmihoub, 2018). Bektache's (2009) study that investigated attitudes among university students towards languages in the Kabyle setting revealed that English is represented as an international/global/universal language, a language of technology and science, and the language of future and openness to the world. This confirms teachers' attitudes toward English in this research.

Many participants from the Chaoui context perceived French as a limiting language as it is limited in terms of expansion. Only a few countries, according to participants, speak French such as France and Belgium. Some participants constantly compared French to English, which is according to them an international language and the common language of the world. This is indicated in the following excerpts:

...English, an international language. It is an open language for everyone. The entire world speaks it. It opens scopes for you, for instance, for traveling and doing research. English holds a

kind of comfort more than other languages hold. For instance, French sounds good, but when you travel outside, it is limited. French is only in France and Belgium that is all (Chaoui 10).

Chaoui 1 highlighted an important point. She indicated that “from an international level, not a national level” she prefers English to French because French is a limited language internationally. That leads to another point, which is the expansion of French in different domains nationally such as administrations (in Algeria). This is supported by Chaoui 5, who stated that French in Algeria is more valuable than Arabic. This is indicated in the following quotation:

Publications in French are better than in Arabic. Journals that are in French are more than journals that are in Arabic. Even TV programs, which are in French, are better than those in Arabic. French-speaking people are academically more capable (skilled). Even the content they introduce is more calculated as opposed to Arabic. French has a better status in Algeria. However, in general, English is perceived better. Without any discussion, now it is English. It makes you capable in any place in the world. Even in France, if you use the English language in France, you will reach what you want. It is the language of tourism, the language of the economy, and the language of everything. In any place in the world, English is the second language (Chaoui 5).

The above statements of Chaoui 5 and Chaoui 1 indicate that although they consider French as limited globally; however, they see that its roots are expanded in different domains locally (in Algeria). Kabyle 8 reported that French is a language that expands horizons of knowledge for him. He stated that as opposed to Derja, Arabic, and Tamazight French for him represents openness to the world. The following quotation indicates that:

To be honest my passion is for the French language because French for me represents the openness to the world, which is not provided in both Arabic and Tamazight. If I confine myself only to these languages, I will be enclosed to myself. Therefore, the French language is a window allows me to know the new inventions and events happening in the world. That is reality (Kabyle 8).

In line with Le Roux’s (2017) thinking, Kabyle 8 attitudes towards French in the Kabyle context is worth noting. He considers that French is deeply ingrained in Algeria and that as a language it gives access to the world. He also believes that Arabic is a limiting language in terms of global interaction and communication.

Moreover, having a limited vocabulary in certain fields or domains will paralyse the ability to discuss matters in that field. For instance, having an insufficient vocabulary for the scientific field may affect by being unaware of certain concepts that a language may miss or through being aware of the concept but unable to express yourself or discuss matters because of the limitation of vocabulary in that particular language. Some participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) considered that Tamazight is limiting them and hindering any step toward development because it is limited in terms of vocabulary and expansion. This is summarised by Chaoui 3 and Chaoui 9 and Kabyle 8:

Listen. In my opinion, the only reason for teaching Tamazight is not to lose the Algerian identity that is all. Otherwise, we are not going to create a plane using Tamazight. Therefore, if they do it for identity reasons, it will be good. However, for scientific purposes. No. However, we should not forget our origins. It is part of our identity (Kabyle 8).

Chaoui 3 reported that he does not see that Tamazight is as linguistically rich as some other languages. He stated that it holds significance in terms of heritage; However, it is not rich enough to be language or a second language that can be effectively used for various purposes. Additionally, Chaoui 9 stated that Tamazight requires a significant amount of time to be developed. Focusing too much on it could hinder the progress of the country. He reported that they (Algeria) are already late to keep up with the rest of world and giving Tamazight more emphasis could hinder their progress further.

The second focus group discussion (Kabyle) revealed that French is perceived as a language that broadens the horizons for participants. Although they reported that the Arabisation of the educational system and then the Frenchification of scientific streams in higher education are contradictory and may cause failure for students; however, they believed that French is necessary to expand opportunities in life for students. Some participants in the Kabyle context considered French as a window to the world. The study also indicated that participants from the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) considered Tamazight as a limited language in terms of both vocabulary and expansion, while they considered English as an international language that broadens one's horizons. Therefore, the restriction and expansion of languages in participants' linguistic repertoire are subject to the scope or the field in which the language or languages exist.

7.2.6 Language preservation

To investigate participants' (Chaoui and Kabyle) attitudes towards languages in their linguistic they were asked about the language or the languages they want to preserve.

Most participants (9) in the Chaoui context stated that they want to preserve the Arabic language because it is the language of the Quran, religion, and identity and because it is their mother language. Chaoui 7 reported that it is the language of the Quran, and that Allah says in Surat Yusuf (12:2), "We have sent it down as an Arabic Quran"! Chaoui 7 perceived Arabic as a sacred language being the language of the Quran. Moreover, he indicated that Arabic is one of the four most difficult languages to learn in the world. Chaoui (6) also reported the following:

First, Arabic, which is the language of value for me. Away from being a wonderful language, away from all these considerations given by most people to justify their orientations. Some people say that it is the language of the Quran...It is considered the language of identity...I have been raised in a milieu... As I told you before, I studied in the Quranic schools. I learned the language of the Quran. In addition, because I am an Arab, I speak that language (Arabic), which represents for me the language of identity (Chaoui 6).

Some participants (n6) from the Kabyle context reported that they want to preserve the Tamazight language, which represents the mother tongue for them followed by the French language. Kabyle 9 expressed a strong commitment to preserving Tamazight by ensuring that her children, regardless of their location, will learn the language. Additionally, she expressed her desire to preserve the French language, following Tamazight.

Participants in this study expressed fears of language loss. That is, according to participants, the wish for preserving Arabic (Chaoui context) and Tamazight (Kabyle context) originates from their fears of language attrition. Kabyle 8 indicated that the language that she wants to preserve is Tamazight, her mother language, as she does not want it to disappear. According to some participants from the Chaoui setting, Arabic is threatened by the promotion of French, and according to participants from the Kabyle setting Tamazight is threatened by the presence of Arabic.

7.2.7 Language attrition

A few participants (n4) from the Kabyle setting expressed a feeling of the threat of losing their mother language to other languages, which are more valued in the Algerian context. They

related the fear of language attrition to the language they want to preserve. The Algerian context where many languages (Tamazight, Derja, Arabic, French, and English) are in contact may be a solid ground for language attrition. Both the government and the different ethnic groups in Algeria are investing efforts to reinforce and enhance the status of certain languages. This competition between languages may lead to the oppression and the marginalisation of some languages, which eventually may result in language attrition or language loss (Henze and Davis, 1999).

The fear of language attrition among participants (Kabyle) was on two levels. At the individual level where some participants wanted to preserve and learn Tamazight because they do not want to lose it from their linguistic repertoires and at the collective level where language is lost and not spoken anymore.

Chaoui 10 and Chaoui 11 reported that people lose languages when they do not use them, which may be a reason for language attrition over time. This phenomenon is more apparent in the Chaoui context where Tamazight is confined to rural areas and elderlies. Despite the fact that the Chaoui setting is part of the Berber region, a language shift to Derja at the expense of Tamazight is manifested among participants from the Chaoui context as Derja became the common language used in daily life. Rouabah (2020) investigated language shifts in the Chaoui context and found out that the use of Tamazight (Chaoui dialect) is decreasing in the Chaoui setting in favour of Derja.

Figure 6: Thematic Network of Language Representation

7.3 Benefits of multilingual repertoires

The findings in this study revealed that having a multilingual repertoire is perceived very beneficial. All participants (Chaoui and Kabyle) reported that having a multilingual repertoire is important, which is in line with Belmihoub (2018) study where attitudes towards multilingualism in Algeria were positive (Belmihoub, 2018). Although participants in this study had different attitudes, preferences, and perceptions about each language in their linguistic repertoires referring to them as the language of colonialism, the language of prestige, the language of culture, the language of identity, and the common language of the world; however, they agreed that having a multilingual repertoire is beneficial in many ways. This is in line with the study done by Le Roux (2017), which confirmed the importance of multilingualism. He reported that multilingualism promotes adaptability, flexibility, and competitiveness in the globalised world, which would be advantageous to Algeria.

Many participants stated that possessing a multilingual repertoire facilitates communication and understanding between people whether locally or globally. Chaoui 8 considers knowing a language as knowing a culture. Kabyle 8 also states this in the following quotation:

Certainly, it is beneficial! Anything a person knows is an extra for him/her. Therefore, knowing more languages is an addition to us. Our field of thinking will be wider because every language we learn has a culture behind it. Every language drives a culture, which allows openness to other cultures. It also expands humans' visions (Kabyle 8).

Chaoui 5 and Chaoui 7 elaborated on this point by giving examples that explain how a language reflects its culture. Chaoui 5, who lived and taught for many years in the Kabyle setting stated that translation from Tamazight to Arabic or the opposite might be imprisoned to inaccuracy. Therefore, according to Chaoui 5 and Chaoui 7 understanding the language of a particular group grants the ability to understand them, understand the way they think, and how they perceive things. The following quotation demonstrates that:

It is beneficial. Very beneficial! We understand better each society with its language. When you go out with colleagues, and they tell jokes or stories in Tamazight, if you translate them into Arabic, they will not have the same special taste. The same thing in Arabic, if you translate a joke from Arabic to Tamazight, it will lose its meaning. Therefore, when you understand a language of a particular area, you will be able to understand its (people from this area) background and the way people in this area think (Chaoui 5).

Some participants (n5) reported a verse from the Hadith of the prophet Mohamed (PBUH). They quoted, “Whoever learns a people’s language shall be safe from their plots”. That is, understanding a language of a particular group of people protects you from being deceived or manipulated by them as it facilitates communication with and the understanding of that group of people. This was also indicated in the first focus group discussion where participants agreed on the same Hadith of the prophet Mohamed (PBUH). They reported that knowing a language of a particular group of people allows you to understand them. They gave an example of their experiences of being teachers in the Kabyle setting for a period. They indicated that students in the Kabyle context deliberately spoke in Tamazight with them to provoke them and see if they can speak Tamazight. When students realise that teachers can speak Tamazight, they switch to focus on studies rather than provoking teachers. Participants also reported that having a multilingual repertoire is a capital that should be exploited properly. Bourdieu (1991) emphasises the notion that within a specific linguistic market, languages are hierarchically positioned. Speakers with diverse linguistic capital frequently face the decision of employing either the minority language, as a means of expressing their affiliation with a particular group, or the dominant market language, in order to attain power (Bourdieu, 1991)

Some participants also reported that language might be a source of injustice if someone does not speak it in a particular context or situation, for that reason a multilingual repertoire is important and beneficial. For instance, they gave an example of the classroom. Students who are raised in families who speak French fluently at home will be able to speak it fluently too and they will be able to achieve excellent grades when it comes to French as a subject, as opposed to students who were raised in families that do not speak French.

They also gave the example of medical schools. In Algeria, after studying for 13 years using Arabic as a medium of instruction. Students who opt for the medical field at university will be studying in French. Switching suddenly from Arabic to French may influence students’ grades and achievements and may even be a reason for their failure in some cases. Students who are already able to speak French will not struggle when it comes to language as they will be focusing only on the content as opposed to students who do not speak French who will be focusing on learning the language first and then the content. This relates to Bourdieu’s concept of reproduction. Kabyle 10 indicated this in the following excerpt:

The classroom, this helps to avoid injustice. This means, taking into consideration the differences of individuals (as I pointed out before, concerning their (students) linguistic repertoire). Sometimes they do not understand a religious or a historic word, so we diversify the languages to transmit the message and to reach our aim (Kabyle 10).

Kabyle (10) pointed out the necessity of using the linguistic repertoire as a whole with students to communicate and transmit ideas, which helps to avoid the injustice that may take place because of the potential linguistic differences among students. Some participants also stated that having a multilingual repertoire facilitates communication with the student in the classroom and enhance their critical thinking, as they will not be limited to a particular language. Students will focus on the content rather than the language itself.

Some participants (n3) also stated that people might miss working and studying opportunities because they do not speak a particular language. Therefore, having a multilingual repertoire may be a reason for seizing such opportunities. Chaoui 11 gave an example of his friend, who ranked among the best student in the field of medicine in Algeria. His friend wanted to pursue his studies abroad, but he failed because he did not speak English.

Racism is another type of injustice that might occur because of language. Chaoui 8 gave an example of visiting some areas in Algeria where Tamazight is the spoken language. He reported that he was treated differently (negatively) just because he spoke a different language. The following excerpt explains that:

...In some areas, there is what we call racism. If you do not speak Tamazight, they will treat you differently. I mean they will despise and underestimate you. I have lived this experience many times. For instance, I went to buy something, they did not want to deal with me...when I spoke the Chaoui dialect or Tamazight with them, they changed positively (Chaoui 8).

Chaoui 8 also pointed out that in some fields or domains, some languages are more valued that is, if a particular language is used it would bring more privileges to the speaker.

Participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) agreed that multilingual repertoires are beneficial on national, international, personal, and professional levels. A multilingual repertoire according to participants enables communication and mutual understanding between speakers whether locally in the different areas in Algeria including the Kabyle context, where Tamazight is the spoken language or internationally where different cultures and languages are manifested and spoken. A multilingual repertoire also helps to avoid social

and educational injustice that is related to language use. It also helps individuals to seize study and work opportunities whether in Algeria or abroad.

Figure 7: Thematic Network of the Benefits of Multilingual Repertoires

7.4 Conclusion

This chapter presented and discussed Berber teachers' (Chaoui and Kabyle) attitudes toward the languages included in their linguistic repertoires (in Algeria). The chapter aimed to answer the second research question of this study: What are the Algerian Berber teachers' attitudes toward the languages included in their linguistic repertoires? How are these attitudes developed among the teachers? If at all, how do their attitudes differ based on the Berber region they come from?

The study revealed that teachers' attitudes and preferences in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) were influenced by the different representations they have for the languages in their linguistic repertoires. These linguistic representations such as the language of religion, the language of civilisation, the language of culture, the language of emotions, the language of identity, the language of prestige, and the language of colonialism, in addition to the fear of language loss, were accumulated historically through the lived experiences of teachers and became part of their habitus.

The social dispositions or habitus in the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts influenced the individual habitus of participants and therefore affected their attitudes toward the languages

included in their linguistic repertoires. Attitudes towards the French language among participants Chaoui context were generally negative. They linked French to colonialism and therefore they had a feeling of hostility towards the language (French). Although French was considered as a limiting language among participants in the Chaoui context; however, it was also perceived as a valuable and prestigious language in Algeria. French colonialism in Algeria aimed to marginalise and eradicate the native languages (Arabic, Tamazight, Derja) in Algeria and impose French using violent means, these historical events generated a feeling of hostility towards that language. The French colonialist also sought to plant beliefs that French is a language of civilisation and prestige.

Although the Algerian population resisted the colonialist's attempts during and after colonialism; however, the study revealed that the participants in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) perceived French as a prestigious language, which indicates that colonialism is still affecting perceptions towards French in Algeria. On the other hand, the study revealed that teachers' attitudes towards French in the Kabyle context were highly positive. They perceived French as a language of civilisation and prestige: speaking French indicates how educated and prestigious the person is according to participants. The study indicated that French is perceived as part of the culture in the Kabyle context. It was also perceived as a language that expands one's horizons.

The study revealed positive attitudes towards Arabic in the Chaoui context. Arabic was perceived as a language of the Holy Quran and religion; therefore, it has a special and valuable status for them. It was also considered as the language of identity. Although Arabic has an important status for participants (Chaoui); however, many of them indicated that in reality and daily life, it is not used. It is only limited to certain fields such as education and mosques. The study also revealed that Arabic is considered as a foreign language in the Kabyle context as it is learned at schools. Participants (Kabyle) did not show attachment to Arabic.

The findings also revealed that teachers' attitudes towards English in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) were highly positive. Teachers indicated that English has a very important status globally. They perceive English as the common language of the world and the language that broadens and expands one's opportunities in the modern world.

Attitudes towards Tamazight in the Chaoui context were mostly negative, while they were positive in the Kabyle context. The findings revealed that participants in the Chaoui setting

acknowledged that they are originally Amazigh; however, they identified themselves as Arabs. They described Tamazight as a dialect rather than a language, as a primitive dialect that does not elevate to be a language, and as a language that does not have a unifying writing system. The participants also indicated that Tamazight is a limited language in terms of vocabulary and a limiting language as it is restricted only to certain regions. Although participants from the Kabyle context were appreciative and proud of being Amazigh and of having Tamazight as a mother language; however, they also indicated that Tamazight is not a language of science, and learning Tamazight is solely for a cultural and identity purposes. Finally, Derja was perceived as a mixture of languages (Arabic, Tamazight, and French) or as a form of Arabic. Therefore, participants in the context were disregarding it.

The findings in this chapter indicated that although Berber teachers' (Chaoui and Kabyle) attitudes towards the languages included in their linguistic repertoires are different; however, they all agreed that having multilingual repertoires is very important and beneficial. This was also indicated in Belmihoub (2018) where participants had positive attitudes towards multilingualism in Algeria (Belmihoub, K., 2018).

Chapter Eight

Teachers' Perspectives on Language and power relations

8.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses language and power dynamics in the Algerian context from Berber teachers' (Chaoui and Kabyle) perspectives in relation to Bourdieu's sociological framework. The findings in this chapter address the third research question in relation to Bourdieu's theoretical framework. Several key issues emerged in the discussions related to language and power dynamics: frequency of language use, socioeconomic status, language and reproduction, and different fields of power such as education administrations, local and international, and geographical divisions. These emerging issues are perceived by participants as factors that determine the value of languages included in their linguistic repertoires in relation to different fields.

8.2 Language Value

As discussed previously (chapter 7), all participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) agreed that having a multilingual repertoire is beneficial. They perceived language as a linguistic cultural capital that brings benefits in different situations. However, they also indicated that the languages in their linguistic repertoires are not equally valued in different fields of power in Algeria and within different social classes.

Linguistic or language exchanges can convey distinct relations of power. Words in one language are charged with different powers based on who articulates them and how they are articulated in addition to the context in which they are articulated (Bourdieu, 1991). That is, some words would have more power in certain contexts, while they may have less power in other contexts (Bourdieu, 1991). In the same way as monolingualism in which vocabulary in one language may have different values and weight, depending on the capital distributed to some vocabulary and expressions over the others in different fields (Bourdieu, 1991), multilingualism where different languages are used may also display different relations of power according to the contexts in which the speakers are operating. That means that the existing languages may be valued differently based on the fields in which they are used. This relates to Bourdieu's key concepts of 'habitus', 'field', and 'capital', where language can be considered as a linguistic capital and field as the context in which the language or the languages are used (Grenfell, 2004).

Participants (n15) (Chaoui and Kabyle) perceived language as a symbolic capital that can be transformed into power and privileges. They reported that languages in Algeria are perceived to have different values and importance depending on the field in which they are used. To investigate the language and power relationship in Algeria, they (participants) were asked to classify languages in their linguistic repertoires according to their perceived value in Algeria. Participants from the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) indicated that the value of language is connected to the information it provides. That is, the limited languages that have limited vocabulary are unable to resist because they cannot transmit the information such as Tamazight. The participants (n4) agreed that the field of media could make the language valuable as it is considered one of the major fields in the modern world. They provided the example of Turkish, which entered all houses through the television and the Internet. Moreover, they stated that the economic and technological status of the country are what determine the importance of the language. That is, the economic, political, and technological strength of countries are reflected in the perceived value of their languages such as the United States and English (Crystal, 2003), where the value of language is linked to its speakers. People in power make the language valuable by speaking it and legitimise it. This is indicated in Crystal's work 'English as a global language' (2003).

Participants in the study also indicated that language value in Algeria is a multi-layered issue; therefore, in order to be able to classify the languages according to value, they created different small divisions or fields. These fields are education, administration, local and global fields, and regional divisions. This is in line with Bourdieu's concept of 'field', which is a setting of struggles where agents aim to preserve or modify different forms of capital, which are specific to that field (Bourdieu, 1991). Distinct linguistic capitals and properties characterise each of the above-mentioned fields of power (Bourdieu, 1991). That is, each field operates through a specific linguistic capital, which is promoted over the other languages by people who are in power in that field, which influences teachers' use and choice of languages. Therefore, a competent speaker can generate utterances or choose which language to use based on its appropriateness to the 'market' (Bourdieu, 1991). Bourdieu used the concept of "market", which is another metaphorical concept to indicate the field (Bourdieu, 1991). Therefore, education, administrations, the local and international fields, and the different regional divisions of Algeria that are indicated by participants (north, south, east,

west/ Kabyle, Chaoui, and Arab regions) are “markets” where languages are considered as products loaded with different values based on the market in which they are used.

8.2.1 Language Value and Administrations

The study revealed that French is perceived to be the most valuable language in the administrative field in Algeria. Some participants (n3) stated that French occupies a valuable position in the administration. Chaoui 11, who stated that French is more valuable than the other languages, illustrated his point by sharing a story of his friend, who secured a job because of his proficiency in French. Although his friend possessed a degree in English, he secured an administrative position primarily due to his proficiency in French rather than his academic qualification in English. Chaoui 3 on the other hand, reported that French does not provide any value to its speakers; however, he presented a contradictory statement by acknowledging the perceived significance of French in administrative contexts. This is expressed in the following quotation:

French has no value for people who speak it. Except at work, there are some workplaces where the utilisation of the French language is deemed obligatory. There is some government communication, and official documents, which are received, in French. Therefore, administratively one is supposed to deal in French. For example, some national companies necessitate the use of French. For example, the administrative transactions of Sonalgaz Company are conducted exclusively in French (Chaoui 3).

Chaoui 4 confirmed the above statements. He stated that although they got their independence, they are still linked to France. He stated that Algeria is still under the influence of French colonisation especially from a cultural level as they are highly using French in administrations. He reported that using French in job interviews in administrative fields significantly affects the probability of being accepted (see Reilly, et al., 2022). Chaoui 4 also indicated that the behaviour of the Algerian administrations is what makes French exist until now. Therefore, according to some participants French is deemed to be the most valued language in the administrative field; it is a linguistic cultural capital that gives its speakers value and benefits. This is summarised by Chaoui 8 in the following statement:

In certain administrative contexts, such as my experience with Algerian Airlines in Algiers, I utilised Derja to communicate. Unfortunately, the outcome of this interaction was not

favourable, as the airline personnel did not provide satisfactory service. I transitioned to speaking French and there was an improvement in the way I was treated (Chaoui 8).

Findings from the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) confirmed the importance of French in the administrative field in Algeria. They agreed that a language becomes valuable when it is integrated into the major fields of power such as politics, education, art, institutions, and administration. They reported that French is the most valued language in the administrative field as it is the language required for recruitment in Algeria. Participants in the second focus group discussion reported that French used to be the most important language in Algerian administrations; however, after the Arabisation policy Arabic started to have more value.

The above statements of participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) demonstrate how language can be considered as a currency or cultural capital that brings profits to speakers in certain domains, which relates to Bourdieu's theory of practice and particularly his concepts of "field", "habitus" and "capital" (Grenfell, 2004). Therefore, from a Bourdieusian perspective, In the Algerian context, French is considered a linguistic currency (capital) that provides speakers with profits such as job opportunities in the administrative "market" as it is considered a necessary skill for effective engagement with governmental institutions.

8.2.3 Language Value: International versus Local

Local and international spheres are two fields of power that were referred to by some participants in this research (interviews and focus group discussions). About half of the participants (n13) perceived English as the most valuable language on a global scale. According to their perceptions, English serves as a form of currency (linguistic capital) that grant its speakers benefits, privileges, and power on the global level. That is, people, who speak English or whose mother tongue is English, can think, work and progress promptly as opposed to those who do not speak it (Crystal, 2003).

Participants reported that English facilitates communication with people from different nationalities as many people throughout the world speak and understand the English language (Ilyosovna, 2020). They also reported that English is an essential language that opens doors for international opportunities either through the offered abroad studying programs or for international job opportunities (see also Ilyosovna, 2020). Participants stated that English allows students to pursue their education in any country in the world based on their aims and choices and enable them to get job opportunities abroad. The participants also indicated that

English is a language of science and technology, in addition to being a language of tourism. English according to participants makes travelling easier as it is the common language globally (Ilyosovna, 2020).

As noted above, participants in this study seemed to view English as a valuable global language although they failed to see the coloniality of the English language. While Berber (Chaoui and Kabyle) Algerian teachers in this study expressed the importance of English in the modern world, it is necessary to highlight language as a form of cultural hegemony. Dominant colonial languages such as French, Spanish, Portuguese, and English have had a negative impact on the value of local languages in Africa, South America, and other formerly colonised parts of the world (Ilyosovna, 2020). The increasing dominance of English in the modern world, for example, is argued to be a way of promoting neo-colonialism through empowering the powerful and marginalising the powerless (Guo and Beckett, 2007; Majhanovich, 2009). The global dominance of English also contributes to linguistic inequality in the scientific research field (Crystal, 2003; Majhanovich, 2009).

Many participants (n12) in the interviews indicated that French is a valuable language in the Algerian context. Chaoui 5 for instance, indicated that French is valuable in Algeria. He reported that publications in French are perceived more and better than ones in Arabic; TV programs, which are in French, are perceived better than ones, which are in Arabic; and French-speaking people are perceived academically skilled and more capable. Participants of both interviews and focus group discussions revealed that French has a powerful status in Algeria as it is strongly empowered in higher education and administrative fields. Galtung (1972) indicated that when members of a social group choose the language of the ex-coloniser as the language of education in the country, they become colonisers of themselves.

Chaoui 3 reported that in Algeria, some workplaces necessitate the utilisation of the French language, while the utilisation of English in administrative contexts is largely lacking, except for international corporations. The international and the local fields are two fields of power that require and favour different habitus, and different linguistic capital. English, which is considered a crucial linguistic capital internationally according to participants, is less valued locally in Algeria, while French, which has status and value because of the social and economic capital it holds in Algeria (Benrabah, 2013), may be perceived as less valuable globally as it is restricted to limited countries (Moore, 2014). That is, speaking French in the Algerian context

is a way of augmenting the symbolic capital of individuals, while speaking English language is a way of augmenting the symbolic capital of individuals internationally (Bourdieu, 1991).

8.2.4 Language Value and Geographical Divisions

The study revealed that in Algeria, the linguistic dynamics and value of languages are influenced by the geographic divisions of the country. Participants (n6) divided Algeria into four regions, which are North, South, East, and West. They indicated that the field in which the language is used is what determines its value. That is, a language that is used in a particular context may be perceived as more valuable than other languages, while it may be perceived as less valuable if it is used in another field or domain. This is indicated in the following excerpt:

According to the North French comes first and then Arabic, Tamazight, and finally English. Regarding the East of Algeria, Arabic comes first, and Tamazight...the Chaoui dialect, French, and then English language. Concerning the West, French comes first, Arabic, then English, which is almost gone. In the south, I guess they are using their own language, their local dialect, which is Terguia; it comes in the first place. People of the South use their dialect and then Arabic and then French and then English, which I do not see especially among people of the South (Chaoui 1).

The participant in the excerpt above further reported that each field (north, south, east, and west) requires different linguistic capital (see Grenfell, 2014). For instance, she stated that in the north or the west of Algeria, the language that is viewed to have more power is French followed by Arabic, Tamazight, and ultimately English. French is perceived to have a notable presence in the north and the west of Algeria. In these two fields of power, French is required as it provides speakers with social, cultural, and economic profits. It holds considerable importance in administration, education, and professional fields in the Northern regions and major cities. On the other hand, the usage and the value of French in the southern regions, where Arabic and Tamazight are dominant, is comparatively low. Furthermore, in the east, Arabic comes first, and then Tamazight. Participants in the second focus group discussion also indicated that language value is perceived differently in relation to regions, which are north, south, east, and west. They agreed that the French language is notably valuable in northern Algeria. This relates to Bourdieu's idea regarding fields that require different resources or capital (Grenfell, 2014).

Participants (interviews and focus group discussions) also perceived the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts as two fields where language value is perceived differently. They indicated that in the Kabyle context, Tamazight and French are perceived to have more value than other languages (Arabic and Derja) because they have a strong presence and are widely spoken. In contrast, Derja and Arabic are viewed as more valuable in the Chaoui context because Derja is the language used among people in that region, while Arabic is the language of religion and education.

Kabyle 6 reported that in the Kabyle context, they perceive Tamazight as the most valuable language because it is the language of their ancestors. However, in other regions such as Blida, the books of Tamazight were rejected because they did not want to teach it or learn it. Kabyle 8 indicated that the status of languages varies from one region to another. In the Kabyle context, the usage of French is dominant, while in other regions, Arabic may be the dominant language. The human being is the son (product, construct) of its environment. The surrounding environment affects people. Therefore, speakers in the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts value language differently.

Chaoui 7 on the other hand, reported that even the Chaoui context could be divided into subfields. Chaoui 7 stated that although the Chaoui context is regarded as one setting, however, perceptions of language value differ from one place to another within this setting. He stated that in rural areas in the Chaoui context such as Aris, and Tamza, Tamazight is the language used the most, which gives it more importance as opposed to other areas where Tamazight language is not the daily spoken language, which makes it less valuable compared to rural areas.

The East, the south, the north, the west, the Chaoui context, and the Kabyle context are all geographical divisions indicated by participants in this research. From a Bourdieusian perspective, can be viewed as structured spaces; each has its own rules that determine language value. The languages in the participants' linguistic repertoires can, therefore, be different resources or different linguistic capital, and people value each of these linguistic capitals differently according to the context or the field in which it is used.

8.2.5 Language Value and Socioeconomic Divisions

Socioeconomic status was another indicated factor for categorising languages based on their perceived value, as indicated by participants in this study (interviews and focus group discussions). The respondents highlighted socioeconomic status by referring to factors such as education, occupation, and income in their responses.

According to some participants(n8) (interviews), educated people and people who belong to the upper social class in Algeria tend to use French. They stated that French is prestigious symbolic capital; therefore, using it provides speakers with high social status and power, which is also referred to by Benrabah (2007). Speakers of French are commonly regarded as educated and prestigious people by society. Chaoui 8 reported that “Many people love to speak French not because it is a language of communication, but because it is the language of the coloniser. It is a language of prestige. speaking French is considered luxurious”.

The first focus group discussion (Chaoui) confirmed the above perception. Participants reported that people in power in the government (elite) tend to communicate in the French language and prioritise enrolling their children in French educational institutions to keep them ahead of kids from regular families.

Additionally, Chaoui 4 stated that he bases his language choices on the professions of the people he interacts with. For instance, he utilises French when he converses with his intellectual neighbours (doctors and professors). In his turn, Chaoui 5 asserted that “French-speaking people are academically more capable (skilled). Even the content they introduce is more calculated as opposed to when using Arabic. French is better in Algeria”.

This shared perception among participants, which connects French to prestige, brings up the term ‘elite closure’ (Myers-Scotton, 1993; Benrabah, 2007). Elite closure is a strategy used by policymakers and people in power to maintain and preserve certain social order or ladder (Myers-Scotton, 1993; Benrabah, 2007). The Arabisation policy for most of the population in Algeria was limited to ordinary people, while children of the elite were educated in French to ensure less competition in prestigious and well-paid jobs where French proficiency is required (Benrabah, 2007). This strategy in addition to the influence of the French colonisation, which pictured French as the language of civilisation, promoted the belief that French is a prestigious language and represents civilisation and education.

Kabyle 5 on the other hand, suggested another factor that may determine the socioeconomic status of people, which is income. She reported that language choice is related to the income and wealth of people. Therefore, rich people who are regarded as high-class people speak French. She stated that people in Algeria do not speak French because they know it, they speak it because they are rich and because it is a prestigious language.

Chaoui 9 suggested an explanation for why French is important and why it is perceived as a prestigious language in Algeria. He suggested that the past experiences of the Algerian society in the seventies (1970) where bilingualism was the norm, and where the orientation of the society was towards French is what influences the perceptions of people towards French today. In addition, it provides the French with powerful status in modern Algeria (Maamri, 2009). This is in line with Bourdieu's concept of habitus, which indicates that the past and present experiences of agents affect and structure their habitus (Grenfell, 2004).

The higher the social class of individuals the more power they have. This power can be reflected through the language choices they opt for. For instance, according to participants in this study using French is associated with being intellectual, rich, and prestigious and being from a higher class (Guy, 1989). This relates to Bourdieu's notions of habitus field and capital. The social class divisions can be considered fields of power where certain linguistic capital is more valued than the other languages in the repertoires. That is, to fit in a particular social class, the individual should possess a habitus that is in line with that social class. Language as a linguistic cultural capital can function as a marker of social status and symbolic power.

8.2.6 Language Value and Education

Language plays an important role as a tool of power in education; therefore, to discuss the perceived value of languages in Algeria, participants linked education to language. The educational domain among participants was addressed on two levels: education (primary to secondary cycle) and higher education (university).

Most participants (interviews (n20) and focus group discussions) in this study indicated that Arabic is the official language of education (primary, middle, and secondary cycles) (Reilly, et al., 2022). It was promoted after independence in Algeria. According to Holt (2013), the oppression of Arabic by the French colonialist during their occupation of Algeria, and the promotion of French at the expense of the indigenous languages resulted in hostility to French

and more attachment to Arabic. Arabic was considered a tool of unification in Algeria during and after independence in addition to being a great link to religion. Consequently, it was promoted after independence to be the official and national language in the constitution and the official language of the Algerian educational system.

The participants in this research are secondary school teachers from the Berber region (Chaoui and the Kabyle); therefore, education is their field of profession, which makes Arabic more valued for them in relation to the educational field. This is exemplified in the following excerpts:

Arabic remains a language of instruction, a language of work, but it does not exist in daily interactions. There is Derja, not Arabic. You may find Arabic at schools, and maybe at mosques in sermons, but in daily interactions, there is Derja and Tamazight (Kabyle 7).

The official language in secondary, middle, and primary school is Arabic. All subjects are supposed to be taught in Arabic except French and English. However, in mathematics, Physics, and even mechanics we write symbols in French, I mean in Latin when I say French, it is the same thing, same letters (Chaoui2).

Some Kabyle participants indicated that children in the Kabyle context face challenges concerning language, when they start their primary education because their mother tongue is Tamazight, while Arabic is viewed as a foreign language for them. Children, therefore, need to learn the legitimate language of the educational field for academic success.

Regarding higher education, participants (interviews) reported that French holds significant importance in the field of higher education, particularly within scientific streams such as Medicines, Chemistry, Physics, Pharmacy, Biology, and Dentistry (Reilly, et al., 2022). Chaoui 1 reported that “Frenchification of education is the policy adopted by the government. For instance, streams such as Phisic, Mathematics, and Natural Sciences are all in French”. Chaoui 4 also expressed this in the following quotations:

Students study for 13 years in Arabic and then, they switch to French at the university. in the East, we are not that attached to the French language. So, studying for 13 years in Arabic, not focusing much on French, and then when you start university you are only supposed to study in French, especially for scientific streams such as biology, medicine, and engineering. These streams are taught in French at the university (Chaoui 4).

Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) in this research also reported that some students in the medical field fail their studies because of their lack of proficiency in French. These statements are examples of the above:

I have been studying in Chechar (a rural place in the Chaoui context) for 6 years. the level of emphasis on French among students is relatively low. Later, at the university, they face challenges related to language proficiency. I know some students who failed their first year at university because of language barriers. To achieve good marks, it is imperative to attain proficiency in the language (French) of instruction of the subject (medicine). Insufficient proficiency in the language will result in low grades. That is, the reason for the elevated rate of failure experienced among medicine students during the first year of the university. The rupture between Arabic and French and the sudden transition from Arabic to French affects the grades of students at universities creating obstacles for them (Chaoui 4).

Participants (in focus group discussions) reported that French is the predominant language used in scientific disciplines at Algerian universities, which makes it the most valued language at the level of higher education (Maamri, 2009). They indicated that the Algerian government failed to create its independent school, as they continued using the French colonial language in all scientific streams in higher education.

From a Bourdieusian lens, participants in this study considered education as a major field of power, where different linguistic cultural capital such as Arabic and French are favoured and valued over the other languages. The distribution of these linguistic resources (Arabic and French) shapes students' academic success and future opportunities.

The educational field in the Algerian context is perceived by participants as two sub-fields namely education and higher education. Each of the two sub-fields of power is governed by a specific linguistic capital (Arabic and French respectively), which is perceived to be more valued than the other languages in the linguistic repertoires.

The Algerian language policy, which shapes the distribution of power granted to different languages in the educational system, has a significant impact on access to education, employment, and social status and reinforces the educational inequalities and social reproduction.

8.3 Language and Social Reproduction

Many participants in this study reported that the Arabisation of the educational and Frenchification of higher education in Algeria are two language policies that generate social inequalities and reproduction. Chaoui 4 explained that:

Students of this generation lack proficiency in Arabic and French. They are far from fluency in French. they are fluent in French only if their parents are doctors or professors. Parents in this case teach their children French because they know that it is impossible to switch from French to another language in Algeria. Therefore, they taught their children French. However, this is an issue. Teachers notice the huge gap in students' levels in French. They are either excellent or very weak. There is no average level, which can be developed. Either they are very weak to the point that they do not know the Alphabet or excellent to the point that they do not need to learn it further because they speak it at home (Chaoui 4).

The above excerpt demonstrates a connection between the French language intellectuality and the high socioeconomic status (high class) in the Algerian context. In Algeria, doctors and academic scholars (professors) are commonly associated with high prestige and high socioeconomic status. These jobs are regarded as prestigious professions that generate a very high income. Therefore, being a doctor in Algeria is viewed as a valuable form of cultural and economic capital.

Attaining admission into the medical programme at Algerian universities is difficult as it necessitates high performance in the Baccalaureate national examinations, which serve as a determinant factor in selecting one's preferred discipline in higher learning. Furthermore, scientific disciplines including the medical field at the university are taught in French as it is the medium of instruction. Therefore, students who lack proficiency in French may struggle to learn the language first and then to understand the content as opposed to students who already know the language. Some students may even fail because they do not speak French.

Therefore, according to Bourdieu (2018), schools are a source of social inequalities. They contribute to social reproduction and the distribution of the same capital among social classes (Collins, 2009; Bourdieu, 2018). Therefore, one aspect of language power in Algeria can be illustrated through the policies of Arabisation (primary to secondary cycles) and Frenchification (university). Arabisation and Frenchification are two policies that limit the access of non-elite and common people to the French language, which restricts and limit their

chances to get well-paid, prestigious and political positions that require competency in French (Myers-Scotton, 1993; Benrabah, 2007).

The first focus group discussion (Chaoui) also pointed to the “language and reproduction” theme: participants referred to the notion of "elite closure", which was also highlighted by Benrabah (2001, 2004, 2014). Participants reported that despite their public support for the Arabisation policy, the elite and powerful people in the government enrol their children in Lycée International Alexander Dumas, where French is the language of instruction. They cultivate their children, while keeping the children of common people ignorant. They favour the children of the elite and people who hold power in the government to surpass the children of ordinary people. Based on Bourdieu’s theory, children from upper-class and wealthy families acquire the qualities and dispositions of that class. These inherited and embodied dispositions are, socially, acknowledged and valued by society, educational institutions, and teachers (Crossley, 2014; Bourdieu, 1977; Bourdieu, 2018).

8.4 Language Usage

Although participants reflected on the perceived value of languages based on major fields of power such as education, administrations, and different geographical divisions. However, some participants expressed that, in general, the most used language in their linguistic repertoires is Derja (mixed with French), which makes it the most valuable language for them. Therefore, frequency of language use was one factor indicated by participants (n6) to classify the languages in their linguistic repertoires based on their perceived value. They classified what they consider to be the most active (used) languages in their repertoires or the most used languages in the Algerian context in general as the most valuable languages. Chaoui 10 for instance, stated that Derja holds a significant value in his linguistic repertoire because of its extensive usage. He stated that Derja occupies more time and space in his life and that he relies on it for his daily necessities. Similarly, Chaoui 8 reported that Derja comes first in terms of importance because of its widespread accessibility among the Algerian population. This is indicated in the following quotations:

When it comes to importance, Derja holds the highest significance, followed by Chaoui, Arabic, French, and then English. This is in accordance with my timeframe! When I reflect on my time, I see that Derja holds a greater share in terms of time and space. The value here includes the benefits we get from using Derja! For instance, this person runs his daily needs in Derja! For

instance, if you went to public administrative institutions...speaking with people will be in Derja to run my needs and rights! In addition to Chaoui, and then Arabic, French, and English, which is rarely used (Chaoui 10).

Derja comes first. All the Algerians use Derja...From East to West, from North to South. In Ilysie, Tamanrast, and Janet people speak their language, Terguia, However, only among each other. When speaking to someone, not from their region, they use Derja. In Tlemcen, Oran, Algiers, Jijel, Bejaia, and Tebessa...I mean East, West, North, and South! Derja that exists... it is the one that transmits our ideas, that is clear (Chaoui 8).

Based on the above statements, Derja is perceived to be the common language and the most used language among most of the Algerian population. Therefore, for some participants (n6) it is a valuable language.

Figure 8: Thematic Network of the Perceived Value of Languages

8.5 Conclusion

This chapter answered the third research question by exploring language and power dynamics in the Algerian context from teachers' perspectives in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle). It explored how languages in participants' linguistic repertoires are valued in different fields of power that were referred to by participants. The chapter used Bourdieu's theoretical framework as a lens to illustrate the connection between language and power in Algeria and how language can be used as power to access social resources such as education, knowledge, legitimacy, and wealth. The chapter revealed that language is a powerful tool in all fields. Although all languages have value; however, the value is perceived differently from one field

to another based on social and historical conventions in each field. The chapter highlighted different fields of power such as education, higher education, administrations, local, global, Chaoui, Kabyle, North, South, East, and West in addition to social class. These indicated fields of power are factors that influence language practice and language value according to participants.

The study revealed that the historical events during French colonialism, where French was glorified and regarded as the language of civilisation, left its traces in modern Algeria. These traces can be observed through the perceptions of participants in this study towards French. Participants' perceptions about language value revealed that French is perceived as a prestigious language that has symbolic power in the Algerian administrative fields. It has a very important status in Algeria, which was demonstrated in participants' statements regarding the role of the French language in the administrative field in Algeria.

The findings of the study referred to the local and the international contexts as two fields of power that provide languages with different symbolic power. It also revealed that English, which is viewed to be the most valuable language 'globally' is perceived as less valuable in the Algerian context, while French, which has less value compared to English globally because of being a limited language, according to participants, has prominent status in the Algerian context.

The linguistic dynamics and value of languages are also revealed to be subject to geographical division in Algeria such as North, South, East, and West. The study indicated that these fields, in which the language is used are what determine its value, meaning that Arabic, which is considered valuable in the South according to participants might be less valued in the north of the country as French holds a more valued position. That is, language that is used in a particular context may be perceived as more valuable than other languages, while it may be perceived as less valuable if it is used in another field or domain.

The findings of this research also uncover that language value is perceived differently in the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts. Participants indicated that in the Kabyle context, Tamazight and French are perceived to have more value compared to other languages (Arabic and Derja). This preference is attributed to the fact that Tamazight and French are the commonly spoken languages among the inhabitants of the Kabyle setting, which provides them with a sense of legitimacy. In contrast, Derja and Arabic are viewed as more valuable in the Chaoui context

due to their respective roles. Derja serves as the primary means of communication among individuals within the Chaoui context, while Arabic assumes a significant position as the language employed in religious and educational contexts.

The findings showed that language is an indicator of the intellectual and socio-economic status in the Algerian context. French was perceived as a significant symbolic capital among participants as it reflects high socio-economic status and intellectual level.

Furthermore, the study revealed that Arabic is the most valued language in education as it is considered the official language of instruction. The position it holds in the constitution renders it a symbolic capital in the field of education from the primary to secondary cycle. However, concerning higher education, the findings indicated that French is perceived to be the most valuable language as it serves as a medium of instruction for scientific streams, which are regarded as major fields that grant students with prestigious and well-paid job opportunities in the future. The educational field in Algerian is divided by participants into two sub-fields, which are education and higher education. Each of the two sub-fields operates through a specific linguistic capital (Arabic and French respectively), which is valued more than the other languages in the linguistic repertoires. The study also indicated that the Arabisation and then the Frenchification of the two educational fields (education and higher education) reinforces educational inequalities and social reproduction.

To conclude, this study perceived the language value in the Algerian context in relation to different fields of power. A 'field of power' or 'market' is a concept referred to by Bourdieu to describe a structured space where different positions are set in reliance on the different forms of capital in that space (Bourdieu, 1991). That is, in a market, each language is considered as a product to which a certain value is granted. The respondents classified the languages in their repertoires based on the most required linguistic capital in each of the following fields: Education, administrations, politics, media, science, south, east, west and north, Chaoui and Kabyle contexts, local and international, in addition to social-economic status.

Chapter Nine

Language Policy and Politics

9.1 Introduction

This chapter addresses the language policy at the educational and national level in Algeria and highlights its connection to national politics. The chapter starts by exploring participants' awareness of the language policy in education. After that, it discusses Berber Algerian teachers' linguistic practices in the classroom. Then, it examines their attitudes toward the language policy in education. The chapter also highlights the status of Tamazight (the local language spoken by most participants in the location where the study was conducted). Finally, the chapter raises awareness about the tensions and conflicts caused by the implemented language policy. Addressing the language policy in Algeria and education, particularly from the teachers' perspective, may call attention to the issues facing the implementation of this policy in education. The chapter addresses the fourth research question in relation to the literature and the theoretical framework.

9.2 Language Policy in Education

9.2.1 Hesitation Discussing Politics

The study revealed that few participants (n3) were hesitant and felt intimidated when engaging in discussions about language policy in Algeria. This hesitancy can be attributed to the fact that language policy intersects with political matters, which may be perceived as a sensitive topic by participants. Participants' fear of commenting publicly on language and politics stemmed from their awareness of being recorded for this research. One potential concern that arose was the possibility of publicly releasing the recorded interviews, which could potentially give rise to issues with the government, although participants were already informed that the research is conducted according to the university ethical code, which ensures the confidentiality and anonymity of any personal details of participants in this research. The hesitation to express opinions concerning politics may also originate from the historical experiences of the Algerian society with language and politics in Algeria, which was marked by mistrust. This relates to Bourdieu's framework particularly his concept of 'habitus', which reflect the dispositions, belief, and attitudes that are shaped and formed through time and from historical experiences (Grenfell, 2014).

9.2.2 Awareness of Language Policy

According to the findings, many participants (n=16) from the Berber region (Kabyle and Chaoui) demonstrated knowledge regarding the official language of education in Algeria, which is Arabic. Additionally, they reported that French and English are considered foreign languages and are taught as core subjects in primary, middle, and secondary schools. Furthermore, the participants indicated that French is regarded as the primary medium of instruction in academic disciplines such as medicine, pharmacy, biology, and physics at universities. The possession of multilingual repertoires is a characteristic that affords individuals the ability to choose from a variety of linguistic capital or linguistic resources at their disposal to engage in communication and construct meanings across different contexts, including the classroom (Reilly et al., 2022). However, some language policies tend to be monolingual. In other words, they manage the linguistic repertoire in a way that allocates one specific language to certain contexts such as in the language policy adopted by the Algerian government where Arabic is considered the language of education and the language that is supposed to be used in the classroom (Reilly, Colin, et al. 2022). In higher education, a similar monolingual approach is employed within scientific streams, wherein instruction is exclusively conducted in the French language. The monolingual policies implemented in Algeria are not unique to Algeria; instead, they are regarded as a common practice in African nations after independence (Bamgbose, 2000). The origins of these monolingual policies in Algeria might be connected to the historical events of colonialism where the French colonialist imposed strict monolingual policies to force the French language and culture.

The focus group discussion in the Chaoui context revealed that participants have knowledge regarding the language policies adopted by France during colonisation. The participants (n6) agreed that the policy implemented by the colonialist aimed at imposing French in Algeria. After independence, the government continued to implement the same monolingual approach of the French colonialists. Despite the transition from French to Arabic in education, commonly referred to as Arabisation, the government's policies continue to mirror the monolingual approach inherited from the French colonial era (Kamwangamalu, 2018). Moreover, French has been adopted as a medium of instruction for scientific streams in higher education in Algeria, which is inspired by the European monolingual policies (Reilly, Colin, et al., 2022; Kamwangamalu, 2018). Participants reported that the language policy

during colonialism is more successful than the Algerian language policy after independence. According to them, the government failed to create its policy and therefore it continued with the colonialist previous language policy in education.

9.2.3 Perceived Vagueness of Algerian Language Policy

Most participants (n16) demonstrated awareness of the linguistic dynamics in Algeria, recognising Arabic as the primary language of education and French as the medium of instruction for scientific disciplines at universities (Reilly, Colin, et al., 2022). However, they (n12) also indicated that the language policy in Algeria is vague and lacks clarity, which was also confirmed in the study done by Reilly et al (Reilly et al., 2022). Some participants expressed a lack of knowledge regarding the entities responsible for formulating language policies in the field of education as well as the process through which these policies are issued, while other participants presented a range of possibilities for who could potentially be responsible for developing the language policies in Algeria.

Kabyle 5 revealed that Arabic is the official language of education in the constitution; however, she expressed uncertainty regarding the specific entity or individuals responsible for the decision-making process. Chaoui 6 gave a more general answer when he was asked if he knows who is responsible for issuing the language policies in education. She asserted that the entity in question is the government. Chaoui 2 on the other hand, declared that they are still colonised by France, and to her knowledge, France is responsible for language policies in Algeria. She reported that despite military independence, Algeria remains under colonial influence due to the persistent use of French by governmental bodies and politicians. Participants in this study indicated the absence of clear and transparent communication regarding the subject of language policy in the field of education. The decisions made regarding language policy and its implementation exhibit a level of ambiguity, as noted by Reilly et al (2022). The lack of clarity regarding language policy in the field of education was further confirmed in the first focus group discussion conducted in the Chaoui context, wherein participants reached a consensus that the educational language policy is not clear.

Chaoui 5, who lived and worked in Bejaia for an extended period, stated that the celebration of the New Year in the Amazigh calendar, historically occurring on January 12th, had been prohibited in the past. However, the Amazigh community would celebrate this occasion in refusal of the government's opposition. In contrast, now, the government mandates

celebrating the anniversary of that day within the school community. Therefore, according to Chaoui 5, a definitive policy is lacking. The language policy undergoes modifications in response to shifts in the governing body.

Some participants believe that the language policies implemented in education are “top-down” policies that primarily serve the leaders and politicians (ideological positions of the government stakeholders) in the Algerian government. Participants' perceptions indicated that the language policy in Algeria is not aligned with the actual realities and educational issues, which was also confirmed in the study done by Reilly et al (2022).

Furthermore, most participants (n16) in the study indicated that they had not received any written documents from any political party concerning language use in the classroom. The Algerian constitution is the sole document that officially designates Arabic as the language of instruction in the educational system. According to the participants, the information provided by inspectors concerning language use in the classroom was solely communicated orally during their visits. Therefore, the documentation of language policies in education is perceived as limited, which is also confirmed by Reilly et al. (2022).

9.3 Language Practices in the Classroom

9.3.1 Language Inspection in Schools

The study revealed that inspectors visit schools either annually or biennially for inspections. Many participants noted that inspectors insist on the implementation of a monolingual policy that entails the use of a single language within the classroom (Reilly et al., 2022). According to them, school inspectors advocate the use of Arabic as a medium of instruction in the classroom across all subjects, except for French and English, where teachers are required to exclusively use French or English as the language of instruction in the classroom. Chaoui 7 reported that inspectors could punish teachers if they used Derja instead of Arabic in the classroom. He added that inspectors may even lower marks or fail teachers to be promoted to a permanent position.

On the other hand, some participants reported that the remarks concerning language use in the classroom depend on the inspector. Certain inspectors insist on the use of specific languages within the classroom, whereas others exhibit less concern towards language use, instead prioritising the progression of the lesson and the effective communication of its

primary objectives. Kabyle 8 reported that the inspections concerning language use in the classroom align with the linguistic orientation of inspectors. He provided instances of the inspectors who conducted visits to his location. The first inspector possessed a francophone background, consequently leading to a lack of emphasis on language usage within the classroom. The second inspector was from an Arab city, representing the older generation who are fluent in French. Consequently, the inspector himself employed a blend of French and Arabic languages in his communication. However, inspectors currently, according to Kabyle 8, are trained in Arabic; therefore, they tend to use Arabic during the inspection. Chaoui 5 on the other hand, declared that the experienced inspectors impart their inspection methods to the newly appointed inspectors.

the study also revealed that inspections concerning language use in the Kabyle context are more demanding (strict) compared to those in the Chaoui context. That was indicated by Chaoui 5, who worked in the Kabyle setting for many years before returning to the Chaoui context. A possible explanation for the rigorous inspections regarding language use within the educational setting of the Kabyle context is the strong attachment of individuals in this setting to Tamazight, their native language. Historically, Tamazight has been subject to marginalisation by the Algerian government, as documented by Belmihoub (2018) and Roberts (2003). The historical marginalisation of the Tamazight language in Algeria may have contributed to the strong attachment that Kabyle individuals feel towards their linguistic and cultural heritage.

9.3.2 Translanguaging in the Classroom

The findings suggested that although most of the respondents (n18) from Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) acknowledge that Arabic is the language of education in the constitution and that the curriculum should be delivered in Arabic regardless of students' mother tongue; they also acknowledge the practice of translanguaging in the classroom. This is summarised by Chaoui 6, who reported that Arabic is the dominant language because he is a teacher of Arabic; however, he always practises translanguaging as a pedagogical strategy in the classroom to augment educational outcomes and help students. Furthermore, he stated that he is living in a multicultural and multilingual society; therefore, his objective is to effectively convey the lesson's content to students, employing various languages and methods. Participants in the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) also revealed that transmitting the

content of the lesson to the students is more important than debating on which language to use.

On the one hand, some teachers of foreign languages (French, English, and German) interviewed for the study (from the Kabyle context) were convinced that using only the target language to teach foreign languages is better than translanguaging in terms of the efficacy of teaching. That is, according to participants teaching foreign languages adopting a monolingual approach, where only L2 is used, is supposed to be more effective than translanguaging and the incorporation of L1 (mother language) in the lesson. However, they also indicated that they are obliged to use other languages in the classroom to share ideas with students, which contradicts their previous stance. This is in line with a study done by Adder and Bagui (2020) where they investigated the phenomenon of code-switching from English to Arabic among Algerian university teachers and students. Similarly, the findings revealed teachers indicated unfavourable attitudes towards the use of L1 and encouraged the use of L2 in teaching languages (English as a foreign language). However, many teachers perceived the use of L1 as an imperative, especially when aiming to efficiently convey a message to students.

Translanguaging allows people to make use of their linguistic resources and switch between different languages and varieties as needed and as appropriate (Oliver et al., 2021; Simpson and Wigglesworth, 2018; Vaughan, 2018). It maintains effective communication by helping speakers to make themselves understood and to ensure that they understood the interlocutor (Oliver et al., 2021).

Studies seem to contradict what teachers of foreign languages in Berber region (Chaoui and the Kabyle) believe concerning the effectiveness of monolingual policies in teaching foreign languages. These studies demonstrated the importance of translanguaging in the educational sector (Oliver et al., 2021; Sellwood and Angelo, 2013; Angelo and Carter, 2015; García and Wei, 2014).

According to teachers of content subjects, which are supposed to be delivered in Arabic in secondary schools, such as history, geography, and mathematics, the dominant language in the classroom is Arabic. However, these teachers also indicated that they use the other languages in their linguistic repertoires to facilitate teaching and communicating with students. Therefore, translanguaging is inevitable in the classroom, according to participants. The first focus group discussion (Chaoui) revealed that the participants use Derja very often

in the classroom; Derja was reported to be more effective than Arabic (the official language of education). The second focus group discussion (Kabyle), conversely, indicated a lack of support for translanguaging when teaching foreign languages; however, participants did not express opposition to employing translanguaging in the classroom for other subjects if the content of the lesson is effectively conveyed.

As noted above, participants (interviews and focus groups) revealed that the only guidance that teachers received concerning language use in the classroom is provided orally from inspectors, who visit on an annual or biennial basis. Some teachers reported that the inspector never visited them within the first year of their teaching experience, thereby confirming the low frequency of inspections. In the absence of inspections, some participants revealed that they engage in translanguaging as a common practice. However, when inspectors are present, participants adhere to the use of Arabic, which serves as the official language of education. Teachers justified translanguaging in the classroom, reporting that they know better than the inspector does. They are in the classroom, and they know what is needed in the classroom. They stated that it is impossible to rely only on the use of Arabic to explain the lessons. In other words, teachers practice in the classroom in relation to language use is not compatible or harmonious with the language policy in education.

The study revealed that most participants practise translanguaging in the classroom; therefore, they were asked if they also permit students to use all the languages in their linguistic repertoires. Many respondents (n14) (Chaoui and Kabyle) reported that they permit the practice of translanguaging among students in the classroom. Chaoui 10 for instance, reported that he does not impose the use of a particular language on students. Even when it comes to oral answers, the most important thing for Chaoui 10 is that students transmit their ideas using any language they know, and he understands. Chaoui 11 too reported that he allows students to practise translanguaging in the classroom. Chaoui 11 is a teacher of English. He declared that he does not have another option because students need time to learn English; they cannot perfectly speak English overnight. Students need time to learn it gradually. Chaoui 11 added that he has colleagues who do not permit students to use languages in the classroom; consequently, participation in the classroom is getting lower. Students' engagement and involvement are silenced (Angelo and Carter, 2015). He continued that he encourages students to use English; however, he allows them to practise

translanguaging. Chaoui 2 also stated that prohibiting the use of other languages in the classroom would negatively affect students' Progression and academic level. She declared that if she used that approach students would keep staring at her without engagement therefore, she does not want to restrict students (Angelo and Carter, 2015).

On the other hand, a few teachers (n5) indicated that they do not permit translanguaging in the classroom. The participants who do not permit translanguaging among students in the classroom are teachers of Arabic or foreign languages such as French. They justified their method of teaching by stating that students should learn how to speak in Arabic or French because in the exams they would be obliged to answer in Arabic or French. Therefore, according to some participants prohibiting other languages and Teaching following the monolingual policy helps students to achieve good grades in exams.

Kabyle 3, who stated that she insists on speaking French because it is a class of the French language. She also reported that she prohibits the use of other languages in the classroom and added that this is how she studied. Kabyle 7 too reported that she does not encourage a language other than Arabic because students are required to write essays only in Arabic in Exams. According to Khelalfa and Kellil (2023) the role of L1 in the process of learning L2 is one of the longstanding debates in the field of language teaching and learning. For a long time, the utilisation of L1 has been discouraged, especially in light of the development of language teaching methods such as the direct method, the natural approach, and the communicative approach (Howatt and Widdowson, 2004).

According to Krashen and Terrell (1983), these methods emphasise the efficacy of using only L2 in language teaching asserting that this approach facilitates more effective acquisition of the L2 due to its resemblance to the natural process of acquiring one's first language (L1). Littlewood and Yu (2011) argue that resorting to L1 as a means of compensating for any inadequacies in the educational setting has a negative impact on learners as it may impede learners' progress and restrict them from maximum exposure to the language being studied. However, in recent years, there has been a notable shift in viewpoints concerning the role of L1 within L2 classroom. This shift reflects an increasing tendency to reintroduce the use of L1. One potential explanation for this shift could be the perceived limitations of instruction exclusively centred on L2 in meeting the needs of students (Khelalfa and Kellil, 2023).

Although few participants (n5) in this study believe that translanguaging may hinder students' achievement, the majority contradicts them and view translanguaging as inevitable in the classroom and that it is necessary to enable students' engagement and communication in the classroom. Therefore, regardless of the medium of instruction and the associated language policy students should be motivated to use their entire linguistic repertoires in the classroom (Oliver et al., 2021).

9.4 Teachers' Attitudes towards Language Policy in Education

9.4.1 Arabic as the Official Language in Algerian Education

The study revealed varied views concerning supporting or opposing Arabic as an official language in education among participants. Some participants advocated the Arabisation policy that adopts Arabic as the language of instruction in Algeria. Chaoui 1 expressed a preference for Arabic, the language widely used in Algerian society according to her, as well as in religious and scientific contexts. She expressed the view that Arabic holds a significant position within the Algerian context, thus supporting Arabic as a language of instruction, and proposed its adoption as the medium of instruction for scientific disciplines at the university level, instead of French. Moreover, Chaoui 3 indicated that Arabic is a linguistically diverse language with significant potential for producing favourable results if it receives adequate governmental attention and promotional efforts. He asserted that this approach has the potential to produce students who possess exceptional linguistic and scientific abilities across various disciplines. To illustrate his point, he provided an example of a student who attained the highest scores in their baccalaureate examinations and has consistently demonstrated the ability to memorise the Quran from a young age.

Opposition to the Arabisation of the educational system was also expressed by additional participants (n6). Chaoui 5 and Chaoui 11 proposed the adoption of English as an official language for educational instruction. Chaoui 11 shared the experience of his friend, who achieved the highest ranking within their medical cohort. However, failed to pursue his studies abroad because of his lack of proficiency in English. Chaoui 11 asserted that the English language serves as a valuable instrument by which to foster national development within the Algerian context. Chaoui 5 expressed that although adopting English as a medium of instruction would be challenging due to the lack of individuals proficient in English and students prepared to engage in English-medium education; however, providing students with

education in English would offer them the opportunity to pursue studies abroad, as opposed to Arabic that would impose limitations in this regard. Kabyle 1 asserts that the inclusion of Arabic in the educational system is excessive, and proposed the inclusion of French or English, particularly since scientific disciplines are primarily taught in French at the university level. She indicated that Arabic should be taught using Arabic as the medium of instruction, and Tamazight should be taught using Tamazight as the medium of instruction. Additionally, she suggested that scientific subjects would be more effectively taught using either French or English. Kabyle 2 argues that the educational curriculum should be imparted in indigenous languages such as Tamazight and Derja. According to her assertion, individuals residing in the Maghreb region (Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia) typically communicate in one language, while pursuing their studies in a different language, which she perceives as a matter of concern. She offered an illustration of the Kabyle community, whose mother language is Tamazight, yet is compelled to acquire and employ Arabic within schools. Moreover, Kabyle 8 reported that the domain of education is vast, necessitating the delivery of certain subjects in Arabic and others in French. However, it is imperative to establish harmonisation between education, higher education, and the professional sphere.

The first focus group discussion (Chaoui) also revealed a conflict of opposing ideas among participants. Some respondents (n2) supported the Arabisation policy and considered it a unifying policy, while other participants (2) criticised the policy indicating that the government is opting for a policy that promotes tensions between the different groups in Algeria. Chaoui 5, who was against the 'Arabisation' policy shared a post from the internet that according to him, describes the monism in the language policy in Algeria. The post reads as follows: 'A horse cannot handle two riders, the knight cannot bear two banners, the land cannot bear two countries, the country cannot bear two nations, a nation cannot bear two identities and the identity cannot bear two languages'. The participant emphasised that he is against monism in Algeria. Meanwhile, participants (n4) from the second focus group discussion (Kabyle) expressed that they accept the Arabisation of the educational system. They reported that they have grown accustomed to that, and they cannot imagine otherwise.

9.4.2 Perceived Contradictions in the Language Policy in Algeria

This study unveiled several contradictions that participants expressed regarding the language policy in Algeria. The first contradiction referred to by participants in this study (interviews

(n12) and focus group discussions) is the Arabisation of the educational system from primary to secondary school and the Frenchification of the scientific streams in higher education.

Participants reported that students are bearing the consequences of this contradictory language policy that had been implemented. Students study for twelve years in Arabic before switching to French at the university level. This sudden shift poses a significant challenge for students who face difficulties in simultaneously learning language skills and comprehending the subject, consequently diverting their attention from the core content. Some (n9) participants reported that many students in the field of medicine struggle, abandon, or fail their studies in medicine because of their lack of proficiency in French. Mathews (2014) argued that students who had been exposed to Arabic as a language of instruction in primary and secondary school had a "linguistic shock" when they transition to studying in a foreign language for which they lacked the necessary proficiency. According to Gherzouli (2019), the process of Arabisation has been characterised by contradictions. These contradictions can be identified primarily by examining the disparity between the stated commitment to the implementation of Arabic since 1961 and the continuous usage of French as the primary language in the job market until the present time.

Participants in the first focus group discussion agreed that this implemented policy is a disaster. They criticised the existence of two educational ministries, which are the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Higher Education. Participants in the second focus group discussion reported that they are against this contradiction that poses challenges for students; however, they also advocate instruction in French rather than Arabic at the university level as they perceive it as more beneficial for students in the long term, that is, if they wanted to study abroad. Bourdieu used the term 'social reproduction' to explain how the educational systems can lead to injustice among students through the reproduction of power relations (Azaola, 2012). The connection between social reproduction and French in Algeria can be traced back to the historical imposition of French during colonisation. Proficiency in the French language became a marker of social status and access to opportunities, which reinforce social inequalities for individuals lacking fluency in French. Students who are fluent in French would not struggle as non-fluent counterparts when selecting scientific streams.

In Algeria, students who possess fluency in French tend to originate from rich families that allocate their economic resources towards acquiring linguistic capital, specifically the French language. This observation is supported by Kabyle 5, who asserts that most rich people in Algeria speak French. According to Chaoui 4, students who are fluent in French may come from families where parents hold occupations such as medical doctors, pharmacists, and professors. Parents who already possess this linguistic capital (French) influence their children's linguistic habitus too. Chaoui 4 reported a notable observation, which is the significant variation in students' proficiency level in French. Students' levels in French range from excellent, where students possess a mastery that renders further learning unnecessary, to very weak. Moreover, policymakers and the elite, who hold positions in the government enrol their children in private schools that offer a bilingual curriculum encompassing both Arabic and French. Consequently, these children acquire proficiency in French (Benrabah, 2001; 2014b; 2014a).

French dominates political, economic, and scientific fields, which are considered major fields of power in Algeria (Rouabah, 2022; Jacob, 2020). Students who speak fluent French and who usually belong to one of the above-discussed categories always succeed in these fields and get positions of authority easily because of the high demands for French language proficiency in the job market (see Chaouche, 2005). However, students who belong to a working social class and "average" families where Arabic dominates would be barred from public jobs in these sectors. For instance, Chaoui 3 reported that, administratively one is obliged to deal in French, as all its administrative transactions are in French. This is known as the reproduction of power relations (Azaola, 2012). Language is therefore, used as a "weapon in the struggle for power" (Marquand, 2004, P.71). The struggle to learn both the language and the content to succeed in scientific streams does not stop at the university level. Students who succeed in scientific streams at the level of the university will again face the struggle to shift from French to Arabic if they become teachers in primary, middle, or secondary schools. They will be required to teach scientific subjects in Arabic, which may represent another struggle for them. Chaoui 4, who studied for five years in French indicated that when he became a teacher, he faced difficulties in using the Arabic language for work purposes.

One additional contradiction highlighted by participants is the mismatch between the Arabisation policy and the actual linguistic situation in Algeria (Belmihoub, 2018). The

Arabisation policy aimed to prioritise the use of Arabic over the other existing languages in Algeria (Benchehida, 2001; Benrabah, 2014b; Mostari, 2004). Derja and Tamazight, the native languages of Algerians were marginalised under Arabisation (Belmihoub, 2018; Roberts, 2003), while the French language dominated many fields in Algeria (Belmihoub, 2018). The combination of Derja/French and Tamazight/French is the reflection of the actual linguistic situation in Algeria, while Arabic is not prevalent in practical usage in daily interactions.

Chaoui 5 indicated another point where contradiction is demonstrated. He gave an example of former president Bouteflika, who once stated that Tamazight would never be an official language. In September 1999, former president Bouteflika stated that “Tamazight would never be consecrated in law as an Algerian official language and if it were to be a national language, it is up to the entire Algerian people to decide by referendum” (Benrabah, 2007, P.246). However, in 2002 without any referendum, he announced Tamazight as a national language and then made it official in 2016 (Benrabah, 2007; Hamdan and Kessar, 2023). According to Chaoui 5, this event reflects the contradiction and the absence of a future vision in relation to language policy in Algeria.

9.4.3 French versus English Referendum

The participants in this study were asked about an online referendum that was conducted in 2019 at a national level to review the status of the French language in contemporary Algeria (Bouherar and Ghafsi, 2021). Most participants (focus group discussions and interviews (n8)) from the Chaoui context expressed their support for the substitution of French with English in education stating that this policy change would have positive implications for the country. Participants reported that English, which is a global language is more valuable in comparison to French, which is considered a limiting language. Chaoui 11 reported a story of a doctor he knew, who wanted to publish an article in an English journal. However, the article was rejected after the translation was submitted because the translator lacks expertise in the domain of medicine. The article was not accurate. The participants described English as a lingua franca, a language with global reach, a language of science, and a language of development. In contrast, they described French as a limiting and dead language imposed upon Algerians because of the colonialist and the francophone lobby, which according to some participants are the traces of France's presence in Algeria. Advocating English over French in the Chaoui context where Arabisation is more evident is viewed as a way of resisting

French neo-colonialism. Participants highlighted that the French government influences the Algerian government by interfering in the language policy (Jacob, 2020)

On the other hand, many participants in the Kabyle context (n6) expressed their opposition to the replacement of French with English; however, they indicated that they support additive multilingualism by adding English to the educational curriculum along with French (Benrabah, 2007). Some participants (n4) reported that it is impossible to suddenly replace and abandon a language (French) that has been deeply rooted in Algeria for generations. They regarded French as a part of their identity, rather than a language of foreign origin. Kabyle 8 described the referendum as an unintelligent step. He reported that a language constitutes a single component of culture, and the French culture in Algeria is deeply ingrained, extending beyond linguistic aspects. He continued:

In Algeria, we can talk about the French culture that is planted within us. There are professors of English who speak French, and they do not speak English with each other because we cannot erase 130 years of French presence in Algeria. France left to us their films, their books, and even their culinary culture. What do you eat for breakfast? Milk and coffee. Who left this culture for us? It is the heritage of French culture. Therefore, taking just one aspect of the culture that is language, and expecting that you will change the whole culture with such a decision is wrong. You can speak English very well, better than your mother tongue, but you will not feel the link with England. We do not have the historical closeness that we have with France. We have a common history. Even though it was a bloody history, its effects are obstinate. History remains history we cannot erase it (Kabyle 8).

Kabyle 8 continued that he is not against adding English to the curriculum; however, he is against excluding French to achieve that. Participants from the second focus group discussion (Kabyle) expressed uncertainty regarding the potential success of the referendum. They also indicated that Kabyle people are very attached to the French language, and it may take around twenty years to accomplish this linguistic assimilation.

Participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) revealed that English is an important language globally. However, participants from the Chaoui context in particular viewed English as an escape from the French language and colonisation. Therefore, the majority promoted English over French. The participants overlooked the fact that English domination today goes back to British colonisation, and domination in the past, and to the remarkable domination of

America in the present era (Sekhar, 2012). Although both languages (French and English) are associated with colonialism, it is worth noting that the direct experience of French colonisation in the Algerian context has resulted in a sense of resentment towards the French language among participants in the Chaoui context. This statement is following Bourdieu's notion of 'habitus', which posits that an individual's personal experiences influence their perspectives, beliefs, and dispositions (Bourdieu, 1984).

The participants were also asked whether they believe that the referendum was well planned for or not. Many participants (n16) in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) reported that the decision of the online referendum was not well planned. The respondents (n11) perceived the referendum as a mere political matter that sought to promote the implied ideologies of the government. They reported that it was a result of the Hirak and the late political conflicts where people were claiming to cut all ties with France (Bouherar and Ghafsi, 2021). Consequently, the government aimed to repress the anger of the Algerian population by launching an online referendum that sought to review the status of the French language in Algeria. The findings from the focus group discussions (Chaoui and Kabyle) revealed a consensus among participants that the referendum lacked adequate planning and research. It was perceived as a product of political conflicts and the Hirak movement (the population revolution against the government and former president Abdelaziz Bouteflika's fifth term) that took place in 2019 (Bouherar and Ghafsi, 2021).

In this study, Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) reported that the referendum was connected to the balance of powers in Algeria. That is, if Francophone stakeholders ruled the government, they would likely seek to enforce and empower the French language in major domains of power. However, the linguistic dynamics would be changed if the balance of powers changed in the government. Therefore, according to the respondents, the decision regarding language policy is issued based on a "top-down" policy and is related to politics. Two participants from the Chaoui context provided the example of the previous referendum that was held in 1992 in Algeria to replace French with English. They reported that the minister Ali Ben Mohamed in 1991-1992 wanted to apply a project that aimed to offer students in primary school the opportunity to select between studying French or English French or English commencing from the fourth year. The decision faced opposition from the francophone lobby at that time, leading to the disclosure of the baccalaureate exams. The

minister subsequently resigned due to his dissatisfaction with the events that happened. This event according to the participants demonstrated how the balance of powers and how politics affect the language policy. Respondents in the first focus group discussion (Chaoui) described the educational language policy in Algeria as subject to political conflicts and a balance of powers.

9.4.4 Tamazight in Algeria

Many respondents in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) reported that Tamazight is recognised as a national and official language in the constitution alongside Arabic, which is confirmed in a study conducted by Hamdan and Kessar (2023). Many participants (n10) from the Chaoui context reported that Tamazight is taught as an optional subject in only one or two schools in their in the Chaoui setting. In contrast, all participants (n10) from the Kabyle context reported that the instruction of Tamazight is compulsory in all schools there; they were also aware that Tamazight might be an optional subject in other provinces. The findings of the study revealed that the majority of participants from the Chaoui context support the fact that Tamazight is an optional subject. They reported that they prefer Tamazight to be an optional subject rather than mandatory in the curriculum. Conversely, most participants from the Kabyle context indicated that Tamazight must be included in education as a compulsory subject equal in status to Arabic, French, and English.

Most participants in this study (Chaoui and the Kabyle) indicated that Tamazight has the same status as Arabic in the constitution. It is recognised as a national and official language alongside Arabic; however, some respondents reported that the actual implementation of Tamazight does not reflect the important status it has in the constitution, which was also confirmed in the study done by Rouabah (2022). Kabyle 9 criticised the language policy in the following excerpt:

Tamazight is not generalised...it is not compulsory. How can you make a language official and then you do not make it compulsory? Since they make it an official language, why they are not integrating it into any official sermons (Kabyle 9)?

The focus group discussions (Chaoui and Kabyle) indicated that the status that Tamazight has in the constitution is not reflected. The second focus group discussion (Kabyle) revealed that the current state of Tamazight has improved compared to previous times; however, it emphasised the necessity of further efforts to enhance its promotion.

A few participants (n3) in the Chaoui context claimed that the government's decision to include Tamazight as an official language in the constitution was made in an effort to console, please, and satisfy Kabylia people following the historical rioting and social protests that sought to recognise Algeria's linguistic and cultural diversity, which is confirmed by Fenwick (2008). This illustrates how Algerian politics and linguistic policy are intertwined. The struggles and problems encountered, when implementing language policy in practice serve as a reminder of Algeria's lack of preparation and research in this area. Tamazight was officially a national language in the constitution in 2001 and an official language in the constitution in 2016 (Hamdan and Kessar, 2023; Rouabah, 2022). However, even now the government is still facing struggles in implementing these policies.

The study revealed that many challenges are associated with the integration of Tamazight in education. Chaoui 2 and Chaoui 5 documented their experience of invigilating a Tamazight language examination, highlighting the presence of three examination papers: one composed in Latin script, another composed in Arabic script, and a third composed in Tifinagh script (Tamazight symbols). According to Chaoui 2, there were approximately 30 minutes during which teachers debated whether students were required to respond to all three examination papers or only one.

We do not know. We did not study Tamazight at school. We do not know how to read it, and we did not receive any note concerning that. We were just supposed to give the exam papers to the students. We asked the director about that, and he said to let the students answer the three exam papers. However, it is impossible because time is limited. I told them I think that they should answer just one sample, but I could not impose that on them because I did not receive any note that says so. In addition, this is a national exam, not a local one where we can tell students to answer just one sample. Only after half an hour, we received a note; I do not know how, that it is the same exam written in three different alphabets (Latin, Arabic, and Tamazight). Therefore, students should answer one sample based on what they have studied. At that time, we lost time and students cried so much (Chaoui 2).

Chaoui 5 indicated that the absence of a unifying writing system for teaching Tamazight is a challenge for the implementation of Tamazight, which was also indicated by Sadiqi (2011). There is no agreement concerning the writing system of Tamazight throughout the country. The three writing systems of Tamazight in Algeria might be driven by political and ideological endeavours. That is, although the majority of Kabyle people prefer the Latin script (Rouabah,

(2020) it is still viewed as linked to French and colonialism, which is indicated by Chaoui 7, who reported that in Algeria, there are movements that defend Tamazight through using Latin scripts intended to undermine the Islam. Tifinegh, on the other hand, is viewed as a way to preserve the authenticity of the language, while Arabic script for writing Tamazight is perceived as a means for preserving Muslim identity and unity (Rouabah, 2022).

Another challenge facing the integration of Tamazight in education might be the attitudes people hold towards this language. Many participants in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle) reported that Tamazight is a heritage that is learned primarily because it is a cultural and identity-related heritage. Based on the perspectives of many participants in this study, Tamazight is not a language of science or development. Participants described it as a dead language, a dialect that does not rise to be a language, and an obstacle that stands in the way of development. Some participants even prioritised learning other languages over investing time in learning Tamazight. The first focus group discussion (Chaoui) in this study unveiled negative attitudes towards Tamazight, indicating that Tamazight is not a language of science or development. They even questioned the value of Tamazight stating that Tamazight brings no benefit to its speakers.

These attitudes towards Tamazight are dispositions that have been planted in the social and individual habitus of participants through the historical social and political events in Algeria, which aligns with Bourdieu's concept of 'habitus' (Grenfell, 2014). Tamazight has been marginalised for years after independence, and this was reflected in the policies adopted by the Algerian government after independence such as the Arabisation policy that failed to acknowledge the presence of Tamazight and Amazigh communities. This marginalisation was further highlighted by significant events such as the Berber Spring and the Black Spring (see Rouabah, 2022; Benrabah, 2005; Benrabah, 2007). According to Jacob (2020), Tamazight has been associated with regionalism and separatism and has been portrayed as a threat to national cohesion. All these events have contributed to the formation of an unfavourable perception of Tamazight within the Algerian population.

Therefore, the Algerian government needs to start by raising tolerance and fostering acceptance of multilingualism and multiculturalism within the Algerian context. Some participants suggested that the government should undertake efforts to enhance public awareness regarding the significance of Tamazight to change the negative

attitudes towards Tamazight to positive ones. In addition, the inclusion of Tamazight as a compulsory subject in education, similar to Arabic, French, and English, should be considered by the government as an actual measure towards its implementation. Furthermore, it is imperative to develop a unified writing system that facilitates the instruction and acquisition of Tamazight, thus enhancing its accessibility and practicality.

9.4.5 Otherness and Tensions

“Othering” is an important theme that was detected among participants (n2) in this study (Chaoui and Kabyle). Participants referred to themselves as the “in-group” and to others as the “out-group” (Brons, 2015). Participants (interviews and focus group discussion) from the Chaoui context referred to people from the Kabyle context as the “other” by addressing them as “they”, while participants from the Kabyle context kept referring to Arabs as the “other”.

The term racism was used to describe the “other” in this study. Kabyle 1 reported that there is no issue with Tamazight being an official language; however, he expressed that Arabs are racist to Kabyle people, and Kabyle people are racist towards Arabs, which he perceives as a problem. Many (n5) participants from the Kabyle context indicated that there are growing tensions and conflicts between Arabs and Kabyle people or Amazigh in general, which was also highlighted by Prah (2002). Chaoui 10 reported that some people do not want to study or learn Tamazight; He perceived people who want to mandate Tamazight even in the Arab regions as “racists”. Chaoui 10 referred to Kabyle people as ‘racists’ because of their efforts to promote the status of Tamazight and they are calling for generalising it in Algeria. He expressed that Tamazight is not obligatory; therefore, they do not need it.

“Othering” can also be observed through using the term “impose”, especially in the Chaoui context. Although people from the Chaoui context are the second largest group of Amazigh in Algeria; however, many participants (n7) indicated that they do not support the imposition of Tamazight in education. They addressed Tamazight as a language that is imposed on them from another party although it is the language of the Chaoui people too. Kabyle 5 reported that she advocates the compulsory inclusion of Tamazight; however, no one can oblige people to learn. She added that people often argue that learning Tamazight provides no benefits suggesting that it would be more advantageous to learn English, German, or French instead. Chaoui 11 on the other hand, stated that he is against imposing Tamazight on people who do not want to study it. He added that if the majority of people in Algeria believe that Tamazight

is not useful you cannot impose it on them. He continued stating that the acquisition of Tamazight may potentially impede proficiency in other languages being learned, such as English, French, or Arabic.

The feel of rejection and being a member of an “out-group” was expressed by Kabyle 6, who stated that in the Kabyle context, Tamazight has great importance because it is the native language there; however, in other regions, like Blida, there was a notable rejection to the books of Tamazight because they do not want to promote its teaching. Many participants (n 5) from the Chaoui context reported that Tamazight is very important in the Kabyle context and that Kabyle people are the ones who aim to develop the status of Tamazight in Algeria.

Few participants (n3) in this study also “othered” the government. They indirectly referred to the government as a third party that is plotting against them. Chaoui 8 reported that the government is following a policy that aims to destroy Arabic and encourage the French language; however, with the new changes (After Hirak), there will be promising changes. Kabyle 6 also indicated that “The government did not make an effort, or offer tools for learning this Tamazight, even though there are books, libraries etc., but they did not offer tools for the students, or encourage students to learn this language”.

The above excerpt revealed that mistrust is dominating the relationship between people and the government. The Algerian historical events such as the Berber Spring, Black Spring, and Al-Hirak in addition to the other social, economic, and political challenges contributed to the mistrust between the population and the government (Achy, 2013; Rouabah, 2022; Benrabah, 2005; Benrabah, 2007). This relates to Bourdieu’s concept of “habitus” where the feelings of mistrust and “othering” that shape the relationship between the government and population are considered as dispositions that are shaped and influenced by the above-indicated historical experiences (Berber Spring, Black Spring, and Al-Hirak in addition to the other social, economic, and political challenges) (Grenfell, 2004).

The study revealed that the Algerian monolingual policies that encourage “othering” between the different groups in Algeria are also creating tensions and conflicts especially when certain groups are marginalised. Some participants from the Kabyle context indicated that Tamazight is marginalised in Algeria and in North Africa, a comment, which is supported by Roberts (2003), who reported that the implemented policy after independence denied Berbers’ rights and marginalised their language. Many participants in the Kabyle context (n6) indicated that

Tamazight should be a compulsory subject equal to Arabic. They expressed that if Arabs reject studying Tamazight, why should Amazigh people accept to study Arabic? Kabyle 10 stated that Tamazight should be compulsory to preserve unity and to avoid riots and strikes.

Some participants (n2) from the Kabyle context refused to link Islam (religion) to a language. Kabyle 2 and Kabyle 10 reported that Muslim nations such as Indonesia function in their language (Indonesian), which is not Arabic. Kabyle 2 stated that Arabic is not a scale for measuring the understanding of religion, while Kabyle 10 highlighted some Quranic verses that explain the necessity to use the nation's tongue to explain the Quran to them. The surah of Ibrahim verse [14:4] reads as follows “We sent not a messenger except (to teach) in the language of his (own) people, in order to make (things) clear to them”. He also reported through another Quranic verse the surah of The Romans, verse [30:22] that “God created people of different races and tongues as a sign of His supremacy and creation” (El Aissati, 2005). Therefore, Islam's perspective on diversity and multilingualism is favourable in contrast to the post-independence language policies, which aim to establish a homogeneous nation under the same language, culture, and religion (El Aissati, 2005).

Figure 9: Thematic Network of the Language Policy and Politics in Algeria

The Amazigh feel marginalised and excluded from the government because of the Arabisation policy, which was seen as a threat to their culture and their language (Prah, 2002). Chaoui 5 lived and worked in the Kabyle setting for years, and he indicated that the linguistic richness of the country is beneficial for speakers. He reported that Algeria is used to monism (One party, one newspaper, one language, one religion etc.). For that reason, people need to learn

how to accept each other and accept plurality in languages, cultures, and practices: accepting plurality and diversity will decrease tensions and increase tolerance. Chaoui 5 highlighted the importance of learning from the previous experience with colonialism. He indicated that denying a language of a particular group of people would make them more attached to that language and therefore more defensive and aggressive in relation to acknowledging their marginalised languages.

9.5 Conclusion

This chapter examined the educational language policy in Algeria as perceived by Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle), focusing on their implementation of these policies within the classroom setting. The fourth research question, which is “How do Berber teachers in the Kabyle and Chaoui contexts engage with the political rhetoric and national policy on language use in education?” was discussed in the chapter of this study. The chapter started by examining the level of teachers' familiarity with the educational language policy in Algeria. It revealed that participants demonstrated hesitation to openly express their viewpoints on language policy due to its intersection with politics, which was perceived as a sensitive matter. The results of the study revealed that the participants possess knowledge regarding the official languages utilised in educational settings. Arabic is commonly employed as the medium of instruction in educational settings, while French serves as the language of instruction in universities, particularly in scientific disciplines. As reported by the participants, the constitution provides the sole written source of language policy in education. They indicated that there are no written documents specifically addressing language utilisation within the classroom.

Moreover, the study highlighted ambiguity on the level of language policy in education particularly regarding the individuals responsible for issuing the language policy, and the process of issuing it. In other words, the findings revealed the absence of guidance regarding the implementation of the language policy within the classroom. The study revealed that inspectors visit schools either annually or biennially for inspections. It was noted that some inspectors insist on the implementation of a monolingual policy that entails the use of Arabic as a medium of instruction in the classroom across all subjects, except for French and English, where teachers are required to exclusively use French or English as the language of instruction

within the classroom. In contrast, other inspectors pay less attention to language practice in the classroom and focus more on the content of the lesson.

The participants indicated that despite the insistence of many inspectors on the utilisation of Arabic as the language of instruction in the classroom, most of the participants declared the presence and inevitability of practising translanguaging in the classroom. The teachers' rationale for not adhering to the language policy, which mandates the incorporation of Arabic as a language of instruction, was that they know better what is needed in the classroom.

The chapter also unveiled conflicting opinions between supporting and disapproving of the monolingual policy of Arabisation in education and the Frenchification of higher education in Algeria. The participants exhibited distinct opinions regarding their support or opposition to the Arabisation policy in the field of education. Furthermore, they expressed opposition to the transition from Arabic to French at the level of the university. They viewed this shift from Arabic to French as the medium of instruction at the university level as a contradiction that impacts the academic performance of students.

Finally, this chapter discussed the existence of tensions and conflicts among the various groups in Algeria (Arabs and Amazigh) caused by the language policy implemented by the government. According to some participants, the government pursued a divisive policy that failed to take into consideration the sociolinguistic situation in Algeria.

Chapter Ten

Conclusion

10.1 Introduction

In this concluding chapter, the researcher systematically addresses several key elements that summarise the key findings of our investigation. It starts with a comprehensive overview of the main findings, addressing each of the four research questions that guided this research. Subsequently, the chapter highlights the implications of the study's findings. This critical examination extends beyond the immediate scope of the research, exploring the broader impact and relevance of the study. It explains how the insights provided in this research contribute to existing knowledge and identify potential implications for educational practices, policy considerations, and further research endeavours. The chapter also elucidates the contribution of this study. The chapter highlights the limitations, which recognise the constraints, shortcomings and the scope of this research, in addition to the recommendations, which are adjusted to inform educators, policymakers, and researchers, guiding them in areas where our findings suggest potential enhancements, adjustments, or future investigations. Finally, this chapter incorporates a personal touch as I engaged in autobiographical reflections that shaped the course of my study.

10.2 Summary of the main findings

10.2.1 *Research Question 1*

What languages make up the linguistic repertoires of Algerian secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle)? How do Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) use their linguistic repertoires in different fields?

In response to the first research question, the findings indicated that teachers' linguistic repertoires in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) of Algeria are comprised of numerous languages, including Arabic, Tamazight, French, Derja, and English, as well as other languages declared by few participants, such as Turkish, Spanish, and German, which are limited to certain repertoires. Therefore, the study reported that teachers' linguistic repertoires are composed of four main languages as indicated above. However, it also highlighted variations in the competency level in these languages among participants from the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts. In addition, the study identified differences in the learning or acquisition processes across the two contexts.

Teachers' proficiency level in Derja and Arabic seems to be higher in the Chaoui context than in the Kabyle one, while the proficiency level in Tamazight and French is higher in the Kabyle context. Exposure to the language and the cultural background can have an impact on proficiency levels in both contexts. The findings revealed that that Chaoui participants are more exposed to Derja, which is their common language apart from rural areas. The shift from Tamazight to Derja, as many participants indicated that they use Derja in day-to-day interactions, makes participants more exposed to Derja too. The study also revealed an attachment to Arabic among Chaoui participants, which empowered their efforts to preserve and develop their proficiency level in that language. On the other hand, teachers in the Kabyle context are more exposed to Tamazight and French, which are perceived as the mother language and a part of the identity. The positive attitudes towards Tamazight and French and their connection to identity in the Kabyle context resulted in high proficiency levels in these languages.

The findings indicated that the languages included in teachers' linguistic repertoires are acquired or learned through the milieu, education, reading, television, social media, and technological devices. Participants mainly acquired Derja, Tamazight, and French from their milieu or their social network, including family, Friends, and society. Arabic and English are learned through formal education (schools). Teachers were exposed to Arabic from primary, middle and then secondary schools or from mosques where they start learning the Quran; they also learned English in middle and secondary schools and at the university for those who opted for English as a discipline. French was acquired from the milieu as well as through formal education starting from primary school. The study also uncovered that the participants used social media, the internet, television, and technological devices to facilitate and improve the acquisition or learning of certain languages in their linguistic repertoires. The study, therefore, highlighted convertibility between the different forms of capital that participants have. In the process of acquiring and learning the embodied linguistic cultural capital that participants in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) possess they exchanged different forms of capital. The social capital, such as family, friends, and society, was converted into embodied cultural capital and resulted in languages including Derja, Tamazight, and French, while TV, social media, books, and technological devices are all tools, where economic capital was invested to be converted later to linguistic cultural capital such as French, English, and even

Arabic. Finally, schools are considered a source of cultural capital; parents may invest money (economic capital) to provide their children with books and the necessary tools for education to obtain different cultural capital including linguistic ones such as Arabic, French, and English.

The research unveiled two primary factors that influence and explain teachers' choice of language: social context and the interlocutor. Participants reported that their choices of language in a conversation are connected to the field in which the conversation is taking place. That is, the setting such as educational institutions, religious institutions, administrations, homes, streets, and the different regions in Algeria (Chaoui, Kabyle, North, South, East and West). The interlocutor such as family members, friends, acquaintances, and colleagues, in addition to the purpose of conversation (formal, informal, academic, professional, religious, or cultural). Concerning the setting or the field, the study revealed that teachers mainly allocate the Arabic language to education as it is the official formal language of education in the constitution, they also mix Derja and French when needed in informal situations, while French, English, German, or Spanish are mainly the languages utilised when they are the subject being taught (formal context). Participants also related Arabic to religious institutions and events. They indicated that they mix languages when they are home with family or with neighbours in informal casual settings. In the Chaoui context, the mix mainly includes Derja and French, while in the Kabyle context, it includes Tamazight and French reflecting the cultural practices of the region. Participants also related French to administrations as professional contexts in Algeria. Moreover, the study revealed a linguistic transition from Derja/French in the Chaoui context to Tamazight/French in the Kabyle context; from Derja in urban regions in the Chaoui context to Tamazight in rural areas within the Chaoui context. In addition, the study referred to different language practices based on geographical locality (north, south, east, and west).

The study also revealed that language practice (choice of languages) in a static multilingual context is also related to the interlocutor taking part in the conversation. Teachers referred to the language proficiency, and cultural identity of the interlocutor as factors that influence their language choice. Kabyle participants indicated that their common linguistic practice in the Kabyle context is the mix between Tamazight and French; however, when speaking with Arab people, who are not proficient in Tamazight, they switch to Derja and French for effective communication. The participants indicated linguistic accommodation by adjusting

their choice of languages according to the interlocutor's needs and cultural identity and background in order to establish an effective conversation. They also reported that when the interlocutor shares the same component of their linguistic repertoire their choice of language would be Tamazight and French, which reflect their cultural identity and affiliation. Chaoui participants also stated that they switch to Tamazight if they went to the Kabyle context where Tamazight is the common language. Switching from Derja to Tamazight in that case can be regarded as a way of showing membership to the group and therefore facilitating things for the speaker. The study also revealed a connection between the choice of language and power relations. Participants reported that French is perceived as a prestigious language that indicates high socio-economic status in Algeria. Therefore, some participants from the Chaoui context indicated that they would use French when conversating with doctors and professors, who are perceived to have prestigious professions in Algeria. That is, the study revealed that the educational level, the profession, and the socio-economic status of the interlocutor influence language choices. This is supported by Bourdieu (1991), who argues that within a particular linguistic market, languages are positioned in a hierarchical order. Individuals with varying levels of socioeconomic capital often face a decision between utilising their mother tongue, which serves as a marker of group identity, or adopting the language of the dominant market, which can lead to greater economic opportunities, power, and social status (Bourdieu, 1991)

Moreover, the study referred to the multilingual awareness of the participants. It indicated that Chaoui participants were unaware of their multilingualism as a result of disregarding some languages (Tamazight and Derja) from their linguistic repertoires and due to the collective representation or collective habitus in the Chaoui context. The Chaoui context is considered the second most populous group of Berbers following the Kabyle one in Algeria (Maddy-Weitzman, 2001). Although it is recognised as a Berber region; however, many studies documented a shift from Tamazight particularly the Chaoui dialect to Derja, which is perceived by participants as a variant of Arabic (Rouabah, 2020).

The Chaoui context was the first to cause significant trouble to the French military. It was “the centre of command of the Algerian revolution until independence” (Rouabah, 2020, p.134). Moreover, it was highly affected by the nationalist reforms of Ben Badi, which aimed to promote Arabisation as a way of unifying the country's population ignoring the fact that

Algeria is a culturally and linguistically diverse context. These historical events in the Chaoui context left their traces in a form of collective habitus where individuals identify themselves as Arab Muslims whose main language is Arabic the language of the Quran and religion disregarding Derja and Tamazight.

The study brought to light a correlation between rurality and perceived linguistic backwardness in the Chaoui context. The study findings revealed a link between Tamazight and rural areas among Chaoui participants where there is a lack of socio-economic factors such as healthcare, infrastructure, and economic opportunities. Associating Tamazight with rural areas, backwardness, and social stigma can be viewed as another factor for disregarding it. Some Chaoui participants also reported that they have been punished by parents for utilising Tamazight due to its perceived association with low intelligence.

On the other hand, although Kabyle participants disregarded some languages such as Derja, however, they were quite aware of being multilingual, which may be connected to their collective representation or collective habitus as Amazigh whose mother language is Tamazight, in addition to the French language, which is perceived as part of their culture. Arabic is the language learned through education and Derja is the language learned through contact with Arab provinces in Algeria.

The notion of social habitus entails the internalised dispositions that the individual possesses. These dispositions are shaped by the social structure. collective habitus, on the other hand, extends this idea to encompass communal dispositions and customs within a group or collective. The development of a collective habitus is shaped by various determinants, such as shared socialisation experiences, social structure, and cultural backgrounds (Bourdieu, 1990b; Jenkins, 2014; Swartz, 2012; Grenfell, 2014). Therefore, the collective representation or collective habitus among participants in the Berber region (Kabyle and Chaoui) plays a significant role in determining their awareness or lack of awareness of their multilingualism.

10.2.2 Research Question 2

What languages make up the linguistic repertoires of Algerian secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle)? How do Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) use their linguistic repertoires in different fields?

In relation to the second research question, which aimed to investigate the attitudes of Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) towards the languages included in their linguistic repertoires, the study revealed that teachers' attitudes and preferences are influenced by the different representations they have for the languages present in their repertoires. These linguistic representations such as the language of religion, the language of civilisation, the language of culture, the language of emotions, the language of identity, the language of prestige, and the language of colonialism, in addition to the fear of language loss, are accumulated historically through the lived experiences of teachers and became ingrained of their habitus. The above-indicated representations are approached differently in the Chaoui and the Kabyle context. The different collective habitus in the two contexts (Chaoui and Kabyle) affected the individual habitus of participants as well as their attitudes towards the languages included in their repertoires.

Attitudes towards the French among Chaoui participants were mostly negative. The association of French with colonialism engendered a feeling of hostility towards the language (French). French colonialism in Algeria aimed to eliminate the indigenous languages (Arabic, Tamazight, Derja) and impose French using violent tactics. These historical events generated feelings of hostility towards that language among participants and put a significant focus on Arabic and indigenous languages to claim the Algerian identity and distance themselves from the colonialist language. French was also viewed as a constraining language among Chaoui participants; however, it was perceived as a valuable and prestigious language in Algeria. The French colonialist sought to plant beliefs that French is a language of civilisation and prestige. Although the Algerian population resisted the colonialist's attempts during and after colonialism; however, the study revealed that the participants in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) perceive French as a prestigious language, which suggests that the traces of colonialism are still affecting perceptions towards French in Algeria.

On the other hand, the study revealed that Kabyle teachers' attitudes towards French are highly positive. Participants perceived French as a language of civilisation and prestige. The ability to speak French was viewed as an indicator of the individual's level of education and socio-economic status. The study indicated that French is perceived as an integral part of culture in the Kabyle context. French was also perceived as a language that broadens one's horizons in the Kabyle context. Regardless of the negative sentiments towards French in the

Chaoui context, proficiency in French was regarded as a beneficial cultural capital in the realms of academia, career advancement, and engagement with global opportunities.

The research findings indicated positive attitudes towards Arabic in the Chaoui context. Participants associated Arabic with the Holy Quran and religion; therefore, it had a favourable and valuable status for them. Many participants also viewed Arabic as a means for expressing their identity and disconnecting from their colonial past. Despite the significant perceived importance of Arabic among Chaoui participants, many noted that it is not commonly utilised in their daily interactions. The scope of its application is restricted to specific domains such as education and places of worship such as mosques.

Although Kabyle participants showed acceptance of Arabic, they did not show attachment to it as shown among Chaoui participants. It was viewed as a foreign language, that is learned at schools.

The findings also displayed positive attitudes toward English. Berber teachers' attitudes towards English were highly favourable. They perceived English as a global language of communication, science, and technology. Participants reported that English holds a significant role in scientific research and academic publications globally. Moreover, proficiency in English broadens and expands international opportunities in the modern world, as it is viewed as a pathway to scholarships and prestigious job opportunities abroad.

Attitudes towards Tamazight in the Chaoui context were mostly negative, while they were positive in the Kabyle context. The findings revealed that Chaoui participants acknowledge that they are originally Amazigh; however, they self-identify as Arabs. They described Tamazight as a dialect that lacks the necessary features to be a language. It was described as a primitive dialect that does not have a unifying writing system to date. The participants also reported that Tamazight is a limited language in terms of vocabulary and terms of geographical scope. Therefore, it was described as a limited and limiting language. Negative attitudes in the Chaoui context may originate from the historical marginalisation of Tamazight during and after colonialism in Algeria. The language policy in Algeria, which promotes Arabic as the national and official language of prestige, has resulted in the establishment of linguistic hierarchies. This may lead to a less sophisticated picture of Tamazight and consequently, engender negative attitudes towards it. Moreover, the stigma attached to Tamazight as a limited language in rural areas and an indicator of low intelligence can contribute to negative

perceptions. Additionally, despite the national and official recognition of Tamazight in the constitution, the lack of support and resources to actualise the language policy and integrate Tamazight in the different fields of power hinders its promotion and thereby can generate negative attitudes towards the language. On the other hand, the research findings suggest that although Kabyle participants expressed gratitude and a sense of pride in their Amazigh heritage, as well as in their proficiency in Tamazight as a mother language, they also conveyed the notion that Tamazight is not a language that is conducive to scientific discourse. Rather, the acquisition of Tamazight is perceived to serve exclusively cultural and identity-related objectives and to prevent language shift and loss.

Derja was perceived as a mixture of languages (Arabic, Tamazight, and French) or as a variant of Arabic. It was perceived as the primary code of day-to-day communication. The language utilised in casual or informal settings such as homes, and markets, and allows smooth interactions among Algerians. Given its status as the predominant mode of daily communication and its profound entrenchment within the cultural and social framework of the nation, it can be argued that this language holds significant importance.

Algerian vernacular is a form of language that is commonly utilised in casual environments, including households, marketplaces, and communal events, facilitating unforced and spontaneous communication among Algerian individuals.

The findings presented in this study suggest that the attitudes of Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) towards the languages present in their linguistic repertoires are diverse, ranging from positive to negative. However, they all share a common belief in the significance and advantages of possessing multilingual repertoires, a viewpoint that is also supported by Belmihoub (2018) research, where participants displayed positive attitudes towards multilingualism in Algeria.

10.2.3 Research Question 3

What are the Algerian Berber teachers' perceptions about their linguistic repertoires in relation to the complexities of language and power?

In answer to the third research question, the findings of this study indicated that language is valued differently in different domains of power among Berber teachers (Chaoui and the Kabyle). Many fields of power such as education, administration, local and international fields,

and many other geographical divisions were referred to by participants to demonstrate the perceived value of languages in their repertoires. These indicated fields of power are factors that influence both language practice and language value according to participants.

French was perceived as a language of high prestige and symbolic power in the administrative sectors of Algeria. It was viewed as the most valuable language in that field. English was regarded as the most valuable language on a global scale, while less valuable within the Algerian context. Conversely, French, despite being considered a more limited language in terms of global significance when compared to English, holds a prominent status within the Algerian context. The linguistic value of languages is also reported to be subject to geographical divisions in Algeria such as North, South, East, and West. That means that Arabic, which is perceived as valuable in the South according to participants might be less valued in the north of the country as French holds a more valued position. The Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts were also highlighted as two fields that influence language perceived value in Algeria. Tamazight and French were perceived to have more value compared to other languages (Arabic and Derja) in the Kabyle context. In contrast, Derja and Arabic are viewed as more valuable in the Chaoui context. The study revealed that Arabic is the most valued language in education as it is considered the official language of instruction from primary to secondary cycle. However, French is perceived to be the most valuable language in higher education as it serves as a medium of instruction for scientific streams, which are viewed as major disciplines that grant students prestigious and well-paid job opportunities in the future. French was also perceived as a valuable language in the Algerian context as it is indicating a high socio-economic status according to participants. The monolingual policies, such as Arabization and Frenchification, in the fields of education and higher education, were perceived by participants as reinforcing educational inequalities and social reproduction.

To summarise, this study assessed the perceived value of language in the Algerian context in relation to many sectors of power. This is in line with Bourdieu's theoretical framework where he referred to the concept of a 'field of power' or a 'market' to refer to a structured space where distinct positions are formed in dependence on the various types of capital possessed in that field (Bourdieu, 1991). That is, the findings indicated that in the different markets, participants encounter, each language in their repertoires is treated as a product, and it is assigned a value based on its specific characteristics. The respondents valued the languages

in their repertoires according to the linguistic capital that is required the most in each of the following domains: education, administrations, politics, media, science, south, east, west, and north, Chaoui and Kabyle contexts, local and international, in addition to social-economic status.

10.2.4 Research Question 4

How do Berber teachers in the Kabyle and Chaoui contexts engage with the political rhetoric and national policy on language use in education?

Regarding the fourth research question, the finding of the study showed that participants were hesitant to openly discuss language policy in education because of its political implications, which were perceived as a sensitive topic. The study found that the participants have knowledge concerning the official educational languages: Arabic as a language of instruction in education (primary to secondary schools), and French as a language of instruction in universities, particularly in scientific streams. However, the study also sheds light on the ambiguity that exists on the level of language policy in education, specifically regarding individuals who are responsible for issuing the language policy, and the procedure that is used to issue it. The findings, to put it another way, indicated that there was no direction about the execution of the language policy within the classroom. The participants reported that apart from the constitution, there are no written documents specifically addressing language utilisation within the classroom.

The study found that inspectors inspect schools annually or biennially. During inspections, some inspectors require the use of Arabic as a medium of instruction in all subjects, except for French and English, where teachers must use French or English, while other inspectors prioritise course content over classroom language practice. Despite many inspectors' insistence on Arabic as the language of instruction in the classroom according to respondents, most participants indicated that translanguaging was present and inevitable. The participants' reason for not following the language policy, which requires the use of Arabic as a language of instruction, was that they know what was best for the classroom.

As a conclusion, the illustrated tensions and conflicts between different groups in Algeria (Arabs and Amazigh), according to participants in this study, are generated by the linguistic policy that the government has enacted. Some participants reported that the Algerian

government has been pursuing a divisive policy that does not consider the sociolinguistic situation in Algeria.

10.3 Implications of the study's findings

Investigating teachers' linguistic repertoires in the Algerian Berber region particularly the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts can have several implications. First, the linguistic repertoires of Berber Algerian teachers have a significant influence on the way they conduct their classroom practices and implement instructional strategies. The examination of these repertoires facilitates a deeper comprehension of how teachers incorporate native languages into their instructional practices. Secondly, the examination of teachers' linguistic repertoires in Algerian Berber contexts (Chaoui and Kabyle) can provide valuable insights for language policy and planning objectives. This study offers valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to consider the linguistic resources available within the classroom and design policies that support the promotion and integration of native languages (Derja and Tamazight) in the educational system.

Third, the investigation of teachers' linguistic repertoires offers significant data for sociolinguistic research and language documentation. This study enhances the comprehension of language dynamics, language practice, and language attitudes within the Algerian Berber contexts. Fourth, this study also has the potential to contribute to the documentation of endangered or marginalised native languages in the Algerian context from Berber teachers' (Chaoui and Kabyle) perspectives. Next, the study explored ambiguity on the level of educational language policies, the absence of any documentation (apart from the constitution) or instruction regarding the implementation of the language policy in the classroom, and the lack of inclusivity of the language policy in education. Highlighting these issues might provide insight for policymakers to reconsider their policies.

Fifth, the study also identified notable contradictions between the sector of education and higher education regarding language policy. The study also offers insights to policymakers to reconsider these policies, which are reported by participants in this study as contributing factors for students' struggles and failure in the scientific disciplines. Finally, one of the key issues identified in this study is the absence of effective communication between policymakers, who hold theoretical positions, and teachers, who are responsible for the

practical implementation of language policy in education. The study revealed a lack of correlation between these two entities in terms of feedback provision. Therefore, this study can raise awareness about the importance of the correlation between teachers and policymakers.

10.4 Contribution

This study contributes to the literature by presenting an exploration of the linguistic repertoires of Berber teachers particularly from the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts, which are unique among Berbers in that they played a significant role in pivotal events throughout the history of Algeria, and where sentiments remain strong about language as a marker of identity, religion, culture, and power. The study provides insights of how teachers possessed their linguistic repertoires and how they utilise it in various domains of power including their field of profession, which is education.

Furthermore, the study adds understanding regarding the attitudes of Berber teachers (Chaoui and Kabyle) toward the languages included in their repertoires by tracing their personal experiences and exploring how these attitudes were shaped. The study sheds light on post-colonial nationalism and its influence on language policies, which in turn shape teachers' perceptions, attitudes, and language use within their repertoires. By examining how the historical inheritance of colonialism intersects with contemporary language policies, the research unveils the complexities inherent in teachers' language practices and attitudes.

The classroom environment can be impacted by teachers' attitudes toward languages, which can also affect students' motivation and engagement. Therefore, the study's contribution highlights the necessity to embrace linguistic diversity and encourage a more inclusive environment where students freely communicate and share their thoughts and ideas in their mother tongues. This can be established by promoting positive attitudes among teachers and students towards the languages included in their repertoires.

The study also makes a significant contribution to the literature as it raises awareness of the contradictions within language policies in both education and higher education sectors, highlighting their detrimental effects on student outcomes. By shedding light on these discrepancies, the study stresses the urgency for policy reforms to better align with educational objectives and student needs.

Additionally, the research uncovers a significant gap between language policymakers, who often adopt a theoretical stance, and teachers, who navigate the practical realities of the classroom. This emphasizes the importance of bridging this gap to ensure that language policies resonate with and reflect teachers' experiences and perspectives. The study highlights that the lack of communication between policy makers and teachers results in a mismatch between policy objectives and classroom practices. This stresses the necessity for greater collaboration and dialogue between stakeholders to create policies that are feasible and effective for the educational context.

Finally, the research raises awareness of the tensions existing between different ethnic groups in Algeria due to the government's monolingual policies. By highlighting these tensions, the study advocates for more inclusive language policies that recognize and celebrate linguistic diversity, fostering social cohesion and unity within the Algerian society.

10.5 Limitations

While investigating teachers' linguistic repertoires in Algerian Berber contexts provides valuable insights, due to time and structural constraints it is important to address the limitations of this study, which can establish potential paths for future research. While efforts were made to ensure the sample was diverse in terms of age, gender, experience, and the subject taught, the sample size was not large enough to generalise the findings to the broader population of Algerian teachers. The focus was to gain an in-depth understanding of the linguistic repertoires of Algerian teachers in the Berber region particularly the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts.

The focus of the study was exclusively narrowed to the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts (the first and the second largest groups of Berbers in Algeria), which may not fully reflect the linguistic and cultural diversity within the broader Berber communities in Algeria, while the Chaoui and Kabyle contexts are significant in terms of their cultural heritage and linguistic distinctiveness, there are other Berber settings in Algeria, such as the Mozabite or Tuareg, that have their own unique linguistic and cultural characteristics. This is a limitation of a study that is conducted by a single researcher. Secondly, inadequate financial resources and time constraints would not support a full-scale study of Algerian teachers in all Berber regions or the whole country.

Another limitation of this research is the exclusive focus on teachers as participants, without including other key stakeholders or policymakers within the educational system. Teachers play a crucial role in influencing language policies and practices within the Berber context (Chaoui and Kabyle) as they are responsible for applying these policies and potential providers of feedback regarding the issued policies. However, it is important to acknowledge the involvement of other significant stakeholders such as policymakers, administrators, parents, and community members, who are also contributors to the dynamics of language in Algerian education.

The focus of the study is on studying solely the macro sociolinguistic understanding of Berber teachers' linguistic repertoires. The micro-linguistic aspects of languages such as phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics are not discussed in this research.

10.6 Recommendations

Investigating the linguistic repertoires and language practice in relation to the language policy in education from the perspectives of different stakeholders such as policymakers, inspectors, students, and even parents would add valuable insights to the literature. The inclusion of diverse perspectives and experiences can contribute to a more holistic comprehension of the language policies and practices within the Algerian educational system.

Future research should also consider integrating other Berber settings such as the Mozabite and Tuareg in Algeria. The inclusion of other Berber settings would provide a holistic comprehension of the linguistic, cultural, and educational dynamics within the Berber community.

While the study did not initially focus on gender issues, considering that the use of gender lens could enhance the depth of the analysis regarding language use and attitudes. Therefore, this study recommends conducting a supplementary analysis through a gender perspective to explore potential differences in language experiences and attitudes between genders. Incorporating linguistic anthropological concepts, such as language ideologies, indexicality, and figures of personhood, in analysing the linguistic repertoires would enhance the study through uncovering deeper insights into how language shapes and is shaped by social structures, identities, and power dynamics. Such a theoretical lens can offer a rich framework

for exploring the multifaceted nature of language practices and language attitudes of individuals and communities.

10.7 Autobiographical reflections

Reflecting on my personal experience as an Algerian student, who was granted a scholarship to pursue a Ph.D. in the United Kingdom, I am filled with immense feelings of gratitude, growth, and cultural enrichment. The journey has been transformative in numerous ways, both academically and personally.

In 2016 I came to the United Kingdom for the first time to pursue a pre-sessional programme that took place at Canterbury Christ Church University for six months. The initial fear of leaving behind the familiarity of my home country and diving into the unknown was apparent. It evoked feelings of fear, uncertainty, excitement, and curiosity. Being far from home and adjusting to a new cultural, social, and academic environment was challenging and enriching. These six months were a significant turning point in my journey of personal and academic transformation. It marked the beginning of a profound shift in my mindset and preparedness for the academic challenges that awaited me in the UK.

In 2017 I started my PhD at the University of the West of Scotland. In Algeria, the educational system largely relies on traditional teacher-centred approaches, where students play a passive role in the learning process. The emphasis is often placed on memorization and adherence to prescribed curriculum guidelines. Although this system may have its qualities, it imposes constraints on students' opportunities to engage in critical thinking, creativity, and independent exploration. Therefore, it was challenging for me as a Ph.D. student in the United Kingdom to construct my own learning trajectory. I struggled very much to adapt to the autonomous approach of learning and researching. It took me six months to decide the topic of my research, which was influenced by my personal experience as a multilingual person, who belongs to the Chaoui context in Algeria. I was born in a family where multilingualism is the norm. My parents, like many Algerian families in the Chaoui setting, spoke multiple languages, including Tamazight (Chaoui dialect), Derja, French, and Arabic. It was interesting to think about language practice among my family members and within society. How they shift from one language to another or mix languages depending on the context or interlocutor is a skill that connects people from diverse linguistic backgrounds and adapts to different social settings. This laid the foundation for my passion to investigate teachers' linguistic

repertoires in the Berber region particularly the Chaoui and the Kabyle contexts in Algeria. This topic links my personal experience as a multilingual person in the Chaoui context with my academic and career pursuits.

Among the challenges I faced during my PhD journey was the fear and hesitation of participants to sign the consent forms. This fear might stem from various factors, such as cultural norms, mistrust of research processes, or concerns about privacy and confidentiality. The topic of my research was perceived by some participants as a sensitive topic that intersects with politics; therefore, recruiting participants was very challenging. Another challenge I faced as a researcher was trying to schedule interviews with teachers, who were occupied with correcting examination papers for the baccalaureate exam. The period of correcting examination papers is undoubtedly a demanding and time-consuming task for teachers. Therefore, to address this challenge, I employed a snowball sampling technique, where participants were recruited through existing contacts or referrals. This approach helped to make participants more willing to engage in the research process. I also ensured transparency and clear communication with potential participants. I provided detailed explanations about the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality measures, that were in accordance with the University's Ethical code. These experiences deepened my understanding of ethical research practices as a researcher and have reinforced the significance of informed consent, confidentiality, and participant well-being in conducting research that respects and protects the rights of participants.

In addition to these academic challenges that I faced, I also faced personal challenges that added bitterness to my Ph.D. journey. In 2018, I faced the profound loss of my father. The passing of my father, the pillar of support and the source of inspiration in my life, left an indelible void. It was a profound loss that shook the foundations of my world and cast shadows on my experience. Coping with grief while pursuing a Ph.D. required immense strength and resilience. In 2019, I received news of my mother's breast cancer diagnosis, which was a pivotal moment in my life. It was a time filled with mixed emotions, challenges, and profound personal growth. My mother's diagnosis came as a shock, and it shifted my priorities. Being there for her during this challenging time was essential; therefore, I interrupted my studies for one year to be by her side. Being by my mother's side throughout her breast cancer journey was an experience that forever changed me. It was a time filled

with emotional ups and downs, moments of fear and uncertainty, but also moments of hope, and courage.

In conclusion, my journey as an Algerian student pursuing a PhD in the UK has been a complex experience full of moments of joy and sorrow that served as a catalyst for personal and academic growth and discovery. It gradually developed my skills and my confidence, shaped my perspectives, and expanded my horizons.

References

- Abdelhamid, S. (2002) *Pour une approche sociolinguistique de l'apprentissage de la prononciation du français langue étrangère chez les étudiants du département de français université de Batna* [For a sociolinguistic approach of learning pronunciation of French as a foreign language among the students the French department of the University of Batna] PhD thesis. University of El Hadj Lakhdar, Batna.
- Achy, L. (2013) 'The price of stability in Algeria', *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, 25. https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/164642/CMEC_37_price_stability_algeria.pdf
- Adder, F. Z., and Bagui, H. (2020) 'English-Algerian Arabic code-switching in EFL classroom: case of EFL teachers and students in the department of English at Tlemcen University, Algeria', *Arab World English Journal*, 11(4), 144–162.
<https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol11no4.10>
- Al-Nahass, Z. (2009) 'Ibn Badis's Concept of Arabism and Islam (1889-1940)', *Adab Al-Rafidayn*, 39(53), pp.279-296.
- Angelo, D. and Carter, N. (2015) 'Schooling within shifting landscapes: educational responses in complex Indigenous language contact ecologies', *Multilingualism and Language in Education: Current Sociolinguistic and Pedagogical Perspectives from Commonwealth Countries*. Cambridge: CUP.
- Agnihotri, R.K. (2009) 'Multilinguality and a new world order', in Mohanty, A.K., Panda, M., Phillipson, R. and Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (eds.) *Multilingual education for social justice: Globalizing the local*. New Delhi, India: Orient Blackswan, pp. 268-277.
- Ajjawi, R. and Higgs, J. (2007) 'Using hermeneutic phenomenology to investigate how experienced practitioners learn to communicate clinical reasoning', *The Qualitative Report*, 12 (4), pp.612-638. <file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/ajjawi-usinghermeneutic-2007.pdf>
- Al Riyami, T. (2015) 'Main approaches to educational research', *International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Sciences*, 2(5), pp.412-416.
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Thuraya-Al-Riyami/publication/283071843_Main_Approaches_to_Educational_Research/links/5628a82d08ae518e347c5ee3/Main-Approaches-to-Educational-Research.pdf

- Angen, M. J. (2000) 'Evaluating interpretive inquiry: reviewing the validity debate and opening the dialogue', *Qualitative Health Research*, 10 (3), pp.378–395.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/104973230001000308>
- Angrosino, M. V. (2007) *doing ethnographic and observational research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Assous, O. (1985) *Arabization and Cultural Conflicts in Algeria*. PhD thesis, Northeastern University, Boston, MA. Available at:
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/5c9e2163c7f3225c07e946d494be661e/1?pq-origsite=gscholarandcbl=18750anddiss=y> (Accessed: 30 July 2023).
- Attride-Stirling, J. (2001) 'Thematic networks: an analytic tool for qualitative research', *Qualitative Research*, 1(3), pp.385-405.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/146879410100100307>
- Azaola, M.C. (2012) 'Revisiting Bourdieu: alternative educational systems in the light of the theory of social and cultural reproduction', *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, 22(2), pp.81-95.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09620214.2012.700187>
- Bagui, H. (2014) 'Aspects of Diglossic Code Switching Situations: A Sociolinguistic International', *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 2(4), pp. 86-92.
<http://www.idpublications.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/ASPECTS-OF-DIGLOSSIC-CODE-SWITCHING-SITUATIONS-A-SOCIOLINGUISTIC-INTERPRETATION.pdf>
- Baker, C. (1988) *Key issues in bilingualism and bilingual education*. Philadelphia: Multilingual matters.
- Baker, C. (2003) 'Education as a site of language contact', *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 23, pp. 95–112. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/annual-review-of-applied-linguistics/article/abs/6-education-as-a-site-of-language-contact/BB40AC671EBFB41A14113359E09DB3C0>
- Baker, T.L. (1994) *Doing Social research*. 2nded. New York: McGraw-Hill Inc.
- Baldauf, R.B. (1994) 'Unplanned language policy and planning', *Annual review of applied linguistics*, 14, pp. 82-89. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/14984927.pdf>
- Bamgboṣe, A. (2000) *Language and exclusion: the consequences of language policies in Africa*. Hamburg-London: LIT Verlag Münster.

- Barakos, E. and Selleck, C. (2019) 'Elite multilingualism: Discourses, practices, and debates', *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 40(5), pp.361-374. [https://publications.aston.ac.uk/id/eprint/37956/1/Final version of Introduction .pdf](https://publications.aston.ac.uk/id/eprint/37956/1/Final%20version%20of%20Introduction.pdf)
- Barber, C.G. (1952) *Trilingualism in Pascua: the social functions of language in an Arizona Yaqui village*. Master thesis. The University of Arizona. Available at: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=6e3af47d81d98382dc5845805a62054773e4a82a> (Accessed: 01 August 2023).
- Bassetti, B. and Cook, V. (2011) 'Relating language and cognition: The second language user', in B. Bassetti and V. Cook (ed.) *Language and bilingual cognition*. New York: Psychology Press, pp. 157-204. <https://shorturl.at/jTUX6>
- Baxter, P. and Jack, S. (2008) 'Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers', *The qualitative report*, 13 (4), pp.544-559. <https://shorturl.at/gJTZO>
- Becker, A. and Knoll, A. (2022) 'Establishing multiple languages in early childhood. Heritage languages and language hierarchies in German-English daycare centers in Switzerland', *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 25(7), pp.2561-2572. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/13670050.2021.1932719>
- Bektache, M. (2009) 'Contact de langues: entre compétition des langues et enjeux interculturels à l'université de Béjaia', *Synergies Algérie*, 8, pp.91-105. <http://gerflint.fr/Base/Algerie8/bektache.pdf>
- Belmihoub, K. (2018) 'Language attitudes in Algeria', *Language Problems and Language Planning*, 42(2), pp.144-172. https://academicworks.cuny.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2116&context=bb_pubs
- Benchehida, M. (2001) 'La problématique des langues en Algérie: historique, situation et conséquences', *Horizons Philosophiques*, 12(1), pp.125-135. <https://www.erudit.org/en/journals/hphi/1900-v1-n1-hphi3193/801198ar/abstract/>
- Bennoune, M. (2000) Education, Culture et Développement en Algérie: Bilan et Perspectives du Systeme Educatif [Education, Culture and Development in Algeria: Assessment and Perspectives for the Educational System]. Algiers: Marinoor-ENAG.
- Benrabah, M. (2001) 'Language and modernity in Algeria', *Identity, Culture and Globalization*, 10(1-2), pp. 235-242. https://brill.com/display/book/edcoll/9789004475618/B9789004475618_s017.xml

- Benrabah, M. (2004) 'Language and politics in Algeria', *Nationalism and ethnic politics*, 10(1), pp. 59-78.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13537110490450773>
- Benrabah, M. (2005) 'The language planning situation in Algeria', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 6(4), pp.379-502.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14664208.2005.10807312>
- Benrabah, M. (2007a) 'Language maintenance and spread: French in Algeria', *International Journal of Francophone Studies*, 10(1-2), pp.193-215.
<https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/intellect/ijfs/2007/00000010/F0020001/art00012>
- Benrabah, M. (2007b) 'Language-in-education planning in Algeria: historical development and current issues', *Language Policy*, 6(2), pp.225–252.
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10993-007-9046-7>
- Benrabah, M. (2013) *Language conflict in Algeria: from Colonialism to Post-Independence*. Bristol: Multilingual matters.
- Benrabah, M. (2014a) 'Competition between four "world" languages in Algeria', *Journal of World Languages*, 1(1), pp.38-59.
<https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1080/21698252.2014.893676/html>
- Benrabah, M. (2014b) 'Language and politics in Algeria', in W. Safran and J. Laponce (eds.) *Language, Ethnic Identity and the State*. London: Routledge, pp. 59-78.
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&andq=Benrabah%2C+M.+%282004%29+%E2%80%98Language+and+politics+in+Algeria%E2%80%99%2C+andbtnG=>
- Bentahar, Z. (2021) "'Ytnahaw ga'!": Algeria's Cultural Revolution and the Role of Language in the Early Stages of the Spring 2019 Hirak', *Journal of African Cultural Studies*, 33(4), pp.471-488.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13696815.2020.1788517?scroll=top&needAccess=true>
- Bentahila, A. (1983) 'Motivations for code-switching among Arabic-French bilinguals in Morocco', *Language and Communication*, 3(3), pp. 233-243. <https://shorturl.at/ejzJX>
- Berger, A.E. (ed.) (2002) *Algeria in others' languages*. London: Cornell University Press.

- Bernstein, B. (1964) 'Elaborated and restricted codes: their social origins and some consequences', *American Anthropologist*, 66 (6_PART2), pp.55-69.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/668161>
- Berrabah, B. (2013) 'Post-independence Algerian linguistic policy', *Research Journal in Organizational Psychology and Educational Studies*, 2(5), pp. 271-275.
<https://shorturl.at/AFLX5>
- Berthele, R. (2021) 'The selective celebration of linguistic diversity: Evidence from the Swiss language policy discourse', *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 42(2), pp.125-136. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/01434632.2020.1715989>
- Bhat, M.A. (2017) *The changing language roles and linguistic identities of the Kashmiri speech community*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Block, D. (2017) 'What on earth is 'language commodification'?', in S. Breidbach, L. Küster and B. Schmenk (Eds.), *Slogonizations in language education discourse*. Bristol: Multilingual Matters, pp.121-141.
- Blom, J. P. and Gumperz, J. (1972) 'Social meaning in linguistic structures: Code switching in Northern Norway', in Gumperz, J. J. and Hymes, D. (eds.) *Directions in Sociolinguistics: The Ethnography of Communication*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Blom, J.P. and Gumperz, J.J. (2000) 'Social meaning in linguistic structure: Code-switching in Norway', in Wei, L. (ed.) *The bilingualism reader*, pp.111-136.
- Blommaert, J. (2010) *The sociolinguistics of globalization*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Bogdewic, S. P. (1999) 'Participant observation', in Crabtree, B.F. and Miller, W. (eds.) *Doing qualitative research*. London: Sage Publications, pp.47-70. 2nded.
- Bond, M. H., and Lai, T. M. (2001) 'Embarrassment and code-switching in a second language', *Journal of Social Psychology*, 126(2), pp. 179–86.
- Bouherar, S. and Ghafsi, A. (2021) *Algerian Languages in Education*. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.
- Boukhchem, K., Varro. (2001) 'Reviewed work: langue et pouvoir en Algérie', *Histoire d'un traumatisme linguistique by Mohamed Benrabah*, *Cahiers D'études Africaines*, 41(163/164), pp. 836–839. Available: www.jstor.org/stable/4393173 (Accessed: 18 April 2018)
- Bourdieu, P. (1977a) *Outline of a Theory of Practice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University.

- Bourdieu, P. (1977b) 'The economics of linguistic exchanges', *Social Science Information*, 16(6), pp.645-668.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/053901847701600601>
- Bourdieu, P (1980) 'The production of belief: contributing to an economy of symbolic goods', *Media, culture and society*, 2(3), pp.261-293.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/016344378000200305>
- Bourdieu, P. (1982) *Ce que parler veut dire*. Paris: Fayard.
- Bourdieu, P. (1984) *Distinction: A social critique of the judgment of taste*. Translated by R. Nice. London: Routledge.
- Bourdieu, P. (1986) 'The Forms of Capital', in Richardson, J. (ed.) *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education*. Westport, CT: Greenwood, pp. 241-258.
- Bourdieu, P. (1988) *Homo academicus*. Translated by P. Collier. California: Stanford University Press.
- Bourdieu, P. (1990a) *In other words: Essays towards a reflexive sociology*. Translated by M. Adamson. California: Stanford University Press.
- Bourdieu, P. (1990b) *The logic of practice*. Translated by R. Nice. California: Stanford university press.
- Bourdieu, P. (1991) *Language and symbolic power*. Great Britain: Polity Press.
- Bourdieu, P. (1992) *Language and Symbolic Power*. Translated by G. Raymond and M. Adamson. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Bourdieu, P. (1993) *Sociology in question*. Translated by R. Nice. London: Sage.
- Bourdieu, P. (1998) *On Television and Journalism*. Translated by P. Ferguson. London: Pluto Press.
- Bourdieu, P. (2005) *The social structures of the economy*. Translated by C. Turner. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Bourdieu, P. (2012) 'Structures, habitus, practices (1994)', in C. Calhoun et all (ed.) *Contemporary sociological theory*. United Kingdom: Jhon Wiley and Sons, pp.335-358.
- Bourdieu, P. (2018) 'Cultural reproduction and social reproduction', in R. Brown (ed.) *Knowledge, education, and cultural change*. London: Routledge, pp. 71-112.
- Bourdieu P, Passeron J-C. (1977) *Reproduction in Education, Society, and Culture*. Beverly Hills: Sage.

- Bourdieu, P. and Wacquant, L.J. (1992) *An invitation to reflexive sociology*. Great Britain: Polity Press.
- Bourdieu, P., Darbel, A., Rivet, J.P. and Seibel, C. (1963) *Travail et travailleurs en Algérie*. Paris and The Hague: Mouton.
- Bourdieu, P. and Passeron, J. (1977) *Reproduction in education, culture and society*. Translated by R. Nice. London: Sage Publications.
- Bourdieu, P. and Passeron, J. (1979) *The inheritors: French students and their relation to culture*. Translated by R. Nice. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Bourdieu, P., Wacquant, L. (1992) *An invitation to reflexive sociology*. Great Britain: Polity Press.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3 (2), pp.77 – 101.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1191/1478088706QP063OA>
- Briggs, C. (2010) *Language, Identity, and Literary Expression in Algeria*. M.A. dissertation. University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill. Available at:
[file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/Language identity and literary expression in Algeria.pdf](file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/Language_identity_and_literary_expression_in_Algeria.pdf) (Accessed: 30 July 2023).
- Brinkmann, S. and Kvale, S. (2015) *Interviews learning the craft of qualitative research interviews*. 3rdedn. London: Sage.
- Brons, L.L. (2015) 'Othering, an analysis', *Transcience, a Journal of Global Studies*, 6(1), pp.69-90. <https://philpapers.org/rec/BROOAA-4>
- Bryman, A. (2016) *Social research methods*. United Kingdom: Oxford university press.
- Busch, B. (2012) 'The linguistic repertoire revisited', *Applied linguistics*, 33 (5), pp. 503-523.
[https://heteroglossia.net/fileadmin/user_upload/publication/2012-Busch-Applied Ling.pdf](https://heteroglossia.net/fileadmin/user_upload/publication/2012-Busch-Applied_Ling.pdf)
- Calhoun, C. (2006) 'Pierre Bourdieu and social transformation: lessons from Algeria', *Development and Change*, 37 (6), pp.1403-1415.
[https://eprints.lse.ac.uk/42609/1/Pierre%20Bourdieu%20and%20social%20transformation%20\(Isero\).pdf](https://eprints.lse.ac.uk/42609/1/Pierre%20Bourdieu%20and%20social%20transformation%20(Isero).pdf)
- Cameron, D. (2001) *Working with Spoken Discourse*. Sage.
- Cenoz, J. (2013) 'Defining multilingualism', *Annual review of applied linguistics*, 33, pp.3-18.
<http://www.dspace.stellamariscollege.edu.in:8080/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/4057/linguistics.pdf?sequence=1&disAllowed=y>

- Chaker, S. (2001) 'Berber challenge in Algeria: The state of the question', *Race, Gender and Class*, 8(3), pp. 135-156. http://www.centrederechercheberbere.fr/tl_files/doc-pdf/berber%20challenge.pdf
- Chaouche, A.L. (2005) *A Sociolinguistic Study of French: The Case of Oran*. PhD thesis. University of Oran, Algeria.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2002) *Research methods in education*. 5th edn. London: Routledge.
- Collins, J. (2009) 'Social reproduction in classrooms and schools', *Annual review of Anthropology*, 38(1), pp.33-48. <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/abs/10.1146/annurev.anthro.37.081407.085242>
- Costa, J. (2015) 'New speakers, New language: On Being a Legitimate Speaker of a Minority Language in Provence', *International journal of the sociology of language*, 2015(231), pp.127–145. file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/10.1515_ijsl-2014-0035.pdf
- Crabtree, B.F. and Miller, W.L. (1999) *Doing qualitative research*. 2nd edn. London: Sage publications.
- Creswell, J. W. and Miller, D. L. (2000) 'Determining validity in qualitative inquiry', *Theory into Practice*, 39 (3), pp. 124-131. https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1207/s15430421tip3903_2?journalCode=htip20
- Creswell J. (2002) *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed method approaches*. 3rd edn London: Sage.
- Creswell, J.W. (2014) *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. 4thedn. London: Sage publications.
- Creswell, J.W. (2018) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches*. 4th ed. London: Sage Publications.
- Crossley, N. (2014) 'Social class', in M. Grenfell (ed.) *Pierre Bourdieu: key concepts*. London: Routledge, pp. 85-97.
- Crotty, M. (1998) *The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*. Sage Publications.
- Crouch, M and McKenzie, H. (2006) 'The logic of small samples in interview based qualitative research', *Social Science Information*, 45(4), 483-499. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0539018406069584>

- Crystal, D. (1987) *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Language*. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Crystal, D. (2003) *English as a global language*. 2nd edn. New York: Cambridge university press.
- Daly, J., Kellehear, A. and Gliksman, M. (1997) *The public health researcher: a methodological approach*. Melbourne, Australia: Oxford University Press.
- Daoudi, A. (2018) 'Multilingualism in Algeria: between 'soft power', 'Arabisation', 'Islamisation', and 'globalisation'', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 23(3), pp. 460-481. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13629387.2017.1391962>
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2011) *The sage handbook of qualitative research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Dewaele, J.M. (2012) 'Multilingualism and emotions', *The encyclopedia of applied linguistics*. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jean-Marc-Dewaele/publication/284179849_Multilingualism_and_Emotions/links/5a0e9bbf0f7e9b7d4dba6bc7/Multilingualism-and-Emotions.pdf
- Di Maggio, P. (1979) 'Review essay On Pierre Bourdieu', *American Journal of Sociology*, 86 (6), pp. 1460-1474. <https://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/items/1df8384e-0ed3-41ab-a8b0-e2e91f5aaa2f>
- Djennadi, S. (2006) 'Entrepreneurship among the Berber people in Algeria', *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 3(6), pp.691-695. <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJESB.2006.010921>
- Djité, P.G. (1992) 'The Arabization of Algeria: Linguistic and sociopolitical motivations', *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 98(1992), pp. 15-28. <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/ijsl.1992.98.15/html>
- Dourari, A. (2016) Amazighs (Berbers) in Algeria: an ethnic majority yet a linguistic minority. *Minorities, Women and the State in North Africa*, ed. By Moha Ennaji, pp.41-62.
- Edwards, J. (1994) *Multilingualism*. London: Routledge.
- El Aissati, A. (2005) 'A socio-historical perspective on the Amazigh (Berber) cultural movement in North Africa', *Afrika focus*, 18(1-2), pp.59-72. https://brill.com/view/journals/afoc/18/1-2/article-p59_5.xml

Elias-Olivares, L. (1976) *Language use in a Chicano community: a sociolinguistic approach*. Working Papers in Sociolinguistics Number 30. Pan American University. Austin, Tex: Prepared and distributed at Southwest Educational Development Lab, pp.1-26.

El-Mili, M. (1989). تاريخ الجزائر في القديم والحديث [The History of Algeria in the Past and the Modern], *National Book Foundation*, Vol.1.

Ervin-Tripp, S. (1964) 'An analysis of the interaction of language, topic, and listener', *American Anthropologist*, 66 (6_PART2), pp. 86-102. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/668163>

Fenwick, C. (2008) *Archaeology and the search for authenticity: Colonialist, Nationalist, and Berberist visions of an Algerian past*. Oxbow.

<https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/1495996/1/Corisande%20Fenwick%20ArchaeologyandAuthenticityinAlgeria.pdf>

Fereday, J. and Muir-Cochrane, E. (2006) 'Demonstrating rigor using thematic analysis: A hybrid approach of inductive and deductive coding and theme development', *International journal of qualitative methods*, 5 (1), pp.80-92.

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/160940690600500107>

Fidel, R. (1993) 'Qualitative methods in information retrieval research', *Library and Information Science Research*, 15(1993), pp. 219-247.

<http://faculty.washington.edu/fidelr/RayaPubs/QualitativeMethodsInInformationRetrievalResearch.pdf>

Fishman, A. (2020) Who Speaks What Language to Whom and When? in Wei, L. (ed.) *The bilingualism reader*. New York: Routledge, pp. 56-70.

Fowler, B. (1995) *Pierre Bourdieu's sociology of culture: critical investigations*. PhD thesis. University of Glasgow. Available at: <https://theses.gla.ac.uk/5022/1/1995FowlerPhD.pdf> (Accessed: 30 July 2023).

Friedrich, P. (2007) 'English for peace: Toward a framework of peace sociolinguistics', *World Englishes*, 26(1), pp. 72-83. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1467-971X.2007.00489.x>

Gallagher, C.F. (1986) 'North African problems and prospects: language and identity', in Fishman, J.A., Ferguson, C.A. and Gupta, J.D. (eds.) *Language problems of developing nations*. New York: John Wiley and Sons, pp. 129-150.

Gal, S. (1978) 'Peasant men can't get wives: Language change and sex roles in a bilingual community', *Language in society*, 7 (1), pp. 1-16.

<https://web.stanford.edu/~eckert/Institute2015/Readings/Gal1978.pdf>

Gal, S. (1989) 'Language and political economy', *Annual Review of anthropology*, 18(1), pp.345-367.

<https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/abs/10.1146/annurev.an.18.100189.002021?journalCode=anthro>

García, O. (2011) *Bilingual education in the 21st century: A global perspective*. UK: John Wiley and Sons.

García, O. and Wei, L. (2014) 'Language, bilingualism and education', in O. García and L. Wei *Translanguaging: Language, bilingualism and education*. London: Palgrave Pivot, pp. 46-62.

Garza, A. (2017) 'Latino/a Teenagers Using Their Linguistic Repertoire', in C. Ramirez, C. J. Faltis, E. J. De Jong Learning (ed.) *From emergent bilingual Latinx learners in K-12: Critical teacher education*. New York: Routledge.

Galtung, J. (1972) 'A structural theory of imperialism', *African Review*, 1(4), pp.93-138.

https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/AJA00020117_8

Georges, L. and Bernard, P. (2009) 'To be or not to be: a plurilingual speaker'. *International Journal of Multilingualism*. 6 (2), pp. 154-167.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14790710902846715>

Gherzouli, I. (2019) 'Educational reforms and language planning quandary in Algeria: an illustration with Arabization', *Darnioji daugiakalbystė*, (15), pp.27-47.

<https://intapi.sciendo.com/pdf/10.2478/sm-2019-0012>

Gibbs, G.R. (2007) 'Thematic coding and categorizing', *Analyzing qualitative data*, 703, pp.38-56. <https://study.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/analyzing-qualitative-da.pdf>

Giles, H., and Johnson, P. (1981) 'The role of language in ethnic group relations', in Turner. J. C. and Giles. H. (eds.) *Intergroup behaviour*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell, pp. 199-243.

Gillies, D. (2014) 'Human capital, Education, and Sustainability', *Sisyphus Journal of Education*, 2(3), pp.78-99. <https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/5757/575763895005.pdf>

Glesne, C. (1999) *Becoming qualitative researchers: an introduction*. 2nd ed. Canada: Longman Inc.

Golafshani, N. (2003) 'Understanding Reliability and Validity in Qualitative Research', *The Qualitative Report*, 8 (4), pp. 597-606.

<file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/golafshani.pdf>

Goodman, J. (2004) 'Reinterpreting the Berber Spring: From rite of reversal to site of convergence', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 9(3), pp. 60-82.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1362938042000325813>

Gordon, D.C. (1978) *The French Language and National Identity*. The Hague: Mouton publishers.

Grandguillaume, G. (1983) *Arabisation et Politique Linguistique au Maghreb [Arabisation and Language Policy in the Maghreb]*. Paris: G.-P. Maisonneuve et Larose.

<https://cir.nii.ac.jp/crid/1130282272949234048>

Grandguillaume, G. (2004) 'Arabisation au Maghreb', *Revue d'Aménagement Linguistique*, 107, pp. 15–39, Winter. Available:

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=fr&as_sdt=0%2C5andq=Grandguillaume%2C+G.+%282004%29.+L%E2%80%99Arabisation+au+Maghreb.+andbtnG= [Accessed: 18 April 2018].

Greenfield, L. and Fishman, J.A. (1970) 'Situational measures of normative language views in relation to person, place and topic among Puerto Rican bilinguals', *Anthropos*. (H. 3. /4), pp. 602-618. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40457396>

Grenfell, M.J. (2004) *Pierre Bourdieu: agent provocateur*. London: Continuum.

Grenfell, M.J. (2006) 'Bourdieu in the Field from the Béarn and to Algeria', *A Timely Response*, 17 (2), pp. 223-239.

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0957155806064537>

Grenfell, M. (2011) *Bourdieu, language and linguistics*. London: Continuum.

Grenfell, M. (2014) *Pierre Bourdieu: key concepts*. 2nd edn. London: Routledge.

Grosjean, F. (1985) 'The bilingual as a competent but specific speaker-hearer', *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*. 6 (6), pp. 467-477.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01434632.1985.9994221>

Grosjean, F. (1982) *Life with two languages*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.

Gumperz, J.J. (1964) 'Linguistic and social interaction in two communities', *American anthropologist*. 66 (6_PART2), pp.137-153. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/668168>

Gumperz, J.J. (2009) 'The speech community', *Linguistic anthropology: A reader*, 1(66), p.66-73. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Alessandro->

[Duranti/publication/235902633 Linguistic Anthropology A Reader/links/630d3c32acd814437fe70188/Linguistic-Anthropology-A-Reader.pdf#page=79](https://duranti/publication/235902633-Linguistic-Anthropology-A-Reader/links/630d3c32acd814437fe70188/Linguistic-Anthropology-A-Reader.pdf#page=79)

Gumperz, J. J. and Cook-Gumperz, J. (1982) 'Introduction: language and the communication of social identity', in Gumperz, J. J. (ed.) *Language and social identity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 1–22.

Gunzenhauser, M.G. and Gerstl-Pepin, C.I. (2006) 'Engaging graduate education: a pedagogy for epistemological and theoretical diversity', *The Review of Higher Education*, 29(3), pp.319-346. <https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/1/article/195071/summary>

Guo, Y. and Beckett, G.H. (2007) 'The Hegemony of English as a global language: reclaiming local knowledge and culture in China', *convergence*, 40(1-2), p.117.

<https://globalization.anthro-seminars.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/guo-2007.pdf>

Guy, G.R. (1989) 'Language and social class', *Linguistics: The Cambridge Survey*, 4, pp.37-63. https://newuniversityinexileconsortium.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Language-and-Social-Class_RCF-1.pdf

Haddam-Bouabdallah, F. (2022) 'The Linguistic Situation vs Education in Post-colonial Algeria', *Revue plurilingue: Études des Langues, Littératures et Cultures*, 6(1), pp.83-90. <https://journals.univ-tlemcen.dz/ELLIC/index.php/ELLIC/article/view/84>

Hamdan, J.M. and Kessar, S. (2023) 'Language Policy and Planning in Algeria: case study of Berber language planning', *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 13(1), pp.59-68. <https://tpls.academypublication.com/index.php/tpls/article/view/5317>

Hajek, J. and Goglia, F. (2020) 'The East Timorese in Australia: multilingual repertoires, language attitudes, practices and identity in the diaspora', *Journal of multilingual and multicultural development*, 41(3), pp.264-281.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01434632.2019.1617295>

Harbi, M. (1993) *Le FLN mirage et réalité: Des origines à la prise du pouvoir (1945–1962)*. Algiers: NAQD-ENAL.

Heller, M. (1982) *Language, ethnicity and politics in Quebec*. PhD thesis. The University of California, Berkeley. Available at: <https://escholarship.org/content/qt5zz7b8j6/qt5zz7b8j6.pdf> (Accessed: 30 July 2023).

Heller, M. (1992) 'The politics of codeswitching and language choice', *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 13 (1-2), pp.123-142.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01434632.1992.9994487>

- Henze, R., and Davis, K. A. (1999) 'Authenticity and identity: lessons from Indigenous language education', *Anthropology and Education Quarterly*, 30(1), pp. 3-21.
<https://anthrosource.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1525/aeq.1999.30.1.3>
- Heshusius, L. (1994) 'Freeing ourselves from objectivity: managing subjectivity or turning toward a participatory mode of consciousness?', *Educational researcher*, 23(3), pp.15-22.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.3102/0013189X023003015>
- Hilal, A.H. and Alabri, S.S. (2013) 'Using NVivo for data analysis in qualitative research', *International interdisciplinary journal of education*, 2(2), pp.181-186.
https://iijoe.org/v2/IJJOE_06_02_02_2013.pdf
- Hobsbawm, E.J. (1990) *Nations and Nationalism since 1780: Programme, Myth, Reality*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hogan-Brun, G. (2017) *Linguanomics: What is the market potential of multilingualism?* London: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Holmes, P., Fay, R., Andrews, J. and Attia, M. (2013) 'Researching multilingually: New theoretical and methodological directions', *International journal of applied linguistics*, 23(3), pp.285-299. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/ijal.12038>
- Holt, M. (2013) 'Algeria: Language, nation and state', in S. Yasir (ed.) *Arabic sociolinguistics; issues and perspectives*. London: Routledge, pp. 25-41.
- Hornberger, N.H. and Link, H. (2012) 'Translanguaging and transnational literacies in multilingual classrooms: a biliteracy lens', *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 15 (3), pp. 261-278.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13670050.2012.658016>
- Howatt, A. P. R., and Widdowson, H. G. (2004) *A history of English language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Huberman, A.M. and Miles, M.B. (1994) 'Data management and analysis methods', in Denzin. N. K. and Lincoln Y.S. (eds.) *Handbook of qualitative research*. London: Sage Publications, pp. 428-444.
- Hymes, D. (1962) 'The ethnography of speaking', in Gladwin, T. and Sturtevant, W. D. (eds.) *Anthropology and human behavior*. Washington, D. C., Anthropological Society of Washington, pp. 15-53.

- Ibarraran, A., Lasagabaster, D. and Sierra, J.M. (2008) 'Multilingualism and language attitudes: local versus immigrant students' perceptions', *Language awareness*, 17(4), pp. 326-341. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09658410802147311>
- Ilyosovna, N.A. (2020) 'The importance of English language', *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 2(1), pp.22-24. [file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/4730-Article%20Text-12983-2-10-20230524%20\(2\).pdf](file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/4730-Article%20Text-12983-2-10-20230524%20(2).pdf)
- Jacob, C. (2020) 'English as a decolonial language: academic frames, popular discourses and language practices in Algeria', *The journal of North African studies*, 25(6), pp.1013-1032. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13629387.2020.1732627>
- Jaspers, J. (2009) 'Inleiding [Introduction]', in J. Jaspers (Ed.), *De klank van de stad: Stedelijke meer-taligheid en interculturele communicatie [The sound of the city: Urban multilingualism and inter-cultural communication]*. Antwerp: Acco, pp. 7–32.
- Jenkins, R. (2014) *Pierre Bourdieu*. London: Routledge.
- Jorrín Abellán, I.M. (2016) 'Hopscotch building: A model for the generation of qualitative research designs', *Georgia Educational Researcher*, 13(1), p.1. <https://digitalcommons.georgiasouthern.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1088&context=gerjournal>
- Judy, R. (1997) 'On the politics of global language, or unfungible local value', *Boundary 2*, 24(2), pp. 101–143. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/303765>
- Kalu, F.A. and Bwalya, J.C. (2017) 'What makes qualitative research good research? An exploratory analysis of critical elements', *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 5(2), pp.43-56. <https://pureadmin.qub.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/238242851/what.pdf>
- Kamwangamalu, N.M. (2018) 'The issue of the medium of instruction in Africa as an "inheritance situation"', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 19(2), pp.133-135. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14664208.2017.1357987>
- Kaplan, R. (1990) 'Introduction: Language planning in theory and practice', in Baldauf, R.B. and Luke, A. (eds.) *Language Planning and Education in Australia and the South Pacific*. Clevedon: Multilingual matters, pp. 3-13.
- Kaplan, R.B. and Baldauf, R.B. Jr. (1997) *Language planning from practice to theory*. Clevedon: Multilingual matters.

Kaplan, R.B. and Baldauf, R.B. Jr. (2007) *Language planning and policy in Africa*. Great Britain: Multilingual matters.

Kessar, S., Rabab'Ah, G., Al-Khadra, W. and Hamdan, H.J. (2021) 'The representation of the Algerian Hirak protest movement in the international media: France 24 and Al-Jazeera', *Cogent Social Sciences*, 7(1), p.1930646.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/23311886.2021.1930646>

Khelalfa, N. and Kellil, M.B. (2023) 'Reconsidering the Use of L1 in the Algerian EFL Classroom', *Sage Open*, 13(3), p.21582440231193521.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231193521>

Kramersch, C. and Whiteside, A. (2007) 'Three fundamental concepts in second language acquisition and their relevance in multilingual contexts', *The Modern Language Journal*, 91, pp.907-922. [https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1540-](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2007.00677.x?saml_referrer)

[4781.2007.00677.x?saml_referrer](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2007.00677.x?saml_referrer)

Kothari, C.R. (2004) *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International (p) Ltd.

Lamont, M. and Lareau, A. (1988) 'Cultural capital: allusions, gaps and glissandos in recent theoretical developments', *Sociological Theory*, 6(2), pp. 153-168.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/202113>

Lather, P. (1992) 'Critical frames in educational research: feminist and post-structural perspectives', *Theory into Practice*, 31 (2), pp. 87-99.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00405849209543529?journalCode=htip20>

Le Roux, C.S. (2017) 'Language in education in Algeria: a historical vignette of a 'most severe' sociolinguistic problem', *Language and History*, 60(2), pp. 112-128.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17597536.2017.1319103>

Lewis, G., Jones, B. and Baker, C. (2012) 'Translanguaging: origins and development from school to street and beyond', *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 18 (7), pp. 641-654.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13803611.2012.718488>

Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*. London: Sage Publications.

Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (1986) 'But is it rigorous? Trustworthiness and authenticity in naturalistic evaluation', *New directions for program evaluation*, 1986(30), pp.73-84.

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/ev.1427>

Littlewood, W., and Yu, B. (2011) 'First language and target language in the foreign language classroom', *Language Teaching*, 44(1), 64–77. <https://doi:10.1017/S0261444809990310>

Long, A.F. and Godfrey, M. (2004) 'An evaluation tool to assess the quality of qualitative research studies', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 7 (2), pp.181-196.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1364557032000045302>

Lorcin, P.M. (1995) *Imperial Identities: Stereotyping, Prejudice and Race in Colonial Algeria*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.

Kaplan, R.B. and Baldauf, R.B. Jr. (2007) *Language planning and policy in Africa*. Great Britain: Multilingual matters.

Luke, A. and Graham, P. (2006) 'Class Language', in Brown, K. (ed.) *Encyclopedia of Language and Linguistics Second edition*. United Kingdom: Elsevier, pp.428-431.

Maamri, M.R. (2009) 'The syndrome of the French Language in Algeria', *International Journal of Arts and Sciences*, 3(3), pp. 77-89.

<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&doctype=pdf&doi=50823f5c939ee1d42a56c8d7a8cf6d9cb70ef6fe>

Maddy-Weitzman, B. (2001) 'Contested identities: Berbers, 'Berberism'and the state in North Africa', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 6(3), pp. 23-47.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13629380108718442>

Maggio, R. (2018) *Pierre Bourdieu's Outline of a Theory of Practice*. London: Macat Library.

Majhanovich, S. (2009) 'English as a tool of neo-colonialism and globalization in Asian contexts', *World studies in Education*, 10(1), pp. 75-89.

<https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/jnp/wse/2009/00000010/00000001/art00005>

Maraf, B. and Vanci Osam, U. (2023) 'The smile revolution (hirak) as a driving force for an English 'tidal wave'and foreign language policy-making in Algeria', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 24(2), pp.179-200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14664208.2022.2039510>

Marquand, D. (2004) *Decline of the public: the hollowing-out of citizenship*. Cambridge: Polity Press.

- Marshall, C. and Rossman, G.B. (1999) *Designing Qualitative Research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Mathews, D. (2014) Let us learn in our own language, says Algerian scholar. *The Times Higher Education Supplement*, 17.
- Maton, K. (2014) 'Habitus', in M. Grenfell (ed.) *Pierre Bourdieu key concepts*. London: Routledge, pp. 48-64.
- Maxwell, J. A. (1996) *Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach*. London: Sage Publications.
- McDonald, M. (1989) *We are not French: language, culture and identity in Brittany*. London: Routledge.
- Merriam, S.B. (1988) *Case study research in education: a qualitative approach*. Jossey-Bass.
- Messaoudi, K. and Schemla, E. (1995) *Une Algérienne debout*. Paris: Flammarion.
- Mesthrie, R. (2009) *Introducing sociolinguistics*. 2nd edn. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A.M. (1994) *Qualitative data analysis: an expanded sourcebook*. 2nd edn. California: Sage Publications.
- Mohammed, G.B. (2022) 'Multilingualism and the Question of Social Security in Algeria' (from the National Conference on Mapping (In)Security in Western and Postcolonial Spaces, Biskra, 26-27 April 2022). https://univ-biskra.dz/sites/fll/images/site2023/sim-karboua/Dr_ghedeir_brahim.pdf
- Moore, R. (2014) 'Capital', in M. Grenfell (ed.) *Pierre Bourdieu: key concepts*. London: Routledge, pp. 98-113.
- Morrow, S.L. (2005) 'Quality and trustworthiness in qualitative research in counseling psychology', *Journal of counseling psychology*, 52(2), p.250-260. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2005-03263-015>
- Mostari, H.A. (2004) 'A sociolinguistic perspective on Arabization and language use in Algeria', *Language Problems and Language Planning*, 28(1), 25–44. <https://www.jbe-platform.com/content/journals/10.1075/lplp.28.1.04mos>
- Mostari, H.A. (2005) 'The language question in the Arab world: evidence from Algeria', *Journal of Language and Learning*, 3(1), pp. 36–52.

- Mostari, H. A. (2009) 'What do mobiles speak in Algeria? Evidence from SMS language', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 10 (4), pp.377–386.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14664200903554990>
- Mouhlebl, N. (2005) *Language and conflict: Kabylia and the Algerian state*. Master's thesis. University of Oslo. Available at:
<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&doctype=pdf&doi=eef44f464a2638e08eecd2ba5155701f8342b4de> (Accessed: 29 July 2023).
- Myers-Scotton, C. (1993) 'Elite closure as a powerful language strategy: the African case', *International journal of the sociology of language*, 1993(103), pp.149-164.
<https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/ijsl.1993.103.149/html>
- Nash, R. (1999) 'Bourdieu, 'habitus', and educational research: Is it all worth the candle?', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 20 (2), pp.175-187.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01425699995399>
- Negadi, M.N. (2015) 'Investigating language contact situation in Algeria', *Traduction et Langues*, 14(1), pp. 145-150. <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticlepdf/155/14/1/6354>
- Nelde, P.H. (2017). 'Language conflict', in Coulmas. F. (ed.) *The handbook of sociolinguistics*. Oxford: Blackwell, pp. 285-300.
- Nilep, C. (2006) 'Code switching in sociocultural linguistics', *Colorado Research in Linguistics*, 19. <https://journals.colorado.edu/index.php/cril/article/view/273>
- Nye, J. (2004) *Soft power: the means to success in the world*. New York: Public Affairs.
- Oliver, D.G., Serovich, J.M. and Mason, T.L. (2005) 'Constraints and opportunities with interview transcription: Towards reflection in qualitative research', *Social forces*, 84(2), pp.1273-1289.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1400594/>
- Oliver, R., Wigglesworth, G., Angelo, D. and Steele, C. (2021) 'Translating translanguaging into our classrooms: Possibilities and challenges', *Language teaching research*, 25(1), pp.134-150.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/1362168820938822>
- Ortega, L. (2018) 'SLA in uncertain times: Disciplinary constraints, transdisciplinary hopes', *Working Papers in Educational Linguistics (WPEL)*, 33(1), p.1.
<https://wpel.gse.upenn.edu/sites/default/files/WPEL%2033%20Ortega.pdf>
- Or, I.G. (2017) 'Language Policy and Education in the Middle East and North Africa', *Language Policy and Political Issues in Education*, pp.531-543. DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-02344-1_40
- Ouerdane, A. (2003) *Les Berbères et l'arabo-islamisme en Algérie*. Quebec: Editions KMSA.

- Oxley, J., Günhan, E., Kaniamattam, M. and Damico, J. (2017) 'Multilingual issues in qualitative research', *Clinical linguistics and phonetics*, 31(7-9), pp.612-630.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02699206.2017.1302512>
- Pavlenko, A. (2004) 'Stop doing that, ia Komu Skazala! Language choice and emotion in parent– child communication', *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 25 (2-3), pp. 179–203. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01434630408666528>
- Pavlenko, A. (2008) 'Emotion and emotion-laden words in the bilingual lexicon', *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 11 (2), pp. 147–64.
<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/bilingualism-language-and-cognition/article/abs/emotion-and-emotionladen-words-in-the-bilingual-lexicon/05F49CCE9D7A59E759123889F787C0B7>
- Phillipson, R. (1992) *Linguistic imperialism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Park, M.S., (2013) 'Code-switching and translanguaging: Potential functions in multilingual classrooms', *Teachers College, Columbia University Working Papers in TESOL and Applied Linguistics*, 13 (2), pp. 50-52. <file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/3.6-Park-2013.pdf>
- Patton, M.Q. (1990) *Qualitative evaluation and research methods*. 2nd edn. London: Sage Publications.
- Polit, D.F., Beck, C.T. and Hungler, B.P. (2001) *Essentials of Nursing Research: Methods, Appraisal and Utilization*. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins article.
- Prah, K.K. (2002) 'The burden of English in Africa: from colonialism to neo-colonialism', *TESL-EJ (Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language–Electronic Journal)*, 6(1).3.
[file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/TheBurdenofEnglishinAfricaUniversityofBotswanaJune09Version2%20\(1\).pdf](file:///Users/hananebelaidi/Downloads/TheBurdenofEnglishinAfricaUniversityofBotswanaJune09Version2%20(1).pdf)
- Racher, F. (2003) 'Using conjoint interviews to research the lived experience of elderly rural couples', *Nurse Researcher*, 19 (3), pp.60–72.
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/0151fc7c036451a54ffa6dc1f8da8212/1?pq-origsite=gscholarandcbl=33100>
- Reay, D. (2004) 'It's all becoming a habitus: beyond the habitual use of habitus in educational research', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 25 (4), pp.431-444.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0142569042000236934>
- Reilly, C., Bagwasi, M.M., Costley, T., Gibson, H., Kula, N.C., Mapunda, G. and Mwansa, J., 2022. 'Languages don't have bones, so you can just break them: rethinking multilingualism

- in education policy and practice in Africa', *Journal of the British Academy*, 10(s4), pp.1-20.
<https://repository.essex.ac.uk/33042/1/10s4-01-Reilly.pdf>
- Reyes, I. (2004) 'Functions of code switching in schoolchildren's conversations', *Bilingual Research Journal*, 28 (1), pp. 77-98.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15235882.2004.10162613>
- Richards, J.C. and Schmidt, R.W. (2013) *Longman dictionary of language teaching and applied linguistics*. 3rd edn. Harlow, Essex: Longman.
- Roberts, H. (1982) 'The unforeseen development of the Kabyle question in contemporary Algeria', *Government and opposition*, 17(3), pp.312-334.
<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/government-and-opposition/article/abs/unforeseen-development-of-the-kabyle-question-in-contemporary-algeria/4128F11536382DC029DF5AE0ACC2C55F>
- Roberts, H. (2003) *The battlefield: Algeria 1988-2002: Studies in a broken polity*. London: Verso.
- Roberts, H. (2014) *Berber government: The Kabyle polity in pre-colonial Algeria*. London: I.B. Tauris.
- Roberts, H. and Roberts, M.H.P. (2003) *The Battlefield: Algeria 1988-2002: studies in a broken polity*. London: Verso.
- Robson, C. (2002) *Real world research: a resource for social scientists and practitioner-researchers*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Blackwell Publishers.
- Robson, C. and McCartan, K. (2016) *Real world research: a resource for social scientists and practitioner-researchers*. 4th ed. John Wiley and Sons.
- Rouabah, S. (2020) Language Shift or Maintenance in Tamazight: A Sociolinguistic Study of Chaouia in Batna, Algeria. PhD thesis. University of Essex, UK. Available at:
<https://repository.essex.ac.uk/28557/1/SihamRouabah%20Thesis.pdf> (Accessed: 26 March 2024).
- Rouabah, S. (2022) 'Multilingualism in Algeria: educational policies, language practices, and challenges', *Journal of the British Academy*, 10(s4), pp. 21–40.
<https://www.thebritishacademy.ac.uk/documents/4216/10s4-00-FULL.pdf#page=23>
- Rouchdy, A. (2013) *Language contact and language conflict in Arabic*. Canada: Routledge.
- Ruedy, J. (2005) *Modern Algeria: The origins and development of a nation*. 2nd edn. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.

- Saadane, H. and Habash, N. (2015) A conventional orthography for Algerian Arabic. *The Second Workshop on Arabic Natural Language Processing*, pp. 69-79.
<https://hal.science/hal-02012254/document>
- Saad, z. (1992) *Language planning and policy attitudes: A case study of Arabization in Algeria*. PhD Thesis. Columbia University Teachers College. Available at:
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/304d52ef5f08f3037ab985d6172ac060/1?pq-origsite=gscholarandcbl=18750anddiss=y> (Accessed: 30 July 2023)
- Sadiqi, F. (2011) 'The Teaching of Amazigh (Berber) in Morocco', in Fishman, J.A. and Garcia, O. (eds) *Handbook of Language and Ethnic Identity: The Success–Failure Continuum in Language and Ethnic Identity Efforts*. Oxford/New York: Oxford University Press, pp.33–44.
- Sadouki, F. (2023) 'Language contact in Algeria: A sociolinguistic study', *Argumentum*, 19(2023), pp.70-87. <http://argumentum.unideb.hu/2023-anyagok/sadoukif.pdf>
- Schegloff, E.A. (1997) 'Whose text? Whose context?', *Discourse and society*, 8(2), pp.165-187.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0957926597008002002>
- Sekhar, G.R. (2012) 'Colonialism and imperialism and its impact on English language', *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 1(4), pp.111-120. <https://tarj.in/wp-content/uploads/paper/AJMR/2012/AJMR-SEPTEMBER-2012.pdf#page=85>
- Sellwood, J. and Angelo, D. (2013) 'Everywhere and nowhere: invisibility of aboriginal and torres strait islander contact languages in education and Indigenous language contexts', *Australian Review of Applied Linguistics*, 36(3), pp.250-266. <https://www.jbe-platform.com/content/journals/10.1075/aral.36.3.02sel>
- Serai, S. (2022) *Translanguaging in Algerian University EFL Classrooms: Practices and Attitudes*. PhD thesis. University of Portsmouth. Available at: https://pure.port.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/65602152/Translanguaging_in_Algerian_University_EFL_Classroom_Practices_and_attitudes_Safia_Serai_.pdf (Accessed: 29 July 2023).
- Sharma, G., 2017. Pros and cons of different sampling techniques. *International journal of applied research*, 3(7), pp.749-752. <https://tinyurl.com/mpjppdek>
- Shenton, A.K. (2004) 'Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects', *Education for Information*. 22(2), pp.63–75.
https://www.pm.lth.se/fileadmin/migrated/content_uploads/Shenton_Trustworthiness.pdf

- Simpson, J. and Wigglesworth, G. (2018) 'Language diversity in indigenous Australia in the 21st century', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 20(1), pp.67-80.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14664208.2018.1503389>
- Skutnabb-Kangas, T. and McCarty, T.L. (2008) 'Key concepts in bilingual education: Ideological, historical, epistemological, and empirical foundations', *Encyclopedia of language and education*, 5(17), pp.1466-1482. <https://tinyurl.com/y92he4kr>
- Smati, M. (1999) 'Ibn Badis: Un projet de renouveau [Ibn Badis: A project for renewal]', in Kadri, A. (ed.) *Parcours d'Intellectuels Maghrebins. Scolarite, Formation, Socialisation et Positionnements*. Paris: Karthala, pp. 183-91.
- Smith, L.M. (1978) 'An evolving logic of participant observation, educational ethnography, and other case studies', *Review of research in education*, 6(1), pp.316-377.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732X006001316>
- Smith, M. L. (2006) 'Overcoming theory-practice inconsistencies: Critical realism and information systems research', *Information and Organization*, 16 (3), pp.191–211.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S147177270600011X>
- Soudi, Z. and Bessaoud, O. (2011) 'Development of rural areas in Algeria: a new participatory strategy', *New Medit*, 10(1), pp. 17-24.
<https://www.cabdirect.org/cabdirect/abstract/20113134091>
- Srhir, A.M. and Esbert, J.L. (2022) 'Family, school, and crossroads: The language regimentation of multilingual repertoires in youth of Moroccan origin in Spain', *Sociolinguistic Studies*, 16(2), pp.1-22. <https://tinyurl.com/y6es65kd>
- Sridhar, K.K. (1996) 'Societal multilingualism', *Sociolinguistics and language teaching*. [Online], 47 (1996), pp.70.
- Sullivan, A. (2002) 'Bourdieu and education: How useful is Bourdieu's theory for researchers?', *Netherlands Journal of Social Sciences*, 38 (2), pp.144-166.
<https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/1473723/>
- Suminar, P. (2013) 'Bringing in Bourdieu's theory of practice: Understanding community-based dammar agroforest management in Pesisir Krui, West Lampung District, Indonesia', *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3 (6), pp.201-213.
<https://tinyurl.com/3m2z8ewr>
- Swartz, D. (2012) *Culture and power: the sociology of Pierre Bourdieu*. London: University of Chicago Press.

Tajfel, H. (1974) 'Social identity and intergroup behavior', *Social Science Information*, 13 (2), pp. 65–93. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/053901847401300204>

Tawil, S. (2006) 'Le défi de la qualité de l'éducation en Algérie', *Réforme de l'éducation et innovation pédagogique en Algérie*, pp.27-50. <https://tinyurl.com/3xxy9yy5>

Tilmatine, M. (2016) 'French and Spanish colonial policy in North Africa: revisiting the Kabyle and Berber myth', *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 2016(239), pp.95-119. <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/ijsl-2016-0006/html>

Tittenbrun, J. (2016) 'Concepts of capital in Pierre Bourdieu's theory', *Miscellanea Anthropologica et Sociologica*, 17(1), pp.81-103. <https://tinyurl.com/4wzhkk4w>

Valensi, L. (1969) *Le Maghreb avant la prise d'Alger (1790-1830)*. Paris: Flammarion

Van Teijlingen, E.R. and Hundley, V. (2001) 'The importance of pilot studies', *Department of Sociology University of Surrey*, (35), pp. 289-295. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/75457.pdf>

Wacquant, L. (1997) 'Preface', in Bourdieu, P. (ed.) *State Nobility*. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press.

Wacquant, L.J. (1989) 'Towards a reflexive sociology: A workshop with Pierre Bourdieu', *Sociological Theory*, 7 (1), pp.26-63. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/202061>

Wallenbrock, N.B. (2018) The rhizomatic Algerian revolution in three twenty-first-century transnational documentaries: *Algérie tours, détours* (2006), *La Chine est encore loin* (2009), *Fidaï* (2012), *French Politics, Culture and Society*, 36(1), pp. 103-127. <https://www.berghahnjournals.com/view/journals/fpcs/36/1/fpcs360105.xml>

Wardhaugh, R. (1987) *Languages in competition: Dominance, diversity, and decline*. London; New York: Basil Blackwell.

Weirich, A.C. (2021) 'Access and reach of linguistic repertoires in periods of change: A theoretical approach to sociolinguistic inequalities', *international journal of the sociology of language*, 2021(272), pp.157-184. <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/ijsl-2020-0047/html>

Wei, L., 2008. Research perspectives on bilingualism and multilingualism. *The Blackwell guide to research methods in bilingualism and multilingualism*, pp.1-17. https://dirzon.com/file/telegram/yafelesefena%20matzehhafete/Blackwell_Guide_to_Research_Methods.pdf#page=19

- Wei, L. (2011) 'Moment analysis and translanguaging space: discursive construction of identities by multilingual Chinese youth in Britain', *Journal of Pragmatics*, 43 (5), pp. 1222-1235. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378216610002535>
- Welch, M. (1998) 'Phenomenology and hermeneutics', in Polifroni E. C. and Welch. W, (eds.) *Perspectives on Philosophy of Science in Nursing: An Historical and Contemporary Anthology*. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, pp. 235-246.
- Williams, C. (1994) *Arfarniad o ddulliau dysgu ac addysgu yng nghyd-destun addysg uwchradd ddwyieithog*. Bangor University (United Kingdom).
- Wolfram, W. (1998) 'Dialect awareness and the study of language', in Egan-Robertson, A. and Bloome, D. (eds.) *Students as researchers of culture and language in their own communities*. Cresskill, NJ: Hampton, pp.169-190.
- Wong, L.P. (2008) 'Focus group discussion: a tool for health and medical research', *Singapore Med J*, 49 (3), pp. 256-60.
<http://www.smj.org.sg/sites/default/files/4903/4903me1.pdf>
- Yin, R.K. (2003) 'Designing case studies', in L. Maruster and M. Gijsenberg (ed) *Qualitative research methods*. London: Sage, pp.359-386.
- Yin, R. K. (2014) *Case study research: design and method*. 5th edn. London: Sage Publications.
- Zanten, A.V. (2005) 'Bourdieu as education policy analyst and expert: A rich but ambiguous legacy', *Journal of Education Policy*, 20 (6), pp. 671-686.
<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203567203-23/bourdieu-education-policy-analyst-expert-rich-ambiguous-legacy-agn%C3%A8s-van-zanten>
- Zentella, A.C. (1997) *Growing Up Bilingual*. Maiden, MA: Blackwell.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Focus Group Discussions' Protocol

Thank you very much for accepting to take part in this study. My name is Hanane Belaidi, and I am a PhD student in the School of Education, University of West of Scotland, UK. This focus-group discussion will aim to explore the personal and professional experiences of secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) regarding their linguistic repertoires. Through conducting focus group discussions my aim is to understand teachers' perceptions of multilingualism, the component of their repertoires, and their language practice in different fields, in addition to their attitudes and awareness of language policy in Algeria and education. I am interested to hear about teachers' reflections on the socio-politics of language use for them personally, your region and the students you teach. I am particularly keen to know how teachers navigate from one language to another, both in their personal lives and importantly in their professional teaching contexts.

The focus group discussions may take between one hour and one hour and a half. During the session, you may request to take a short break if you need this. You are free to use any language you prefer during the session but will ask that the language you choose should be one that the researcher can also understand and use.

You are free to withdraw from the focus group discussion anytime. Before the start of the session, I will ask you to sign a consent form.

Language attitudes and language policy

1. How do you define someone who is multilingual?
2. Do you consider yourself a multilingual person?
3. How many languages do you speak and understand?
4. Algeria is considered a multilingual country (Algerian Arabic, Standard Arabic, Berber, French) if you are given the chance to allocate each of these languages to a particular domain (Home, street, school, administration, religious affairs, foreign affairs and so on), which language do you think will be suitable for each, and why?
5. Is there a language that is perceived as more valuable than the other languages in Algeria?
6. What do you think about allowing students to use different languages in the classroom?
7. What do you know about the language policy in the Algerian educational system?

8. Do you receive any written notes concerning language use in the classroom?
9. What do you know about the language policy that was implemented in the colonial period, and after independence?
10. What do think about the recent news about replacing the French language with English?
11. Being an Algerian, who belongs to the Berber region, what do you think about the status of the aboriginal language (Tamazight) in the educational system and other domains?
12. How do you sustain the use of the Berber language?

Appendix 2: Interview Protocol

Thank you very much for accepting to take a part in this study. My name is Hanane Belaidi and I am a PhD student in the school of Education, University of West of Scotland, UK. The focus-group discussion will aim to explore the personal and professional experiences of secondary school teachers in the Berber region, particularly Chaoui and Kabyle context, regarding their linguistic repertoires.

Through conducting the interviews my aim is to understand teachers' perceptions and experiences of acquiring and using a repertoire of languages. I am interested to hear about teachers' reflections on socio-politics of language use for them personally, your region and the students you teach. I am particularly keen to know how teachers navigate from one language to another, both in their personal lives and importantly in their professional teaching contexts.

The interview may take between one hour and one hour and half. During the interviews, you may request to take a short break if you need this. You are free to use any language you prefer during the session but will ask that the language you choose should be one that the researcher can also understand and use.

You are free to withdraw from the interview at any time. Before the start of the session, I will ask you to sign a consent form.

Background information

- How old are you?
- How long have you been teaching?
- What qualifications do you have?

Language Acquisition Experiences

1. Do you consider yourself a multilingual person, and why?
2. How many languages do you speak and understand?
3. How did you acquire each of the languages in your repertoire?
4. What are the factors that influenced the learning process of these languages?
5. How do you sustain the use of these of these languages?

Language attitudes and choice in different contexts

13. Do you use each of the languages in your repertoire separately or mix between them? Why?
14. Do you think that having a multilingual repertoire is beneficial or not in your personal and professional life as a teacher, and why?
15. Do you prefer any of the languages in your repertoire to the others? Why?
16. Do you find yourself more comfortable using a particular language in your repertoire? Which one and why?
17. Which language or languages do you think are more valuable in your repertoire, and why?

Language policy and professional context

1. As a teacher, which language or languages do you use in your teaching and why?
2. When teaching do you use one language or mix-different languages, and why?
3. Which language is dominant among your students in the classroom and why?
4. Are students allowed to mix languages in classroom discourse? If they mix, which are the common languages?
5. When speaking to colleagues and other teachers in your school, which language do you use and why?
6. Do you find it beneficial using different languages in your personal life and professional work, and why?
7. As a teacher, are you aware of the government's national policy on language use in education?
8. What are your views on the languages the government has designated as official and to be used in education?
9. Do headteachers monitor if teachers and students use official national languages in schools?
10. If you were suggesting to policymakers, which languages would designate as official for Algeria, and why?
11. Do you feel forced by school management to use certain languages, whether official or not, in your professional work?

Appendix 3: Participants Information Sheet

The West of Scotland University.

School of Education.

Participants Information Sheet

Title of the Project: A Bourdieusian Analysis of the Linguistic Repertoires of Algerian Secondary School Teachers in the Berber Regions of Chaoui and Kabyle.

My name is Hanane Belaidi. I am conducting a study that aims to examine the linguistic repertoire of Algerian secondary school teachers in the Berber region (Chaoui and Kabyle) from a Bourdieusian perspective, as part of my PhD programme at The West of Scotland University, Scotland, UK. Therefore, Semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions will be conducted to understand the notion of linguistic repertoire through exploring teachers' linguistic experiences.

This study aims at investigating how teachers acquired or learned their linguistic repertoire, and what forms of capital were associated with the process of internalisation of their verbal repertoire. It also examines their linguistic practices in different fields with an emphasis on the educational field since it is considered the professional setting or field for teachers. In addition, the study investigates teachers' attitudes towards each of the languages existing in their repertoire and tackles the question of language policy in education and how it affects their practice in the educational context. The study uses Bourdieu's three conceptual terms, or as he calls them thinking tools: "habitus, field, and capital" as a lens for understanding this phenomenon. These three concepts will serve as a guiding tool for collecting and analysing data.

The interviews and focus-group discussions will be audio-recorded with your permission. I would like to invite you to participate in my research study. Please take time to read this information sheet before deciding to participate. If you have any inquiries concerning the research study or the information mentioned in the information sheet, please do not hesitate to contact me via email address.

Your participation is very much appreciated!! Thanks.

Why have I been invited?

You have been selected because you fulfil the following criteria:

1. Adults, therefore, are easy to deal with and with a strong potential of providing the study with in-depth information and Data.
2. An Algerian secondary school teacher in Chaoui or Kabyle contexts.

Do I have to take part in the study?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to participate. If you decide to participate, you will be able to withdraw at any time and without giving reasons, at any stage of the research. In case you withdraw from the study, all the information gathered from you will be removed from the research study along with your anonymised name.

For participants in the research study. The written consent is a required document that states that you agree to the terms and conditions of the study.

Will my taking part in the study be confidential?

All personal data enabling your identification will be securely protected by the researcher. Details you consider threatening to your confidentiality will be separated from the interviews and the focus groups. The records will be accessed by the researcher only. The transcripts of the interviews will be checked by the supervisory team and the examiner only with the personal data of participants made anonymous to preserve your identity.

What am I asked to do?

As a participant, you will be requested either to:

1. Participate in face-to-face interviews that may take up to 1 hour and 30 minutes. The interviews will be scheduled whenever and wherever it is convenient for you.

Or to:

2. Participate in a focus-group discussions that may take from 30 to 45 minutes.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you accept to be a participant in this study, you will be part of a face-to-face interview, or you will be part of focus-group discussions that will be held for this research study.

Your details will be completely secured and confidential. You will be asked to choose a pseudonym -that will make you anonymous- at the beginning of the interviews and the focus groups. Both the interviews and the focus group discussions will be recorded -for research

purposes only- with your permission. The recorded materials will be confidential with access only to the researcher. The transcribed interviews and focus-group discussions will be shared only with the supervisory team.

You will be asked to speak about your linguistic personal experiences throughout your life trajectory in relation to the research questions and aim.

You will be asked about how you acquired your linguistic repertoire. What factors influence this process?

You will be asked about your use of the linguistic repertoire in different fields including your professional field.

You will be asked about the influence of educational policy on your linguistic practices.

You will be asked about how having a repertoire of languages influences your linguistic professional practice.

You will be asked to talk about your feelings, attitudes and your thoughts about different languages in your repertoire.

Please note that you will have the right to withdraw at any point in time –during the interview if you do not want to continue or after if you change your mind about participating, without giving any reasons to the researcher.

Appendix 4: consent form

Title of Project: A Bourdieusian Analysis of the Linguistic Repertoires of Algerian

Secondary School Teachers in the Berber Regions of Chaoui and Kabyle.

Contact details: Address: [REDACTED]

Tel: [REDACTED]

Email: [REDACTED]

If you have further questions about the study, please contact my lead supervisor

Dr Yonah Matemba: [REDACTED]

1.	I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.	
2.	I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.	
3.	I understand that any personal information that I provide to the researchers will be kept strictly confidential	
4.	I understand that while being interviewed, or in the focus group, everything will be audio-recorded	
5.	I understand that the researcher will ask me some very detailed questions about my linguistic personal experience, and I am required to answer as detailed and as accurately as possible.	
6.	I agree to take part in the above study as:	
	Interviewee	Part of the focus group

Name of Participant:

Date:

Signature:

Researcher:

Date:

Signature:

Copies: 1 for participant/ 1 for researcher.

Appendix 5: Participants Information Sheet translated

جامعة ذو واست اوف اسكتلندا

قسم التعليم

2019-04-29

عنوان البحث: الذخيرة اللغوية لمعلمي المدارس الثانوية في منطقتي القبائل والشاوي: منظور بورديو

ورقة معلومات المشاركين

اسمي حنان بلعدي. أقوم بإجراء دراسة تهدف إلى فحص المرجع اللغوي والذخيرة اللغوية لمعلمي المدارس الثانوية في منطقة الامازيغ بالتحديد الشاوية والقبائل من منظور بورديو (نظريه بورديو) كجزء من برنامج الدكتوراه في جامعة ذو واست اوف اسكتلندا بإسكتلندا، المملكة المتحدة البريطانية. سيتم التواصل مع المشاركين في الدراسة عن طريق مقابلات فردية شبه منظمة ومناقشات جماعية مركزة لفهم مفهوم المهارات اللغوية من خلال استكشاف تجارب المعلمين اللغوية. تهدف هذه الدراسة لمعرفة كيف اكتسب المعلمون ذخيرتهم اللغوية، وما هي أشكال رأس المال المرتبطة بعملية استيعاب الذخيرة اللفظية لديهم. ويهدف أيضًا إلى دراسة مدى اختلاف استخدام الذخيرة اللغوية للمعلمين من مجال إلى آخر مع التركيز على المجال التعليمي نظرًا لأنه يعتبر المجال المهني لهم. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، سنتنظر هذه الدراسة إلى مواقف وراء المعلمين تجاه كل لغة من اللغات الموجودة في مرجعهم اللغوي، وستتناول أيضًا مسألة سياسة اللغة في التعليم وكيف تتأثر بالمرجع اللغوي للمعلمين أو كيف تؤثر الممارسة اللغوية في المجال المهني للمعلمين. أود أن أدعوك للمشاركة في بحثي العلمي لذلك يرجى منكم قضاء بعض الوقت لقراءة ورقة المعلومات هذه قبل اتخاذ قرار المشاركة. إذا كان لديك أي استفسارات بشأن الدراسة أو المعلومات الواردة في ورقة المعلومات، فلا تتردد في الاتصال بي عبر عنوان البريد الإلكتروني. سيتم تسجيل المقابلات الفردية والمناقشات الجماعية المركزة صوتيًا بإذن منك.

مشاركتكم هي محل تقدير كبير! شكر

لماذا دعيت؟

لقد تم اختيارك لأنك تستوفي المعايير التالية:

مدرس جزائري ثانوي منطقة الامازيغ القبائل والشاوي

هل يجب على المشاركة في الدراسة؟

مشاركتك في هذه الدراسة تطوعية تمامًا. يمكنك اختيار عدم المشاركة. إذا قررت المشاركة فستتمكن من الانسحاب في أي وقت ودون إبداء الأسباب في أي مرحلة من مراحل البحث. في حالة انسحابك من الدراسة، ستتم إزالة جميع المعلومات التي تم جمعها منك من الدراسة مع اسمك المجهول.

للمشاركين في هذه الدراسة الموافقة الكتابية هي وثيقة مطلوبة تنص على موافقتك على المشاركة في الدراسة

هل ستكون مشاركتي في الدراسة سرية؟

سيتم حماية جميع البيانات الشخصية التي تمكن من تحديد هويتك بشكل آمن من قبل الباحث. سيتم فصل التفاصيل التي تعتبرها تهديدًا لسريتك عن سجل المقابلات الفردية والمناقشات الجماعية المركزة. سيتم الوصول إلى السجلات من قبل

الباحث فقط. وسيتم فحص نصوص المقابلات من قِبل الفريق الإشرافي من خلال بيانات شخصية للمشاركين مع جعل الاسماء مجهولة للحفاظ على هويتك.

ما المطلوب مني القيام به؟

كمشارك، سيُطلب منك إما

1- المشاركة في مقابلة وجها لوجه التي قد تستغرق ما يصل من ساعة إلى ساعة و30 دقيقة و سيتم جدولة المقابلات في مكان احترافي أو عام يناسبك أو

2- المشاركة في مناقشات جماعية مركزة قد تستغرق من ساعة إلى ساعة و30 دقيقة

ماذا سيحدث لي إذا شاركت؟

إذا وافقت على المشاركة في هذه الدراسة، فستكون جزءًا من مقابلة وجهاً لوجه، أو ستكون جزءًا من المناقشات الجماعية المركزة التي ستعقد لغرض هذه الدراسة.

ستكون بياناتك الشخصية آمنة وسرية تمامًا.

سيُطلب منك اختيار اسم مستعار في بداية المقابلات وهذا سيجعلك مجهول الهوية.

سيتم تسجيل كل من المقابلات والمناقشات الجماعية المركزة صوتياً - لأغراض البحث فقط - بإذن منك. المواد المسجلة ستكون سرية.

سيُطلب منك التحدث عن خبراتك اللغوية الشخصية خلال مسار حياتك

سوف تسأل عن كيفية حصولك على ذخيرتك اللغوية والعوامل التي أثرت على ذلك

سيتم سؤالك عن استخدامك للمرجع اللغوي في مجالات مختلفة بما في ذلك مجالك المهني

سيتم سؤالك عن تأثير السياسة التعليمية على الممارسات اللغوية

سيتم سؤالك عن كيفية تأثير ذخيرة اللغات على ممارستك اللغوية المهنية

سيُطلب منك التحدث عن مشاعرك ومواقفك وأفكارك حول اللغات المختلفة في ذخيرتك

ليكن في علمك أن نتائج هذه الدراسة سوف تنتج أطروحة منشورة والتي يمكن الاعتماد عليها في أوراق المؤتمرات

وغيرها من المنشورات الأكاديمية، ولكن سيتم حماية معلوماتك السرية في كل ما سبق.

ليكن في علمك أنه لديك الحق في الانسحاب في أي وقت من الأوقات - أثناء المقابلة إذا كنت لا ترغب في المتابعة أو بعد تغيير رأيك للمشاركة، دون تقديم أي أسباب للباحث.

Appendix 6: Consent form translated

عنوان المشروع: الذخيرة اللغوية لمعلمي المدارس الثانوية في منطقتي القبائل والشاوي: منظور بورديو

اسم الباحث: حنان بلعدي

تفاصيل الاتصال:

العنوان

هـ +

البريد الإلكتروني

1	أؤكد أنني قد قرأت وفهمت ورقة المعلومات للدراسة المذكورة أعلاه وأتحت لي الفرصة لطرح الأسئلة
2	فهم أن مشاركتي طوعية وأنني حر في الانسحاب في أي وقت، دون إبداء أي سبب
3	أدرك أن أي معلومات شخصية أقدمها للباحثين سيتم الاحتفاظ بسرية تامة
4	أفهم أنه أثناء إجراء المقابلات أو في مجموعة التركيز، سيتم تسجيل كل شيء بشكل صوتي
5	أتفهم أن الباحث سوف يسألني بعض الأسئلة التفصيلية حول تجربتي الشخصية اللغوية
6	وافق على المشاركة في الدراسة أعلاه على النحو التالي
	جزء من المقابلة الفردية
	جزء من المناقشة الجماعية المركزة

اسم المشارك:

تاريخ:

التوقيع:

الباحث:

تاريخ:

التوقيع:

نسخ: 1 للمشارك / 1 للباحث

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 7: Participant Invitation Letter

Participant Invitation Letter

My name is Hanane Belaidi, and I am a PhD student in the school of Education, University of West of Scotland, UK. I am inviting you to take part in my study, which aims to explore the personal and professional experiences of secondary school teachers in the Berber region, particularly Kabyle and Chaoui, regions regarding their linguistic repertoires.

Through conducting the interviews and focus group discussions, the study seeks to understand teachers' perceptions and experiences of acquiring and using a repertoire of languages. I am interested to hear about teachers' reflections on socio-politics of language use for them personally, their region and the students they teach. I am particularly keen to know how teachers navigate from one language to another, both in their everyday experiences and importantly their professional teaching contexts.

Before making the decision to take part in this study or not, it is important to understand the aim of this research. Therefore, please take time to read the information sheet, and to think about participating or not in the present study.

With your consent, I will record the research sessions. The information obtained from you will be securely stored, and only my supervisory team and I will have access to the data. Your names and contact details will be separate from the data you provide and will not be shared with third parties. In reporting the data, your names will be changed and replaced with pseudonyms so that no one can identify you in the study.

You are able to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any explanation to the researcher. You are free to use any language you prefer during the session but will ask that the language you choose should be one that the researcher can also understand and use.

If you have any questions concerning the study, please do not hesitate to contact me via phone or email. My mobile/cell phone number is [REDACTED] and my email address is [REDACTED]. If you have further questions about the study, please contact my lead supervisor, Dr Yonah Matemba: [REDACTED]

Thank you for considering taking part in my study.

Yours sincerely,

Hanane Belaidi

PhD Student, University of the West of Scotland, UK

Appendix 8: Participant Invitation Letter translated

دعوة مشاركة

اسمي حنان بلعيدي وأنا طالبة دكتوراه في كلية التربية، جامعة ذو واست اوف اسكتلندا، المملكة المتحدة البريطانية. أدعوكم للمشاركة في دراستي، التي تهدف إلى استكشاف التجارب الشخصية والمهنية لمعلمي المدارس الثانوية في منطقتي القبائل والشاوية فيما يتعلق بمهاراتهم اللغوية.

من خلال إجراء المقابلات ومناقشات الجماعة المركزة، تسعى هذه الدراسة إلى فهم تصورات المعلمين وتجاربهم في اكتساب واستخدام مجموعة من اللغات. أنا مهتم بمعرفة أفكار المعلمين حول السياسة الاجتماعية لاستخدام اللغة لهم شخصياً ومنطقتهم والطلاب الذين يقومون بتدريسهم. أنا حريص بشكل خاص على معرفة كيفية انتقال المدرسين من لغة إلى أخرى، سواء في تجاربهم اليومية أو في سياقات التدريس المهني الخاصة بهم.

قبل اتخاذ قرار بالمشاركة في هذه الدراسة، من المهم أن فهم الهدف من هذا البحث. لذلك يرجى قضاء بعض الوقت لقراءة ورقة المعلومات.

بموافقتك، سوف يتم تسجيل جلسات البحث صوتياً. سيتم تخزين المعلومات التي تم الحصول عليها منك بشكل آمن، ولن يتمكن من الوصول إلى البيانات إلا فريق الإشراف الخاص بي. سيتم فصل أسماءك وتفاصيل الاتصال الخاصة بك عن البيانات التي تقدمها ولن تتم مشاركتها مع أطراف ثالثة. سيتم تغيير أسماءك واستبدالها بأسماء مستعارة بحيث لا يمكن لأحد التعرف عليك في الدراسة يمكنك الانسحاب من البحث في أي وقت دون تقديم أي تفسير للباحث. أنت حر في استخدام أي لغة تفضلها أثناء الجلسة بشرط أن تكون اللغة التي تختارها هي اللغة التي يمكن للباحث أن يفهمها ويستخدمها أيضاً.

إذا كان لديك أي أسئلة بخصوص الدراسة، يرجى عدم التردد في الاتصال بي عبر الهاتف أو البريد الإلكتروني.

رقم هاتفي هو:

[REDACTED]

وعنوان بريدي الإلكتروني هو:

[REDACTED]

شكراً لك على المشاركة في دراستي.

تقبلوا مني فائق الاحترام،

حنان بلعيدي

طالبة دكتوراه، جامعة ذو واست اوف اسكتلندا، المملكة المتحدة

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 9: Participants' Profiles

Teachers' codes	Age	Subject	Qualifications	Experience	Gender	Main Languages forming the linguistic repertoire
Chaoui 1	30	Arabic	PhD in Linguistics and Discourse Analysis (Arabic language and literature).	5 years	Female	Derja, Arabic, Tamazight, French, English
Chaoui 2	50	Mechanics	State engineer in Mechanical engineering	26 years	Female	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight, English
Chaoui 3	33	Chemistry	State engineer in Chemistry	3 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight.
Chaoui 4	35	Science	State engineer in Environment		Male	Derja, Arabic, French
Chaoui 5	42	Mathematic	Postgraduate in Mathematic	18 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight.
Chaoui 6	40	Arabic	PhD student in Modern Arabic Literature	6 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight, English
Chaoui 7	36	Arabic	Master's in Comparative literature (Arabic language)	8 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight.
Chaoui 8	30	Islamic laws	PhD in Comparative Religion	8 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight, English, German.
Chaoui 9	36	Mathematic	Master's in Mathematic and Computing	More than 3 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight.
Chaoui 10	38	History and Geography	Master's in history	14 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, French, Tamazight.
Chaoui 11	29	English	Master's in Didactics of foreign languages and cultures. PhD student in Didactics and literary texts.	7 years	Male	Derja, Arabic, English, French, Tamazight.
Kabyle 1	25	Chemistry	ENS Diploma in Chemistry	05 months	Female	Tamazight, Arabic, French, Derja
Kabyle 2	22	Computing	Diploma in Computing Science	1 year	Female	Tamazight, Arabic, French, English
Kabyle 3	32	French	Bachelor's in Translation and Interpretation (Arabic, French and German)	8 years	Female	Tamazight, Arabic, Derja, French, English, German
Kabyle 4	30	English	ENS Diploma in French Language	4 years	Female	Tamazight, Arabic, French, English
Kabyle 5	38	German	Bachelor's in German Language	13 years	Female	Tamazight, Arabic, French, German, English
Kabyle 6	32	German	Diploma in German Language	9 years	Female	Tamazight, German, French, English, Arabic, Derja
Kabyle 7	45	Philosophy	Diploma in Philosophy	20 years		Tamazight, Arabic, French, Derja
Kabyle 8	57	Economic Sciences	Bachelor's in Economic Sciences	33 Years	Male	French, Arabic, Derja, Tamazight
Kabyle 9	32	Arabic	ENS Diploma in Arabic Literature	10 years	Female	Arabic, Tamazight, French, Derja
Kabyle 10	46	Islamic laws	Bachelor's in religious sciences	14 years	Male	French, Arabic, Derja, Tamazight

Appendix 10: The Process of Data Analysis in the Study

Appendix 11: Thematic Map of the Study

Thematic Network of the Study

Appendix 12: Initial Organisation of Themes

Global Themes	Organisational Themes	Basic Themes
1-The formation and usage of the linguistic repertoires	<i>Awareness of being a multilingual person</i>	<i>Social habitus Disregarding languages self-representation</i>
	<i>Languages forming the linguistic repertoires</i>	
	<i>Learning, acquiring and usage of the linguistic repertoires</i>	<i>Language as a capital Mother tongue Milieu Schooling Books Television, internet and technological devices Convertibility of capital Interlocutor influence on language use Contextual influence on language use Code switching</i>
2-Attitudes towards the languages forming the linguistic repertoires	<i>Language preference and Representation</i>	<i>Language as a capital Language and religion Language and civilisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of nationalism Language and culture Language and emotions Language of identity Identity confusion Language of prestige Language of the colonial Disregarding languages Limitations of languages Openness to the world Comfortable</i>
	<i>Language preservation</i>	<i>Language loss Marginalisation</i>
	<i>Benefits of a multilingual repertoires</i>	<i>Enabling and facilitating communication Personal level Professional level</i>
3-Language and power	<i>Habitus, Capital and Field</i>	<i>Language as a capital Language value in Algeria <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prestige • Regions • Social class • Fields of power • Frequency of use Language and reproduction Disregarding languages</i>

<p>4-Language policy in education versus teachers' linguistic practice in the classroom.</p>	<p><i>Language policy in education</i></p>	<p>Hesitation to talk about politics Awareness of language policy in education Inconsistency in language policy Vagueness of language policy in Algeria ENS Written notes concerning language use in the classroom Language inspection in the classroom Teachers' reactions to language policy Frequency of language inspection in the classroom</p>
	<p><i>Teachers' linguistic practice in the classroom</i></p>	<p>Translanguaging in the classroom Tolerance of Translanguaging among students in the classroom</p>
	<p><i>Teachers' attitudes towards the language policy in education</i></p>	<p>Arabic as an official language in education Arabisation Referendum Lack of studies and planning Political decisions Adding vs excluding languages in education Contradictions in language policy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level of students • Obstacles • ENS Top-down policies Imposing languages A lesson to be learned Arabic claimed qualities</p>
	<p><i>Tamazight in Algeria</i></p>	<p>Tamazight in education Compulsoriness of Tamazight Status of Tamazight in Algeria <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing Tamazight status • Manipulating people Tamazight a heritage Tamazight as a minority Marginalisation</p>
	<p><i>Otherness and tensions</i></p>	<p>Regionalism Marginalisation Movements Generations' linguistic difference Equality Tolerance and acceptance of the other Suggestion to policy makers Diversity</p>

Appendix 13: Visual Representation of Nvivo

The screenshot displays the NVivo 12 Pro interface for a project titled "The linguistic Repertoires.nvp". The ribbon menu at the top includes "File", "Home", "Import", "Create", "Explore", "Share", "Document", and "Edit". The ribbon contains various tool icons for creating and managing nodes, documents, and searches.

The left-hand navigation pane is organized into several sections:

- Quick Access:** Files, Memos, Nodes
- Data:** Files, Case One, Case Two, File Classifications, Externals
- Codes:** Nodes, Relationships, Relationship Types
- Cases:** (empty)
- Notes:** (empty)
- Search:** (empty)
- Maps:** Maps
- Output:** (empty)

The central "Nodes" pane shows a table of nodes with the following data:

Name	Files	Referen
Arabisation	7	10
Awareness about being a multilingual	21	25
Awareness about language policy in e	19	32
The inconsistency of the Algerian la	4	5
Benefits of multilingual repertoires	21	65
Language as a capital	12	45
Books	15	17
Chaoui self representation	8	15
Code switching or mixing	21	46
Comfortable	20	26
Compulsoriness of Tamazight	19	23
Contradictions in language policy	19	44
Low level of students	5	5
Obstacles	5	5
Convertibility of capital	8	13
Derja	2	3
Disregarding languages	20	60
Diversity	4	7

The right-hand pane displays a transcript from "Interview 6 (Ely D)". The transcript includes several segments of text, some of which are highlighted in different colors to indicate they belong to specific nodes:

- Blue highlights:** "R: Why?", "R: Do you have a particular language that you feel more comfortable when you use?", "R: Why?", "H: which language do you think has more value in your linguistic repertoire?", "R: Can you classify these languages according to preference? The languages you prefer more.", "R: I mean..which one do you prefer?"
- Green highlights:** "Chaoui 6: Just like that! I learned it, and I can manifest my opinions in a clear and smooth way, and with strong arguments using it!", "Chaoui 6: The French language!", "Chaoui 6: I can discuss things using it! I can give arguments that support my views in a short and simple way! However, the interlocutors should understand this language, which is French; otherwise, I will be obliged to use Arabic or Derja!", "Chaoui 6: The language of communication! The Derja! Derja and Arabic, since we are an Arab society! However, when it comes to learning sciences and scientific researches, scientific research in a general way, English is considered the first language! It is a lingua franca! It is a vehicle language in a very wide air! It is used in a way...It is number one! The language of science! The majority of researchers in the scientific and literary fields, and human sciences write their articles in English language to get higher percentage of readers! The reason for that is the usage of this language in the educational curricula all over the world!"
- Red highlights:** "Chaoui 6: To be honest, I love Arabic language! However, regarding the fluency in speaking, I speak French smoothly! I cannot say that I master it, but I am good at it, and I speak Arabic!"

The status bar at the bottom indicates "97 Items", "Editable", and "Line: 69 Column: 20".